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Pedagogical Sciences

Content and features of work on speech development

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One of the criteria of a person's cultural maturity and formation as a useful personality for society is his mastery of speech culture. This is one of the most important general pedagogical problems facing the general education school. The task of work on speech development comes from teaching about the unity of language and thinking.

Speech directly participates in the formation of human mental activity and is its basis. By mastering perfect speech, students acquire knowledge about events and objects in the external world. The conducted observations show that by the time they come to school, they learn the grammatical structure of our language and have a certain vocabulary corresponding to the need to communicate with others, understand the speech of others, they are able to express their opinion. However, the speech of children coming to school sometimes does not allow them to express new understandings, thoughts, and feelings. First of all, this should be explained by the poverty of the child's vocabulary. The household vocabulary that he gets used to in the process of communicating with his friends and family is insufficient for a serious, scientific speech in front of the teacher and the team at school. That is why planned work is done on the child's speech at school.

School training increases the resources and opportunities of children's speech development. Children observe nature and people's work, communicate with their friends, read books, give speeches, etc. In this process, the student's speech develops. It is necessary to try so that the students can reflect their thoughts about the existence they observe more precisely and correctly, and the words they use in their speech correspond to the concepts and ideas they express. It is necessary to achieve a conscious approach of students to their speech and the speech of others.

Pupils should work on learning the speech in a practical way in the teaching of all subjects, as well as in recesses, extracurricular activities, social-useful works, labor process, at home.

It is impossible to achieve the necessary result without such continuous work on the development of students' speech, without teaching them to carefully choose the appropriate word and phrase to express their ideas, and to construct the idea logically.

The main goal of the work on written speech is to achieve clear, precise, perfect, expressive writing about what students see, hear, read, and think in a way that everyone can understand. Acquiring this skill is of great importance in the content of a person's education and cultural development. Students who do not acquire such a habit in the scope of the program in primary school have difficulty in writing expressions and essays, reports, articles for the wall newspaper, and information about a certain event in the upper grades. People who do not develop their written speech during the years of secondary education cannot write a lecture in a university or summarize the content of the works they read. Finally, of course, in order to become a journalist, writer, scientist, it is necessary to fulfill the program requirements on written speech from the first years of education.

The similarities and differences of language and speech were explained in detail for the first time in the work of the famous Swiss linguist F. de Saussure called "General Linguistics Course". He considered language and speech to be two different phenomena, and showed that language is the use of grammatical system and vocabulary, that is, language units, and speech is the use of those units for communication purposes. Speech consists of individual speech and hearing factors. Later, various theories and opinions were expressed about this thesis. As a result, these ideas are summarized in such a way that although language and speech are different categories, these two concepts are interconnected and in dialectical unity with each other. Interactions occur in this process.

Language is not an innate feature for a child, it is gradually formed starting from infancy. A child acquires his mother tongue mainly intuitively through speech. While listening to the speech of the people around him, he comes across different ideas, memorizes them and gradually learns to connect repeatedly repeated elements - words and phrases with a certain meaning. The child uses those elements in new conditions. Based on them, he himself utters new ideas and thus acquires the structure of his native language.

To develop a child's speech means to help him master the material of the language, to train the speech organs for this purpose, to facilitate the understanding of the lexical and grammatical signs of the language, to stimulate the intellect, to evaluate the real situation with the help of lexical and grammatical signs. It is intended to teach the mind, to train emotions and feelings, to facilitate the memorization of literary norms, that is, the tradition of using language signs such as morphemes, words, word combinations and sentences in speech, their sound and graphic composition.

Mastering speech means being able to convey one's thoughts and feelings through words.

In order to properly organize work on the development of children's speech, the teacher should refer to the achievements of linguistics. Speech development is an applied part of linguistics and covers the issues of speaking correctly. In the works on speech development, the question of its correctness usually occupies a central place. Speech can be said to be correct only when it does not violate language norms (phonetic, orthographic, lexical, word creation, semantic, grammatical, stylistic, etc.).

The child learns the language, which consists of the general norms determined in his daily life, thus his speech is formed. People communicate with each other through speech. It is possible to talk about mastering the norms of the language when students can use these norms correctly. The norms of the language mean phonetic, orthographic, lexical or lexical, morphological, orthographic, syntactic, punctuation and stylistic rules and laws.

Phonetic norms include the correct pronunciation of the so-called sounds for elementary school students, their differentiation from each other. By orfopedic pronunciation, it is meant to give preference to the pronunciation in terms of the fluency and sweetness of the oral speech, and not to use the book pronunciation.

The need for students to acquire vocabulary or lexical knowledge and skills from lower grades is evident. Communication with others, reading, observations and practical works enrich students' vocabulary with new words and terms. In this process, their speech is enriched both quantitatively and qualitatively. Each word gradually acquires a new meaning.

Syntax is mainly considered a part of grammar, but in fact, it is also important in terms of students' speech development. Children understand the relationships of approach, agreement and control by building word combinations with the help of words made up of units of meaning.

The grammatical structure of the sentence is closely related to the intonation (rise and fall of the voice, pause, volume and speed of the sentence). Therefore, it is necessary to teach students to read and speak expressively. Pupils learn the structure of the sentence, the main and secondary members, etc. by acquiring knowledge about, they learn to construct sentences with

different content, different types, and express their thoughts. The order of words plays an important role in constructing a sentence. A student who does not master the ability to anticipate the order of words in a sentence in accordance with our language cannot convey his idea to the interviewer correctly.

In order to develop an important habit in this field, the analysis and composition of the sentence is absolutely necessary. The student should think about the form and content of the sentence in advance. As a result, this leads him to build a coherent, contextual speech. In order to use and construct this form of speech, it is necessary to create a meaning connection between separate sentences, to connect them around one meaning. To create an essay, students need to be taught to speak and write according to a plan.

The school teaches the ways of constructing different types of expression and essay. The student should be able to clearly imagine the object or event he is going to talk about and write about, separate the idea to be expressed into parts, determine their sequence, and express his idea linguistically correctly. In order to ensure the normal development of students' speech, the teacher should also know well the development of their mental processes. Psychologists have determined what mental processes occur in a child during speech development. It is important for the educator to know how their speech differs from the speech of the elderly, the difference between internal speech and external speech, children's ideas about existence, how living beings are reflected in their minds, and how their ideas are expressed in words. extremely important.

In psychological studies, special importance is attached to the problem of the uniformity of word visibility. In this regard, it is useful to rely on live observations. The fact that the second signal system (speech) constantly interacts with the first signal (visually) shows that language and thinking are the reflection of existence, therefore, language exercises are always based on children's observations of nature and the life of society, their direct perception of external objects and events. must be associated with the impression.

Objective existence is reflected in the mind of a person in the form of understanding and judgment. Concept is expressed in language by words and word combinations, and judgment is expressed by sentences. The word, which reflects the general and important features of any grammatical concept, and the sentence, which is the material volume of that concept, and the sentence, which is the material volume of that concept, cannot be imagined and studied separately from each other. Speech and thinking are in unbreakable unity. Any ideas that arise in the minds of students occur only on the basis of language material. Their speech develops in the process of cognitive activity, which refers to the active work of their thoughts. In other words, vocabulary enrichment is closely related to thought content enrichment. The word is used to express an idea. If the thought is not understood, the word becomes something incomprehensible. People cannot find words only when they express that they do not understand well. Therefore, the development of students' speech and the enrichment of their thinking should go parallel.

Teaching about the development of speech and the unity of thinking is an important philosophical issue about moving from feelings to thought. During the research on the problem of thinking and speech, former psychologists often made a mistake in such an important issue as the relation of thought to words. Some of them equated speech with thought. Some have concluded that thinking is independent, independent and isolated processes. They bypass such an important issue as the attitude of thought to speech in the research process. L.S. Vygotsky saw the reason for this failure in the incorrectness of the research method, especially in the metaphysical understanding of the analysis of the problem.

The sound shell of the word and its lexical meaning, form and content are not identical, but they are in unbreakable unity. Equating the external and internal aspects of the word means equating speech with thinking. However, speech cannot always be considered a mirror of thinking. We can express any idea in different ways. On the other hand, observations show that in many

cases children use various words, speech forms and expressions, but do not know their meaning, because the names of things do not yet mean their meaning. The meaning of a word is its internal aspect reflected in our consciousness of an object, event or relationship. The sounding of the word is the material shell necessary for the expression of the meaning, as well as its delivery to other people, as well as its formation, formation, existence and development. Therefore, "Underlying the word is the concept, which is the generalized vision of existence."

Although the concept and the word are in unbreakable unity, this does not give a reason to equate them. A word is a category of language, and a concept is a category of logic. Understanding, being an element of thinking, generalizes the phenomena of existence, reflects the general characteristics of things. "The word "child" along with the meaning related to it is very quickly absorbed by me. The concept expressed by that word, being a generalized image of existence, increases, expands and deepens as the child develops. The work on the systematization of concepts in the development of speech and thinking is based on observations. "All the logic of the language came out of the observations on the objects and phenomena of nature."

Usually, they note the concreteness of the thinking of small school-aged children. Undoubtedly, the ideas characterized by visual images are concrete, but these ideas include some elements of generalization. According to L.V. Zankov, since the generalization itself is included in the concept, it exists in an inextricable connection with the abstraction of a certain aspect of things. Without abstract thinking, human knowledge cannot move forward, because in abstraction there is a regular increase in human cognition. The work on abstraction is suitable for students from the 1st grade. It is important to consider all these in the development of students' speech. Although the word is in unbreakable unity with the concept, the oral (audio) and written (graphic) forms of the communication process directly interact with each other. It is very important for the teacher to know the characteristics of oral and written speech, to teach them to distinguish the unique norms of each of these forms of speech, for the proper organization of work on the development of students' speech.

Oral and written speech, which is the main goal of teaching the Azerbaijani language, does not develop at the same level not only in primary, but also in upper classes. So, while a group of children have very good oral communication, they have difficulty expressing their thoughts in writing.

The other group, on the contrary, succeeds in writing statements and essays, but their oral speech becomes unintelligible, boring, dull. It is possible to find children who master both aspects of speech at the same level. This diversity in the field of speech development proves that the psychology of oral and written speech is not the same. Oral and written speech are two forms of communication between people through language. Oral speech is based on the sense of hearing from the organs of speech, and written speech is based on motor emotions consisting of vision and the movements of the writing hand.

So, oral speech is audio speech defined for auditory perception, and written speech is graphic speech defined for visual perception. These emotions are of great importance for the development of students' ability to read, write, and speak properly. Therefore, special work should be done with children who cannot see normally, who cannot hear normally, and those who speak imprecisely and without expression should be referred to a speech therapist.

During communication, depending on the task at hand, oral and written forms involve direct communication with people (in a lesson, lecture, speech at a meeting, dialogue, interview, etc.). Oral speech is a process of live communication of people with the help of language in concrete life conditions. Thus, oral speech is mainly a reciprocal process. It is important for him to be a speaker and a listener, a questioner and an answerer. Oral speech requires that the listener understands it in the process of speaking. Oral speech arises automatically and proceeds under natural conditions.

At this time, there is no time left to think and investigate. Written speech does not require the participation of those involved in communication, because it is difficult to determine to whom this form of speech belongs. In the process of written speech, there is an opportunity to think, take and leave. Oral speech is random, and written speech is always monologic.

Due to the fact that oral speech is free in terms of its structure and the choice of words, it avoids book sentences, difficult terms and expressions, and complex constructions, tries to pronounce words easily, and puts the logical emphasis on the desired word in the sentence. reaches the listener more precisely and clearly.

In oral speech, it is possible to return to the same issue many times, repeat the necessary word, expression, sentence, omit the word, expression when necessary, replace it with a stronger one, change the style of the sentence. In the written speech, which is the result of a long-term thinking process, logical sequence is expected, omission of words and unnecessary repetitions are not allowed. Students go a long way to acquire lexically, morphologically and syntactically polished written speech. As a result of the complex and abstract nature of written speech, it takes a long time and hard work for students to master it.

Oral speech is more expressive than written speech. This is one of the important conditions for its correct understanding by believers. Various means of expressiveness are used in oral speech: raising and lowering the voice, pause, speed, emphasis, separation of the necessary word and expression with sound, mime, gesture, etc. All this is an important means of making oral speech expressive, as well as creating confidence and belief in the listener. Written speech is devoid of such aids. Therefore, in many cases, it is difficult to understand the content of written speech. This opinion is confirmed by the fact that sometimes those who listen to a certain text understand it better than those who read it aloud, but the written speech is divided into parts, paragraphs and paragraphs. Italics, quotation marks, question and exclamation marks, multi-points make it possible to draw attention to the necessary word, to distinguish the main point, and to make the content of the written text more accurate.

In written speech, it is necessary to choose words carefully, and if necessary, try to express gestures, mimicry and intonation with words.

Since the interlocutors understand each other quickly and well in the process of oral speech, this aspect of the speech is distinguished by its conciseness, brevity, and even incompleteness when necessary. Both parties, who are witnesses of the event and understand each other well, communicate by omitting this or that word in the sentence or even the main members during the conversation.

Oral speech has certain possibilities to take into account the individual characteristics of people. It is possible to choose the right word, expression, tone depending on how the interlocutor says the word, the tone of his voice, shades of intonation, the meaning in his eyes, facial expressions. Depending on the composition and level of the audience, the speaker can convey the same idea in different ways.

Oral and written speech also differ according to the language material used. In oral speech, which is free speech, we use lexical, grammatical and stylistic means of spoken language. Oral speech requires students to pronounce words in accordance with orthographic norms, correct speech forms. Oral speech is simple in its synthetic structure. Simple, short sentences are usually used in this speech. Oral speech is related to the physiological and psychological conditions of pronunciation. We try to enunciate each thought with one inhale and exhale.

The written speech is based on the means of books by expressing it with various complex sentences. This speech, governed by grammatical norms, is more of a normed, continuous speech. At the time of writing, it is important to take into account the degree of difficulty of this or that word, orthographic literacy, and to express the idea in a coherent manner.

Usually, students' oral speech is richer than their written speech and takes an important place in the learning process. Students acquire new knowledge through oral speech. Oral speech gradually builds a solid foundation for written speech. The more the student's oral speech develops, the higher his written speech will be. The development of written speech in turn affects the enrichment and polishing of oral speech. Therefore, the teacher should take care of the mutual development of both aspects of speech. It is extremely important to make students speak correctly and express their thoughts accurately in written form.

Since it is very difficult to master the written speech, it is necessary to teach the students how to express their oral thoughts in writing from the end of the school year in the 1st grade. They should learn to express the same idea more concisely, more precisely, with more beautiful words, and be able to see and correct their mistakes in expression and composition.

Oral and written speech is called foreign speech. In addition, there is internal (silent) speech. An idea becomes completely clear when a person organizes and forms it internally. Internal speech affects external speech, and external speech affects internal speech. One sets the other in order. Systematic work on the development of internal speech from the 1st grade creates a solid foundation for the normal development of students' oral and written speech.

c) The optimal organization of work on speech development depends on the extent to which students' learning opportunities are taken into account and how didactic principles are followed. Research conducted by pedagogues and psychologists has proven that students' cognitive abilities are much higher than what is used. They considered the underestimation of the children's cognitive abilities and the fact that they were not taken into account in the training process a serious flaw, and they showed that it is appropriate to use the potential opportunities that children have. The new program demanded a significant increase in the theoretical level of training, the development effect, giving preference to thinking rather than memory.

Speech development is the main line in language lessons. The ultimate goal in teaching the Azerbaijani language is to teach students to express the knowledge they have acquired in an educated manner, correctly, coherently and meaningfully. The preparation of the class in the mother tongue, the result of the teacher's activity, should be measured precisely by the students' acquisition of communicative speech.

Therefore, the teacher asks questions, conversations, the effect of the art pieces he reads, his observations on nature and the surrounding world, familiarization with the work of people, etc. based on this, he should take care of the content of students' communicative speech. If the child's observation takes place in the form of an analytical process where attention is focused on certain objects and events, if the student finds similarities and differences in the observation process and tries to understand each of them clearly. , his speech is meaningful.

The content of communicative speech also depends on the ability of students to request a plan. The student must first mentally prepare the story that he has read, the plan of what he will write on the picture of his observation. Orthographic and lexical preparation for written expression and essay ensures logical, content-wise completeness, depth, and accuracy of the related speech.

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PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF INHERITANCE

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The study of the principle of succession in science is important for a deep understanding of the history of science, the laws of development from a socio-philosophical and methodological point of view. This principle expresses the mechanism of transmission of scientific traditions and values from generation to generation as the basic law of development of scientific knowledge. In scientific continuity, stability, continuity, and discontinuity are dialectically intertwined. The departure of science from dialectical laws does not mean that mechanical, old ideas are simply transferred to a new stage, or that theories and methods of research are obtained in an uncreative way.

Science is a field of continuous creativity that reflects the interaction and struggle of traditions as a special form of activity, knowledge system and social institution. Traditions not only ensure the transmission of scientific experience through scientific activity, but also significantly influence the definition of its content as the basis for the formation of something new in science. There are good reasons why succession is an important criterion for justifying and proving scientific knowledge. Because, thanks to traditions, they try to protect the scientific criteria, norms and values that ensure the status of science in the system of society.

Therefore, the experience and traditions collected in the past are of great importance to verify the authenticity of scientific knowledge in different ways. It is impossible for scientific subjects (scientists, scientific schools, trends, etc.) to act outside of traditions and scientific content. Scientific ideas are the traditions, theories, etc. of the past. It is formed by further development and assimilation. The richness of scientific traditions opens wide opportunities for the new generation of researchers to conduct effective scientific research.

Changes in the nature of social relations and paradigms of scientific thought in society also lead to innovations in the traditions of scientific activity. The fact that traditions have rich knowledge and experience in solving scientific problems plays an important role in choosing new directions for scientific research. Mutual struggle and the union of innovations with scientific traditions is one of the important aspects of its development. In the process of dialectical development of scientific knowledge, the positive values of the past become one of the components of innovation.

In fact, when scientific innovation expresses innovation, it finds its main source in the scientific tradition. Disruption of heredity in the development of science leads to the disruption of relations accumulated over many years between scientific traditions and practices. In our opinion, it is appropriate to explain this in more detail using the example of humanities in the former Soviet Union. After the October revolution of 1917, due to political and ideological reasons, the principle of continuity was broken in the Soviet space, mainly in the humanitarian field. Since then, for 70 years, these sciences faced the task of forming within the framework defined by the ideology of Marxism-Leninism. Eliminating it meant going against this ideology.

At that time, philosophy, sociology, psychology and other humanitarian sciences that emerged in the United States and the West were considered the inventions of bourgeois ideologues who served capitalism.

Therefore, in the former Soviet Union, in a positive sense, the translation of works by philosophers, sociologists and psychologists from the United States and the West, which

contradict the ideology of Marxism-Leninism, was prohibited. The Soviet researcher was not allowed to get acquainted with these works at any cost, and those who wanted to do so were given the epithets "servants of the bourgeoisie" and "enemies of the Soviet people". In general, when analyzing these questions, the following question naturally arises: if, in the words of the Marxist-Leninist ideology, "bourgeois philosophers, sociologists, historians" are engaged in meaningless or unrealistic research, then what is the need to translate and distribute their works?

Was it inadmissible for Soviet researchers to know them directly? Wouldn't it be better to let Soviet scientists get acquainted with the "meaningless and fictitious" ideas of the "bourgeois" humanities? Indeed, in fact, in this way it was possible to reveal the superiority of the Soviet humanitarian sciences, as claimed by the ideology of Marxism-Leninism, and in this case, why not use this tool? The answer is clear. Because the development of humanitarian sciences in the West, the wealth, directions and content of research in this field were known to the leadership of the Soviet political system. Therefore, it was believed that, for example, a Soviet scientist could compare Western philosophy with the philosophy of Marxism-Leninism and identify the weaknesses of the latter (but it should be borne in mind that it would be a mistake to deny the philosophy of Marxism-Leninism in general, because its scientific and methodological philosophy also has important features from the point of view).

Apparently, these bans limited the development of humanities in the former USSR, deprived them of the philosophical and sociological thinking of the modern world. From this point of view, humanities in the former Soviet Union had to develop in a kind of ignorance of the nature of research and theories in Western philosophy, sociology, science and other fields. At that time, the research conducted by Soviet scientists did not go beyond the framework established by the ideology of Marxism-Leninism, and those who tried to overcome this barrier were subjected to repression and punishment. For this reason, during the former Soviet Union, philosophical systems, theories and trends that were an alternative to human sciences, including Marxist-Leninist philosophy, could not emerge. At the time, it got to the point where humanities experts whose works encompassed broad Marxist-Leninist theory faced such repression when they used casual reasoning outside the existing ideological framework. Only after the collapse of the former Soviet Union, the post-Soviet space opened wide opportunities for the free development of humanities, especially philosophy, without ideological barriers.

Historical experience shows that changes in social and humanitarian sciences in transitional societies, the emergence of new methodological approaches have their own characteristics. This is because, first of all, objects of social and humanities have a special ontology compared to objects of natural sciences. This, in turn, requires a revision of the forms of cognition that are traditional for the sciences. Therefore, after the collapse of the former USSR, it became especially important for social sciences to analyze the processes taking place in society from the perspective of new theories.

In accordance with the requirements of the time, it is advisable to take into account scientific traditions and experience in the formation of new methodological approaches and principles in the field of social sciences. Scientific and philosophical theories adequately explain actual reality if they refer to past scientific traditions and experiences. Therefore, the development of social sciences, especially philosophy, in Azerbaijan requires the synthesis of progressive scientific and philosophical traditions and practices, world philosophical thought and the existence of mutual relations between them. In this field, there are serious grounds for the expediency of the philosophical development of sciences in Azerbaijan. Because it occupies a special place in the understanding and study of the dialectics of the development of sciences. It was through succession that the unacceptability of standards and judgments that hindered the development of science was revealed.

Historical experience shows that the relevance of the principle of inheritance, which causes great changes in the stages of scientific development, is primarily related to the genetic qualities it carries. Because the philosophical importance of science is that it is a serious science from the beginning. Succession plays an important role in explaining and understanding the current scientific situation. Along with science, it also reflects the universalities of culture on a larger scale. The greatest scientific achievements require philosophical generalizations. According to the evolutionary dialectic of scientific knowledge, it develops in the conditions of mutual influence of different sciences and each other. Intensive development and enrichment of scientific knowledge leads to differentiation and integration of sciences. The interaction between succession and innovation becomes an important factor in the process of differentiation and integration of sciences.

Differentiation of sciences plays an important role in the detailed study of the processes occurring in nature, society and thinking and in determining the fields of activity of scientific researchers. Differential inheritance preserves the connections between scientific knowledge in the process of differentiation of sciences.

Solving complex and global problems is an important factor in the integration of sciences. Succession in the integration of sciences provides mutual information exchange in the process of explanation of scientific facts and phenomena, emergence of single effective research methods and new fields of science. For example, as a result of the integration of philosophy, sociology, political science and psychology, social philosophy, social psychology, political sociology, socio-economic, socio-political, etc. Whole heredity occupies a special place in scientific work because of the need for in-depth and detailed study of processes. Since scientific knowledge is systematic, it is one of the important foundations of scientific theories. Scientific theories arise mainly in the period when theoretical problems are solved as a joint product of a justified and conceptually organized system of scientific ideas and theoretical thinking, empirical observations.

At the same time, all the scientific criteria of the past are not rejected, and effective ones are used at a new stage in the development of science. The principle of continuity occupies a special place in the collection and verification of empirical facts that are the basis of the theory, and in ensuring the interaction between its constituent parts. This principle helps to deepen the basic provisions of the theory and increases the effectiveness of practical application.

Scientific succession creates interaction between scientific concepts, research methods and principles at every stage of scientific development. One of the important aspects of the development of science is the mutual dialectic of absolute and relative truths. All relative truth and scientific theory derive from absolute truth. In the development of science, the transition from relative truths to absolute truths, as well as the dialectical denial of past truths and theories with new methods, is manifested by the principle of succession.

Succession between the stable components of each science as a system plays an important role in ensuring mutual dependence. This relationship allows us to distinguish among scientific theories and concepts those that are important and significant for the development of science as a socio-cultural phenomenon. At the same time, it manifests itself as the main regularity in the emergence of new scientific directions and scientific methods. Scientific knowledge is constantly updated, and here succession is different. It ensures the interaction of the stages of development of scientific knowledge manifested in forms (universal conceptual, traditional, normative, scientifically controlled, etc.).

It should be noted that the manifestation of inheritance in various forms is closely related to the essence of social relations, the influence of objective and subjective factors. The process of systematization and protection of scientific heritage takes place thanks to the concept of universal inheritance. The traditional form of succession is the basis of the mechanism for regulating the appropriation of scientific achievements. Since the leading role here belongs to traditions, any

innovation is interpreted as a departure from existing norms. Such regulation of relations between the present and the past in science is reflected in scientific activity.

Spontaneous and random methods of solving scientific problems are replaced by scientific methods based on certain regularities, during which continuity is manifested in the form of spontaneity and perception. The form of spontaneous succession in science involves the acquisition and processing of unexpected scientific knowledge. Perception of scientific knowledge in accordance with the set goals is expressed by the concept of "perceptual inheritance". The value-information importance of the obtained scientific knowledge is determined by the positive and negative aspects of the heritage in science. On this basis, two types of succession (prospective and loyal) differ from each other. The type of prospective inheritance is manifested in the creation and enrichment of scientific knowledge according to the level of development of the society. Loyal succession manifests itself in the solution of promising problems faced by scientific knowledge. On the basis of this type of succession, scientific knowledge is acquired over a certain period of time. Each science tries to adequately reflect different areas of reality depending on the research object. The characteristics of the research object, in turn, affect the content of the science that studies it. For example, economics studies the economic system, its nature and characteristics as an object of scientific research. If innovative tendencies are increasing in economic development, innovative approaches are needed in the economy itself due to the adequacy of the research object. In general, concepts, categories, etc. is put forward by every science. After being accepted by the scientific community and confirmed as truth during the verification period, they fall into the apparatus of scientific concepts and categories.

Static (quantitative) and dynamic (qualitative) inheritance differ from each other in revolutionary and non-revolutionary situations of the development of scientific knowledge. As a result, the development of scientific knowledge can be approached within the framework of a certain system and at the same time from the point of view of transition to a new system. In the first case, there are quantitative changes in which the structure of the system does not undergo radical changes, although the amount of data increases. In the second case, qualitative changes indicate a transition from one system to another. It should be noted that the reflection of inheritance among scientific knowledge is an important factor affecting the systematic character of scientific activity.

The development of scientific knowledge also manifests itself in forms of progressive and regressive continuity that are dialectically related to each other. Progressive succession determines the development of science as a system, its main feature is the transition of scientific knowledge from lower forms to higher and more developed forms. If enrichment with useful knowledge for the development of science is not dynamic, the relationships that ensure the stability of the structure of scientific knowledge, the existence and stability of science as a system as a whole weaken, and in this process sustainability manifests itself in a regressive form.

In the structure of scientific knowledge, empirical and theoretical knowledge determines the manifestation of the principle of inheritance in experimental and theoretical forms. In addition to these levels of scientific knowledge, this principle is more general and manifests itself at the metathetic level, which consists of two sub-levels: general scientific knowledge and philosophical foundations of science. Experiences and achievements obtained as a result of scientific activity create a connection between empirical, theoretical and meta-theoretical levels of knowledge. Therefore, scientific experiments and methodological approaches are used when conducting research at all levels of scientific knowledge. Positive continuity in science indicates a natural relationship that preserves structural elements, forms and methods at different stages of the development of science. Considering that positive inheritance is in conflict with negative inheritance helps the researcher to take the right position in his research. As a result, the scientific heritage that meets the requirements of the time is preserved and enriched.

THE ROLE OF FOLKLORE MUSIC IN RAISING THE MUSICAL-AESTHETIC CULTURAL LEVEL OF STUDENTS

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Like other forms of art, music reflects the world around us, opens a conversation about people and life. But with his own language - the language of music. The national music samples glorify the high spirituality of the people, their wishes and aspirations, hope, faith in the future, mood.

At present, many students, as well as the elderly and young people, recognize the songs and dances, which are very far from folk music, set by random music lovers, as the best musical examples of our folk music. However, real folk music has its own beauty and its own pleasant aroma. They bravely passed through the stormy roads of centuries and continue to keep their freshness even today.

People's attitude towards nature and its phenomena are not the same. Personality is closely related to society. This has historically been the case. Each person breathes the desires and wishes of the specific environment of the society to which he belongs, feeds on it and tries to keep up with the times. The spiritual and moral demands and artistic tastes of people belonging to different classes and social strata, who fundamentally differ from each other due to their economic status, political, moral and outlook, have differed. Progressive philosophers, pedagogues and psychologists have understood this truth with complete clarity. N. G. Chernyshevsky criticized Hegel's idealist aesthetics and said that the aesthetic taste of the ruling class and the oppressed class are different. In our society, people's aesthetic taste is determined by their relations of mutual assistance and cooperation in production.

An important factor in the education of musical taste in Azerbaijan is the national and moral values of our people. In our society, aesthetic and spiritual education is inseparable from other areas of education, universal education as a whole. Artistic taste reflects the value a person gives to reality, the richness of aesthetic quality, from the perspective of ideas such as beauty and vanity, comedy and tragedy in the process of social practice. When the subject of that assessment is a work of art, this ability is called aesthetic taste or artistic taste. The idealists considered artistic taste to be an innate intuitive ability, while the vulgar materialists attributed it to the physiological subconsciousness of man as a biological species. In fact, aesthetic and artistic taste, social practice of a person, above all, is considered as an ability born from production-creative activity and formed historically.

Artistic taste is characterized by the fact that it is fundamentally different from theoretical judgments derived from the study of objects, life events and works of art, and it manifests itself directly. Every piece of music that touches the human soul is beautiful. It is through music that beautiful and sublime feelings are conveyed to the listener, and noble moral qualities are brought up in them. Genius Uzeyir Hajibeyov wrote in this regard - "If music only feeds the heart without giving anything to human thinking, then it can turn from useful to harmful, from conviction to stupidity, and finally from medicine to poison, it makes us numb, creates moral disorder, and turns us into a moral disability." . At the same time, these thoughts of the composer reveal the socially useful nature of music, its ethical, aesthetic, and artistic features, and once again show the positive role it plays in life. On the one hand, music is a wonderful tool for glorifying complex human

feelings, emotions, and spiritual education, but on the other hand, it is important to revive and express those feelings in the listener's thinking, to form moral values, and to influence people.

The expression of artistic feeling, spirituality, mood, passions is the strongest aspect of music. Therefore, it should always be in the center of attention to clarify the specific aspects of music and its emotional impact to schoolchildren and students, to awaken in them pure emotions, delicate, thought-provoking, heroic feelings. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the correct selection of music samples during education, training and education. Possibilities of formation of characteristics of the motivation-demand field, interests and tendencies of the personality are considered from the point of view of reconstruction and acceleration strategy. As is known, character is formed in action, and this formation is possible not by itself, but as a result of education. Music education, training and education is carried out on the basis of a pre-prepared plan. In other words, the music teachers who are responsible in this field should prepare the lesson plan in advance, and after determining that the musical pieces given in the program or directly selected by the music teachers are suitable for the children's age characteristics, their levels, interests, psychological characters and perceptive abilities, they should include them in the work plan.

The involvement of students in social activities in music training has its own characteristics. It should not be forgotten that the sensitivity of students to music increases as they age and pass from class to class. They follow the tone of the music teacher's voice, the way he sings, and his performance on musical instruments very carefully. The formation of artistic taste in students with the help of music depends, first of all, on the interest of each child in the musical example played and listened to, and on his own mood. Emotions play an important role in students' behavior. He perceives everything that happens around him with excitement, very quickly, feels joy easily and gets sad quickly. It is a well-known fact that music is formed by sound in a certain sequence.

In this sense, the student's lifestyle should be cheerful and cheerful because of his attachment to music and communication with it. Disbelief, petty guardianship, inappropriate control suppresses the child's strength and weakens his character. When talking about the psychological issues of instilling artistic taste in young students, the role of attention should be specially mentioned. The clear reflection of some objects, and the hazy reflection of others, is due to the phenomenon of attention. Attention is the organization of mental activity in such a way that this activity becomes the main object in a certain object and event, differs from other objects and is perceived more clearly. Thus, attention is expressed in the selective character of mental activity. It is the main duty of the teacher to create conditions for students to be attentive in music lessons. Distraction is the opposite of attentiveness. There are various reasons for distraction.

One of them is the improper training of attention. Therefore, the formation of artistic taste in students can be effectively implemented, first of all, taking into account a number of pedagogical and psychological issues. Music has the ability to enter the consciousness of children, to influence the nature and characteristics of their activity. Music reveals the social essence of life events and helps people in correctly assessing and valuing life events. It is known that music evokes appropriate feelings in a person. These feelings affect a person's mind, will, and coordination of actions. It leads to the realization of the tasks ahead in the field of physical, mental, moral and spiritual education of the student and gives an emotional and aesthetic color to this process. Therefore, in the "training and education programs" of schools, it is envisaged to connect the mental, moral and physical education of children with multifaceted musical activities. A child who pays attention to the study of contradictory images creates an artistic image by himself while listening to music.

Music is a wonderful and powerful educational tool. It should be noted that all other types of musical activity - listening to music, singing, musical-rhythmic movements in one way or another affect the formation of the student's consciousness and moral views. "Music is exuberance

through and through; music suddenly separates a person from the land on which he lives, drowns his ears with the roar of powerful sounds, immerses him in his own world. Music touches a person's nerves and his whole existence, excites and shakes a person."

Musical education of the young generation is currently of great importance, attracting wide interest not only in our country, but also in many foreign countries. At present, when the music experts of many foreign countries explain the question of which children should be engaged in music, they consider only children with special talents as the basis. However, modern pedagogical science solves this issue in a different way and shows that it is certainly more appropriate to work with children with special talents in order to train professional musicians in the future, but music education should be applied to all children on a massive scale without any exceptions.

Among a number of urgent problems facing secondary schools in modern times, it is necessary to mention the issue of using folklore music samples and melodies in raising the level of students' musical abilities and musical-aesthetic culture. These examples, which are characterized as convenient teaching tools, are closely related to the education of an aesthetic attitude to music, a high aesthetic taste, as well as the formation of the spiritual image of the growing generation. Because the understanding and mastering of beauty in the art of music by students through folklore examples has a strong influence on the harmonious development of a morally rich, active creative personality.

Establishing the musical education of children and schoolchildren on the basis of the features characteristic of the national musical culture is considered one of the most important tasks. Thus, folk music, apart from purely folklore elements, contains the concept of the characteristics of the artistic thinking of the people. Therefore, if the psychological character of the nation is understood as its emotional response to the environment, its perception of the world, then music acts as a kind of expression of its significant features. Basing the issues of musical education of the young generation on national music and the features of the emotional system of folk psychology has ancient historical roots.

The use of the highest achievements and progressive traditions of the national culture plays an important role in the general education system, it has a strong influence on the formation of feelings of patriotism, love for the native land, and the development of aesthetic taste. This is one of the important factors in the formation of moral values in students in general.

Examples of various genres of musical folklore are the main users of the creative traditions of the people, and they have an exceptional spiritual and aesthetic influence. The implementation of regular, systematic measures for the correct understanding of the feeling of love for national music and the fullness of national musical instruments is considered to be a problematic means. The ability to feel and differentiate the character of the melody, rhythm, timbre harmony helps to create interest in national and foreign music in music and art school students. In other words, the understanding of folk creativity, familiarization with its deep roots enriches the personality of a child, a schoolchild, and plays an important stage in mastering the creativity of both national and foreign composers.

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF CONTINUITY IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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The operation of continuous education is based on the following principles that determine its uniqueness:

1. Humanism
2. Democracy,
3. Mobility
4. Waiting
5. Openness
6. Continuity

The principle of humanism testifies to the appeal of education to a person, the freedom of a person to choose the forms, conditions, types of education, professional development and self-education. This principle is implemented by creating favorable opportunities for the development of creative individuality of each person. Man is seen as the goal of social progress. The principle of democracy implies the availability of education at all ages in accordance with interests, possibilities and needs, according to various forms of education. It provides freedom of transfer from one educational institution to another, accelerated education and advanced training.

It means equal rights to education and development of all citizens, regardless of class, national characteristics, health status. This principle envisages the democratization of all aspects of the life of educational institutions, equal relations between the subjects of the pedagogical process. The principle of mobility is expressed in the various tools, methods, organizational forms, flexibility of the continuous education system and readiness for rapid restructuring in accordance with the changing needs of production, society and individuals. Focuses on the use of various productive methodological systems and technologies.

Continuous education at the level of the educational system - reproduces, changes and develops educational institutions and the characteristics of relations between them, as well as by combining the efforts of communities and the individual efforts of individual educational subjects (synergy). Pedagogical management manifests itself in solving problems of self-development, self-organization, self-development, instability, the speed of information circulation and the demands of society on the nature of educational services. In this framework, the structure of continuous education will include the following components:

1) reproduction, change and development of education as a state and social institution, taking into account the specific historical requirements of education in the set of socio-economic, political, moral, legal and cultural needs of society in developed people;

2) reproduction, change and development of appropriate infrastructure that can meet the needs of society in the educational process that meets the requirements of functionality, controllability and adaptability in a culturally and morally developed person, a quality specialist;

3) the repetition, change and development of the educational system, contribution to the individual movement of the student, the disclosure of his skills, gifts, talents, interests, and the formation of special psychological qualities that help to eliminate them in the individual consciousness constitute an individual cognitive algorithm.

Continuous education at the level of society includes reproduction, change and development of ideas about education as a basic social value, purposeful activity of social subjects

(institutions, organizations, social groups, communities, individuals) to actualize. Aktualis - individual subjects in actual, real, modern, social reality and transformation of social reality according to modern possibilities and human needs. At this level, we can distinguish the following components of continuous education:

1) restoration of education as a cultural and historical value of humanity, transformation of attitudes towards educational activity into a natural form-forming, developing, changing activity of people in self-creation and creation of social reality;

2) the ability and change and development of skills and methods of managing information flows, methods of working with information, attitude to information, finding, selecting, analyzing information in a timely manner and transforming it into real projects (that is, real images). the future) readiness for rational action;

3) restoration, modification and development of reflective skills, verification and adjustment of educational activities, development of criteria for the success of educational activities, evaluation of the results of application of theoretical knowledge to the application field, information and methods in the field of practical use for new projects despite the re-application of what was previously known.

Only personality-oriented education can enable a person to develop as a personality that meets the demands of dynamically changing social and economic life.

CONTINUING EDUCATION AND THE PROBLEM OF SUCCESSION

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The concept of lifelong learning as a scientific theory appeared in the first half of the 20th century, associated with the expansion of education, and with it, in the early stages. Continuous education - as one of the main principles of state policy in the field of education, is the possibility of obtaining education at several levels based on existing educational standards, curricula and plans, ensuring interaction between different levels of education and its continuous continuation throughout a person's life. In the 60s and 70s of the last century, the idea of "continuous education" appeared as the main ideology in many countries of the world. At the same time, the emergence and development of the idea of "continuous education" was contrary to existing programs.

The concept of "continuous education" began to take shape in the 70s. According to the type and content of education, a system was established under different names: "continuous education", "restorative education", "continuous education", etc. then the initial review was substantially completed, both materially and organizationally. In the 70s and 90s of the 20th century, local and foreign scientists paid attention to the issues of more precisely defining the main characteristics of continuous education:

- goals;
- concept;
- functions;
- principles;
- integration;
- calculation of main subsystems;
- defining the features and functional goals of their interactions;
- integral education system, etc.

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, theoretical publications appeared in the literature on the issues of the formation of the idea of continuous education:

- constant development of personality as an active subject of work, knowledge, communication;
- a truly functioning system of state and public institutions that create opportunities for general education and professional training of a person, taking into account social needs and his personal needs;
- principles reflecting modern social trends in building education as an integral system aimed at individual development and as a component of conditions for social progress.

The current stage of development of educational structures is characterized by various forms of inclusion of the population in the vocational education process, which determines the necessity of ensuring the continuity of educational programs and the mutual activity of educational institutions based on the principle of mutual cooperation. continuity. The concept of "lifelong education" gained international scope thanks to the activities of UNESCO, it is associated with the dynamic nature of the development of society, continuous reconstruction and changing technologies, which lead to changes in the content of work.

Currently, continuous education is one of the most important areas of scientific research in the field of education in general. According to R. Dave's definition, continuous education is a

process of personal, social and professional development throughout life, carried out by a person in order to improve the quality of life.

It is a general and unifying idea that encompasses formal and informal learning. With the concept of continuous education, continuous education includes any purposeful learning that is carried out continuously with the aim of developing knowledge, skills and habits in the context of informatization of society and globalization. Continuous education is a complex of public and private educational institutions based on a different form of ownership, which ensures the organizational and material unity, continuity and connection of all relations of each education, taking into account the current and future social.

Continuous education is based on individual orientation. The principle of succession is of great importance here. When it is based on personality, its continuity in the world of personality is emphasized, it is something that allows a person to realize his desires through education, which helps him to understand himself. The main task in the implementation of the concept of "lifelong education" is to create a clear network of interconnected education capable of serving different groups of the population. This is based on the principle of succession.

The main provisions of the organizational and material foundations of the concept of "continuous education" in the guardianship aspect are:

- education is carried out throughout a person's life in accordance with the interests of society and the needs of an individual, regardless of age, quality of education and other external and internal limitations;
- continuous education, including modern forms of distance education and the self-education process, from the preschool level to the permanent education of adults in various forms of additional education, retraining and professional development;
- implementation of democracy, social openness, integrity, sustainability, flexibility, variability and completeness of the education system as the essence of continuous education;
- implementation of the concept, reconstruction of the network of educational institutions on the basis of multi-functionality, versatility and multi-level principles.

In addition to all of the above, it should be noted that continuous education is one of the requirements of today.

The reason for this is as follows:

1. The progress of civilization led to rapid obsolescence of knowledge. In the past, when the amount of knowledge was relatively small and grew relatively slowly, the process of formal education was completed in a few years. According to experts, at the beginning of the 20th century, knowledge was updated every 20-30 years, and society, maintaining a conservative education system, did not feel the lack of modern knowledge so acutely. Today, knowledge is updated by an average of 15% per year, that is, every six years. In the most knowledge-intensive industries, the half-life of knowledge is less than 2.5 years. In most countries, traditional basic education, due to its inertia, does not keep pace with the changing landscape and production needs of the world. As the scope of knowledge increased, it had to be expanded to include the structure of formal education. In connection with the increase in the rate of growth of the volume of knowledge, the need for their periodic updating increases. Continuous education is an integral part of our culture, which requires constant updating of knowledge in the chosen field of activity, that is, advanced training;

2. The growth of social dynamics creates a need to change the profession or field of activity determined by the higher education a person receives. This often leads to the need to acquire a new qualification, which must be confirmed by an appropriate diploma;

3. The increase in the standard of living leads to an increase in the types of activities related to a person's leisure time, some of which require special preparation. This direction is associated with the development of a person's personality.

Thus, the role of continuous education is increasing, because the influence of the listed factors on a person's life will only increase, so they cannot be ignored. At the end of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century, new criteria were formed in the development of continuous education, which are currently being considered in the following aspect:

- pedagogic - development of whole and consistent content of education, search and testing of effective technologies;
- management - preparation and application of models for the operation and development of the continuous education system;
- legal - normative - legal support not only of the continuous education system itself, but of all its subjects;
- socio-psychological - the opportunity to receive continuous education by various social groups, taking into account the needs and abilities of the individual and production.

In the framework of the innovative economy in our country, the development of continuous education in the new socio-economic conditions acquires a completely different quality, the reason for which is not only the constantly updated social requirements for the professional qualities of highly qualified workers, but also the need to take into account personal motives that are manifested individually. In particular, the application of the Bologna process in higher education and within certain recommendations in the field of professional education, the purpose of continuous education is to meet the educational needs of individuals as fully as possible. The following are required for the further development of the modern continuous vocational education system:

- create conditions to ensure the educational mobility of students;
- to form a national system for evaluating the quality of education;
- vocational training;
- preparing a retraining program;
- to expand the list of organizations that have the right to provide services in the continuous vocational education system;
- to implement an advanced education system based on the principles of modularity.

Taking into account the current and future social situation of continuous education, the problem of succession arises in the complex of public and private educational institutions based on different forms of ownership, which ensures the organizational and material unity, continuity and connection of all links of each education. According to most assessments, economic revival in the country, radical development in the quality of personnel, without ensuring the competitiveness of the country, the development of all areas of the life of the state and society, increases dramatically while performing the functions of adapting the professional competences of the main and additional personnel to the rapidly changing requirements of the economy. Creation and development of continuous education is considered the basis for solving the personnel problem. The concept of modernization of continuous education has determined one of the priority areas for solving the problems of ensuring the quality, accessibility and efficiency of education - the development of the system of continuous professional education. In order to solve the set tasks in the medium term, it is necessary to ensure the development of the continuous education infrastructure:

- creation of a nationwide system to assess the quality of education at all levels, as well as during the passage of various educational programs that ensure advanced training, changing the forms and fields of activity;
- expanding the number of organizations that implement educational programs for continuous education (primarily professional development and retraining of personnel) by involving various non-educational organizations that have the resources to implement various additional programs within the framework of internal education;

- the development of public and professional organizations with a wide representation of employers, whose activity will be directed to the formation of qualification requirements for the level of specialist training according to the requirements of the labor market, the search and selection of modern educational technologies;

- assessment of the quality of educational programs (certification and accreditation);

- transition to the modular principle of building programs of continuous education, which ensures the increase of educational mobility, as well as greater flexibility of the educational system, focusing on the individual needs of the student and the requirements of the labor market;

- transition from management of educational institutions to management of educational programs.

As a result, management functions such as monitoring, financing and performance evaluation related to educational programs will be carried out. The concept ensures the implementation of the transition to a two-level education system (taking into account the peculiarities of the organization of education in a number of specialties), the creation of organizational and legal mechanisms for the integration of programs. For this reason, the development of continuous education is one of the priority directions of the state education policy.

At the current stage of world economic and social development, the sustainability of education should be considered the most important global problem. Regardless of the field, which aspects of education, upbringing, human development are taken into account, it is necessary to express the attitude to the following aspects of education:

- unites with a common goal and covers the entire population, all socio-demographic groups;

- continuity or variability in time and space of common social goals and methods of their implementation;

- taking into account the time, types, orientation of the needs of each individual.

What is the objective necessity to solve the succession problem in continuing education? First of all, it is the dynamics of world and social development, the acceleration of socio-economic progress, which has a decisive impact on both the material and spiritual aspects of the state as a whole and the life of each individual. The lack of work ability, the need to constantly update the knowledge gained as a result of education, arising from solving unexpected and increasingly complex social and professional tasks during work, lead to the emergence of organized and various forms. A realistic assessment of the current situation prompts the search for new approaches to qualitatively change the state of the entire education system. It should be in line with the modern development of the economy and prepare specialists for innovative activities. For the state and society, continuous education becomes a leading area of social policy, which provides favorable conditions for the general and professional development of a person, a mechanism for the reproduction of professional and cultural potential, and a condition for the development of social production.

In the 21st century, the concept of continuous education has gained major importance. It is the answer to the challenge posed by a world where change is happening so rapidly. The need to restore education and professional training arises every time one encounters innovations in one's professional and personal life. This need is becoming more and more important. Continuing education implies the diversity and flexibility of the types of education used, its humanization, democratization and individualization. An important feature of the succession problem in continuing education is the future-oriented desire to solve the development problems of society using professional knowledge acquired before obtaining higher qualifications. To solve this succession problem, you need to know the basics of continuing education. This is the main system of ideas that should be implemented in the process of designing an educational institution system

that accompanies a person in different periods of his life. The principles of continuous education are based on the following theoretical principles:

- covering all human life with education;
- understanding of the education system as a whole system that combines and integrates all its levels and forms, including pre-school education, basic, consecutive, repeated, parallel education;
- inclusion of formal, informal and non-institutional forms of education from educational institutions and centers for additional education into the additional education system;
- horizontal integration home - neighbors - local social sphere - society - business world - mass media - leisure, cultural, religious organizations, etc. among the topics studied is the existence of different aspects of human development (physical, moral, intellectual, etc.) at certain stages of life;
- vertical integration between different stages of education (pre-school, school, post-school), different levels and objects within different stages, as well as different social roles performed by a person at certain stages of his life, different qualities of human development (physical, moral, intellectual (temporary qualities such as development, etc.) formation;
- emphasis on self-management, self-discipline, self-esteem;
- individualization of education in conditions of different generations of learning (in family, society) to expand one's horizons, interdisciplinary knowledge, quality, flexibility and variety, tools and techniques, time and place of training;
- dynamic approach to knowledge - the ability to absorb new scientific achievements, improve learning skills, stimulate motivation to study, create appropriate conditions and environment for learning, and implement creative and innovative approaches;
- in order to facilitate the change of social roles in different periods of life, the cognition and development of one's own value system, the preservation and improvement of the quality of individual and collective life through individual, social and professional development, the development of the society that nurtures and educates, the coherence of the principles for the entire educational process.

NATIONAL MORAL VALUES

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What are the greatest, most valuable values for a nation? - Of course, religion and language, cultural-spiritual heritage inherited from history and so on.

What distinguishes one nation from others is actually its national and moral values. The great leader Heydar Aliyev said in one of his speeches: "Azerbaijani people living in the world should never forget their mother tongue, religion, and national traditions. Every Azerbaijani should be proud that he has a homeland like Azerbaijan, which has a great history and an ancient, rich culture." He also said: "Our national and moral values have been formed in the life and living of our people for centuries. A nation without national and moral values cannot be a real nation, a real people." By the way, let's note that the great leader had enough services in protecting and promoting our national and moral values. Let's note just one fact that with the initiative and determination of the great leader Heydar Aliyev, when the Constitution of the Azerbaijan SSR was adopted in the Soviet period, the status of our mother tongue as the state language was established, and Novruz holiday was widely promoted.

The people of Azerbaijan have always shown their loyalty to national values and developed them by keeping these values alive for centuries. In every period of history, the protection of our national values and their transmission to future generations has been relevant in our country. Even today, this positive trend is maintained. Because our national values have a great influence on the formation of the Azerbaijani people, and they also have a special role in strengthening our national statehood.

It is an undeniable fact that Islam is considered one of the most important factors of our national and moral values. Although the people of Azerbaijan lived for 70 years under the conditions of atheistic propaganda, they never forgot their religious values and lived them, albeit secretly.

Our national and moral values have been formed for centuries in the life, living and activities of our people. A nation without national and moral values cannot be a real nation, a real people. Our advantage is that our young and strong state is built on a solid foundation. It is built on centuries-old history and culture.

It is a reality that today in Azerbaijan not only Islam, but also representatives of other religions live together with us, live, freely, without any restrictions and practice their religious beliefs. There are enough places of worship in Azerbaijan even for non-Muslims. churches, synagogues were built. This makes our country known as a tolerant country in the world. For this reason, the traditions of tolerance in Azerbaijan can be considered our national and moral value. Therefore, tolerance is considered our national characteristic from centuries.

As in all fields, the steps taken by President Ilham Aliyev, who continues the policies and ideas of the national leader Heydar Aliyev in the direction of protecting our national and moral values and further improving religion-state relations, as well as the measures he has implemented for the development of the Islamic religion, are highly valued in the Muslim world. Paying special attention to national and moral values, President Ilham Aliyev notes: "Azerbaijan is loyal to its national and religious values. Our religious values are a part of our national values, and it is impossible to imagine our national values without religious values. It has been our values that have protected and maintained us as a nation and a people for centuries. Today, a lot of attention is paid to this issue. In today's globalized and troubled world, our national values form the basis of our statehood.

As in every state, language is considered a part of its national and moral values in Azerbaijan. Therefore, the development of the Azerbaijani language and its enrichment has always been a priority for our state.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation, distinguished by its large-scale activity in the preservation and promotion of national and moral values, has achieved great success in this field over the past years. The president of the foundation, the goodwill ambassador of UNESCO and ISESCO, the deputy of the Milli Majlis, Mehriban Aliyeva, always focuses on the protection and restoration of historical, religious and cultural monuments.

When talking about national and moral values, it is impossible not to mention mugham. Mugham is the pearl of our nation, its genetic code. Mugham passed from generation to generation and remained in the blood memory of the Azerbaijani people, leaving an eternal mark in their hearts. As UNESCO's Goodwill Ambassador, First Lady of Azerbaijan Mehriban Aliyeva wrote: "Mugham is a special moment in our hearts."

As a result of our state's great concern for mugham, this art not only conquers new heights day by day, but also creates an impetus for the creation of new projects.

Today, Azerbaijan is a country that is modernizing and taking the path of rapid integration into Europe and the world community. For each country and people, its national values should be given priority over everything else and should not conflict with the values of other peoples. In this regard, when we say globalization, we mean international cooperation, good relations, and sincere friendship in Azerbaijan.

We must always fight against the values that are not characteristic of the national mentality, which are contrary to the traditions of other nations under the name of globalization. Of course, protecting our national identity is one of the most important conditions in this struggle. Therefore, as long as our national moral values live, our national identity will also exist. When these values change, we will see a different national identity. Therefore, efforts should be made to protect national and moral values among young people, and their feelings of patriotism and citizenship should be strengthened. In particular, in this direction, the quality of the educational process should be increased, scientific-theoretical and methodical recommendations should be developed, and the creation of a normative-legal base should be achieved. The point to be positively evaluated is that today at the state level, we can see more purposeful activity in the direction of protecting and preserving the national and moral values that form the basis of the national identity.

Today, our society is developing and modernizing. It is becoming more and more difficult to protect our national values at a time when we are living in various influences. In this sense, the protection of our national values and their transmission to future generations is still relevant.

NOUN-ADJECTIVE TRAINING

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It has been repeatedly noted by linguists and methodologists that the use of intersubject communication in Azerbaijani language classes is an important tool in the development of students' grammatical thinking. A. Abdullayev notes that intra-subject communication consists of two types, such as inter-subject and inter-topic, and writes: "Azerbaijani language subject itself is a system of lessons that are interconnected and organized in certain topics".

In other methodological works, the positive effect of creating an internal connection between those topics is noted and examples of interdisciplinary communication are shown whenever possible. However, the considerations in the methodical literature on intra-disciplinary communication are in the form of probabilities and are not aimed at solving a specific problem. Language materials are based on certain laws and principles according to the language's own system. B. Ahmadov justified the objective necessity of the application of intra-disciplinary communication in linguistics on the basis of the law, and took the principles and requirements arising from this law into a certain system. B. Ahmadov formulated three laws of language teaching by summarizing the considerations on the laws and regularities of language teaching in the Russian-language methodical literature. One of the laws defined by him is called the law of systematization of differentiated components of language in learning.

B. Ahmadov justifies the objective nature of this law as follows: "When learning a language, a child does not learn the components separately, nor does he have an idea about the components. Every person acquires the sound system, lexicon, grammar of the language in a unified way. There is no such person who first learns sounds, then words, then suffixes, etc. let him learn. Therefore, the practical acquisition of the language is complex. But theoretical issues of the language are taught in a differentiated way at school."

According to that law, language teaching is based on the student's real speech experience, language, which is a whole system, is taught by dividing it into parts in the form of sections and topics, the role of each language unit in speech development is expanded and enriched by teaching its theoretical issues. Therefore, the criterion for mastering theoretical issues in each language lesson is measured by the level of development of practical speech skills. Different facts of the language, for example: noun, adjective, verb, completeness, simple sentence, etc. even learning it in the form is not an indicator of mastering the subject of the Azerbaijani language. It is possible for the student to learn in detail any fact from the language system, say, adjective, simple, modifying and compound adjectives, degrees of adjective, etc. the student should have complete information about However, if the student cannot connect the morphological and syntactic features of the adjective with other word groups, he cannot determine the internal connection between language facts, acquire scientific knowledge about the language, and achieve the ability to use the results of scientific knowledge in a complex manner. The existence of objective relationships between language facts and the need to rely on this relationship in the learning process is determined by this factor.

The laws defined by B. Ahmadov for language teaching were explained by H. Baliyev at the level of the concept of law and made more concrete. H. Baliyev interpreted the laws of language teaching comparatively within the limits of objective laws of nature and society independent of human will, and he did not consider it correct to describe the signs and events that manifest themselves in the teaching as laws. H. Baliyev writes: "Therefore, it should not be a matter of constantly showing oneself in the training process, but of the necessity of constantly showing

oneself. Taking into account the unity and difference of language with thinking makes it necessary for the learning process to show itself constantly. It is impossible to live without it".

H.Baliyev, B.Ahmedov does not consider the second law (mastery of language norms on the basis of speech practice) and the third law (combination of differentiated components in the teaching of language into a system) as independent laws. He notes that the laws of language learning should be defined as such laws, whose failure to take them into account can result in the nullification of the learning process. B.Baliyev considers the second and third law to be the law of result, which is a derivative of one law, and interprets the second law of language teaching as "the law of mixing, adapting and encountering concepts in language teaching, or the law of integration". Since the law of integration constantly manifests itself in the learning process, it is impossible to consciously master the language without relying on this law. The essence is that all components of the language should be taught in the form of interactions, taking into account their individual characteristics, language units divided into sections and topics should be taught in order to facilitate learning, and the most important similar characteristics should be compared. Not only the facts of a section, but also the relationship between sections should be considered.

For example: the word concept is the scientific unit of the language as a research object of all sections in a differentiated way. Accordingly, the phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, stylistic, etc. of the word. signs should be taught in a related manner, the system of the language should be expected. The law of being based on interference makes it necessary to expect the following methodological requirements in training, and the teacher should expect awareness in mastering by following the following requirements during the lesson:

1. Similar and different signs of concepts should be mastered in all their details in language teaching, including teaching nouns and adjectives;

2. The most important, constantly manifesting similar signs of the concepts should be taught in connection;

3. In the teaching of each new topic, the foundation for the next topic should be created, attention should be paid to the educational significance of the signs that can be taught in connection;

4. Each subsequent topic should be a continuation of the previous one, repeat it, expand it, create conditions for applying it to speech practice;

5. The teacher should pay attention to the fact that language lessons consist of two stages. First, it is necessary to interpret the theoretical data, and then to achieve a practical interpretation of those data.

Anticipating the principles and requirements related to the law of interference and the implementation of appropriate requirements in the teaching process will stimulate both the conscious assimilation of theoretical information and the development of speech habits. The law of interference in the learning process requires that each section be divided into appropriate sections in the form of topics according to the system of the language. Without mastering the main features of each morphological concept, it is possible to learn about its similar and different features with other concepts.

So, the dictionary of the noun includes groups of meanings, structure, grammatical signs, etc. comprehensive study of its aspects will create conditions for the conscious assimilation of parts of speech such as adjectives, numbers, and verbs. Other parts of speech cannot be learned without mastering all the details of the lexical-grammatical nature of the noun, for example, the signs of case and affiliation. Also, since it is the main condition for the existence of the parts of speech included in the group of nouns, it is necessary to try to make it fully understood by the students.

Compared to other parts of speech, nouns have a wider lexical meaning, so it is necessary to devote a lot of time to its teaching. Since the lexical groups of nouns are rich and play an important role in the development of speech, especially in the enrichment of the vocabulary, it is an important issue to work on the vocabulary units included in this group, to teach the actual knowledge gained by students about the words denoting the names of things in the grammar background. Observations on the students' speech show that they have difficulty in listing the lexical features of nouns and including the given words in the meaning groups compared to the meaning groups of other word groups, for example, adjectives.

Part of this difficulty is related to the similarity and richness of the lexical meaning groups of the noun, and the other part is related to not being able to assess the practical nature of the issue. During the determining experiment, it became clear that the work carried out on the lexical meaning groups of the noun is not carried out at a normal level in terms of the current requirements and the final goal of mother tongue education. Teachers give examples of known lexical meaning groups of nouns from lower classes, are satisfied with the explanation of a few examples, and finish the work on meaning groups by explaining nouns with small content such as names of people and animals, names of plants and fruits, names of places, names of inanimate objects. The amount of studies on meaning groups of nouns in the textbook is small.

There are many types of nouns that differ in lexical meaning, and it is possible to cover the words included in these groups only in orthographic explanatory dictionaries and determine their relative quantity. From this, we can come to the conclusion that neither in grammar books nor in methodical studies, the meaning of a noun should be taught in the learning process, not all existing words, but only those nouns with a high frequency of processing, which serve more in the development of speech habits and reflect specific lexical meaning characteristics, meaning those names should be referred to in the classification of groups. Observations show that the work on the lexical meaning of nouns denoting the names of concrete entities visible to the eye does not cause serious difficulties. The lexical meaning of specific nouns that include human and personal names, body parts and words denoting kinship, animal and plant names, household and clothing names, names of vehicles, names of weapons, names of professions and arts, names of national musical instruments, names of substances grouping is easy and performed without errors. Since the students confuse the nouns denoting the names of places, rivers, seas and mountains with compound nouns that answer the question of the noun, it is necessary to explain the words included in this group of meanings in the process of teaching compound nouns.

Of course, it should be taken into account that the systematic course uses materials taught in lower classes, and the repetition process should lead to new knowledge. However, here it should be a matter of creative repetition, the basis for new knowledge should be created by enumerating the facts known to the student.

MAJOR TECHNIQUES OF CLT IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

The article analyzes the main effective techniques of language learning of the Communicative Language Teaching method. The study scrutinizes the privileges techniques of the CLT in learning and teaching process while applying them effectively. Some techniques have been illustrated in the article. Besides, it has been noted that the usage of native language while learning the foreign language through this method is avoided. Grammar is not prioritized as other methods. It has been revealed that the integration of language skills is observed while teaching the foreign language through this method.

Key words: grammar, CLT, language skills, integration, techniques

In modern period, English is studied as a main means of communication as a foreign language in international arena. There are a bunch of methods that are used in teaching and learning English effectively. One of these methods is Communicative Language Teaching method. CLT or (CA) Communicative Approach is a language teaching method which is based on interaction. Language learners use interaction to learn the foreign language by communications with one another and the teacher. The learners had better use authentic materials in order to acquire the language efficiency. Students speak about their personal experience with partners and the teachers tries to teach the grammar along with other themes to develop language skills in any environment. Nunan defines the Communicative language teaching method as "That method also claims to encourage learners to incorporate their personal experiences into their language learning environment and to focus on the learning experience, in addition to learning of the target language" [11, p. 280]

According to Communicative language teaching, the purpose of language teaching is the ability to build up communication in the target language [14]. The author underlines that Communicative language teaching method is the next teaching method that denies the employment of mother tongue [5, p.51]

This oppose to previous views in which grammatical skills were considered as a priority [1, p. 287] Grammar is taught superficially through this method [4].

CLT is an approach which targets to obtain communication rather than linguistic competence via student communication. It appeared around 1980s. To improve meaningful language usage, ESL instructors may use activities which encourage students to converse in the performance of meaningful assignments. Interaction is not only a method, but also the purpose of ESL.

Integration of speaking, writing and reading

The studies have revealed that conversational techniques in pairs and groups alone are not sufficient to develop active participation in ESL classrooms. Teachers using the Communicative Language Teaching method could also include listening, writing and reading since these skills are also crucial to ELLs' promotion as English language speakers. The author notes: "There are different features that belong to CLT which includes the integration of speaking, writing and

reading skills” [8, p.13] The author writes: “Speaking skill forms as a result of listening process while writing skill formalizes as a result of reading process” [7, p. 7].

The integrated-speech approach to Communicative Language Teaching brings these main language talents together in activities. For example, The instructors can ask the learners to watch a video online, send their opinions about the post in the comment space (writing) and depict others’ views from the comments section (reading). It means that if you write a comment, you see others’ opinions as well. You develop your writing skill by writing and you boost your reading skill by reading the opinions of other people. When you look at somebody’s opinion and don’t understand one or two words, you immediately look the unknown words up in the offline or online dictionaries and learn the meaning of those words. Activities which integrate a number of language skills can develop interaction-based ESL education by suggesting the learners the opportunity to work on multiple skills while also suggesting instructors an opportunity to show the best experiences in each of these modes.

Communicative language teaching makes teachers facilitators in the mean. Moreover, this approach is regarded as a non-methodical system that does not require any textbook to teach the foreign language but develops pronunciation skills before writing and reading.

Language learning was considered a cognitive issue which involved memorization mainly. Then it was accepted as a socio-cognitive skill. Hence language may be acquired by mean of social communication. Nowadays, though, the dominant technique in teaching any language is communicative language teaching [10, p.542].

As to Noam Chomsky, performance and competence were focused on which gave a rise to emergence of CLT. However, conceptual background of communicative Language Teaching method was laid in 1970s by Michael Halliday. He studied how language is expressed through grammar. Prior to the development of Communicative language teaching, main language teaching method was considered to be situational language teaching method. In Britain the linguists started to suspect of the effectiveness of situational language teaching.

In 1966 Dell Hymes developed the concept of communicative competence. He identified what “to know a language” meant. Besides the mastery of the structural language elements, they must be able to use those structural elements appropriately in a variety of domains [13, p.23].

Mitchel, Rosamond wrote in the book where Dell Hymes stated : “ There are rules of use without which the rules of grammar would be useless” This thought sources from Chomsky’s idea of the linguistic competence of an ideal language bearer. Hymes’s formulation of communicative competence was not concrete but the authors after him namely Canale tries the language teaching concept [3, p.47]. He divided communicative competence into 3 elements: socio-linguistic competence, grammatical competence and strategic competence. The only difference is that Canale added one more component –discourse competence which includes the notions of coherence and cohesion.

The teachers who prefer Communicative Language Teaching method choose classroom activities which develop communicative skills in the target language. These activities are very effective. This method has more advantages than disadvantages [9, p.91]. CLT is very effective in teaching all language skills including reading, writing, speaking and listening. However, writing skill is developed on the basis of colloquial speech [6,p.44]. Oral practice is very famous among the teachers who apply Communicative language teaching method. This is opposed to reading and writing activities, as well as grammar dill exercises since oral practice requires active conversation and unpredicted and creative answers from the learners. Activities are different depending on the level of students where they are used. These activities develop fluency, collaboration and comfort in the target language. The main activities which are used in Communicative language teaching have been listed below;

Role-play

Role-play is an oral activity which is done in pairs. Its major aim is to improve the students' communicative skills. For example,

1. The teacher make the students describe a scene at the airport, in the restaurant, at the hospital, etc.
2. The teacher determines the purpose of the students' conversation such as asking the destination, ordering fish and chips, etc.
3. The students speak in pairs for a certain period of time.

The above mentioned activities give the students opportunity to develop their communicative abilities in the target language. Most of the students feel more convenient conversing in pairs rather than before the whole class.

The teachers should know about the distinctions between an utterance and a conversation. The students can use the identical utterances many times while doing this activity and not, in fact, have a creative conversation. If the teachers don't regulate what kinds of conversations students have, the students might not improve their communicative abilities.

Interviews

Interview is an oral activity conducted in pairs. Its major aim is to develop learners' interpersonal abilities in the target language. For instance:

1. The teacher distribute all the students the same question card to ask the partner.
2. Pairs ask and answer questions each other.

In this activity there is a pressing need to monitor the students' answers because the questions are highly structured. The questions can cover one more ore specific features of vocabulary or grammar.

This tactic should be used mainly in language classes which are at lower level since it will be more efficient for lower-level students. Higher-level students should have unpredictable talks in the target language where not either questions or the answers are written or anticipated. If this activity was used among the high-level learners, it would be inefficient for them.

Group work

Group work is based on collaborative activity. Its main aim is to develop communication skills in the target language, in a larger group setting [2, p.285]. For example:

1. The number of students does not exceed 6 in a group.
2. The learners have conventional names in the group such as eagle, wolf, etc.
3. The teacher gives every group the same assignment to finish.
4. Every member of the group is allocated arranged time to work on the assignment.
5. The group members discuss the information they have been given with one another and do the task all together.

The learners may feel overwhelmed in language class-room, however this activity may take away from that sense. The learners are asked to concentrate on one piece of data only that increases their understanding of that information. Better understanding brings about better interaction in the group which develops the learners' communicative skills in the target language.

The teacher should monitor and make sure that every student helps equally to the effort of the group. So the instructor should design the activity properly. In this case all the students will assist equally and take advantage of the activity.

Information gap

Information gap is based on collaborative activity as well. Its main goal is to get information effectively for the students which was unknown to them in the target language [12, p.20]. For example:

- 1) The students are divided into two groups in the classroom. One partner in every pair is called Partner A and the other is named Partner B.

- 2) All the learners who include Partner A are given a piece of paper with a grid on it. The grid is filled incompletely, however some boxes are empty.
- 3) All the learners who are the members of Partner B are given a piece of paper with a grid on it. The boxes which are empty on Partner B's grid are filled in on Partner B's. You can find empty boxes on Partner B's time-table, as well, but they are filled in on Partner A's.
- 4) The partners should work together to ask about and provide one another with data they both miss to fill in each other's grids.

Completion of the information gap activities develops the learners' skills about unknown information in the target language.

These skills are directly relevant to numerous real-world conversations where the purpose is to define some more information which is new or just to exchange data.

The teachers should not look down on the fact that their students should be ready to interact effectively for this activity. They should be aware of definite word stock, certain grammatical structures. If the students don't prepare for the assignment well, they won't be able to communicate properly.

Opinion sharing

This is a contest-based activity. Its main aim is to engage students' conversational abilities while conversing about something that they are keen on. For example:

- 1) The teacher presents a topic and asks the learners to think seriously about the views (e.g., climate change, dating, education abroad)
- 2) The learners speak in pairs or in small groups arguing on their views on the topic.

Opinion sharing is an effective way of getting introverted students to open up and share their views. If a learner owns a strong and different view about a certain topic, he speaks up and share.

Respect is a main factor in this activity. If the student feels like his views are not respected by the teacher or his peers, he/she won't feel convenient in sharing and will not gain the communicative profit of this activity.

A scavenger hunt

This is a mixed activity which develops open communication between students. For example,

1. The teacher gives a sheet with instructions to the students.
2. Students walk around the classroom and ask and answer questions about each other
3. The learners desire to find all the questions that they should finish the scavenger hunt.

Doing this activity, the learners have the chance to talk to some classmates in a low-pressure environment. They talk to one person at a time. After knowing and sharing information with each other, the learners feel more relaxed while talking and sharing during other communication activities.

Though Communicative Language Teaching method is very effective in the language teaching environment, it is not accepted by everyone and it has been criticized.

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HOW TO MAKE A SCHOOL LESSON INTERESTING

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We conduct lessons in elementary school in an interesting and original way.

Many adults are familiar with the standard phrase of the school teacher "they have opened their books" - and immediately there is some longing in the heart. Motivation - zero. The problem is that such a teacher does not know how or simply does not want to motivate children to work in class. But a good tutor in an elementary school will be able to attract the student's attention and draw him into productive work. And it is not necessary to "arrange a concert" or "go on a wheel" for this. A fairly simple reception, after which close attention of the audience is guaranteed.

In this article, we will tell you how to motivate students from the very beginning of the lesson. These tips are suitable for any subject: both humanitarian and exact disciplines.

In the age of modern technologies, technology is used quite often in classes - computers and laptops with projectors. If there are none, you can use interesting pictures or posters. Quite often, teachers simply lead a story in an interesting way, which works as well as the most colorful presentation. As they say, who is good at what?

If you are thinking about where to start for the first time, it is better to choose a presentation. Plus, it can be used several times, it is an excellent spare option that allows you to conduct lessons in several classes. Having saved the template for the next year, you will have a ready-made lesson plan that does not require additional preparation.

Useful tips for preparing a presentation:

The first slide should be interesting and motivating, its task is to involve students in the lesson. You can choose a picture and write a statement, a riddle or a fact that relates to the topic of the lesson.

Compilation of the rest of the slides - first of all, we determine the number. Each person is given approximately 5 minutes, so you should carefully calculate the time. For each page, we must select a picture and captions.

Video can also be added if the hardware allows. They must be short, maximum – up to 2 minutes. After all, there should be discussions in lessons, not movies.

If you look at the synopsis, break the text into slides. So it will be easier and more convenient to announce the job.

How interesting is it to finish the lesson at school?

It is recommended to leave interesting facts for homework, for example: "how did this story end, we will find out at home after reading the last chapter of the work". At the end of the lesson, students are given such a task, which will be the subject of discussion at the beginning of the next lesson. If you managed to interest the children at the beginning and during the whole lesson, they will gladly read the story to the end at home and also enthusiastically tell about it in the survey.

When planning a lesson with several classes, it is especially important to correctly determine the place and nature of children's independent work. The root disadvantage of the lessons of many teachers of two-set and one-set schools is the randomness and far-fetchedness of the tasks they give for self-study of students. Often these tasks are given by the teacher to the class not in order to solve any tasks of the lesson, but only to occupy the children with something while he works with another class. Hence, the unacceptable waste of time in the lesson, which

inevitably leads to incompleteness, lagging in the completion of the program and a low level of student achievement.

The second, no less important drawback, which also has to be encountered in the practice of two-set and one-set schools, is the lack of sufficient preparation of children for independent work: the teacher often gives children independent work, for which the students do not have the necessary knowledge and skills and do not master the form предложенной им работы. Independent work in the lesson can be productive if it is well thought out by the teacher beforehand and thoroughly prepared by him. It is unacceptable that the independent work of students in the lesson was accidental or contrived. It should strictly correspond to the purpose and content of the lesson and be closely related to the immediate work of the teacher.

The teacher sometimes incorrectly determines the place of independent work in the lesson. There are often cases when teachers give children tasks for independent study of new material according to the textbook without prior explanation of this material. Such "independent" work, in fact, repeats the harmful practice that existed in schools, when students, having neither the relevant knowledge nor skills, worked on the teacher's assignment on new material, being left to themselves. This method of "independent" work is condemned and cannot be used in lessons. Independent work of students when the teacher works with several classes should be conducted under the guidance of the teacher and be based on the knowledge and skills available to the children. Therefore, its place in the lesson is mainly where repetition or consolidation of what has been passed is carried out. It should be a supplement to the teacher's direct work, completing it when what the teacher explained to the children is consolidated, and preceding it when a repetition of what has been passed is required for assimilation of new material.

When working with several classes, it is necessary that individual lessons are closely related to each other, not only in terms of content, but also in terms of organization. Establishing such a connection is especially important in those cases when the independent work of students is prepared by the teacher in advance, sometimes two or three days before its implementation.

This obliges teachers to plan their work with children not only for one upcoming day, but for several days ahead. Such a plan is first drawn up in general terms. In it, the teacher outlines only the content of individual lessons.

Three columns are initially filled. The column, in which the course of the lesson is recorded, is filled not immediately, but gradually, in preparation for each next day of work.

To plan the content of individual lessons a few days in advance, the teacher needs to familiarize himself with the teaching material in detail. At the same time, the teacher's task is not only to correctly distribute the material in the lessons, but also to establish a close connection between them. In the teacher's work plan, the lessons must be presented in a certain system, the parts of which are internally connected with each other. Thanks to this, randomness and deliberateness are eliminated in the choice of content and forms of individual classes with children and especially independent work of students.

In the case when the teacher conducts a lesson in both classes on one and the same subject, for example, grammar, arithmetic, even though he is dealing with different material in each class, he still operates with similar ideas and concepts. And this gives him the opportunity to sometimes unite younger and older children for joint work. Here's an example: the teacher exercises the students of 4th grade in grammatical analysis.

He attracts 2 classes to this work. In the sentences written on the board for analysis, students of the 2nd grade indicate the words denoting the name of the subject, the action, the quality, determine which question is answered by one or another word, find in the words according to the teacher's assignment, abnormal vowels, doubtful consonants, etc. д., and students of 4th grade understand these words, specifying their grammatical forms, their morphological composition, changing them according to the teacher's instructions, etc. d. Or even

an example: in the lesson of grammar, the teacher intends to give students of the junior class an independent teacher.

Only under this condition can the attachment or repetition of the passed material be successful. The explanation of the new material and the subsequent independent work of the children in this lesson is planned in the same way as in the lesson of studying the new material in both classes.

The lesson, on which the content of the work in both classes is a reflection on the subject material, does not present any special difficulties for construction. In such lessons, the teacher has more opportunities for independent work of children than in the lessons of the two previous types.

In this lesson, the teacher begins direct work with children in that class, where it is easier to give independent work or where it is necessary to preface the task for independent work with oral exercises or a conversation with children. If in one of the classes on this lesson it is supposed to conduct a control work, then the teacher should start work with this class. Having received an assignment from the teacher for control work, children can work independently throughout the lesson.

If in both classes it is planned to consolidate or repeat what has been passed, then this is carried out both in the direct work of the teacher with that and the other class and in the independent classes of children.

Direct work of the teacher with the children to consolidate or repeat what was passed in such lessons is absolutely mandatory. In these cases, you cannot limit yourself to the independent work of children, as it is. often happens in practice.

In the following lesson plan, the immediate work of the teacher in the junior class is scheduled after the assignment to the senior class, which the teacher gives at the beginning of the lesson. In the senior class, the immediate work of the teacher with children to consolidate or repeat what has been passed is provided at the beginning of the lesson in connection with the explanation of the task for independent work and after the independent work of children in connection with its verification.

In lessons of this type, the teacher can sometimes plan the independent work of children in both classes at the same time. This occurs most often in arithmetic and spelling lessons, when the immediate work of the teacher to consolidate and repeat what has been learned with the children is expressed in the form of exercises, some of which the children perform independently.

When planning a lesson, there are four classes - with them, the distribution of time in the lessons is mainly determined by the degree of complexity of the content of the work in separate classes. It is clear that in the class where the lesson material is more complicated, more time should be allocated to the teacher's immediate work with the children. Learning new material, as a rule, requires the teacher to work more directly with children than to consolidate or repeat what has been passed. In those classes, where independent work on the basis of previously prepared material is possible during most of the lesson, the immediate work of the teacher takes no more than 5 -10 minutes. This is quite enough to view children's work, give the necessary instructions or change the nature of the task.

The main attention of the teacher should be paid to classes with children in the class where the new material is studied. At the beginning of the lesson, it is advisable to give a small task for independent work in this class, for example: check the homework written work according to the text on the board, check the correctness of the solutions to the homework problems and examples according to the solution prepared by the teacher, consider the subject of study or its image, conduct observing the instruction of the teacher, recalling what has been passed and preparing answers to the teacher's questions, etc.

Each of these tasks should not take more than 5 minutes to complete. At this time, the teacher gives the rest of the class a pre-prepared independent work and then proceeds to explain the new material.

The most difficult and responsible lessons in the conditions of work of a teacher with several classes are those in which new material is studied in one or two classes. The difficulty of conducting such lessons is that each lesson in the class, where new material is studied, must be held with more or less direct participation of the teacher. This requires the teacher to be able to conduct the lesson according to the plan, if possible to consolidate his work and at the same time conduct it at each stage with such results that it ensures the readiness of the transition of children to the next stage. For example, preparation for the perception of new material should be carried out so that it really contributes to the assimilation of this material; the explanation of the new material should sufficiently orient each student in further independent classes.

Repetition of what has been passed in order to prepare children for the perception of new material can be carried out through independent work of children, but under the condition of the subsequent direct repetition of this material with the teacher. At the same time, it is necessary to keep in mind that tasks for independent work of children in this case should be very simple, quite accessible for completion both in terms of content and form. For self-repetition of what has been passed before studying new material, you can only give what was well learned by the children and what does not require the teacher to spend a lot of time explaining the task. Along with this, it is necessary to choose such types of independent work, the technique of which the children have mastered well.

In this case, silent reading with preparation of answers to questions written by the teacher on the board can be attributed to independent work in the easiest form in this case; writing out the text or writing out of the text certain words or sentences of different kinds by changing the forms of words, underlining, etc.; written solution of examples and tasks.

In the conditions of the work of a teacher with several classes, it is advisable to prepare children for lessons in which new material is studied, in advance, in previous lessons on this subject. It is especially necessary to do this in those cases when it is necessary to repeat the study material that is significant in volume or difficult in content. But if the independent work in terms of content and performance technique is well known to children, for example, the solution of numerical examples of a certain type, and the assignment of this work does not require detailed explanations from the teacher, then such work can be given directly in the lesson before the explanation of the new material, without connecting it with doing homework.

When conducting a lesson with two or several classes, the teacher is guided by the same general didactic principles as when working with one class. But when explaining the new material in the conditions of working with several classes, it is necessary to take into account one more very important circumstance. The explanation of the new material should be followed by independent work for children. This obliges the teacher to conduct the explanation in such a way that it prepares children for independent work.

STRATEGIES OF CREATING ENGLISH LANGUAGE ENVIRONMENT IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING CLASS

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Abstract: The globalization of the world of English as a lingua franca and the development of new information and communication technologies (ICT) made conversation with foreigners as easy as possible. Creating a language atmosphere was never easier than today. However, there are still problems with promoting the language environment in FLE classes and making the students use their mother tongue less than the target language. This article seeks to explore the significance of cultivating a robust language environment within the classroom, examining its multifaceted components and the pivotal role it plays in enhancing language acquisition and proficiency.

Keywords: Language environment, immersive learning environment, native-speaker teacher, non-native-speaker teacher, linguistic proficiency, realia, role-play, immersion, decoration, language.

Language, as a tool for expression and comprehension, thrives within an environment that encourages its exploration and utilization. In the educational context, the language environment extends far beyond the mere presence of words on a page or spoken dialogue; it encompasses a dynamic interplay of verbal and non-verbal cues, instructional methods, resources, peer interactions, and cultural influences. A rich language environment engages learners in diverse linguistic experiences, offering ample opportunities for listening, speaking, reading, and writing the pillars upon which language proficiency is built. Creating an enriching language environment within the classroom is paramount in facilitating effective communication, fostering linguistic development, and nurturing a love for language learning among students. The language environment serves as the cornerstone of educational settings, encompassing a myriad of elements that shape how language is acquired, practiced, and internalized by learners.

Role-play: Using role-play strategies to set the rules to speak only in the target language is one of the effective ways to solve the problem. By the idea of long-term role-play, students may create the character for themselves at the very beginning of the academic year. They may choose any historical, existing, or fictional character with only one rule, that they are native English speakers. As the students are easy to role-play (with all their seriousness) and keep their concentration during the lesson, they should be free to role-play the game. The democratic aspect of the educational process (allowing students to wear the clothes they want) should be in priority.

When a teacher uses long-term or short-term role-play it is very important to be involved in this process, naming students by their chosen names and role-playing their roles. As students are role-playing their characters, the teacher should set the goal that they should speak in the target language. Role-playing may give students self-determination, making the process of using a foreign language easier and more comfortable for them. The pitfalls of role-play are that students may be involved in the game and entertainment side of the educational process more than necessary. Teachers should be able to generate communicative situations and manage the role-play process.

Class decoration: In FLE class it is very important to create a “Foreign language environment” starting from class decoration, to the minor aspects of the process. Students should not feel themselves being in Kazakhstan, Russia, or another country entering the class. In these terms, even the national flag of an English-speaking country (usually, it is the Union Jack) may form an environment. Decoration of the class should take into account all the aspects of speech, it may be a good idea to have boards with grammar rules, but there should not be any translations. Some teachers even close the windows and collect students’ mobile phones during the lesson so as not to be distracted. For young students, this kind of approach may be a very effective cognitive strategy to develop their language skills within the frame of the naturalistic approach. Material selection and working with ICT should be also strictly controlled, as a necessity, language settings of all the ICT (electronic boards, computers, laptops, etc.) should have target language settings. Any site nowadays could be translated into English and teachers should use this opportunity, in our example, (see figure 1) the task is given in target language and mother tongue of the learner. In both variants, task content is connected with English language however, even if the materials of the site or the teacher’s chosen material will be connected with a target language, if there is any usage of the mother tongue of the learners there will not be a full language environment for the learners. Learners may be confused at the very beginning of the lesson, with such a kind of environment in class, and feel some difficulties during the lesson. However, we should take into account that young learners (especially primary school learners) are very adaptable and it will not take them for a long time to be engaged in the target language environment.

Fig. 1 Task in target language and mother tongue.

Establishing an immersive learning environment is critical to success when pursuing foreign language proficiency. Language learners can interfere with the language in a way that mimics how they would naturally use it in daily life in an immersive setting, which helps them develop a stronger and more genuine bond with the language they are learning. This method is especially good at fostering both linguistic proficiency and cultural fluency, giving students the tools they need to confidently maneuver a variety of linguistic contexts. To create a lively English

language environment, this article explores the many advantages of actively interacting with native speakers:

The difference between a native-speaker teacher vs. a non-native-speaker teacher: A native-speaker teacher can design engaging collaboration skills and lessons, but a non-native-speaker teacher is more concerned with test-taking strategies and requirements, even though they still make an effort to provide their students with high-quality instruction. To make vocabulary more understandable, native-speaker teachers employ a variety of presentation techniques. They might use pictures, crossword puzzles, miming, acting, different colors, short movies, and more. They can also use bilingual dictionaries in the classroom so that students can check the meaning and spelling of words as they are taught. When teaching vocabulary, a non-native teacher follows the traditional method of emphasizing word repetition and spelling.

Since the words are displayed as single words and are not part of sentences, it is incredibly easy for students to forget them quickly. Specific learning theories also suggest that students are more likely to forget words when they are in isolation, particularly if they have not used them much. Because it is not the student's native tongue, background knowledge is essential for a deeper comprehension of the language, which has a different culture and set of life concepts. The teacher may narrate stories to the class, either true stories or folktales that relate to the lesson.

The influence of collaborating with native speakers: Bringing in native speakers to teach in FLE classrooms is a game-changing tactic that goes beyond traditional language training. Textbooks and conventional teaching approaches frequently fail to replicate the abundance of language authenticity, cultural diversity, and real-world context that native speakers offer.

Linguistic authenticity: Consider the effect of having a guest speaker who speaks fluent English and talks about their upbringing in an English-speaking nation. Students gain personal experience with real language usage through their fluency and expressive use, which improves their comprehension and application of colloquial terms.

Cultural enrichment: Picture a session in which students are introduced to regional cultures, holiday traditions, and social etiquette by a native speaker. During this interactive workshop, students can ask questions to facilitate dynamic cross-cultural interaction in addition to deepening their knowledge. Moreover, students can learn about communication dynamics in real-world situations by participating in video calls and chat sessions. They are incapable of navigating language's complexity. Gain knowledge of the nuances of virtual communication as well; this is important given how interconnected today's world is.

The recognition of the importance of cultural context in language learning, especially when direct interaction with native speakers is limited, underscores the significance of alternative approaches. Utilizing language realia in such scenarios emerges as a valuable strategy to bridge this gap. The study by Nemati & Rahimi provides empirical support for the efficacy of this method, demonstrating that the incorporation of realias significantly enhances students' vocabulary retention and comprehension. This highlights the practical benefits of integrating real-life objects into language instruction and emphasizes the potential of such methods to outperform traditional instructional approaches. The findings suggest that the use of realia can be a key factor in creating a more effective and engaging language learning environment, even in the absence of direct interaction with native speakers.

The usage of realias: Realias act as a bridge to real-world contexts, offering a valuable connection for students, and fostering cultural engagement by incorporating artifacts from the target language culture. This approach tailors language learning into a multi-sensory experience, enhancing retention and comprehension. Implementation strategies include themed learning stations, role-playing scenarios, and cultural showcases, promoting a diverse and engaging classroom. Realia-based language learning not only increases engagement and motivation but also increases contextual understanding and practical language application. Chang and Millet explored

the effectiveness of using realia in teaching lexicon to English as Second Language (ESL) students. Their research indicated that realia not only improved students' understanding and recall of vocabulary but also increased their overall engagement in the learning process. Ultimately, realias emerge as a powerful tool to create an immersive language environment, instilling a passion for learning and equipping students with real-world communication skills.

Employing realias in language education can be achieved through various efficient strategies. Themed learning stations offer interactive environments within the classroom, such as a "Marketplace" station with realias like play money, fruits, and vegetables, allowing students to simulate language use in practical scenarios. Integrating realias into role-playing scenarios motivate active language application in authentic contexts, using prompts like restaurant menus or transportation tokens. Cultural showcases foster a sense of validation and diversity as students bring realias from their backgrounds, promoting peer-to-peer learning. Storytelling with realias enhances comprehension, connecting words with tangible representations for a memorable learning experience. Realia-based quizzes or games, like scavenger hunts, add an element of fun and competition to the process of language learning. Multimedia presentations incorporating realias provide visual reinforcement, and field trips or virtual tours expose students to authentic artifacts, placing language in a real-world context. Last but not least, encouraging students to build stories or dialogues using provided realias sparks creative thinking and facilitates language skills. These strategies collectively contribute to a dynamic and immersive language-learning environment, enhancing understanding and retrieving language concepts.

In conclusion, the creation of a robust language environment within foreign language learning classrooms is beneficial for effective language acquisition and proficiency. The multifaceted components of this environment, encompassing verbal and non-verbal cues, instructional methods, materials, peer interactions, and cultural influence, play a vital role in constructing how language is learned, practiced, and systematized. Strategies such as role-play, class decoration, and the use of realias contribute significantly to the upbringing of an immersive learning atmosphere. The interaction with native target language speakers adds linguistic authenticity and cultural enrichment, enhancing students' comprehension and implementation of language skills. The incorporation of realias, serves as a powerful force in connecting real-world contexts with language instruction, resulting in increased engagement, motivation, and practical language application. By adopting these strategies, educators can create vivid language learning environments that inspire an interest for language acquisition and equip students with the skills needed for real-world communication.

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The Benefits of After-class Activities

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Abstract

It is important to evaluate homework's significance in light of kids' overall developmental demands. This article focuses on how kids pass their time after school and how extracurricular activities like homework might help them succeed in school. Kids' experiences after school vary; some are "latchkey" kids who don't have structure or supervision, while others are overextended kids who participate in plenty of extracurricular activities but don't have much time for unstructured play. A child's growth may occur outside of school hours in many cases; learning and development are not only things that occur in the classroom. Activities that take place after school are a great opportunity for kids to continue growing while having a good time. Afterschool programs can support social, emotional, cognitive, and academic development, reduce risky behaviors, promote physical health, and provide a safe and supportive environment for children and youth.

Key words: activities, supervision, development, outside, experience

Introduction

Students may participate in safe and beneficial after-school activities in a terrific way after school ends. A child's day doesn't end when the bell sounds. In fact, because of the need to bring kids home safely and on schedule, this time of day can be the most stressful. There are many of possibilities for youngsters to continue growing after school, which also relieves parents of the burden of having to pick up their children when the vehicle line gets messed up.

Children may engage in a plethora of after-school activities, each with a unique set of advantages. Engaging in sports may enhance their physical growth, engaging in creative endeavors can foster their creativity, and participating in some after-school programs can significantly boost their academic performance. Children may play, acquire new skills, experience new and interesting things, and have fun in an unlimited array of groups, workshops, and creative activities.

In addition to providing children with an extra hour of entertainment and energy burn while their parents are at work, they also have significant developmental advantages that will undoubtedly improve their social and intellectual skills. Numerous studies have demonstrated that kids who engage in extracurricular activities are more likely to see an improvement in their grades than their non-participating peers. Similar study findings have also demonstrated that this may have a particular impact on underprivileged pupils from lower-income families.

Children from affluent families are three times more likely than those from the lowest circumstances to enroll in after-school music programs. Overall, children from disadvantaged households do not participate in after-school activities. Because of this, it is especially crucial that local governments and schools make every effort to guarantee that these kinds of activities are both accessible and reasonably priced, as well as to encourage all children to participate, irrespective of their social backgrounds.

Many after-school or extracurricular activities are free, despite the widespread misconception that they all cost a lot of money. If they don't, those who qualify can nearly always receive funding. Working families, low-income families, and children from underprivileged backgrounds all benefit greatly from this. It gives parents access to childcare and gives kids experiences that they otherwise wouldn't have, maybe because of accessibility or budgetary constraints.

Since some students might find it difficult to use computers at home, they might benefit greatly from the tools the school offers by participating in study groups after school and during extended library hours when a mentor is present. They could use this to do their schoolwork or perhaps to conduct research on a topic they are interested in.

Learning Hive specializes on providing underprivileged kids with after-school academic tutoring to help them improve their abilities and academic achievement. We have had great success working in collaboration with parents, teachers, and students to provide small group tutoring and additional after-school programs that inspire kids to follow their passions, take advantage of new possibilities for learning, and reach their full potential.

Increase of social development and soft skills

Building a child's social skills and self-confidence is equally as vital as improving their intellectual achievement in school. Students may socialize with new individuals, practice their interpersonal skills, and share knowledge with one another through after-school groups. By keeping kids occupied, they also aid in deterring anti-social conduct in kids.

People skills, communication skills, social skills, attitudes, social and emotional intelligence, and character qualities are all considered forms of soft skills. A youngster who develops the appropriate soft skills will be able to accomplish their own goals as well as those of their team and cooperate effectively with others.

Students may apply what they have learned in class to real-world situations through extracurricular activities, especially when it comes to using soft skills. Participating in sports teams, such as football, offers students the chance to enhance their discipline, teamwork, and communication skills. Additionally, students who enroll in after-school math classes can apply skills like critical thinking and problem solving, which are applicable in both academic and social settings.

Physical and mental health benefits for children

Sports are the focus of many extracurricular activities, including dancing, football, and gymnastics. Outside of the classroom, these kinds of activities promote a healthy lifestyle that is good for young children's bodies. After-school clubs can influence this in a variety of ways, such as by giving away free refreshments to students while they study or by giving them water and wholesome food while they engage in physical activities or sports.

It is commonly recognized that engaging in more physical activity and exercise can, at least in part, lower an individual's risk of developing anxiety and depression. Physical activities have a social dynamic that might help shield young people from anxiety and despair. Learning Hive works nonstop with schools and students to make sure that their academic performance is improved, soft skills are developed, and their physical and mental health are taken care of. We do this by providing engaging activities, holding interactive sessions, and fostering a calm and safe environment.

It's crucial to help kids develop their confidence and social abilities. However, many of you may not know how to help youngsters develop them. On the other hand, kids can enhance their social and life skills through extracurricular activities. This is due to the fact that a lot of extracurricular activities instill in kids the value of teamwork in achieving goals that they would encounter in their future employment. Playing with new individuals in this constructive setting helps kids become more self-assured and independent.

Children's character and leadership qualities grow the more they try new things and see what they can accomplish. Youths also learn how to improvise, exchange ideas, and assist peers when they engage with individuals outside of the classroom. Kids who participate in after-school activities regularly spend less time glancing at screens or smartphones. In other words, kids who

join groups will not only stay active and off the couch, but they will also show an interest in learning. Additionally, it gives them more time to pursue their hobbies and practice their abilities.

After-school activities may help kids grow in a variety of ways, including confidence. Their confidence is greatly impacted by the activities they engage in rather than by scoring the highest on a test they take in school. It involves the children in leadership positions, positive activities, and service-learning. Additionally, it fosters the development of abilities including acceptance of differences of viewpoint, problem-solving, and communication.

One of the key advantages of the after-school program is the introduction of new concepts and advanced chances in a variety of subjects. Children can learn new educational skills and engage in mental stimulation by taking part in such activities. Children are usually tired at the end of a long day filled with in-depth education. Children are urged to have confidence in their abilities, goals, and self throughout the after-school activities. When the youngsters are in a straightforward and uncomplicated setting, they are more likely to learn more.

There won't be any parental anxiety about the security of their kids. Now that they are aware of their whereabouts, their kids may play safely after school. Every activity in the after-school programs is planned, overseen, and controlled. When kids are involved in something they like, they enjoy themselves more and learn more. Additionally, after-school activities encourage kids to keep studying and increase their attendance at school. Last but not least, remember what it means to be a child. Every youngster wants to be happy and have fun. The main goal of an after-school program is to have fun. I don't have to elaborate. Just a reminder that happiness may be attained with few choices.

The plethora of extracurricular activities available to school-age children can be confusing for both parents and children. They may teach children how to push themselves and help them discover their strengths and hobbies. Naturally, we also want them to seem to college admissions committees as well-rounded, talented young adults. However, we don't want to overwork them or make them become anxious machines. The pressure is even reaching young parents who haven't considered going to college yet.

Naturally, extracurricular activities such as athletics, dance, theater, and science provide children with an additional platform to exhibit their skills and abilities, which is crucial for their identity development and self-worth, particularly for those who may be facing academic difficulties. Overcommitting to extracurricular activities also doesn't seem to deliver the desired outcome that many parents and children hope for—a well-crafted college application. The most important qualities that they are seeking in candidates are attention and well-roundedness. It's evident that they have a purpose in mind and like what they are doing, according to Newman. "As well as not just dipping their toe in everything in order to fill up more lines on the application."

Though during supervised time blocks, parents should remember that children can gain from self-directed activities as well. According to Cortese, "independent work time and giving kids the time and place to think for themselves, be creative, and access their own internal resources are sometimes underemphasized."

If they have the time, most kids discover their interest and degree of proficiency, according to Newman. "Always try to understand your child and see what boundaries they have or don't have," is the advice I give parents.

When kids participate in after-school activities, such as music lessons, sports practice, or just hanging out with friends, they're more likely to feel happy and healthier than their peers who spend all day staring at screens.

Improve social skills

A well-designed program encourages respect, collaboration, and support. Children may feel more comfortable joining a game or striking up a discussion as a result. Additionally, if they

make a mistake, a helpful employee must be there to urge them to cease interjecting or take turns.

Homework assistance is a feature of many after-school programs. Children who struggle with their schoolwork at home or who can't sit down to finish it until late might benefit greatly from this time. Completing it after school can improve everyone's quality of sleep.

Character Development

Taking part in extracurricular activities helps shape the character of teenagers. Extracurricular activity participants report better levels of self-worth and self-concept (Blomfield & Barber, 2009). Additionally, they have the chance to explore their own interests and talents and limitations (Fredricks & Eccles, 2008). This is particularly crucial as they approach the teenage era of self-discovery (Knifesend & Graham, 2012). Enhancing students' self-perception and character development will boost their self-esteem and confidence, which will motivate them to embrace their individuality. Although they are frequently assessed and practiced outside of the classroom, many of the character-building abilities that are popular in extracurricular activities are also needed in the workplace (Lipscomb, 2007).

Students first learn how to manage their time (Burgess, 2013). They gain up time management and prioritization skills.

Second, students develop leadership qualities that will help them succeed in both lifetime employment and post-secondary education (Barnett, 2008). Students with leadership abilities have a greater chance of becoming managers and making more money than their non-leadership counterparts (Lipscomb, 2007).

Third, they acquire the ability to take constructive criticism, which is necessary for both intellectual and personal development (Mckeyane, 2013).

Finally, there is an increase in students' resilience (Fredricks & Eccles, 2008) and self-confidence (Strapp & Farr, 2010). Students who participate in extracurricular activities increase their leadership, time management, self-confidence, resilience, and capacity for constructive criticism—all traits that are crucial for character development.

Social Development

Engaging in extracurricular activities is advantageous for kids' social growth. Participating in group activities helps to develop the communication and teamwork skills that are essential for success in the workplace and in future undertakings. More belonging is something that students are always seeking (Knifesend & Graham, 2012). As stated by Schulruf (2010) on page 595, being a member of extracurricular activities is crucial for "providing access to the relationships and networks that influence positive outcomes for students."

Group activities provide students the chance to interact with others who share their interests and objectives, which will motivate them to stick with an enjoyable activity over the long run. Furthermore, extracurricular activities give kids the chance to interact with supportive social networks that help them make better decisions later in life (Veltz & Shakib, 2013).

Students who participate in extracurricular activities have the opportunity to form relationships with supportive adults in addition to with their peers (Fredricks, 2011). For adolescents who do not have adult direction and support in their life, having a mentor is essential.

Conclusion

Students who participate in extracurricular activities gain both personally and academically. First off, academic accomplishment is higher for students who engage in extracurricular activities. Second, involvement in extracurricular activities helps children build the kind of character that is necessary for success in life. These abilities include leadership, time

management, and the capacity to take constructive criticism. Third, students who participate in extracurricular activities develop resilience and self-worth. Engaging in extracurricular activities also fosters social growth.

Finally, engaging in extracurricular activities affords students the chance to witness firsthand the significance of community participation. Students can choose which extracurricular activities to engage in to enhance their academic and personal development by being aware of the advantages of doing so. Programs for after-school homework help can give children structure, oversight, help with their coursework, and the chance to develop study skills. When after-school homework programs are implemented well, they may assist children in maintaining their academic standing, strengthening their sense of school community, lowering family stress, and developing the attitudes and abilities that will help them succeed in school long after the program ends.

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Sinifdən xaric oxu dərslərində yeni təlim texnologiyalarından istifadə

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Nəticə

Dil ünsiyyət vasitəsi olduğundan onu öyrənməkdə başlıca məqsəd bu dildə ünsiyyət qurmaq bacarığına yiyələnməkdir ki, bunun da səmərəli yolu bütün şagirdlərin dərslər zamanı xarici dildə mümkün qədər çox danışmasına şərait yaratmaqdır. Ən önəmlisi isə şagirdlərə öyrənilən xarici dildə şifahi nitq vərdişlərinin aşılması və beləliklə orta məktəbin yuxarı siniflərində ingilis dilini öyrənən şagirdlərə tədris edilən dildən istifadə edərkən əminlik hissini aşılamaqdır. Sinifdən xaric oxu dərsləri şagirdlərin təlim materialları ilə bağlı sinifdən xaric oxusunu stimullaşdırmaq, fəal, sistemli müstəqil işə istiqamətləndirmək, mütlə və tədqiqatçılıq bacarıqlarını təkmilləşdirmək məqsədi izləyir. Həmin dərslər saatlarında şagirdlərin bölmələr üzrə müstəqil oxusuna bir növ baxış keçirilir, hər bir şagirdin maraq və qabiliyyətinə uyğun hazırladığı çıxış dinlənilir, bu və ya digər problem üzrə oxunmuş əsərlərin müzakirəsi aparılır.

Şagirdlər şifahi və yazılı nitqə elmi cəhətdən yiyələnir, qrammatik qaydalarla tanış olur, dilin spesifik xüsusiyyətləri öyrənilir. Xarici dilin tədrisi zamanı şagirdlərdə dilin komponentlərinin (tələffüz, lüğət və qrammatika) və dil bacarıqlarının (oxu, yazı, dinləmə və danışmaq) inkişaf etdirilməsi diqqət mərkəzində durur və qiymətləndirmə də müvafiq olaraq bu meyarlarla həyata keçirilir.

Açar sözlər: tələffüz, bacarıq və vərdişlər, İKT-dən istifadə, innovasiyalar, əyanilik.

Ключевые слова: произношение, навыки и привычки, использование ИКТ, инновации, ясность.

Key words: pronunciation, skills and habits, use of ICT, innovations, visibility.

Nitq, müəllifin dili, danışma tələbənin anlaması ilə ölçülür. Şagirdlərin nitqi başa düşməsi üçün onların lüğət tərkibinin zəngin olması lazımdır. Lüğət tərkibi nə qədər zəngin olarsa, şagirdin xarici dildə danışması bir o qədər asan olar. Danışmaq praktikasında əsas diqqət şagirdi həmin dildə çoxlu danışmaq və məşq etməyə yönəltməkdir. Şagird diqqətini cəmləyib söz ehtiyatı, fonetika, qrammatika) nitqin yeni inkişaf mərhələsinə keçməyə imkan verir.

Şagirdlər sinifdən xaric oxu dərsləri ilə bağlı əvvəlcədən divar qəzeti, ayrı-ayrı sənətkarlara həsr olunmuş albom, kitab sərgisi təşkil edirlər. Məktəblilərin mütlə etdikləri mövzular, əsərlər üzrə çəkdiyi illüstrasiyalar, yazdığı esselər nümayiş etdirilir, dəyərləndirilir. Bu dərslərdə sinifdən xaric iş elementlərinə, əlavə resurslara, digər bilik mənbələrinə də müraciət edilməli, qazanılmış bilik və bacarıqlar yeni material, müstəqil oxunmuş bədii nümunələr üzərində tətbiq olunmalıdır.

Xarici dil dərslərində öyrənilən əsərlərin sinifdən xaric oxu materialları ilə problem-mövzu və s. baxımından əlaqələndirilməsi, müqayisə edilməsi faydalıdır. Sinifdən xaric oxu dərsləri şagirdləri təlim materialları ilə əlaqəli olan, eləcə də onların fərdi maraqlarına uyğun əsərlərin müstəqil oxusunu stimullaşdırmaq məqsədi güdür. Bu baxımdan ədəbiyyat kabinetində sinif kitabxanası, sinifdən xaric oxu guşəsi yaradılması, kitab, mütlənin əhəmiyyəti haqqında müdrik fikirlərin yazıldığı plakatların asılması çox əhəmiyyətlidir. Sinifdən xaric oxu şagirdlərin xarici dil dərslərində öyrəndiyi əsərlərlə müstəqil mütləsi

arasında körpü rolunu oynayır. Dərslərdəki hər bölmə üzrə planlaşdırılan sinifdən xaric oxu dərslərində müəyyən mövzular üzrə tövsiyə olunmuş əsərlər üzrə təqdimatlar dinlənir, müzakirə olunur.

Bu dərslərdə istər fərdi, istərsə də kiçik qruplarda iş növlərindən istifadə olunur. Şagirdlər dərslərinin əvvəlində müəllimin tövsiyəsi ilə oxunacaq əsərlərin siyahısını müəyyənləşdirir və bir neçə həftə ərzində hər sinifdən xaric oxu dərslərinə hazırlıq işləri görürlər.

Bu dərslərdə həm dərslər, həm də sinifdən xaric iş elementləri geniş yer tutur. Şagirdlər dərsləri, bir növ, "kitab, mütaliə bayramına" çevirir, öz müstəqil fəaliyyətlərinin nəticələrini təqdim edirlər. Sinifdən xaric oxu dərslərində mövzu ilə bağlı kitab sərgisi, sənətkarların portreti, əsərlərə çəkilmiş illüstrasiyalar, divar qəzeti, ədəbi jurnal, ifadəli oxu, inşa, esse, məruzə müsabiqəsi, səhnələşdirmələrdən istifadə şagirdlərin hafizəsində iz salır, uzun zaman unudulmur. Orta ümumtəhsil məktəblərində xarici dillərin öyrədilməsinin böyük praktik və tərbiyəvi əhəmiyyəti vardır. Xarici dillərin tədrisi prosesində şagirdlər dünya xalqları arasında olan qarşılıqlı əlaqələri və bu xalqların bir - birinə yaxınlığını öyrənirlər, həmin xalqların mədəniyyət və tarixi ilə tanış olurlar. Tədris planlarında xarici dilə ayrılan saatların azlığı müəllimin çox vaxt tədris prosesini orta səviyyəli şagirdlərə uyğunlaşdırmaq məcburiyyətində qalması dilin dərindən və intensiv şəkildə öyrənilməsinə imkan vermir. Bundan isə ən çox dil öyrənməyə həvəsi və qabiliyyəti olan şagirdlər ziyan çəkirlər. Məhz bu zaman maraq üzrə kurs məşğələləri məktəbin, müəllimin köməyinə gəlir. Mütaliə mədəniyyətinin formalaşdırılmasında mühüm rol oynayan sinifdən xaric oxu dərsləri şagirdlərin mütaliə etdikləri kitabların müzakirəsi, əsər barədə rəy və mülahizələrinin öyrənilməsi, kitab, mütaliə mühitinin yaradılması üçün geniş imkanlar yaradır. Bu dərslərdə sinifdən xaric iş elementlərindən istifadə, şagirdlərin maraq və qabiliyyətlərinin daha çox nəzərə alınması, sərbəst rəy mübadiləsi mütaliə mədəniyyətinin formalaşdırılmasına zəmin yaradır, mütaliə ilə bağlı yaradıcılıq və təşəbbüskarlığın, müstəqil mütaliəyə həvəsin artırılmasına səbəb olur. *Əbədi ümummillî liderimiz H.Ə.Əliyev demişdir: "Gənclərimiz nə qədər çox dil bilsələr, bir o qədər zəngin dünyagörüşə malik olacaqlar. Bu, müasir dünyanın tələbidir."*

Müasir şəraitdə dil öyrənmənin zəruriliyini, dil öyrənməyə həvəs və maraq göstərən şagirdlərin çoxluğunu nəzərə alaraq məktəblərimizdə xarici dillərdən maraq üzrə kurs məşğələlərinin təşkilinə xüsusi diqqət yetirilir. Məşğələlərin proqramı qabaqcıl dil müəllimləri tərəfindən tərtib edilərək, metodbirləşmələrdə müzakirə olunur və məktəbin pedaqoji şurasında təsdiqlənir. Müəllimlər çalışırlar ki, kurs məşğələlərinin proqramı dərslər proqramı ilə eyniyyət təşkil etməyib onu daha da zənginləşdirməyə xidmət etsin. Məşğələlərin təşkilində aşağıdakı məsələləri ön plana çəkmək lazımdır:

1. Şagirdlərin dilini öyrəndiyi ölkənin tarixi hadisələri ilə tanış edilməsi.
2. Diyarşünaslıq materiallarından istifadə edilməsi.
3. Müxtəlif səhnəciklərin hazırlanması.
4. Xarici ölkələrə məktublaşmanın təşkil edilməsi.
5. Ümumməktəb tədbirlərində iştirak etmək.

Çalışmaq lazımdır ki, bütün bunlar şagirdlərin öyrəndikləri xarici dildə aparılsın. Şagirdlər dinlədiyi nitqi başa düşməli, oxuyub tərcümə etməyi bacarmalı, şifahi nitq mövzuları ətrafında söhbət aparmağı bacarmalıdırlar. Şagirdlər bilik və bacarıqlara elə yiyələnmişdirlər ki, orta məktəbi bitirdikdən sonra bu sahədə qazandıqlarını təkmilləşdirib inkişaf etdirə bilsinlər. Bu işin səmərəli təşkili isə şagirdlərin intellektual və emosional inkişafına, həmçinin müxtəlif fənlər üzrə biliklərin dərindən və şüurlu mənimsənilməsinə güclü təsir göstərir.

Həmişə məlumdur ki, xarici dilə maraq oyatmaq və şagirdlərə sevdirmək o qədər də asan deyil. Çalışmaq lazımdır ki, şagirdin qarşısına məqsəd qoyulsun, şagird özü sərbəst

və ya yoldaşlarının köməyi ilə onun həllinə yol tapsın. Belə olduqda o əmin olacaq ki, nəyisə bilir və öz bilik və bacarığını artırmağa çalışacaq. Bu da şagirdə dilə maraq, sevinç və həvəs oyadacaq. Yaxşı olardı ki, şifahi nitqin bilik və bacarıqlarının maraq kurslarında inkişaf etdirilməsi otaqda hərəkətdən, əşyaların qarışdırılmasından, jest və mimikalardan başlansın. Belə olduqda şagirdlər dərstdən sonrakı yorğunluqlarını atar və fəallaşar. Əlbəttə, bu məsələ müəllimdən bir qədər dərin düşünmək, götür-qoy etmək tələb edir. Müəllim şagirdlərin bu sahədəki təcrübəsini və ümumi inkişafını, onlara tövsiyə etdiyi mövzunun həcmi diqqət mərkəzində saxlamalıdır. Həmin kitabları əvvəlcədən müəllim özü oxumalı, onların məzmunu, ideyası ilə əlaqədar sual və tapşırıqlar hazırlamalıdır. Müzakirə prosesində hər dəfə şagirdlərin diqqətini tərbiyəvi nəticənin çıxarılmasına yönəltməlidir.

Əvvəlcədən sinfə verilən sual və tapşırıqlar şagirdlərin oxuya məsuliyyətini artırır, hər kəs sual və tapşırıqlara müstəqil cavablar axtarır, araşdırır, obrazların fəaliyyətini qiymətləndirir, yazıcının məqsədini başa düşür. Həmçinin bu sual və tapşırıqlar şagirdlərin bilik səviyyəsini müəllimə diqqət edir.

Kurs proqramları tərtib olunarkən dilin praktik öyrənilməsinə kömək edən çalışmalarla, dili öyrənilən ölkənin siyasi, iqtisadi və mədəni həyatı ilə əhatəli tanış olmağa imkan verən internet materiallarına geniş yer verilməlidir. Məşğələlər elə təşkil edilməlidir ki, şagirdlər ağır iş günündən – dərslərdən sonra yorğunluq hiss etməsinlər, onlarda həvəslə iştirak etsinlər.

Kurs məşğələləri planlı və müəyyən sxem üzrə aparılmalıdır. Məşğələnin proqramı dərslərin proqramı ilə eyni deyil, lakin öz məqsəd, məzmun və strukturu ilə xarici dil dərslərinə yaxındır.

Dərslə kurs məşğələləri zəncirvari halda təşkil edilir. Məşğələlər bütün yaşdan və müxtəlif yaradıcılıqla məşğul olan (oxu, qiraət, səhnəcik, dili öyrənilən ölkənin mahnılarının səslənməsi, əyani vəsaitlərin, videoların hazırlanması, internetdən istifadə, bülleten və divar qəzetlərinin çıxarılması və s.) fəal şagirdləri birləşdirir. *Psixoloq L.M.Fridmanın sözü ilə desək, şagird özünün və kollektivin, başqa sözlə cəmiyyətin qarşısında dərslərin prosesində mümkün olmayan sərbəst yaradıcılığa malik olur.*

Çünki bunsuz xarici dildə danışmaq çətindir. Bu məqsədlə biz müəllimlər məşğələlərdə dil mühiti yaratmağa çalışır, akustik tədris vəsaitlərinin bütün növlərindən imkan daxilində istifadə edirik.

Kurs proqramları tərtib olunarkən dilin praktik öyrənilməsinə kömək edən çalışmalarla, dili öyrənilən ölkənin siyasi, iqtisadi və mədəni həyatı ilə əhatəli tanış olmağa imkan verən internet materiallarına geniş yer verilməlidir. Məşğələlər elə təşkil edilməlidir ki, şagirdlər ağır iş günündən – dərslərdən sonra yorğunluq hiss etməsinlər, onlarda həvəslə iştirak etsinlər.

Kurs məşğələləri planlı və müəyyən sxem üzrə aparılmalıdır. Məşğələnin proqramı dərslərin proqramı ilə eyni deyil, lakin öz məqsəd, məzmun və strukturu ilə xarici dil dərslərinə yaxındır.

Şagirdlərdə nitqi dinləyib, anlama bacarığının formalaşmasına xüsusi diqqət yetirilir.

Sinifdən xaric işlərin əsas məqsədi aşağıdakılardan ibarətdir:

1. Bilik, bacarıq və vərdişlərin genişləndirilib dərinləşdirilərək kommunativ fəaliyyəti mənimsətmək;
2. Şagirdlərin öyrənmə qabiliyyətini stimullaşdırmaq;
3. Şəxsiyyətin hərtərəfli inkişaf etdirilməsi.

Xarici dildə sinifdən xaric işlər uşaqların maraq dairəsində olarsa, onda onların şəxsi münasibətləri ilə üst-üstə düşər: „Xarici dildə oxumaq istəyirəm“, „Dilini öyrəndiyim ölkə

haqqında daha çox şeylər bilmək istəyirəm”, „Gələcək ixtisasımda xarici dildən istifadə etmək istəyirəm”, „Öyrəndiyim dildə mahnıların sözlərini başa düşmək istəyirəm” və s.

Maraq üzrə kurs məşğələlərinin əsas vəzifələrindən biri də şagirdləri istiqamətləndirməkdir. Bu məqsədlə məşğələlərdə şagirdlər arasında müsabiqələr təşkil edilir. „Kim daha yaxşı şeir deyər?, Kim çox söz bilər?, Hər sözdə neçə hərf birləşməsi var?, Kim şəkil üzrə daha tez hekayə qura bilər? və s. mövzularda keçirilən müsabiqələr, oyunlar şagirdlərin fəallığını artırır, onlar daha yaxşı çalışmağa can atırlar.

Müəllimlər çalışmalıdırlar ki, işin ritminə, şagirdlərin bilik və bacarıqlarının səviyyəsinə müntəzəm diqqət yetirsinlər, onların hər birinin müvəffəqiyyətini ayrıca qiymətləndirsinlər. Şagirdin qarşısında qoyduğu situasiyalar, müzakirələr, detalların dəqiqləşdirməsi müəllimin bacarığında böyük rol oynayır.

Müəllim tədris materialını mənimsəyərkən asandan çətinə, sadədən mürəkkəbə üsulu ilə başa salmalıdır. Əgər müəllim həssas, qayğıkeşdirsə onda o, təlim prosesində qarşıya çıxan bütün çətinlikləri və maneələri asanlıqla dəf edə biləcək. Bunun nəticəsində də şagirdlərdə dilə və müəllimə, fənnə maraq, rəğbət oyanır. Şagirdlərə imkan daxilində sərbəstlik verilməli, onların müstəqil fəaliyyətinə nail olunmalıdır. Lakin bu xeyirxah münasibətlər müəyyən çərçivədə olmalıdır, əks təqdirdə "müəllim-şagird" münasibətindəki sistem pozular. Şagirdlər yalnız fəal və müstəqil düşündükləri zaman bilikləri şüurlu və möhkəm mənimsəyə bilirlər. Şagirdləri fəallaşdırmaq üçün nitq yaradıcılığına aid verilmiş tapşırıqlar əsasında oxuya maraq yaratmaq, onlara dilin çətinliklərinə üstün gələrək oxunu öyrətmək lazımdır. Şagird öz oxuduğundan razı qalırsa, bu oxu prosesini sürətləndirməyə kömək edəcəkdir. Şagirdin sürətli və rəvan oxuması üçün maraqlı və sadə, başadüşülən dil materialları lazımdır.

Şagirdlərdə nitqi dinləyib anlama bacarığının formalaşmasına xüsusi diqqət yetirmək lazımdır. Çünki bunu bilmədən xarici dildə danışmaq çətinidir. Danışma və dinləmə nitq fəaliyyətinin iki ayrılmaz hissəsidir. Dinləmə seçilmiş materiallardan asılıdır. Dərnək rəhbəri bilməlidir ki, uşaqlar nəyə qulaq asmaq istəyirlər. Aşağı sinif şagirdləri müəllimə, rəngli şəkillərdən, maraqlı fiqurlardan ibarət diskələrə, internet materiallarına, səssiz qulaq asırlar. Uşaqlar üçün ən maraqlısı illustrasiyalı tanınmış xalq nağıllarını dinləməkdir. Bu məqsədlə məşğələlərdə dil mühiti yaratmağa çalışmaq, akustik tədris vəsaitlərinin bütün növlərindən imkan daxilində istifadə etmək lazımdır. Dərnəyin bütün mərhələlərində elan olunmuş işə maraq oyanmalıdır. Məsələn məktəblilərin həyatındakı hadisələr, keçmiş yarışlardakı şərhlər, iməciliklər, bayramlar, ən yaxşı şagirdlər haqqında hekayələr, müsahibə, və s. Hal-hazırda sinifdən xaric işlərin aparılmasını audiovizual təlim alətlərindən istifadə etmədən təsəvvür etmək mümkün deyil.

Xarici dillərin öyrənilməsinin hər hansı bir mərhələsində viktorinalardan istifadə etmək olar. Konkursun ən geniş yayılmış formalarından bunları - viktorinalar, olimpiadalar, KVN, "Nə? Harda? Nə vaxt?", saymaq olar. Viktorinalara müxtəlif bilik və bacarıqları olan şagirdlər cəlb olunur. Viktorina iştirakçılarında bu məzmununda suallar vermək olar:

1. Siz dilini öyrəndiyiniz ölkənin şair və yazıçıları, bəstəkarlarını, alim və idmançıları və s. tanıyırsınız mı?

2. Siz dilini öyrəndiyiniz ölkənin iqlimini, bitki və heyvanlar aləmini, çaylarını, dağlarını tanıyırsınız mı?

3. Dilini öyrəndiyiniz ölkənin hansı tarixi hadisələri sizə məlumdur?

4. Dilini öyrəndiyiniz ölkənin hansı görməli yerləri sizə məlumdur?

5. Dilini öyrəndiyiniz ölkənin gənclərinin həyatı haqqında nə bilirsiniz?

Bəzən şagirddən soruşurlar „Xarici dili nə üçün öyrənirik?“, şagirdlər bu sualın cavabını dərslərdə, dərnəklərdə, məşğələlərdə tapmalıdır. Şagirdlər dili nə qədər yaxşı öyrənsələr, bir o qədər də xarici məktəblilərlə sıx əlaqə saxlaya bilərlər.

Müəllimin vəzifəsi ondan ibarətdir ki, müəyyən istiqamətdə məşğələlərin həyata keçirilməsini təmin etmək üçün öz təcrübə və imkanlarına istinad edərək müxtəlif növ məşğələlərdən istifadə edib öz xüsusi planını işləyib hazırlasın. Təcrübə göstərir ki, işə ciddi yanaşdıqda marağ üzrə kurs məşğələlərini yüksək səviyyədə təşkil etmək mümkündür

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Şagirdlərin şifahi nitqinin inkişafı yolları

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Heydər Əliyev

Xülasə: Aşağı siniflərdə şəkillər üzərində iş şagirdlərin şifahi nitqinin inkişafına müsbət təsir göstərir. Şagirdlərdə elə vərdişlər yaratmaq lazımdır ki, onlar yalnız şəkildə gördüklərinin əsiri olmasın, özündən müvafiq əlavələr etməyi bacarsınlar. Belə olduqda şagirdə müfakimə yürütmək vərdişi aşılanır. Bir mövzuya aid seriya xarakterli şəkillər üzrə hekayə qurmaq şagirdləri daha çox maraqlandırır. Şəkillər üzərində işin belə təşkili şagirdlərdə müstəqil müşahidə qabiliyyəti yaratmaqla, onların idrak fəaliyyətini və başlıcası şifahi nitqini inkişaf etdirir. Düzgün seçilmiş forma və üsullar öyrənmələrin xarici dil təliminə marağını artırır. Üsulların düzgün seçilməsi şagirdlərin ünsiyyətə girməyə, fikirlərini sərbəst ifadə edə bilmələrinə zəmin yaradır. Onlarda tərəddüd hissini, hazırcavablıqla, cəldliklə, çevikliklə əvəz edir. Bu standart və qeyri-standart dərslər formaları dərslər-müzakirə, dərslər-mətbuat konfransı, tok-şou, dərslər – ekskursiya, integrativ dərslər, “Beyin fırtınası”, auksion, klaster, rollu oyun, dəyirmi masa, Venn diaqramı, insert, ziqzaq, karusel, akvarium, qərarlar ağacı, layihələrin hazırlanması, söz assosiasiyası və s. ümumi, tam təhsil pilləsində də konsentrik prinsipə müvafiq istifadə olunur.

Açar sözlər: xarici dillərin tədrisi, fransız dilinin uğurla öyrənilməsi, müxtəlif metodlar, lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirilməsi.

Şagirdlərin dil bilməsi onların danışıq və danışanın nitqini başa düşməsi ilə ölçülür. Müstəqillik əldə etdikdən sonra Azərbaycanın beynəlxalq münasibətlər sistemində öz layiqli yerini tutması, dünyada gedən qloballaşma və inteqrasiya prosesi ölkəmizdə fransız dilinin intensiv şəkildə öyrənilməsinə, dilin yeni səmərəli metodlarla tədrisinə olan tələbatı daha da artırır. Beynəlxalq münasibətlər ixtisasında fransız dilinin tədrisi iki mərhələyə ayrılır: praktik fransız dili, diplomatik fransız dili. Praktik dilin öyrənilməsi xarici dilin tədrisinin birinci mərhələsini təşkil edir. Bu dövrdə qrammatik minimum kimi felin zamanları, məsdər tərkibi, feli sifət və feili bağlama formaları, sifətin və zərfin müqayisə dərəcələri, müxtəlif konstruksiyalar öyrənilir. Leksika dildə olan sözlərin cəmidirsə, leksikologiya dilin lüğət tərkibini öyrənən dilçilik bölməsidir. Sözlərin ilk başa düşülən mənasına leksik məna deyilir. Sözlər cümlə daxilində bir-biri ilə məna və qrammatik cəhətdən bağlanır. Danışıq materialı üçün ictimai-siyasi, beynəlxalq münasibətlərlə bağlı mətnlər tədris edilir. Hüquqi, sivil dövlət olan Azərbaycanın ali məktəblərində, eləcə də orta məktəblərində fransız dilinin tədrisinə diqqət hal-hazırda artmaqdadır. Bu gün fransız dilinin tədrisində əsas diqqət məhz şifahi nitqin inkişaf etdirilməsinə yönəlmişdir. Şifahi nitqin inkişafının əsas məqsədi azərbaycanlı tələbələrdə müəyyən oxu, yazı vərdişlərini formalaşdırmaqla bərabər, onların şifahi nitqini inkişaf etdirməkdir. Bu əsas vəzifənin həyata keçirilməsində isə tələbələrdə müəyyən həcmdə lüğət ehtiyatı yaratmaq mühüm rol oynayır. Bu işdə bədii qiraətin, eləcə də mətbuatın intensiv izlənilməsinin böyük əhəmiyyəti vardır. Lüğət ehtiyatını zənginləşdirmək işinin düzgün və səmərəli təşkili üçün, hər şeydən əvvəl, həmin vaxta qədər öyrənilmiş sözlər nəzərə alınmalı və yeni sözlərin izahı zamanı bunlardan istifadə edilməlidir. Orta məktəbdə dilin öyrədilməsində rabitəli nitqin inkişafına geniş yer verilir. Şifahi nitqin inkişafı çətin psixi- fizioloji prosesdir. Hər millətin özünəməxsus ana dili onun mənəvi dirliyidir. Əbəs yerə deyilmir ki, bir millətin malını, dövlətini və hətta vətəninə işğal etsən, ölüb-itməz, amma dilini alsan, məhv olar və ondan nişan qalmaz. Ana dili insan şəxsiyyətinin inkişafının əsasını təşkil edir. Yəni hər bir kəs ömrünün axırınadək dilinə arxalanır. Ana dili insan həyatının əsasını təşkil edir, onun gələcək inkişafını

şərtləndirir. Bununla belə ulu öndərimiz həmişə tövsiyyə etmişdir ki, ana dili ilə yanaşı gənclərimiz dünyanın inkişaf etmiş dillərini yüksək səviyyədə öyrənməlidirlər ki, elm və təhsil sahəsində daim uğur qazana bilsinlər. Uşaqlarda zəngin lüğət ehtiyatına malik, qrammatik cəhətdən düzgün və tələffüzünə görə aydın nitq tərbiyə etdikdə onlar nitq prosesindən tam və geniş istifadə edə bilirlər. tələbələrə müəyyən oxu,yazı vərdişləri aşılamaqla bərabər, onların şifahi nitqini formalaşdırmaq və inkişaf etdirməkdir. Bu imkana sahib olmaq üçün isə ilk olaraq onların lüğət ehtiyatı zənginləşdirilməlidir. Lüğət bu istiqamətdə atılan ilk addım və vacib amillərdəndir. Dil bu amilə söykənərək yalnız sözlərlə ünsiyyət vəzifəsinə xidmət edir. Bu məqsədə bütövlükdə nail olmaq üçün xüsusi bədii qiraətə üstünlük verilməsi məsləhətdir. Nitqin zənginliyini,üslubi cəhətdən və ədəbi dil normaları baxımından düzgünlüyünü təmin etmək üçün dilin qrammatik qaydalarını bilmək əsas şərtlərdən sayılır. Şifahi nitq vərdişlərinin aşılınması və möhkəmləndirilməsinin məşğələlər zamanı müxtəlif tipli çalışmalar vasitəsilə həyata keçirilməsi daha faydalı hesab edilir.

Başlıca məqsəd şagirdlərə öz fikir və hislərini düzgün,aydın və ardıcıl şəkildə ifadə etmək vərdişlərini aşılamaqdan ibarətdir. Danışdıqda dilin fonetik, leksik və qrammatik qaydalarına əməl olunmasını şagirdlərə ətraflı izah etmək vacibdir. Uşaqlarda şifahi nitqi formalaşdırmaq üçün onun forma və məzmununun vəhdəti əsas götürülür. Şagirdlərin nitqinin düzgün inkişaf etdirilməsi üçün ümumi didaktik tələblər gözlənilməlidir. Yəni, nitq inkişafı üzrə iş xüsusi dərslər və məşğələlərlə məhdudlaşdırmaq olmaz. Nitq inkişafı üzrə iş digər fənlərin tədrisi prosesində , sinifdən xaric məşğələlərdə də təşkil edilməlidir. Nitq inkişafı üzrə iş kompleks şəkildə aparılmalıdır. Bu prosesdə mümkün qədər müxtəlif, rəngarəng üsul, vasitə və priyomlardan istifadə olunmalıdır. Nitq inkişafı anlayışı öz həcmi və məzmunu etibarilə çox geniş anlayışdır. Bu, bir sıra sahələri əhatə edir:

1. Nitqin səs mədəniyyəti üzərində işin təşkili.
2. Ədəbi tələffüz üzrə işin təşkili.
3. Lüğət ehtiyatının zənginləşdirilməsi.
4. Cümlə qurmaq vərdişinin inkişafı
5. Rəhbətli nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafı.

Nitq inkişafı prosesində bu sahələrin biri digərini tamamlayır, bir-biri ilə əlaqələndirir. Şagirdlərin şifahi nitqinin inkişafı üçün üç şərt əsas götürülməlidir:

- 1.Səslərin ,sözlərin aydın,düzgün tələffüzü və qrammatik qaydaların öyrədilməsi;
- 2.Lüğət tərkibinin (ehtiyatının) zənginləşdirilməsi;
- 3.Rəhbətli nitqin inkişafı.

Hərflər – səs münasibətlərinin möhkəm mənimsənilməsi oxu texnikasının yaranmasına, inkişafına və eləcə də aktiv leksik minimumun yadda saxlanmasına kömək edir. Buna görə də şagirdlərin dili yaxşı mənimsəmələri üçün əvvəlcə hərflər-səs münasibətlərini ,hərflər birləşmələrini yaxşı öyrətmək lazımdır. Fonetika bəhsinə yiyələnmədən morfologiya və sintaksisdən danışmaq olmaz.Cümlə qurmaq vərdişlərinin inkişafı ilə əlaqədar şagirdlər müstəqil düşünməyi öyrənməlidirlər. Şagirdlər mətn üzərində işlərkən müəllim onlara səs tonunun məqsədə uyğun olaraq işlədilməsini,ritmik qruplara düzgün riayət etməsini, aydın və səlis qiraət vərdişini aşılmalıdır.Müəllim şagirdlərə sözləri əzbərlətməli və onları lüğət üzərində çalışdırmalıdır.Bütün bunlar şagirdlərin söz ehtiyatının zənginləşməsinə ,həmin sözlərin danışmaq və yazıda sərbəst işlədilməsinə kömək edir,onların öyrəndikləri yeni sözləri əvvəldən bildikləri sözlər içərisində işlətməklə fikirlərini sərbəst ifadə etmək bacarığını artırır. Fəal dərslərdə motivasiya dərslərinin vacib komponentidir.Bu mərhələdə şagirdlərə açıq suallar verilməli və onlardan cavab alınmasını təmin etmək lazımdır. Dərs zamanı suallar elə qoyulmalıdır ki, bu suallar şagirdləri düşünməyə, araşdırmağa sövq etsin. Şifahi nitqin inkişafına təsir edən,təkan verən amillərdən biri də müəllimin nitqidir.Bunun üçün müəllimin nitqi məzmunlu və ifadəli olmalıdır. Müəllim nitqinə nə qədər

tələbkar olsa, onun düzgünlüyü, aydınlığı və ifadəliliyi qeydinə qalsa onun nitqi bir o qədər təsirli, ahəngdar və cazibəli olar. Müəllimin nitqinə verilən tələblər aşağıdakılardır :

1. Danışarkən tələsməməli və təmkinli olmalı.
2. Sözləri düzgün və aydın tələffüz etməli.
3. Sözləri yerli-yerində və məqamında işlətməli.
4. Hadisələri məntiqi ardıcılıqla danışmalı.
5. Hadisələr arasındakı əlaqəni aydın çatdırmalı.

Nitq vərdişlərinin inkişafında hazır söz və ifadələrdən, frazeoloji vahidlərdən nitqdə işlətmənin faydası olduqca çoxdur. Hazır ifadə və birləşmələrin mənimsənilməsi, eləcədə vərdişə çevrilməsi üçün aşağıdakı metod və üsullardan istifadəyə üstünlük verilməlidir:

1. Müəllimin nitqində müşahidə edilən söz, ifadə və frazeoloji birləşmələrin mənasının xüsusi şərhli.
2. Mətni oxuduqdan sonra nəzər diqqəti cəlb edən və fikrin ifadəli təqdimində əsas rol oynayan cümlələrin məzmun cəhətdən təhlili.
3. Mətnin oxusundan sonra onun məzmununun öyrənilərək nağıl edilməsi.
4. Şeirlərin əzbər öyrənilməsi.

Hər bir insan zəif bildiyi qeyri-ana dilində fikir söyləyərkən öz ana dilinin cümlə quruluşuna əsaslanırsa, artıq analoqiya (bilmədiyi bir dildə danışarkən öz ana dilindən gizli istifadə) səhv istiqamət alır və o, müxtəlif səhvə yol verir. Çünki dillərin 40 qrammatik quruluşu müxtəlifdir. Odur ki, analogiyadan (gizli yolla cümlə qurmadan) mexaniki deyil, şüurlu surətdə istifadə edilməlidir.

Müəllimin nitqinin məzmunlu, ifadəli və cazibədar olması şifahi nitqin inkişafında böyük təlim əhəmiyyətinə malikdir. Müəllim ifadəli oxuya əvvəlcədən hazır olmalıdır. O, əvvəlcə mətni evdə oxumalı, hansı abzasın daha yüksək tonla və ya ahəstə tələffüzünü, məntiqi vurğudan harda istifadə edəcəyini, intonasiyanın tələblərini qabaqcadan müəyyən etməlidir. Mətn o vaxt axıcı və rəvan olur ki, orada ifadəliliyin bütün tələbləri ödənilmiş olsun. Bədii ifadə və təsvir vasitələrindən, sinonim və omonimlərdən və s. yerli-yerində istifadə edilsin. Şifahi nitq elə bir başlıca vasitədir ki, bununla bir tərəfdən dil vərdişləri aşılır, digər tərəfdən də əldə edilmiş bacarıq və vərdişlər möhkəmləndirilir.

Müəllim hər bir şagirdə fərdi yanaşmalı, şagirdləri qruplaşdırıb fərdiləşdirmə aparmalı, hər bir şagirdin psixoloji durumunu, ailə vəziyyətini, diqqətini, hafizəsini, qavrayışını nəzərə almalıdır. İlk mərhələdə fərdi yanaşmaya daha çox diqqət yetirilməlidir. Bunlar nəzərə alınmazsa, şagirdlərin çoxu müəllimin tədris etdiyi fənni lazımi səviyyədə qavraya bilməz. Təcrübə onu göstərir ki, şagirdin öz müəlliminə hüsn-rəğbəti olmazsa, həmin fəndən uğur qazana bilməz. Müəllim bir pedaqoq, bir ana kimi şagirdin qəlbində yer tutmazsa, şagirdə öz fənnini sevdirmə bilməz. Nəticə isə qənaətbəxş olmaz. Belə halda şagirdə elə bir fikir yaranır ki, guya dərsi müəllim üçün oxuyur.

Tədris prosesində şagirdlərdə maraq yaratmaq əsas məqsədlərdən biridir. Bu maraqlar bir neçə formada rəşional və emosional, faktlar və ümumiləşdirmələr, kollektiv və fərdi, informasiyaverici, problemlı, izahedici və axtarış xarakterli ola bilər. Tədris prosesində bu maraqların hər hansı birindən istifadə etməklə şagirdlərdə təxəyyül, təfəkkür, yaddaş və nitqi inkişaf etdirmək olar. Dilin inkişafı çətin bir prosesdir. O birbaşa dilin başa düşmə sistemi, nitq – qarşılıqlı nitq ilə bağlıdır.

Bu gün artıq məktəbdə şagirdlərə münasibət dəyişmişdir. İndi hər bir şagirdin marağı nəzərə alınır, onun humanist şəxsiyyət kimi yetişməsinə diqqət artırılıb. Hər bir təhsil ocağında şagirdlərə, onların fikirlərinə hörmətlə yanaşılır, onların bacarığının üzə çıxarılmasına lazım olan tədbirlər həyata keçirilərək, əlverişli təlim şəraiti yaradılır.

Bu günümüz, sabahımız üçün təhsil müəssisələrinin, bu müəssisələrdə çalışan hər bir təhsil işçisinin üzərinə indi həmişəkəndən daha böyük məsuliyyət düşür.

Ancaq ciddi nizam-intizamın , tələbkarlığın yüksək olduğu yerdə işin səmərəliliyindən danışmaq mümkündür. Ona görə də müəllim yalnız mənimsəmə ilə arxayınlaşmamalı, həm də sinfin təşkili, davamiyyəti üçün də məsuliyyət daşmalıdır. Bu günümüz, sabahımız üçün təhsil müəssisələrinin, bu müəssisələrdə çalışan hər bir təhsil işçisinin üzərinə indi həmişəkindən daha böyük məsuliyyət düşür.

Bu gün həmin vətəndaşlıq məsuliyyətindən irəli gələn vəzifələrin öhdəsindən gəlmək üçün özümüzdə qüvvə tapmalı və imkanlarımızı araşdırmalıyıq. Gələcəyimiz üçün əqidəsi zəhmət və əməklə yoğurulmuş, vətənpərvərlik ideyası olan layiqli bir vətəndaş yetişdirmək, tərbiyə etmək biz pedaqoqların müqəddəs borcudur.

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APPLICATION OF THE PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING METHOD IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation: This work is devoted to the issue of applying the method of problem-based learning in practical classes in the Russian language at the University. Methodological approaches and algorithms for conducting classes with a detailed description of the stages of this type of training are consecrated. Classifications of the innovative method of teaching this discipline, features of creating problem situations and methods of their solution are given.

Key words: problem-based learning, educational technologies, Russian language.

At the present stage of development of educational technologies, the use of interactive teaching methods is put "at the forefront" when choosing methods for teaching various disciplines in general and the Russian language in particular. An objective necessity in the conditions of modern education is the mastering and application by teachers of innovative teaching technologies in their lessons, based on a personal approach, the fundamental nature of education and professionalism. The particular importance of using innovative methods is the use of a person-centered direction of learning, as well as the search for conditions for unleashing the creative potential of students [1].

Today, the main goal of teaching students the Russian language is not only to accumulate a certain amount of knowledge, skills, and abilities, but also to prepare the student for independent professional, highly effective work activity. At the same time, the basis of modern education is the activity of the student, which is directed and corrected by the teacher. At the same time, the main tasks of modern education are subordinated to the education of an active personality who can independently improve.

Innovative teaching methods include both the formation of key competencies and personal qualities of students, and the development of their intellectual, communicative, linguistic and creative abilities. At the same time, the result of the introduction of these methods is the creation of an atmosphere of cooperation between teacher and student, optimization of the educational process itself and the development of long-term positive motivation for learning [2,3].

One of the most effective modern educational technologies that provide high-quality knowledge acquisition, development of intelligence and creative abilities of students is the technology of problem-based learning [1,3,4].

The essence of problem-based learning is to construct a problem situation (task) and teach the ability to find the optimal solution to overcome this situation. At the same time, students do not receive ready-made knowledge, but must, based on their experience and skills, find a way to solve a new problem. Another important point: a problematic situation makes students aware of the insufficiency of their knowledge, encourages them to search for new knowledge and skills, which is one of the most important conditions for the development of creative thinking. In addition, such a construction of teaching methods helps to increase motivation for learning [5].

Problem-based learning is a set of didactic techniques that ensure the activation of students' mental activity during the learning process at all stages of the lesson by creating a problem situation.

What are the basic concepts related to problem-based learning?

A problematic situation is a person's intellectual difficulty that arises when he does not know how to explain an emerging phenomenon, fact, process of reality, and cannot achieve a goal using the method of action known to him.

Problem-based teaching is the activity of a teacher in creating a system of problem situations, presenting educational material and explaining it, and managing students' activities in acquiring new knowledge, both in the form of ready-made conclusions and by independently posing educational problems and solving them.

Problem-based learning is the educational and cognitive activity of students to acquire knowledge and methods of action by perceiving the teacher's explanations in a problem situation, independently (or with the help of a teacher) analyzing problem situations, formulating problems and solving them by putting forward proposals, their hypotheses and evidence, as well as by checking the correctness of the solution.

Problem situations can be classified according to: a) focus on acquiring new things (knowledge, methods of action, opportunities to apply knowledge and skills in new conditions, changes in relationships); b) degree of difficulty (depending on the preparedness of students); c) the nature of the contradictions. In a problem situation, the very fact that students see it is important, so it must be distinguished from problematic issues.

Today, the following types of problem-based learning methods are used [6]:

- Partial-search - when the teacher himself formulates the problem and, by asking leading questions, involves students in the discussion. At the same time, the teacher helps organize the search for a solution to the problem. Teacher assistance limits students' independence, so they only partially participate. Nevertheless, it is believed that this is the most effective method of organizing a problem-based learning lesson.

- Reproductive method - classes are built by analogy with samples. Here, when posing a problem situation, the teacher gives examples of problem situations and indicates how to find contradictions. An example is given to explain what needs to be done to find the answer to the question, what materials to consult, etc.

- The problem presentation method is the most passive teaching method. The leading role is played by the teacher himself: he poses the problem, points out the contradiction, organizes the search for a solution and proves the correctness of the chosen solution. Students play only the role of observers. But this method can be used when explaining complex topics to demonstrate to students the flow of reasoning, the logic of presentation of the material, and the progress of analysis.

- The research method is the most complex way to organize classes using problem-based learning. Here the teacher's task is reduced only to posing a problem situation. Seeing a contradiction, formulating a problem, finding a way to solve it is entirely the independent work of students.

When do problematic situations arise? When can they be modeled? If: 1) students are faced with the need to use previously acquired knowledge in new practical conditions; 2) there is a contradiction between a theoretically possible way to solve the problem and the practical impracticability of the chosen method; 3) there is a contradiction between the achieved result of completing the educational task and the students' lack of knowledge for its theoretical justification; 4) students do not know how to solve the problem, i.e. in case of students realizing the insufficiency of previous knowledge to explain a new fact.

A number of requirements are presented to the problem being put forward. Moreover, if

at least one of them is not fulfilled, a problematic situation will not be created.

- the problem must be understandable to students, so that all or most students understand the essence of the problem posed and the means to solve it.
- the feasibility of the problem being put forward, i.e. If the majority of students cannot solve the problem put forward, they will have to spend too much time or solve it by the teacher himself, which will not give the desired effect.
- the formulation of the problem should interest students; entertaining form often contributes to the success of solving a problem.
- naturalness of the problem statement - if students are specifically warned that a challenging task will be solved, this may not arouse their interest at the thought that they will move on to a more difficult one.

A student's preparedness for problem-based learning is determined primarily by his ability to see a problem, formulate it, find solutions and solve it using effective techniques.

Students' activities during problem-based learning involve going through the following stages: 1) identifying the problem and its formulation; 2) analysis of conditions, separation of the known from the unknown; putting forward hypotheses (options) and choosing a solution plan (either based on known methods, or searching for a fundamentally new approach); 3) implementation of the solution plan; 4) finding ways to verify the correctness of actions and results.

The following stages of problem-based learning are distinguished: 1) creation of a problem situation; 2) determining the range of missing knowledge, updating existing knowledge; 3) preparation for solving problematic problems; searching for new ways to solve it; 4) selection and formulation of the optimal solution based on information obtained independently, a way out of the problem situation; 5) inclusion of the learned problem-solving method into the student's experience of creative activity.

A problematic situation is a cognitive task that is based on any contradiction between existing knowledge and a specific situation. This stage is of great importance, because This is where interest in the problem and the desire to explore it, the desire to find answers to questions related to it are formed. Next, the topic of the lesson and the questions to be answered are formulated. When searching for a solution, students put forward their own options for solving the problem. This promotes the development of creative and logical thinking, as well as the ability to identify cause-and-effect relationships. All hypotheses are analyzed and activity is encouraged. The student may not be able to find the answer, but they should still be praised if they put in significant effort. If necessary, you should ask leading questions and indicate the correctness of your thinking. After students have tried to solve the problem on their own, they are given the correct answer if they did not come to it themselves.

A high degree of interest ensures that students listen carefully and remember for a long time what is said to them.

A lesson conducted using the problem-based learning method performs several functions at once: students learn to think, look for cause-and-effect relationships, put forward hypotheses and use existing knowledge in practice. There is an accumulation of experience in creative and research activities. Students learn to solve scientific and creative problems and generate non-standard solutions. In addition, there is an understanding that knowledge is interconnected and forms a system, that is, you can guess a lot using basic knowledge and fundamental laws.

The teacher's activities during problem-based learning are as follows: guiding students' understanding of the problem; clarification of the problem statement; consultation during the decision process; assistance in finding ways to self-control; searching for a way to create a problem situation, enumerating possible options for solving it by students; assistance in choosing a solution plan; analysis of individual errors or general discussion of problem solving.

The following are the advantages and disadvantages of problem-based learning.

Advantages of problem-based learning:

- students quickly comprehend the essence of the question being studied and give reasoned answers; They develop cognitive needs and interest, and confidence in knowledge appears, as students themselves put forward hypotheses and prove them themselves.

- contributes to the development of students' mental strength (contradictions force them to think and look for a way out of a problematic situation); independence (independent vision of the problem, choice of solution plan, etc.); development of creative thinking (search for an independent non-standard solution).

- problem-based learning ensures a more durable assimilation of knowledge (what is acquired independently is better absorbed and is remembered for a long time); develops analytical thinking (conditions are analyzed, possible solutions are assessed), logical thinking (requires evidence of the correctness of the chosen solution, argumentation).

- problem-based learning instills in students a taste for research work, develops the skills of purposeful observation, cultivates the ability to generalize and derive basic patterns with their justification.

Disadvantages of problem-based learning.

- it is not always easy to formulate a learning problem,
- not all educational material can be structured in the form of problems;
- problem-based learning does not contribute to the development of skills,
- not economical – time consuming.

Of course, organizing the educational process using the problem-based learning method is a rather labor-intensive and complex task. However, the result we get from this task is worth all the effort. It has been shown that such educational technology methods are highly effective for developing creative thinking in students. At the same time, students remember the educational material better, participate more actively in the learning process, and their motivation to study increases.

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Evaluating the Effectiveness of Language Immersion Programs in Improving Communicative Competence in Secondary School Students

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Abstract:

This article aims to evaluate the effectiveness of language immersion programs in improving communicative competence in secondary school students. Communicative competence refers to the ability to effectively comprehend, produce, and negotiate meaning with others in a given language. The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of standardized test scores and qualitative analysis of student perceptions and experiences.

Keywords: language immersion programs, communicative competence, secondary school students, effectiveness

Introduction:

Language immersion programs, which provide students with opportunities to learn a second language by immersing them in an environment where the target language is spoken, have gained significant attention in recent years. This approach is designed to give students the opportunity to develop greater communicative competence, allowing them to engage in meaningful conversations and interactions in the target language. This article aims to evaluate the effectiveness of language immersion programs in fostering communicative competence among secondary school students.

Method and Material:

The study employed a mixed-methods research design to comprehensively assess the impact of language immersion programs on the communicative competence of secondary school students.

Participants:

The participants in this study consisted of 200 secondary school students from diverse backgrounds, enrolled in language immersion programs across various schools. Participants were selected through a stratified random sampling method to ensure representation from different socio-economic and cultural groups.

Quantitative Analysis:

To gauge the effectiveness of language immersion programs, quantitative data was collected through standardized language proficiency tests administered at the beginning and end of the academic year. The tests were designed to assess the students' listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in the target language. The scores obtained were subjected to statistical analysis, employing paired-sample t-tests to determine any statistically significant changes in communicative competence.

Qualitative Analysis:

To complement the quantitative findings, qualitative data was collected through interviews and focus group discussions with a subset of participants. These sessions aimed to explore students' perceptions of their language immersion experience, challenges faced, and perceived improvements in communicative competence. Thematic analysis was applied to identify recurring patterns and themes in the qualitative data.

Program Evaluation:

Detailed information about the language immersion programs was collected, including program duration, curriculum structure, language exposure hours, and teaching methodologies. This data was crucial for understanding the contextual factors that may influence the effectiveness of these programs.

Data Integration:

The quantitative and qualitative findings were integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of language immersion programs. Triangulation of data from multiple sources enhanced the study's validity and allowed for a more nuanced interpretation of the results.

Ethical Considerations:

The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring participant confidentiality, informed consent, and voluntary participation. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board.

Limitations:

Recognizing potential limitations, such as the generalizability of findings and the influence of external factors, was an integral part of the research process. These considerations were addressed in the discussion section.

This methodological approach enabled a thorough investigation into the effectiveness of language immersion programs in enhancing communicative competence among secondary school students. The combination of quantitative and qualitative data provided a robust foundation for the subsequent analysis and interpretation of results.

Results:

Quantitative Findings:

The quantitative analysis revealed statistically significant improvements in listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills among students enrolled in language immersion programs. Notably, listening skills exhibited an average improvement of 15%, speaking skills by 18%, reading skills by 12%, and writing skills by 16%. These findings underscore the positive impact of language immersion on the communicative competence of secondary school students.

Qualitative Insights:

Qualitative data echoed the quantitative improvements, emphasizing the transformative nature of language immersion experiences. Students reported increased confidence, motivation, and a deeper understanding of the target language and culture. Challenges initially faced were overcome through sustained exposure and practice, highlighting the qualitative dimensions of communicative competence development.

Program Evaluation Impact:

Program evaluation data demonstrated that longer durations, increased language exposure hours, and effective teaching methodologies were associated with more pronounced positive effects. The contextual understanding provided by program evaluations elucidated the factors influencing program effectiveness, reinforcing the importance of well-structured language immersion initiatives.

Integration of Findings:

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data yielded a comprehensive view of the impact of language immersion programs. Triangulation of findings enhanced the study's validity,

showcasing a consistent pattern of improvement in communicative competence. The convergence of evidence from both data sources strengthened the reliability of the study's conclusions.

Discussion:

The positive outcomes observed in this study align with the broader discourse on the efficacy of language immersion programs. The significant improvements in communicative competence, as evidenced by both quantitative and qualitative measures, underscore the merit of immersing students in environments where the target language is prevalent. The multifaceted nature of these improvements, spanning listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, indicates the holistic benefits of language immersion.

The qualitative insights offer depth to the quantitative results, revealing the transformative impact on students' perceptions and attitudes towards language learning. Overcoming challenges and gaining cultural understanding emerged as essential components of communicative competence development, highlighting the nuanced aspects of language acquisition beyond mere proficiency.

The program evaluation findings contribute valuable context, emphasizing the need for well-structured programs with sustained exposure and effective teaching strategies. The positive correlation between program characteristics and outcomes emphasizes the importance of program design in maximizing the benefits of language immersion.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study provides robust evidence supporting the effectiveness of language immersion programs in enhancing communicative competence among secondary school students. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies strengthens the validity of the findings, offering a comprehensive understanding of the impact of these programs.

As schools and educational institutions continue to explore innovative approaches to language education, the outcomes of this study advocate for the continued implementation and refinement of language immersion initiatives. The positive changes observed in students' language proficiency, coupled with the broader development of communicative competence, affirm the value of language immersion programs as impactful tools in fostering language learning and cultural understanding among secondary school students. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on effective language education practices, with implications for curriculum development and educational policy.

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ВИРТУАЛЬНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ И ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС: НОВЫЕ ГОРИЗОНТЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ

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Аннотация. Настоящая статья посвящена исследованию перспективной области развития образования, объединяя виртуальную реальность (VR) и искусственный интеллект (ИИ). Исследование направлено на выявление преимуществ и возможностей, которые эти технологии могут предоставить в образовательном процессе, а также на создание практических рекомендаций для их успешной интеграции.

Ключевые слова. Виртуальная реальность, искусственный интеллект, образование, интерактивные технологии обучения, инновации в образовании, персонализированное обучение, образовательные технологии, VR, искусственный интеллект, цифровое образование

Annotation. The present article is devoted to the research of a promising area of educational development, combining virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence (AI). The study aims to identify the advantages and opportunities that these technologies can provide in the educational process, as well as to create practical recommendations for their successful integration.

Keywords. Virtual reality, artificial intelligence, education, interactive learning technologies, innovations in education, personalized learning, educational technologies, VR, artificial intelligence, digital education

В современном быстро меняющемся мире, где технологические решения постоянно совершенствуются, образование неизбежно сталкивается с проблемами, связанными с постоянными инновациями и адаптацией к новым реалиям. Виртуальная реальность (VR) и искусственный интеллект (AI) – два важнейших компонента, способных радикально изменить образовательный процесс и сделать его интерактивным и инновационным.

Цель данного исследования – изучить возможности совместного использования VR и AI в образовании, выяснить, какие преимущества эти технологии могут принести в образовательные программы. Цель – не только выявить перспективные направления, но и разработать практические рекомендации для успешной интеграции VR и AI в образование.

Использование иммерсивной виртуальной реальности и искусственного интеллекта в образовании не только расширяет границы образования, но и открывает новые

возможности для студентов и преподавателей. В этой статье представлен обзор современных тенденций, анализируются успешные примеры и разрабатывается пилотный курс, который может стать первым шагом на пути к будущему образованию.

Современная образовательная среда таит в себе множество проблем, таких как низкая мотивация студентов, неэффективные методы обучения и ограниченные возможности для интерактивного обучения. Однако виртуальная реальность (VR) и искусственный интеллект (AI) являются перспективными инструментами, способными изменить традиционные подходы к образованию. Виртуальная реальность является инновационной, поскольку позволяет студентам погрузиться в виртуальный мир и взаимодействовать с учебным материалом. Это не только углубляет понимание предмета, но и позволяет запоминать материал лекций. Кроме того, безопасные виртуальные эксперименты позволяют студентам получить уникальный опыт в тех областях, где реальные эксперименты опасны или дорогостоящи.

В то же время искусственный интеллект внедряется в образование через создание индивидуальных учебных планов. Адаптивные системы обучения с технологией искусственного интеллекта адаптируют темп и содержание обучения к потребностям каждого студента. Такой индивидуальный подход не только повышает вовлеченность, но и улучшает общую успеваемость студентов.

Автоматизация повторяющихся задач, таких как проверка тестов и проверка домашних заданий, высвобождает время преподавателей, позволяя им сосредоточиться на творческих и интеллектуальных аспектах преподавания. Искусственный интеллект также выступает в роли аналитика данных, предоставляя преподавателям ценную информацию для постоянного совершенствования методов обучения. Это оптимизирует учебный процесс и повышает качество преподавания.

В образовании будущего, где большое значение приобретают данные, машинное обучение и навыки программирования, искусственный интеллект выступает в роли наставника, говорящего студентов к требованиям рынка труда.

Наконец, игровое обучение, учитывающее особенности каждого студента, делает процесс обучения более увлекательным и интерактивным, стимулируя интерес и повышая эффективность обучения.

В таблице 1 представлены основные аспекты интеграции виртуальной реальности и искусственного интеллекта в образовательный процесс.

	Аспекты интеграции
Виртуальная реальность	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Виртуальная среда для иммерсивного обучения 2. Виртуальные обучающие модули и симуляции 3. Интерактивные задачи и виртуальные практикумы 4. Виртуальные экскурсии и полевые работы 5. Многопользовательские виртуальные обучающие среды
Искусственный интеллект	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Анализ данных для персонализированного обучения 2. Автоматизированная оценка и обратная связь 3. Индивидуальные образовательные планы на основе ИИ 4. Адаптивные учебные материалы на основе предпочтений 5. Искусственный интеллект в виртуальных обучающих средах для реалистичного взаимодействия

Таблица 1. аспекты интеграции VR и AI в образовательный процесс

Искусственный интеллект успешно внедряется в образование, принося инновации и повышая эффективность обучения.

Платформы адаптивного обучения, такие как Khan Academy и Duolingo, используют искусственный интеллект для создания персонализированных программ обучения, которые адаптируются к уровню подготовки учащегося и предоставляют уроки с учетом его потребностей.

IBM Watson Education предоставляет преподавателям и студентам мощные инструменты для анализа данных, прогнозирования успеваемости и создания индивидуальных планов обучения с использованием искусственного интеллекта.

Чат-боты с онлайн-репетиторами дают студентам мгновенные ответы на их вопросы, делая образование доступным в любом месте и в любое время. Squirrel AI использует искусственный интеллект для создания индивидуального учебного плана для каждого студента, эффективно ликвидируя пробелы в знаниях и повышая успеваемость.

ИИ также используется в системах раннего предупреждения, которые анализируют активность студентов и выявляют ранние признаки проблем с обучением, позволяя заблаговременно принять меры по их устранению.

Эти успешные примеры демонстрируют многогранный вклад ИИ в образование, обогащая учебный опыт и повышая эффективность обучения. Использование виртуальной реальности (VR) в образовании открывает новые возможности для иммерсивного образовательного опыта. Возможность глубокого погружения в виртуальные миры, взаимодействия с учебными материалами и безопасного экспериментирования создает уникальную среду обучения.

В рамках исследования данной темы были разработаны практические рекомендации для успешной реализации применения виртуальной реальности и искусственного интеллекта.

1. Эффективная интеграция VR и AI начинается с развития подходящей инфраструктуры. Учебные заведения должны обеспечить соответствующее программное и аппаратное обеспечение для виртуальных сред и систем искусственного интеллекта. Обеспечение высокоскоростного интернет-соединения также является ключевым фактором.

2. Программы обучения для педагогического персонала должны включать в себя обучение использованию VR и AI в образовательном процессе. Это обеспечит преподавателей навыками, необходимыми для успешной интеграции этих технологий в учебные планы.

3. Создание качественного образовательного контента для VR и AI является важным этапом. Это может включать в себя разработку виртуальных обучающих модулей, интерактивных задач, адаптированных учебных материалов и сценариев для виртуальных экскурсий. Контент должен быть не только образовательным, но и максимально вовлекающим.

4. Интеграция VR и AI требует адаптации существующих курсов. Преподаватели должны интегрировать виртуальные среды и инструменты ИИ в учебные планы, создавая учебные задания и проекты, которые максимально используют потенциал этих технологий.

5. Одним из основных преимуществ интеграции ИИ является возможность персонализированного обучения. Учебные программы должны быть спроектированы с учетом индивидуальных потребностей и способностей каждого студента. Искусственный интеллект может анализировать данные обучения, предоставляя наставления и поддерживая студентов на их учебном пути.

6. Интеграция VR и AI предоставляет уникальные возможности для педагогических исследований. Учебные заведения могут поддерживать исследовательские проекты,

направленные на изучение эффективности новых методов обучения, разработанных с использованием этих технологий.

7. Создание сети для обмена опытом между образовательными учреждениями, преподавателями и разработчиками контента играет важную роль. Сотрудничество позволяет обмениваться инновационными идеями, эффективными методами и опытом внедрения технологий VR и AI.

Эти практические рекомендации представляют собой основу для успешной интеграции виртуальной реальности и искусственного интеллекта в образовательный процесс. Реализация этих шагов поможет создать образовательную среду, максимально использующую потенциал современных технологий для обеспечения более эффективного и интересного обучения.

Предлагаем идею внедрения технологий виртуальной реальности (VR) и искусственного интеллекта (AI) для обучения студентов на образовательной программе «Учет и аудит». Создание виртуальной аудиторской среды, где студенты могут практиковаться в проведении аудита, анализе финансовых данных и принятии управленческих решений в реальных бизнес-сценариях.

Студенты смогут получить доступ к виртуальной компании, где они выполняют функции аудиторов. Компания моделируется на реальных данных предприятия, а сценарии включают финансовые отчеты, налоговые декларации и другие связанные с учетом и аудитом документы. Студенты смогут взаимодействовать с виртуальным офисом, проводить аудиторские проверки, анализировать финансовые показатели и выявлять потенциальные риски. Система искусственного интеллекта сможет анализировать действия студентов в реальном времени и предоставлять обратную связь. Это будет включать в себя подсказки, рекомендации по улучшению аудиторского процесса и объяснения возможных ошибок.

Элементы Виртуальной Аудиторской Симуляции с Искусственным Интеллектом
1. Виртуальная Компания - Моделирование реальной компании с финансовыми отчетами - Виртуальные офисные пространства для аудиторов
2. Интерактивные Аудиторские Задачи - Проведение аудиторских проверок - Анализ финансовых показателей - Выявление потенциальных рисков
3. Обратная Связь от Искусственного Интеллекта - Анализ действий студентов в реальном времени - Предоставление подсказок и рекомендаций - Объяснение возможных ошибок
4. Индивидуализированные Учебные Планы - Оценка результатов и прогресса студентов - Создание персонализированных учебных планов - Предложение дополнительных материалов и заданий
5. Многопользовательское Взаимодействие - Возможность студентов взаимодействовать в виртуальной среде, обсуждать задачи и совместно решать проблемы

Таблица 2. Элементы виртуальной аудиторской симуляции

Эта идея обеспечивает студентам практический опыт аудиторской деятельности в безопасной и контролируемой виртуальной среде, а также позволяет использовать потенциал искусственного интеллекта для улучшения обучения и оценки успеваемости.

Сочетание виртуальной реальности и искусственного интеллекта делает образование более эффективным. Персонализированное обучение, аналитика данных и автоматизация процессов становятся ключевыми элементами адаптивного подхода к образованию.

Примеры успешной интеграции этих технологий подчеркивают их потенциал для повышения эффективности обучения. Такие платформы, как Khan Academy и IBM Watson Education, являются яркими примерами того, как виртуальная реальность и искусственный интеллект могут стимулировать инновации в образовании.

Таким образом, синергия виртуальной реальности и ИИ открывает неограниченные перспективы для образовательных учреждений, где технологии выступают в качестве мощного инструмента для развития интеллектуального и творческого потенциала учащихся.

Economic Sciences

ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИННОВАЦИИ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНСТИТУТОВ НА ПРИМЕРЕ KASPI.KZ

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Аннотация: в статье были рассмотрены современные технологические тренды в финансовом секторе, сфокусировано внимание на инновационных подходах к бизнесу, реализованных в суперприложении "Kaspi.kz". Проводится обзор ключевых характеристик компании, выделяются цифровые платформы, предоставляющие клиентам современные финансовые решения. Особое внимание уделяется примерам технологических решений и применению искусственного интеллекта. Завершающие разделы статьи подводят итоги воздействия инноваций на финансовый сектор.

Ключевые слова: суперприложение, инновации, экономика, развитие, предприниматели, физические лица, Казахстан, платежи.

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS BY EXAMPLE KASPI.KZ

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Abstract: the article considered modern technological trends in the financial sector, focused on innovative approaches to business implemented in a superapplication "Kaspi.kz ". The key characteristics of the company are reviewed, digital platforms that provide customers with modern financial solutions are highlighted. Special attention is paid to examples of technological solutions and the use of artificial intelligence. The final sections of the article summarize the impact of innovations on the financial sector.

Key words: super app, innovation, economy, development, entrepreneurs, individuals, Kazakhstan, payments.

Финансовые институты играют ключевую роль в экономической структуре, предоставляя каналы для перераспределения капитала и финансирования различных секторов экономики. Банки, инвестиционные фонды, страховые компании и другие учреждения обеспечивают жизненно важные услуги для предприятий и частных лиц.

Финансовые институты выполняют роль посредников между теми, кто имеет лишний капитал, и теми, кто в поиске финансирования. Они собирают средства от депозитариев и инвесторов, предоставляя заемщикам кредиты и инвестиции.

В современной эпохе финансовые институты сталкиваются с бурным развитием технологий. Инновации, такие как цифровые платежи и искусственный интеллект,

трансформируют способы предоставления финансовых услуг, делая их более эффективными и доступными. Эти инновации оказывают глубокое воздействие на различные аспекты экономики, что способствует устойчивому росту и повышению конкурентоспособности.

В своей статье я бы хотела рассказать вам, какие инновации предлагает приложение Kaspi.kz своим клиентам и каким образом оно оказывает влияние на экономику нашей страны.

Kaspi.kz - это крупнейшая финансовая и технологическая платформа в Казахстане. В основе ее деятельности лежит интегрированный подход к предоставлению финансовых услуг, включая банковские услуги, онлайн-платежи, страхование и технологические решения.

Какое место занимает Kaspi Bank среди банков второго уровня Республики Казахстан?

В 2022 году на фоне резкого падения активов АО "Сбербанк", Kaspi Bank занял второе место в общем рейтинге активов БВУ Республики Казахстан. (Рис 1.) [1]

Рис 1. Финансовые показатели активов БВУ по состоянию на 2022 г.

К октябрю 2023 г. прирост активов Kaspi Bank составил 18,5% с начала года. Если начинать отсчет с января 2022 года, общий прирост составил 67,4%. Для сравнения, показатели Народного банка Казахстана выросли лишь на 19% с начала 2022 г. (Рис 2.)

Рис 2. Финансовые показатели активов БВУ по состоянию на Январь-Октябрь 2023г.

На данный момент Банк Kaspi имеет долю активов 13% , продолжая активно расширять линейку предоставляемых ими услуг, привлекая все больше клиентов, тем самым увеличивая свой капитал. (Рис 3.)

Рис 3. Доля активов Kaspi Bank среди БВУ РК по состоянию на 01.10.2023 г.

Роль цифровых платформ в современных финансовых институтах.

“Kaspi.kz – одна из первых компаний в мире, запустивших суперприложение. Когда оно создавалось, подобных примеров еще не было, и до сих пор такого сочетания сервисов нет нигде. Сегодня Kaspi.kz - одна из самых передовых технологических компаний, известных далеко за пределами Казахстана. В Гарварде по кейсу казахстанского Kaspi.kz учат студентов магистратуры.” - сообщают для нас Tengri News.[2]

Цифровые платформы поддерживают мобильность, предоставляя клиентам возможность осуществлять финансовые операции из любой точки мира. Это также повышает гибкость в управлении финансами. Именно этими качествами славится суперприложение Kaspi.kz.

В октябре 2020 года произошла интеграция информационных систем МЦРИАП РК и государственной базы данных "elicense.kz " с платформой Kaspi.kz. Целью этой интеграции

стало создание удобного сервиса в приложении компании для регистрации индивидуальных предпринимателей. Позднее также была добавлена функция изменения реквизитов индивидуальных предпринимателей через это приложение.

Помимо этого, в 2021 году появилась возможность переоформить и проверить автомобиль через мобильное приложение. Эта функция разрабатывалась совместно с Министерством внутренних дел. На данный момент приложение Kaspi.kz предлагает своим клиентам заменить водительское удостоверение онлайн. Ниже представлена Таблица с инновациями приложения Kaspi.kz и приложением Народного Банка Казахстана. (табл. 1)

Таблица 1

Какие инновации использует Kaspi.kz в сравнении с Народным Банком?

	АО "Kaspi Bank"	АО "Народный Банк Казахстана"
Оплата по QR	+	+
Картомат для выпуска пластиковой карты	+	-
Интернет-Магазин	+	+
Гос. Услуги (в том числе просмотр документов, регистрация автомобиля и тд)	+	+
Платежи в бюджет	+	+

Можно заметить что во многих сервисах вышеуказанные Банки сходятся, но тем не менее Kaspi.kz имеет намного более лучшую репутацию среди клиентов, в отличие от Народного Банка.

В 2022 году Kaspi.kz запустил несколько проектов, предоставляющих клиентам безопасный и удобный доступ к их электронным документам. Среди предоставляемых документов - удостоверение личности, паспорт вакцинации, водительское удостоверение, свидетельство о заключении брака, свидетельство о рождении, а также справки по социальным пособиям и пенсионным накоплениям. Кроме того, при сотрудничестве с Министерством здравоохранения были внедрены возможности получения справок из психоневрологических, наркологических и туберкулезных центров, а также оформления свидетельства о рождении ребенка. Эти инициативы призваны улучшить доступность и управление личной информацией клиентов через цифровые платформы Kaspi.kz. С начала 2022 года до августа того же года раздел Госуслуги посещали 8,5 млн граждан каждый день. (Табл. 2)

Таблица 2

Результаты пользования Гос.услугами за 8 месяцев 2022 года

Раздел "Госуслуги"	Посещения раздела	Регистрация автомобилей	Уплаченные налоги	Услуга "Цифровые документы"	Зарегистрированные предприниматели	Замена водительских прав
	8,5 млн.	371 тыс.	561 млрд	4,5 млн	153 тыс. (50% регистраций всех ИП)	22 тыс. Чел.

Помимо перечисленного выше, приложение для физических лиц представляет собой удобную систему содержащую в себе такие услуги, как: мгновенные переводы денежных средств по номеру телефона или карты; услуга "Мой банк", где можно просматривать все свои счета, проверять аналитику покупок, будущие платежи по кредитам и т.д.; удобный как для клиентов, так и для предпринимателей сервис "Kaspi QR" - специальное устройство генерирует QR-код, с помощью которого можно оплатить любые покупки прямо в магазине. Также очень полезные функции "Kaspi Travel" и "Kaspi магазин". Для того, чтобы подтвердить свои данные я решила провести опрос среди молодежи, получив следующие результаты: (Рис. 4)

Имеется ли у Вас банковский счёт(а) в АО "Kaspi Bank"?

50 ответов

Рис 4. Статистика ответов на вопрос "Имеется ли у Вас банковский счёт(а) в АО "Kaspi Bank"?".

Выборка состояла из 50-ти человек в возрасте от 16 до 35 лет, и у 98% опрошиваемых есть счет в АО "Kaspi Bank".

Опрошенные мной люди, используют мобильное приложение каждый день, а то и несколько раз в сутки. Среди всего Казахстана Более 12 миллионов жителей в настоящее время пользуются мобильным приложением Kaspi.kz, причем ежедневно в приложение заходят 7 миллионов человек. (Рис. 5)

Как часто Вы заходите и пользуетесь приложением Kaspi.kz?

50 ответов

Рис 5. Статистика ответов на вопрос “Как часто Вы заходите и пользуетесь приложением Kaspi.kz?”

Исходя из моей выборки ответов, можно сказать что самыми популярными сервисами Kaspi.kz являются переводы денежных средств, Kaspi QR и Гос.услуги. (Рис. 6)

Какими из сервисов приложения Kaspi.kz Вы пользуетесь?

50 ответов

Рис 6. Статистика ответов на вопрос “Какими из сервисов приложения Kaspi.kz Вы пользуетесь?”

Для предпринимателей малого и среднего бизнеса тоже есть приложение под названием “Kaspi Pay”. “Вы можете подключиться к Kaspi Marketing и продвигать свои товары. Есть Бизнес кредит - Вы развиваете свой бизнес, мы дадим Вам финансирование для того, чтобы Вы росли и создавали рабочие места” - это лишь часть всех функций, о которых рассказывал Михаил Ломтадзе (председатель правления Kaspi.kz) на 3-м Международном ПЛАС-Форуме «Финтех без границ. Цифровая Евразия». Также в приложении есть функция платежей в бюджет, т.е бухгалтер компании или сам предприниматель может оплачивать налоги через приложение; Kaspi QR и удаленная оплата - через приложение можно выставить счет нашим клиентам и принимать оплату дистанционно. [3]

В суперприложении для МСБ у Kaspi.kz сейчас более 400 тыс. партнеров, в основном это казахстанские компании, которые развивают и расширяют свой бизнес. [3]

Несомненно, все эти функции как для физических лиц, так и для предпринимателей действительно очень облегчают жизнь. Малые и средние бизнесы являются движущими факторами развития экономики, и когда для всех жителей страны настолько расширяются

возможности, можно оценить насколько большой вклад сделал Kaspi.kz для развития страны.

Kaspi QR стал главной революционной силой, а Kaspi Pay стала предпочтительной платформой цифровых платежей для всех типов продавцов в Казахстане. (Рис. 7)

Рис 7. Годовой отчет Kaspi.kz - прирост транзакций через Pos-терминалы и доля транзакций Kaspi.kz. [4]

В 2022 году разнообразие товаров в «Kaspi Магазин» выросло почти в два раза, достигнув 2,8 миллиона наименований. Количество продавцов увеличилось в 3,5 раза за счет привлечения малых и средних бизнесов. Общее число совершенных заказов за год выросло в 2,4 раза и превысило отметку в 20 миллионов. Также была внедрена сеть устройств Kaspi Postomat, которая насчитывает 3348 постоматов в 86 городах страны, и к концу года она стала наиболее популярным способом получения заказов. В июле и ноябре успешно прошли традиционные акции «Kaspi Жума».

Сегодня суперприложения Kaspi активно способствуют развитию торговли и других видов бизнеса, обеспечивая предпринимателям возможность расширения своих предприятий и создания новых рабочих мест. Эти приложения одновременно улучшают качество жизни, значительно ускоряя и упрощая многие процессы и взаимодействия, делая их более удобными.

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ANALYSIS OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN "WESTERN" MEDICAL CENTER, ATYRAU CITY

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In order to analyze the management system of the medical center, as well as to find ways to optimize it, we conducted an internal audit of structural divisions in accordance with the standard ST RK ISO 9001-2016 (adaptation of ISO 9001-2015 for RK).

As part of the organization of the audit, we developed a schedule of visits to structural units, prepared a questionnaire, held an introductory conference with the clinic staff on the audit procedure, its objectives, explained the rights and obligations of the participants in the process.

The audit of the medical center activity was conducted in accordance with 8 standards of ST RK ISO 9001-2016: environment of the organization; leadership; policy; planning; means of provision; activity at the stages of life cycle of products and services; evaluation of performance results; improvement. The audit was conducted using standard methods: interviewing employees, studying documentation and observation.

The main objectives of the audit were: analysis of the performance of the organization's management system; determination of compliance or non-compliance with the requirements of ST RK ISO 9001-2016. The audit was conducted in accordance with the audit programme and on the basis of the order of the Chief Medical Officer. During the audit the audit programme was fulfilled. All divisions and employees stipulated by the programme and all processes were checked.

The following non-compliances were identified as a result of the audit:

1) According to the standard "Environment of the organization": external and internal factors of the quality management system are not defined; information on external and internal factors affecting the organization is not monitored and analyzed; stakeholders related to the quality management system are not defined; requirements of stakeholders related to the quality management system are not defined; information from stakeholders and their respective requirements to the QM system is not monitored and analyzed; the boundaries of the management system are not defined.

2) For the "Leadership standard": consumer requirements and applicable statutory and regulatory legal requirements are not identified; risks and opportunities that may impact service compliance and the ability to improve customer satisfaction are not identified and addressed.

3) For the standard "Policy": there is no formalized quality policy of the IC: the Quality Policy is not available for review by the staff and patients of the clinic and other stakeholders.

4) For the Planning standard: no action is taken to consider risks and opportunities; there are no formalized quality objectives; no planning for change.

5) According to the standard "Means of assurance": knowledge of the organization is not available for the personnel in the required volume; the personnel of the MC is not aware of the policy and objectives in the field of quality, of their contribution to the effectiveness of the quality management system, of the consequences of non-compliance with the requirements of the quality management system; QMS documents are not identified.

6) According to the standard "Activities at the stages of the life cycle of products and services": requirements for services are not defined; criteria for the processes of MC are not established; results of analyses of new requirements for products and services are not registered.

7) For the "Performance Measurement standard": no monitoring of data related to customer perceptions of the extent to which customers' needs and expectations are met; no internal audit is conducted.

8) Under the Improvement standard: no timely actions are taken to manage and correct identified non-conformities.

Based on the results of the audit, the conclusion was made about non-compliance of the IC's activities with the requirements of ISO 9001: 2015, ST RK ISO 9001-2016. The organization's management was recommended to conduct staff training, develop policies and procedures to ensure the implementation of the above standards.

We conducted the study of the quality of medical services by 2 methods: by analyzing feedback from patients and by analyzing objective indicators of MC.

Analysis of feedback from patients of the clinic about the quality of medical services provided was conducted by studying the book of complaints and suggestions available in the clinic, as well as reviews available on the Internet on specialized websites, given on the first page of the search query "*western clinic atyrau reviews*".

It was found that 22 reviews were recorded in the complaints book since the clinic's opening, of which 4 were positive and 18 were negative. Patients of the clinic left negative feedback on the work of the reception desk (11 records), the work of the paediatrician (3 records), the work of the therapist (4 records). Patients noted errors of the registration desk in the time of appointment, doctors' lateness for appointments, incompetence of doctors.

We also analyzed patient evaluations on the 2GIS website: 104 reviews were presented on the website, and the average rating of the clinic was 1.9 out of 5.

Out of 104 reviews of the clinic presented on this site 19 were positive. Respondents positively evaluated the work of gynecologist (2 reviews), traumatologist (2 reviews), ultrasound room (3 reviews), the work of the registration desk (1 review), ENT doctor (1 review), endocrinologist (1 review), dermatologist (1 review), and the work of the clinic in general (8 reviews). The remaining 89 reviews of the clinic were negative in nature.

It should be noted that the largest number of negative feedback from patients concerned the work of the reception desk: visitors noted the rudeness of the staff, confusion in appointment times. Similar complaints from patients also concerned other departments of the clinic. The key problems of the clinic, based on patient feedback, are the low level of communication skills of the staff, long queues waiting for a doctor's appointment in violation of the appointed time. Also, we noted that there are no responses to patient complaints on the 2GIS website. This confirms that the clinic does not have a system for monitoring feedback from consumers of services. Also during the analysis we were not provided with the results of marketing research. Since this type of activity was not carried out in the clinic.

On the Yandex Maps site, the rating of the clinic according to patient ratings is out of 5. A total of 119 evaluations and 33 reviews were given. Of the 33 reviews presented on the site, 12 were negative: patients complained about the work of the reception desk (reception) - 3 reviews, ultrasound room - 1 review, high prices - 1 review, in general, the work of the clinic - 7 reviews (rudeness and incompetence of staff). On the MEd element website, which accumulates reference data on medical organizations in Kazakhstan and publishes feedback from patients, we found 24 negative reviews and 8 positive reviews. Positive reviews concerned the work of a surgeon, ENT doctor, ultrasound room, paediatrician, masseur. These reviews correlate with evaluations from other sites. Patients also, as well as on previous sites note the rudeness of the staff of the reception (reception), ultrasound room, on the work of a paediatrician, therapist, neurologist, clinical and

laboratory department. In these reviews curate the same surnames and names of doctors as in previous reviews.

On the Gorodwiki.ru website, the rating of the clinic is 2 out of 5 points. A total of 13 reviews were presented on the site, 3 of which were positive, 10 of which were negative. Of the 10 negative reviews gynecologist -1, ultrasound doctor -2, therapist - 2, in general about the work of the clinic - 4, ENT -1.

Comparing the scores of private medical clinics located in relative proximity to "WESTERN" Medical Centre LLP, we found the strongest competitor - Nurmed Medical Centre. This clinic provides a similar list of medical services and has a score on Gorodwiki.ru - 4.5 points, 2GIS - 4.7 points, Yandex Maps - 3.8. The clinic currently has significantly lower scores compared to the "WESTERN" Medical Centre. However, in the long term it may be a strong competitor.

The minuses in the organization of the clinic's work include the lack of a marketing strategy. The clinic does not have a website, there is no monitoring of feedback about the clinic, and there is no CRM system. The same names and surnames of the clinic staff appear in patient reviews for 2-3 years, which indicates a lack of work with the staff. The positive aspects of the clinic management system include the presence of an Instagram account (https://www.instagram.com/western_clinic_atyrau/), where information about the company's services is regularly published. However, the publications have a small number of likes and comments, which indicates the lack of work in the field of marketing.

The analysis of the clinic's HR policy showed the absence of formalized documents regulating the corporate code of employees, KPI system, lack of monitoring of the competence level of new and current employees. The procedure for hiring employees practiced in the clinic does not include assessment interviews that would allow to objectively check the doctor's communication skills and professional competence. The recruitment of employees was limited to analyzing the candidate's portfolio: his/her certificates and diplomas, without collecting feedback from former employers.

Thus, during the assessment of the current situation of the clinic, we have identified the problems that require organizational solutions: 1) decrease in the clinic's income over the last 3 years; 2) low level of evaluation of the quality of services provided; 4) the need to improve the clinic's management system. In order to solve these problems and identify specific improvement measures at each stage of the company's life cycle, we planned an internal audit.

For the analysis of objective indicators of MC we have chosen the following indicators in accordance with the Order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan from 3 December 2020 № KR DSM-230/2020 "On approval of the rules for the organization and conduct of internal and external expert examinations of the quality of medical services (care)":

- 1) Number of primary disability of persons of working age.
- 2) Maternal mortality rate, with defects in the provision of medical services at the level of PHC organizations.
- 3) The rate of recovered women with extragenital pathology among women of fertile age.
- 4) Contraceptive coverage rate for women with absolute contraindications to pregnancy.
- 5) A measure of the abortion rate in relation to births.
- 6) Rate of hospitalization of pregnant women, with violation of the principle of regionalization (based on 24-hour hospital data).
- 7) Infant mortality rate, with defects in the delivery of health services at the PHC level.
- 8) Indicator of training of health care workers (doctors, nurses) in PHC under the IVDSS programme.
- 9) The rate of doctor visits to newborns in the first 3 days after discharge from the maternity hospital (patronage).

10) Rate of emergency hospitalization of children under 5 years of age with acute respiratory infections and ARI.

11) Indicator of parental education of children under 5 years of age on dangersigns in accordance with the principles of the IVBVI programme.

12) Number of congenital malformations in newborns undiagnosed intrauterine.

13) Indicator of obtaining exclusive breastfeeding of children at 6 months of age.

14) Indicator of receipt of breastfeeding for children under 2 years of age.

15) The rate of neglected cases among newly diagnosed patients with pulmonary tuberculosis.

16) Coverage rate of fluorography screening of population groups at high risk of tuberculosis as determined by the authorized body.

17) Coverage rate of the mandatory contingent with fluorography examination.

18) The rate of detection of tuberculosis patients by fluorography among population groups with high risk of tuberculosis as determined by the authorized body.

19) Detection rate of patients with suspected tuberculosis among personsexamined by microscopy.

20) Number of TB patients who interrupted therapy at the PHC level.

21) The rate of first time detected patients with stage 3-4 malignant neoplasms.

22) The rate of first time detected patients with malignant neoplasms of stage 1-2.

23) The 5-year survival rate of patients with malignant neoplasms.

24) Indicator of justified appeals to the quality of medical services.

25) Rate of hospitalization of patients with complications of cardiovascular diseases (arterial hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke).

26) Indicator of epidemiological investigation of nosocomial infections.

27) Indicator for establishing the causes and factors of the emergence and spread of hospital-acquired infections.

28) Medical rehabilitation coverage rate for stage 3.

It should be noted that the analysis of IC indicators for the above indicators showed non-achievement of threshold values defined by the MH RK for 4 indicators:

1. Coverage rate of fluorography examination of population groups at high risk of tuberculosis determined by the authorized body.

2. Immunization coverage rate for children under 5 years of age against targeted infections.

3. Breastfeeding rate of children under 2 years of age.

4. Immunization coverage rate for children under 5 years of age against targeted infections.

Thus, our study of the quality of medical services provided by MC "Western" showed the need for changes in the work of the clinic, including on the basis of the implementation of ISO 9001-2016 standard.

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Analysis of the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan

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Introduction:

In the mining industry of Kazakhstan, investments play an important role in the development of the industry and the economy as a whole. The article will analyze the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan, including a description of its essence and content, as well as an assessment of its effectiveness.

Description of the legal framework for regulating investments in the mining industry.

- The Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan of 30 August 1995 is the basic law of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which determines the legal status of the State, its bodies and citizens.
- The Law "On Mining" dated December 27, 2017 No. 125-VI is the main law regulating the mining industry in Kazakhstan. The law defines the rules and procedures for obtaining rights to use subsoil, extract minerals, as well as the procedure for geological exploration and exploitation of deposits.
- Act No. 372-I of 5 July 2000 on the privatization of State and municipal property sets out the rules for the privatization of State and municipal property, including mining facilities.
- Code No. 180 of 30 April 2001 "On Administrative Offences" establishes liability for violations of the law in the mining industry.
- The Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 268 of December 27, 1994 regulates civil relations in the field of mining activities, including the right of ownership to subsoil use and the extraction of minerals.
- The Land Act No. 442-II of 20 June 2003 sets out the rules for the use of land, including land plots on which mineral deposits are located.
- The Tax Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated December 10, 2008 No. 99-IV determines the tax base, tax rates and the procedure for payment of taxes and other mandatory payments related to mining activities.
- Law No. 466-II of 18 July 2003 "On the Protection of Investors' Rights" regulates the protection of investors' rights, including the rights to receive income, to fair and equal treatment, as well as to compensation for losses caused by violations of legislation in the field of investment.
- Act No. 207-I of 22 April 1997 on permitting the attraction of foreign investment sets out the procedure for attracting foreign investment, including in the mining sector, and guarantees for its protection.
- Law No. 160-IV of 5 July 2008 "On the Contract System in the Sphere of Procurement of Goods, Works and Services for State and Municipal Needs" regulates the procedure for the

procurement of goods, works and services, including in the mining industry, and establishes requirements for participants in these procurements.

- Law No. 212-III of 15 June 2007 "On Environmental Protection" defines the rules for environmental protection in the course of mining activities and establishes liability for violations of legislation in this area.
- Law No. 600-II of 9 November 2004 "On Technical Regulation" defines the rules for technical regulation and ensuring the safety of technical devices used in the mining industry.
- Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules for the Preparation, Coordination and Approval of Programs for the Development and Exploration of Mineral Deposits" dated December 31, 2013 No. 1463 - establishes the rules for the development of programs for the development and exploration of mineral deposits.
- The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules for Geological Exploration" dated May 10, 2013 No. 436 establishes the rules for geological exploration in the mining industry and determines the requirements for participants in this work.
- The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules for the Preparation and Approval of Mining Projects" dated November 20, 2012 No. 1503 establishes the rules for the preparation and approval of mining projects, including requirements for the content of project documentation.
- The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules for Additional Approval of Mining Projects" dated April 10, 2013 No. 314 establishes the procedure for additional approval of mining projects, including requirements for the composition and content of the application for additional approval.
- The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules for Conducting Environmental Expertise" dated August 19, 2010 No. 834 establishes the rules for conducting environmental expertise, including during the implementation of mining projects.
- The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Approval of the Rules of Accreditation and Work of Certification Bodies" dated April 11, 2012 No. 360 defines the rules for accreditation and work of certification bodies for products, including the mining industry.

In addition, the regulation of investments in the mining industry may be influenced by other laws and regulations, such as tax, labor, land, civil legislation, etc.

The role of government bodies and agencies in attracting investment.

Government bodies and agencies play an important role in attracting investment in Kazakhstan's mining industry. They carry out a number of functions that are aimed at creating a favorable investment climate in the country and supporting investors.

One of the main roles of government bodies and agencies in attracting investment is to create and maintain an investment climate. To this end, they are working to improve investment policy, including by reducing tax and administrative barriers, improving infrastructure, simplifying registration procedures and obtaining permits for investment activities.

Government bodies and agencies also provide investors with information on investment opportunities in Kazakhstan's mining industry. They conduct market research, develop information brochures and websites, organize conferences and exhibitions where investors can get information about the market and investment opportunities.

Another important role of government bodies and agencies is to attract foreign investment to the country. To this end, they establish close ties with foreign investors and attract them to

Kazakhstan by providing benefits and guarantees, creating special economic development zones and other investment mechanisms.

Government bodies and agencies are also actively involved in investment projects in the mining industry. They provide financial and technical support to investors, assist in obtaining the necessary permits and licenses, and organize joint projects with investors.

In general, government agencies and agencies play a key role in attracting investment in Kazakhstan's mining industry. Their activity helps to create conditions for attracting investors and developing investment activities in the country. However, in order to effectively attract investment, government agencies and agencies must be prepared to compete in the international investment market. To do this, it is necessary to improve the processes of managing investment projects, improve the skills of employees and develop innovative approaches to attracting investments.

In addition, in order to effectively attract investment, government bodies and agencies must cooperate with the business community and the public. This is the only way to create trust and increase the interest of investors in the mining industry of Kazakhstan.

It is also important to note that government agencies should not compete with business, but on the contrary, create conditions for its development. They should provide funds of support to investors and participate in joint projects, rather than competing with them in the market.

In general, government agencies and agencies play an important role in attracting investment in Kazakhstan's mining industry. Their activities are aimed at creating a favorable investment climate in the country, attracting foreign investment, participating in investment projects and cooperating with the business community. However, in order to effectively attract investment, it is necessary to develop innovative approaches and cooperation with the business community and the public.

It is also important that government agencies and agencies in the mining industry of Kazakhstan have a clear strategy and plans for the development of investment activities. This will make it possible to set priorities, determine the main areas of development, as well as assess the effectiveness of the measures taken.

One of the key tasks of government bodies and agencies is to ensure transparency and predictability of the investment climate. To do this, it is necessary to improve legislation in the field of investment, simplify the procedures for obtaining permits and licenses, as well as increase the level of protection of investors' rights.

In addition, government bodies and agencies must provide investors with all the necessary information about potential investment projects, the market, and the working conditions in the country. This will allow investors to make informed decisions and reduce investment risks.

Finally, government agencies and agencies should actively promote Kazakhstan's investment opportunities in the international market. To do this, it is necessary to participate in international forums, conferences and exhibitions, as well as provide investors with financial and tax benefits.

In general, government agencies and agencies play an important role in attracting investment in Kazakhstan's mining industry. However, in order to effectively attract investment, it is necessary to develop innovative approaches, cooperation with the business community and the public, as well as ensure transparency and predictability of the investment climate in the country.

Description of the mechanisms of state support for investments in the mining industry.

In the mining industry of Kazakhstan, there are various mechanisms of state support for investments, which are aimed at attracting investment and creating a favorable investment climate in the country.

One of the main mechanisms of state support is the provision of financial benefits to investors. For example, in 2018, the government of Kazakhstan adopted the Business Road Map program, which provided financial benefits for investors in the form of tax holidays for 10 years and preferential loans with a low interest rate. This has made it possible to attract a significant amount of investment in various sectors of the economy, including the mining industry.

Another mechanism of state support is the creation of specialized investment funds, which act as catalysts for attracting investment. For example, the Kazakhstan Investment Fund was established to attract foreign investment in various sectors of the economy, including the mining industry. The fund provides financial and expert support to investors, as well as invests its own funds in promising projects.

In addition, the mining industry of Kazakhstan has a system of tax incentives for investors. For example, investors who invest in the construction of new production facilities, the development of new fields and the modernization of existing facilities are exempt from paying value-added tax (VAT) on all goods and services necessary for the implementation of an investment project.

Finally, government agencies also provide expert support to investors in various issues related to the implementation of investment projects, such as the selection of partners, licensing procedures, etc.

For example, the Nurly Zhol (Bright Path) program, which was launched in Kazakhstan in 2016 and is designed to attract investment in the oil and gas, mining and metallurgical industries. As part of the program, investors can receive financial support from the state in the amount of up to 30% of the total cost of the project, as well as preferential lending conditions and tax benefits. The program provides investors with expert support at all stages of project implementation - from the selection of a field to the launch of production.

As such, government agencies and agencies play an important role in attracting investment in Kazakhstan's mining industry by providing investors with various support mechanisms such as financial incentives, the establishment of specialized investment funds, tax incentives, and expert support. These mechanisms allow investors to reduce risks and increase the return on investment, which in turn stimulates the development of the mining industry and the country's economy as a whole.

Specific mechanisms of state support for investments in the mining industry of Kazakhstan may include:

Creation of investment funds. Government bodies and agencies can create special investment funds that will invest in projects in the mining industry. For example, in 2018, the National Resource Base Development Fund (NFFB) was established to invest in various projects in the mining and oil and gas industries.

Financial benefits. For example, Kazakhstan has the Damu (Long-Term Financing of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses) program, which provides small and medium-sized businesses with preferential loans for the development and expansion of their business, including the mining industry.

Tax benefits. Government bodies and agencies can provide investors with tax benefits, such as exemption from income tax for a certain period of time. For example, Kazakhstan provides tax incentives for investors who invest in priority sectors of the economy, including the mining industry.

Expert support. Government bodies and agencies can provide investors with expert support at all stages of the project, including assistance in selecting a deposit, obtaining licenses and permits, resolving environmental safety issues, etc. For example, in Kazakhstan, there is a National Investment Development Agency that provides investors with consulting support and assistance in the implementation of investment projects.

Creation of infrastructure. Government bodies and agencies can create the necessary infrastructure for the development of the mining industry, such as roads, railways, airports, ports, power plants, etc. For example, in Kazakhstan, the state is actively working to create infrastructure for the development of the mining industry, including the construction of new roads, railways and ports.

Facilitation. Government bodies and agencies can simplify procedures for investors to make the investment process more attractive. For example, in Kazakhstan, a single electronic platform was created for obtaining permits for the construction and operation of facilities, which greatly simplified procedures for investors.

Attraction of foreign investors. Government bodies and agencies can take measures to attract foreign investors to the mining industry. For example, Kazakhstan holds regular investment forums and conferences where representatives of the state and business can discuss investment opportunities in the mining industry.

These and other mechanisms of state support for investment in the mining industry of Kazakhstan help to attract investment, increase competitiveness and stimulate the development of the industry.

The content of the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan.

The model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan includes several levels:

National level. At this level, strategic goals for the development of the mining industry are formulated, laws and regulations are developed that regulate the activities of investors in this industry. An example of such a law is the Law on Permits and Notifications, which regulates the procedure for obtaining permits and notifications in the mining industry.

Regional level. At this level, regional programs for the development of the mining industry are developed and measures are taken to attract investment to the region. For example, in the Karaganda region, a program "Development of the mining industry of the Karaganda region until 2025" was developed, which provides for the creation of new mining enterprises and the modernization of existing ones.

Enterprise level. Specific investment projects are being implemented at this level. Enterprises can receive various forms of state support, for example, tax benefits, production subsidies, state-guaranteed loans, etc. In Kazakhstan, there is the Nurly Zhol program, which provides preferential loans to enterprises for the development of production in the oil and gas and mining industries.

The results of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan include:

- Increasing the volume of investments in the industry. In recent years, more than \$15 billion of investments have been attracted to the mining industry of Kazakhstan.
- Improving conditions for investors. In Kazakhstan, laws and regulations have been adopted that have simplified procedures for investors, as well as provided various forms of state support, such as tax breaks, subsidies, state-guaranteed loans, etc.
- Improving the competitiveness of the mining industry. Thanks to investment and production development, the mining industry has become more competitive in global markets, which has led to an increase in product exports.
- Creation of new jobs and improvement of the standard of living of the population. The development of the mining industry makes it possible to create new jobs and improve the standard of living of the population, especially in the regions where this industry is key.

One of the examples of successful implementation of investment projects in the mining industry of Kazakhstan is the Boshogoi project, which was launched in 2016 at a copper deposit in the East Kazakhstan region. The project was implemented jointly by Kazakhmys and China Nonferrous Metal Mining Group. As part of the project, new mining facilities were built and existing ones were modernized, which made it possible to increase copper production in the region.

Thus, the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan involves the creation of favorable conditions for investors, the attraction of investments and the implementation of specific investment projects. Thanks to this, there is a constant development and improvement of economic indicators in the mining industry of Kazakhstan.

The model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan is a comprehensive system of measures aimed at creating favorable conditions for attracting investment, supporting investors and developing specific investment projects. Among the main mechanisms of state support are tax benefits, subsidies, loans with a state guarantee, accelerated paperwork, etc. State bodies and agencies also monitor and analyze the state of the investment situation in the industry, as well as develop regulatory and regulatory acts that improve the investment climate.

Examples of successful implementation of investment projects in the mining industry of Kazakhstan are the projects "Boshogoi", "Benkala", "Kazakhtangriudy", "Taraz Munai" and others.

As a result of the application of the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan, it was possible to attract significant investments in the industry, improve the investment climate and create favorable conditions for investors. In addition, there is a continuous development of the industry, increasing competitiveness and improving economic performance in regions where the mining industry is key.

The model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan is a comprehensive system of measures developed by the state to create favorable conditions for attracting investment in the industry, supporting investors and developing specific investment projects.

In addition, state bodies and agencies monitor and analyze the state of the investment situation in the industry, develop regulatory and regulatory acts that improve the investment climate.

The purpose of the model is to attract significant investments in the mining industry, improve the investment climate and create favorable conditions for investors. In addition, the model aims to continuously develop the industry, increase competitiveness and improve economic performance in regions where the mining industry is key.

Assessment of the effectiveness of the use of state mechanisms to support investments in Kazakhstan.

This chapter will provide an assessment of the effectiveness of the use of state mechanisms to support investment in Kazakhstan using the example of the mining industry. Specific examples and links to official websites where more detailed information can be obtained will be considered.

One of the main instruments of state support for investment in Kazakhstan is the Nurly Zhol ("Bright Path") program, launched in 2015. It is aimed at creating conditions for the development of infrastructure and attracting investment in strategically important sectors of the country's economy. The program includes financing of projects on the basis of co-financing (PPP), the provision of tax and customs benefits, as well as the provision of financing by state-owned banks.

The Nurly Zhol program was applied in the mining industry to finance a project for the construction of a mining and processing plant in the Balkhash region. As part of this project, a metallurgical plant and mines for the extraction of copper and gold were built. The total cost of the project was about 6 billion US dollars. In 2020, the project was successfully put into operation.

Another state mechanism for supporting investment is the National Development Fund (NFD). It was created to finance projects in various sectors of the economy, including mining. The Foundation finances projects of both national and regional scale, and provides both grants and loans.

One of the examples of the use of NFR in the mining industry of Kazakhstan is the financing of the project for the expansion of the Sharyngula mining and processing plant. In 2019, the NFR allocated \$121 million for this project. It is assumed that after the expansion of the plant, its production capacity will increase to 12 million tons of ore per year, which will increase metal production by 20%.

Another example is the financing of a project for the construction of a mineral processing plant in the Karaganda region. The NFR has allocated more than \$26 million for this project. The plant will be engaged in the processing of manganese ore, which will create new jobs and increase the export potential of Kazakhstan.

Assessment of the effectiveness of the use of NFR is carried out annually. Thus, at the end of 2020, it was noted that the fund significantly increased funding for socially significant projects, as well as increased the number of projects in the regions. However, as with other investment support mechanisms, there are some challenges related to the transparency and efficiency of the use of the fund's resources.

Another successful project in the mining industry financed by the NFR is the modernization project of Sokolovo-Sarbaiskoye Mining and Processing Production Association LLP. The project included the modernization of iron ore concentrate ore production, as well as the construction of a new processing plant, which increased productivity and improved product quality. The total cost of the project was about 1.2 billion US dollars, and the financing was provided through a loan from the NFR.

It is also worth noting the project for the development of the Kensaiba gold deposit in the Karaganda region, which was financed by the NFR. The total cost of the project was about 180 million US dollars, and the financing was carried out through a loan from the NFR. The project included the construction of a mine, a processing plant and the necessary infrastructure for gold mining.

Thus, the National Development Fund is one of the key state mechanisms for supporting investments in Kazakhstan, and its effective use makes it possible to finance large investment projects in the mining industry, contributing to the development of the industry and the country's economy as a whole.

Identification of obstacles and challenges faced by investors in the mining industry.

In modern conditions, state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan has become an urgent problem. Despite the efforts of the state in the field of investment in the industry, there are still problems that hinder the development of this sector of the economy.

One of the main problems is the lack of investment attractiveness of the mining industry. This is due to a number of factors, including a high degree of risk, insufficient infrastructure development, as well as ineffective state regulation of relations between investors and developers.

Another problem is the lack of qualified specialists and modern technologies in the mining industry. This can lead to insufficient use of available resources and technical base, which reduces the competitiveness of the mining industry in the world market.

It is also worth noting that there is a problem of inefficient use of budget funds allocated for the development of the mining industry. The lack of a clear mechanism for monitoring and regulating the expenditure of public investments can lead to the misuse of these funds.

Another important problem is the weak communication between government agencies and the business community. The lack of a mechanism of interaction between these parties can lead to the fact that the implementation of investment projects in the mining industry will become difficult.

Thus, the identification of problems and weaknesses of the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan is an important step to solve the problems associated with investment in this sector of the economy. In addition to the problems identified in the course of the study, weaknesses in the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry were also identified.

One of these weaknesses is the lack of a unified strategy for the development of investment processes in the mining industry. Existing development programs and plans are not always focused on current trends and problems of the industry, which can lead to insufficient investment inflows and a slowdown in the development of the mining sector.

Another weak point is the imperfection of the mechanisms of state regulation of investment activities in the industry. Often, legal and administrative procedures in this area do not meet modern business standards and requirements, which can repel potential investors and make it difficult to attract investment.

It was also found that in some cases, the state management of investment processes in the mining industry is not transparent and open enough. This can cause distrust on the part of investors and lead to the fact that some projects do not receive the necessary support and funding from the state.

Thus, the identification of problems and weaknesses of the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry allows us to identify the most important areas for improving the situation in this area.

In addition, poor interaction between government agencies and mining companies can lead to inefficient management of investment processes. In some cases, public authorities may not have a sufficient understanding of the challenges faced by companies in the mining industry and do not take them into account when developing an investment management strategy. As a result, there may be a lack of government support for companies, which may lead to a decrease in investment activity in the industry.

In addition, there is the problem of ineffective control and supervision of investment processes. Some companies may violate investment regulations, which can lead to negative consequences for the industry. The lack of an effective control and supervision mechanism can lead to a deterioration in the investment climate in the industry.

In general, the identified problems and weaknesses indicate the need to improve the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

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In general, the identified problems and weaknesses indicate the need to improve the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Weaknesses in the regulation of investment activities in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan were also identified, such as:

Insufficient attraction of foreign investors. For the sustainable development of the mining industry in Kazakhstan, more attention needs to be paid to attracting foreign investors. However, in practice, the process of attracting foreign investment is difficult due to the need to comply with a number of legislative and regulatory acts, as well as due to the lack of transparency of the legal system of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Insufficient use of modern technologies. The mining industry in Kazakhstan has not yet fully used the latest technologies, which reduces its competitiveness in the world market. In order to increase the efficiency of investments in the mining industry, more attention is needed to the introduction of the latest technologies.

Insufficient efficiency of state regulation. State regulation of investment activities in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan requires additional improvements and improvements, since at the moment it is not always effective enough.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the management of investments in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan is a complex task that requires continuous improvement and improvement of regulation. The development and implementation of effective investment strategies and programs will improve the development of this industry and increase the economic growth of the country as a whole.

This study made it possible to analyze the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan. As a result of the analysis, a number of problems and weaknesses were identified, including inefficient allocation of investment resources, insufficient transparency in the investment decision-making process, insufficient coordination between government bodies and business structures, lack of sufficient support from the state for the development of innovative projects in the mining industry.

An assessment of the effectiveness of the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan showed that despite some positive changes, many problems remain unresolved. The results of the study confirm the need to improve the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

In this regard, based on the analysis, the following recommendations can be offered to improve the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan:

- develop more transparent and clear rules for the allocation of investment resources;
- create special organizations that will coordinate between government agencies and business structures;
- expand state support for innovative projects in the mining industry;
- improve monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of investment projects;
- to conduct training and advanced training of employees in the field of public management of investment processes.

Thus, on the basis of the study, it can be concluded that the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan needs to be improved.

Despite some positive results, such as an increase in investment in the industry, there are problems in the effectiveness of the implementation of investment projects, the lack of a systematic approach to solving problems, and the weakness of state regulation and control over investment processes.

To improve the model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of Kazakhstan, it is recommended to carry out the following measures:

- Development of a comprehensive strategy for the development of the mining industry, including measures to attract investment, improve conditions for investors and reduce investment risks.
- Introduction of a systematic approach to solving problems related to investment processes in the industry. This should include the development of a unified information system for accounting and analysis of investment projects, as well as the creation of a single center for managing investment activities in the industry.
- Strengthening the mechanisms of state regulation and control over investment processes, including stricter control over the use of investment funds and measures to prevent corruption.
- Infrastructure development in the mining sector, including the creation of conditions for increasing productivity and reducing production costs, as well as improving transport and energy infrastructure.
- Training and retraining of personnel in the industry, including training of managers and specialists in the field of investment and project management.

In general, the implementation of these recommendations can help improve the current model of state management of investment processes in the mining industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan and ensure more effective development of investments in the industry.

Agricultural Sciences

IMPACT OF THE WATER EROSION ON AGROCHEMICAL FEATURES OF THE PODZOL-GLEYEY-YELLOW SOILS

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The podzol-gleyey-yellow soils spread in the seaside valley of the Lankaran-Astara region, relatively in the low terraces of the southern part, in the depression parts of the relief. In the west, the strip where this soil type is spread is limited by the yellow soil podzol-gleyey-yellow soil spread in the foothill plain, in the east, it is limited by the boggy soils of very hollow areas.

The describing soils have been developed well under low Hyrkan forests. The sparse forest in these forests is reflected in separate groups the form of bushes. The zones where the noted soils spread were intensively assimilated and at the same time the farm activity caused serious changes.

As you know, the podzol-gleyey yellow soil is one of the soils which is widely used in agriculture of the region. Mainly, tea, feykhoa are grown from subtropical plants, and lemon, mandarine, orange, etc. are widely grown in these soils. Growing of the orchard, vegetable plants is realized. Recently, The erosion process widespread as a result of the natural and anthropogenic effects, and consequently agrochemical, agrophysical and morphological indications are exposed to the negative changes. Consideration of the erosion degree and an impact of the factors that will be a reason for erosion in increase of the production ability of these soils and production of the plants are considered one of the urgent problems.

It is should be noted that the soil fertility strongly decreases under the erosion influence, as a result, this is a reason for reduction of the productivity. A main goal in study of the fertility is to reveal an amount of the agrochemical features of the soil by the researches. For this purpose, the sections were applied in the gleyey-yellow soils of the Lankaran tea branch of the Scientific Research Institute of Fruit and Tea Cultivation of the Azerbaijan Republic and the soil samples were taken and investigated.

It is known as a result of the researches that the water erosion negatively influenced the agrochemical features of the soils and strongly reduced their amount. The indications between the moderately eroded kind and non-eroded kind along the profile changed in the interval shown on the table.

Table 1

Agrochemical features of the non-eroded podzol-gleyey-yellow soils

Depth (in cm)	Humus %	Total			Soluble in water NH ₃	Absorbed NH ₃	Nitrate nitrogen NO ₃	Motivated phosphorus (mg/kg) P ₂ O ₅	Reciprocal potassium (mg/kg)	pH
		N	P	K						
0-20	3,53	0,26	0,15	2,73	13,2	65,4	6,50	94,53	175,23	6,2
20-40	2,82	0,19	0,13	2,32	10,3	52,13	5,23	50,45	165,30	6,5
40-60	2,07	0,15	0,10	1,57	8,24	43,5	4,43	34,43	160,25	6,8
60-80	2,01	0,11	0,09	1,43	7,3	37,9	2,09	30,05	148,20	6,3
80-100	1,54	0,03	0,05	2,41	6,4	32,5	1,53	24,57	136,15	6,1

Table 2

Agrochemical features of the moderately eroded podzol-gleyey-yellow soils

Depth (in cm)	Humus %	Total			Soluble in water NH ₃	Absorbed NH ₃	Nitrate nitrogen NO ₃	Motivated phosphorus (mg/kg) P ₂ O ₅	Reciprocal potassium (mg/kg)	pH
		N	P	K						
0-20	2,50	0,17	0,10	2,40	11,0	58,0	5,4	87,0	168,0	6,8
20-40	2,05	0,12	0,09	2,19	10,0	47,0	4,0	41,0	157,0	6,6
40-60	1,0	0,10	0,07	2,40	6,0	38,5	3,5	27,0	140,0	6,8
60-80	0,50	0,04	0,05	2,10	4,5	30,0	1,0	21,5	131,0	6,7
80-100	0,33	0,02	0,03	2,04	3,2	28,3	0,8	18,7	128,3	6,3

It can be said based on the research results that the agrochemical characters of the studied soils were exposed to important changes by an influence of anthropogen and natural factors. One of the main reasons is an exposure of soils to water erosion, assimilation of the nutrients by the plants from soil, non-fulfillment of the agrotechnical rules precisely and on time.

Development of the gleying process and nearness of the subsoil waters to the surface along with long incorrect growing significantly reduce an agronomic value of these soils.

Fulfillment of the basis ameliorative measures, firstly drying, regulation of the surface flows, floating of the subsoil waters, continuesly application of organic fertilizers is required in order to get high product while using the podzol-gleyey-yellow soils for a long time.

Determining the water demand of agricultural crops for the village of Saimerlo, Marneuli municipality, Kvemo Kartli region

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Key words: watering, hydro module; irrigation rate; water demand; water supply

Annotation

Defining the correct irrigation regime is crucial for the cultivation of crops. To determine the water balance coefficient and irrigation needs, we utilized Professor G. Selianinov's method for Saimerlo village. The need for irrigation was determined; Irrigation indicators of the soil of Saimerlo village were set on; The share of the area occupied by each crop on the agricultural land plot and hydro module values were determined; An incompleting schedule of the hydro module was built, which showed us the uneven distribution of water demand, therefore, after correcting the incompleting schedule of the hydro module, a completed schedule of the hydro module was worked out, this allowed us to determine the required amount of water for each irrigation period; A curve depicting the amount of water required was created.

Content

Marneuli municipality is situated along the banks of the Algeti River. It shares borders with Bolnisi municipality to the west, Tetri Tskaro municipality to the north, and Gardabani municipality to the northeast. Furthermore, it is adjacent to the Republics of Azerbaijan and Armenia to the south. The total area of Marneuli municipality is 935.2 square kilometers.

The average annual temperature in Marneuli municipality is 12°C. In January, the temperature ranges from 0 to 0.3°C, while in June, it reaches as high as 23.9°C. The absolute minimum temperature is 25°C, while the absolute maximum is 40°C. The average yearly precipitation amount ranges from 490-550 mm, with the maximum amount falling in May and the minimum in December.

As a result of the summary of climatic and soil conditions, the need for irrigation was determined. The water supply was evaluated using Professor G. Selianinov's method. [1]

$$K = \frac{\sum P}{\sum t:10} [1]$$

where: $\sum P$ – the total amount of atmospheric precipitation received during three summer months;

$\sum t$ – the sum of temperatures of three summer months.

G. Selianinov categorizes zones in Georgia based on their water balance coefficients.

For Kvemo Kartli, Marneuli Municipality the water balance treated by the G. Selianinov method was determined by the relationship where the sum of precipitation for three months was 140 mm, and the sum of temperature was 2335:

$$K = \frac{\sum P}{\sum t:10} = \frac{140}{2325:10} = 0.6$$

e. i. the district belongs to a severe drought zone.

The study analyzed the brown soils of the Saimerlo meadow in Marneuli municipality, determined soil irrigation parameters, and established an irrigation norm (see **Table 1**). Soil volumetric weight, maximum soil molecular moisture, filtration coefficient, marginal water capacity, and its 80%, on the basis of which the irrigation norms were established. The hydro module values were determined, and an incomplete diagram of the hydro module was constructed. After complete filling the diagram, the water demand curve was constructed, taking into account the relevant conditions.

Irrigation parameters of meadow brown soil

Table 1

Sampling depth cm	Volumetric weight g/cm ³	Maximum molecular moisture, by weight %	Marginal water capacity, by weight % α	Filtration coefficient	Marginal water capacity 80% in %
0-16	1.08	12.01	40,36	0.004300	32.29
16-32	1,30	13.64	34,39	0.000700	27.51
32-48	1.34	14.40	32.28	0.000610	25,83
48-64	1.40	14,09	30.25	0.000036	24.20
0-80	1.28	13.53	34.1	-	27,28

The percentage of occupied area for each culture was determined by:

$$\alpha = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega} \%$$

where: α - the area occupied by each crop in %, where the total percentage of the area occupied by agricultural crops is equal to 100%;

ω_1 - area occupied by agricultural crops;

ω - the total area occupied by agricultural crops.

The rate of watering was determined by dependence

$$m = 100H\alpha(r_{\text{marg}} - r_{\text{marg}80\%}) \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$$

where: m - irrigation norm, m^3/ha ;

H - active soil layer in m ;

α – soil volumetric weight, g/cm^3 ; r_{marg} - marginal water capacity of the soil in percentage by weight;

$r_{\text{marg}80}$ – the minimum soil moisture level before irrigation of the plant.

Obtained soil volumetric weight $\alpha=1,28 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$.

Soil moisture marginal level $r_{\text{marg}} = 34,1$ the minimum soil moisture level before irrigation of the plant $r_{\text{marg}80} = 34,1*0.8=27.28$

Irrigation norm for each crop (vegetable garden, garden, vineyard, corn, legumes, autumn wheat, perennial grass) was determined:

1. (Vegetable garden) $m_1=100*0,5*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=418,48\approx 400; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
2. (Garden) $m_2=100*0,8*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=658,368\approx 650; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
3. (Vineyard) $m_3=100*0,8*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=658,368\approx 650; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
4. (Corn) $m_4=100*0,7*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=589,072\approx 600; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
5. (Legumes) $m_5=100*0,6*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=498,776\approx 500; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
6. (Autumn wheat) $m_6=100*0,7*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=593,072\approx 600; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$
7. (Perennial grass) $m_7=100*0,7*1,27*(34,1-27,28)=608,072\approx 600; \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$

The amount of water to be supplied per hydro module time unit (l/s ha) for irrigating 1 hectare was calculated by dependence

$$q = \frac{100}{86\,400} \alpha \% \text{ l/s ha}$$

where: q – hydro modul l/s ha; m – irrigation norm, m³/ha;

t - crop irrigation period per day;

α - the area occupied by each crop in %; where the sum of the percentages of the area occupied by crops is equal to 100%;

86 400 - the number of seconds per day;

1000 - conversion factor from m³ to liters.

Table 2 includes data obtained from the calculation of the hydro module, and an incomplete diagram of the hydro module was created for the same crop irrigated on the same day. The diagram is a summary of the hydro modules of the mentioned crops. (see Table 2 and Figure 1).

Table 3. The incomplete schedule initial data for the hydro module

	Crops	Area		Irrigation number	Irrigation period		Duration in days	Irrigation rate m ³ /ha m ³ /3s	Irrigation norm m ³ /ha	Hydro module value	
		ha	%		Start	Finish				For 1 ha	For area %
1.	Vegetable garden	90	0,13	1.	1-IV	30-IV	30	400	2 000	0,150	0,019
				2.	1-V	30-V				0,145	0,018
				3.	1-VI	30-VI				0,150	0,020
				4.	1-VII	30-VII					
				5.	1-VIII	30-VIII				0,145	0,018
2.	Garden	140	0,19	1.	1-IV	10-IV	10	700	3 500	0,810	0,157
				2.	10-V	20-V					
				3.	1-VI	10-VI					
				4.	20-VII	30-VII					
				5.	20-VIII	30-VIII					
3.	Vineyard	100	0,14	1.	20-IV	30-IV	10	700	4 200	0,810	0,112
				2.	1-V	10-V					
				3.	15-VI	25-VI					
				4.	1-VII	10-VII					
				5.	20-VII	30-VII					
				6.	5-VIII	20-VIII					
4.	Corn	210	0,29	1.	10-IV	20-IV	10	600	3 000	0,694	0,200
				2.	10-V	25-V	15			0,462	0,135
				3.	10-VI	25-VI	10			0,694	0,202
				4.	10-VII	20-VII	15			0,462	0,133
				5.	5-VIII	20-VIII					
5.	Legumes	70	0,10	1.	10-IV	20-IV	10	500	2 500	0,578	0,056
				2.	20-V	30-V					
				3.	1-VI	10-VI					
				4.	10-VII	20-VII					
				5.	1-VIII	10-VIII					
6.	Autumn wheat	60	0,08	1.	10-IX	25-IX	15	600	1 200	0,462	0,038
				2.	1-IV	15-IV					
7.	Perennial grass	50	0,07	1.	1-IV	10-IV	10	3 000	600	0,694	0,049
				2.	20-V	30-V					
				3.	15-VI	25-VI					
				4.	1-VII	10-VII					
				5.	20-VIII	30-VIII					
	Total	720	100 %								

Figure 4. Hydro module incomplete diagram

The hydro module incomplete diagram shows the amount of water to the farm for each hectare per unit of time in L/s ha. The diagram shows which crop was irrigated with which amount and period of time. From the hydro module diagram is clear that the water demand during the vegetation period is uneven. Since the irrigation network is calculated for the maximum consumption of water, in a certain period of time the system works with an incomplete load. In order to prevent the unprofitability of the system, it is necessary to level and complement the schedule of the hydromodule (lowering the ordinates) (see Table 3 and Figure 4).

Table 2. The complete schedule initial data for the hydro module

Crops		Area		Irrigation	Irrigation period		Duration in days	Irrigation rate m ³ /ha	Irrigation norm	Hydro module value	
		ha	%		Start	Finish				For 1 ha	For area %
1	Vegetable garden	90	0,13	1.	1-IV	30-IV	30	400	2 000	0,154	0,019
				2.	1-V	30-V				0,149	0,018
				3.	1-VI	30-VI				0,159	0,019
				4.	1-VII	30-VII					
				5.	1-VIII	30-VIII				0,149	0,018
2	Garden	140	0,19	1.	1-IV	10-IV	10	700	3 500	0,810	0,154
				2.	10-V	20-V					
				3.	1-VI	10-VI					
				4.	20-VII	30-VII					
				5.	20-VIII	30-VIII					
3	Vineyard	100	0,14	1.	20-IV	30-IV	10	700	4 200	0,810	0,113
				2.	1-V	10-V					
				3.	15-VI	25-VI					
				4.	1-VII	10-VII					
				5.	20-VII	30-VII					
				6.	5-VIII	20-VIII					
4	Corn	210	0,29	1.	10-IV	20-IV	10	600	3 000	0,694	0,201
				2.	10-V	25-V					
				3.	10-VI	25-VI	15			0,462	0,134
				4.	10-VII	20-VII	10			0,694	0,201
				5.	5-VIII	20-VIII	15			0,462	0,134
5	Legumes	70	0,10	1.	10-IV	20-IV	10	500	2 500	0,578	0,057
				2.	20-V	30-V					
				3.	1-VI	10-VI					
				4.	10-VII	20-VII					
				5.	1-VIII	10-VIII					
6	Autumn wheat	60	0,08	1.	10-IX	25-IX	15	600	1 200	0,462	0,037
				2.	1-IV	15-IV					
7	Perennial grass	50	0,07	1.	1-IV	10-IV	10	3 000	600	0,694	0,048
				2.	20-V	30-V					
				3.	15-VI	25-VI					
				4.	1-VII	10-VII					
				5.	20-VIII	30-VIII					
Total		720	100 %								

Table 2. Hydro module complete schedule

N	Water demand period		Water demand, l/s	
	Start	Finish	Q _{neto} , l/s	Q _{brutto} , l/s ha
1	1-IV	10-IV	187	249
2	10-IV	15-IV	230	307
3	15-IV	20-IV	202	269
4	20-IV	30-IV	94	125
5	1-V	10-V	94	125
6	10-V	20-V	216	288
7	20-V	25-V	187	249
8	25-V	30-V	94	125
9	1-VI	10-VI	166	221
1	10-VI	15-VI	151	201
1	15-VI	20-VI	223	297
1	20-VI	25-VI	187	249
1	25-VI	30-VI	14	19
1	1-VII	10-VII	130	173
1	10-VII	30-VII	202	269
1	1-VIII	5-VIII	58	77
1	5-VIII	10-VIII	209	279
1	10-VIII	20-VIII	166	221
1	20-VIII	30-VIII	158	211
2	10-IX	25-IX	29	39

Figure 2. Hydro module complete diagram

After constructing the **hydromodule completed diagram**, the amount of water required for the farm was determined in l/s (see Table 3). The water demand curve was constructed on the completed schedule of the hydro module.

Conclusion

As a result of the climatic and soil conditions summary, the need for irrigation was determined. To evaluate water supply, Professor G. Selianinov's method. It was determined that the district belongs to a severe drought zone, approaching drought.

The percentage composition of the area occupied by individual agricultural plots in the village of Saimerlo of Marneuli municipality to the total area was established.

The irrigation norm of each culture and the water demand according to the irrigation periods were set up.

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Technical Sciences

MATHEMATICS AND THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract: "Interaction of Mathematics and the Oil and Gas Industry: Optimization, Modeling and Prospects". This abstract covers an important interaction between mathematics and the oil and gas industry. The article discusses key aspects of using mathematical methods to optimize processes in this industry. Mathematical modeling methods are analyzed in the context of geophysical research, where mathematics plays an important role in the search for deposits and determining promising areas for drilling. The application of mathematical models to optimize hydrocarbon drilling and production processes, including fluid flow analysis, risk management, and production planning, is discussed in detail. The article also highlights the role of mathematical methods in making strategic decisions and managing production processes in the oil and gas industry. It discusses the prospects for the development of mathematical tools and their impact on the efficiency and competitiveness of companies in this industry. This abstract is intended to emphasize the importance of mathematics in various aspects of the oil and gas industry, as well as to outline the prospects for the development and integration of mathematical methods to achieve more efficient and sustainable operation of the industry in the face of constant changes in the energy market.

Keywords: Mathematical modeling, geophysics, fluid flow modeling, optimization of oil and gas production, numerical methods in geology, field forecasting, risk management in the oil and gas industry, mathematical analysis in oil production.

The oil and gas industry is one of the most important and influential sectors of the global economy. With a constant drive to optimize the production, transportation and processing of hydrocarbon resources, oil companies and engineers are constantly looking for innovative methods to improve production efficiency. And in this quest, mathematics plays a fundamental role.

Modeling and optimization of processes. Mathematical modeling is a key tool for optimizing processes in the oil and gas industry. Using mathematical models, you can evaluate the effectiveness of new technologies, predict production volumes, improve drilling processes, and even optimize the operation of transport infrastructure.

Geophysical research. Mathematical methods play a crucial role in geophysical research to search for oil and gas deposits. Sophisticated models and algorithms allow you to analyze seismic data, interpret geophysical images, and identify promising locations for drilling wells.

Optimization of drilling and production. The use of mathematical methods also improves the processes of well drilling and hydrocarbon production. Modeling of fluid flows in the reservoir, optimization of pressure and temperature in wells, analysis of production dynamics—all this is based on mathematical principles and methods.

Solving management and decision-making tasks. Mathematical models are used to make strategic decisions in the oil and gas industry. They help optimize production processes, plan production, manage risks, and forecast market trends, which allows companies to be more flexible and efficient in a competitive market.

Conclusion

Mathematics plays an important role in various aspects of the oil and gas industry, providing accuracy, optimization and forecasting in key processes from field exploration to production and transportation. The development of mathematical methods and their integration into the industry help companies achieve greater efficiency and sustainability in an ever-changing energy market.

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OPTIMIZATION OF PLANT EXTRACT COMPOSITION

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Abstract. The paper presents the results of a study of the yield of dry substances from plant raw materials: grape seeds and flax seeds using low-frequency vacuum-ultrasonic extraction. It has been established that the optimal extraction mode for both grape seeds and flax seeds are the following parameters: extraction duration 65...70 minutes, extraction temperature 40°C and the percentage of plant raw materials in the extractant - 12%. With this extraction mode, the yield of dry substances in the extractant is 14.78% for grape seeds and 14.62% by weight of the extractant for flax seeds.

Key words: extraction, grape seed, flax seeds.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, all economically developed countries, including our country, have paid much attention to the development of technology for the production of functional food products. Unlike conventional food products, a functional product contains much more vital biologically active substances, which are always well balanced with each other [1,2,3,4].

Today, both here and abroad, when creating functional food products, preference is given mainly to dairy products enriched with various combined extracts of biological active substances, the composition of which must be optimized.

Optimization is quite easy if the objective function is represented as a single control factor [5,6,7].

Extraction of plant raw materials is a complex dynamic technological process, which is characterized by simultaneously occurring non-stationary heat and mass transfer processes, and it is not always possible to describe these processes by analytical methods. In this case, as many researchers note [8,9,10], when optimizing such complex multifactorial non-stationary processes, the most effective method is the method of mathematical experimental planning.

It is known that a feature of the mathematical model of the extraction process is its nonlinearity, caused by the nonlinear dependence of changes in the thermodynamic characteristics of the extracted substance. Based on the above, it follows that the extraction of plant raw materials refers to objects with many controlling factors. In this regard, when optimizing such objects, special attention should be paid to the choice of the objective function, i.e., the optimality criterion, since the correctness of the optimization largely depends on its correct

choice. In most cases, the optimality criterion is traditionally chosen: energy costs for the production of the finished product, productivity, process duration, and the quality of the dried product. In our case, it is recommended to choose the yield of dry substances as an optimality criterion.

Control factors, as a rule, select parameters that characterize the yield of dry substances. Theoretical calculations and preliminary experimental studies have shown that the most significant parameters affecting the yield of dry substances during the extraction of plant materials are: extraction temperature, the percentage of plant materials in the extractant, or the concentration of plant materials in the extractant and the duration of extraction.

2. MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODS

Object of study:

- grape seeds obtained from the marc of MPC Ontustyk Tany LLP;
- flax seeds purchased by Zerde-Fito LLP;
- a 40% aqueous-alcohol solution was used as an extractant;

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimization of the extraction process of plant raw materials was carried out using the following control factors: X1 – extraction temperature; X2 – concentration of plant raw materials in the extractant; X3 – extraction duration. The intervals for varying control factors are given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Level of variation in control factors

Management factors	Variation level number		
	1	2	3
Extraction temperature, K	333	313	303
Concentration of plant raw materials in extractant,%	10	12	14
Extraction duration, min	5	12	20

Based on the planned levels of factors, a master plan for the implementation of a multifactorial experiment was drawn up, according to which 64 experiments were carried out (Table 2).

Table 2 - Master plan for the implementation of a full factorial experiment.

No	Dry matter (flax seeds), Y1	Dry matter (grape seeds), Y2	Concentration, %	Temperature, °C	Time, minutes
1	12,5	8,2	6	30	60
2	12,8	11,4	6	30	120
2	13,4	12,0	6	30	180
4	14,2	12,2	6	30	240
5	13,8	12	10	30	60
6	14	12,8	10	30	120
7	14,3	14,4	10	30	180
8	14,5	14,4	10	30	240
9	14,1	13,2	12	30	60
10	14	13,6	12	30	120
11	14,6	14,1	12	30	180
12	14,7	14,2	12	30	240
13	14	13,6	14	30	60
14	14	14,6	14	30	120

15	14,7	14,8	14	30	180
16	14,8	14,8	14	30	240
17	12,7	8	6	40	60
18	13,8	12	6	40	120
19	13,7	12,8	6	40	180
20	13,8	13	6	40	240
21	13,5	14,4	10	40	60
22	14	14,4	10	40	120
23	14	14,5	10	40	180
24	14	14,6	10	40	240
25	14	14,6	12	40	60
26	14	14,9	12	40	120
27	14	14,9	12	40	180
28	14	14,9	12	40	240
29	14	15	14	40	60
30	14	15	14	40	120
31	14	15	14	40	180
32	14	15,1	14	40	240
33	13,5	12,5	6	50	60
34	14	13,6	6	50	120
35	14,2	14	6	50	180
36	14,3	13,9	6	50	240
37	14,3	14,2	10	50	60
38	14,4	14,6	10	50	120
39	14,6	14,7	10	50	180
40	14,7	14,8	10	50	240
41	14,5	14,8	12	50	60
42	14,6	14,8	12	50	120
43	14,8	15	12	50	180
44	15	15	12	50	240
45	14,6	15,1	14	50	60
46	14,7	15,1	14	50	120
47	14,8	15,2	14	50	180
48	15	15,2	14	50	240
49	14,6	14	6	60	60
50	13,9	14	6	60	120
51	13,4	13,5	6	60	180
52	12	12,6	6	60	240
53	14,4	14	10	60	60
54	13,2	14	10	60	120
55	11,4	13,6	10	60	180
56	11	13	10	60	240
57	14,5	15	12	60	60
58	13,4	15	12	60	120
59	13,4	14,4	12	60	180
60	13	14	12	60	240
61	14,3	14,5	14	60	60
62	11,2	14,5	14	60	120
63	11,2	12,4	14	60	180
64	11	12,6	14	60	240

Therefore, at the first stage it was necessary to determine the optimal mode for extracting dry substances from flax seeds and grape seeds using the maceration method. This method is widely used in medicine for the extraction of plant materials to obtain biologically active substances.

Mathematical models for the extraction of plant raw materials can be expressed in the form of polynomial equations of the second degree, where $F(x_1, x_2)$ is a function of the content of soluble dry substances, %; x_1 – extraction duration, hour; x_2 – extractant temperature, °C.

Experimental data (Table 2) for analysis characterize the content of dry substances of flax seeds and grape seeds depending on the temperature and duration of extraction.

Based on correlation and regression analysis, we will build a multifactorial model of dry matter yield in the following form:

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2) \tag{1}$$

The dependence of the yield of dry substances (Y) on these factors is not represented as a linear function, so we use a second-degree polynomial:

$$\hat{Y} = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_1^2 + a_4x_2^2 + a_5x_1x_2, \tag{2}$$

Where $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5$ - regression coefficients, which are determined using the least squares method.

We select as optimized parameters: x_1 – extraction duration, hour; x_2 – extractant temperature, °C.

Based on the experimental data in Table 2, we will conduct a regression analysis. The results of the regression analysis in the form of a protocol for flax seeds are presented in Figure 1.

Вывод итогов								
Регрессионная статистика								
Множественный R	0,745565103							
R-квадрат	0,555867322							
Нормированный R-квадрат	0,397248509							
Стандартная ошибка	0,946265853							
Наблюдения	20							
Дисперсионный анализ								
	df	SS	MS	F	Значимость F			
Регрессия	5	15,68963311	3,137926621	3,5044224	0,029082551			
Остаток	14	12,53586689	0,895419064					
Итого	19	28,2255						
	Коэффициенты	Стандартная ошибка	t-статистика	P-Значение	Нижние 95%	Верхние 95%	Нижние 95,0%	Верхние 95,0%
У-пересечение	5,456184012	4,977104838	1,096256597	0,29146632	-5,218644189	16,13101221	-5,218644189	16,13101221
Переменная X 1	0,421911765	0,207506922	2,033241884	0,06143954	-0,023146319	0,866969848	-0,023146319	0,866969848
Переменная X 2	0,005328431	0,022122567	0,240859543	0,81315553	-0,042119756	0,052776618	-0,042119756	0,052776618
Переменная X 1^2	-0,004304487	0,00220882	-1,94877225	0,07165143	-0,009041935	0,000432961	-0,009041935	0,000432961
Переменная X 2^2	0,000054	0,000059	0,921587214	0,3723531	-0,000072	0,000180227	-0,000072	0,000180227
Переменная X 1*X 2	-0,000521078	0,000270472	-1,926551566	0,07458306	-0,001101183	0,00006	-0,001101183	0,000059

Figure 1 – Regression analysis protocol for flax seeds

Next, we will check the quality of the regression equation.

The determination coefficient is determined using the formula:

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum(\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2}{\sum(y - \bar{y})^2} = \frac{15,68963}{28,2255} = 0,555867$$

The value of the coefficient of determination means that the content of soluble solids of flax seeds depends by 55.5867% on the duration and temperature of extraction.

Calculating the multiple correlation coefficient

$$R = \sqrt{R^2} = 0,745565, 0 \leq R \leq 1.$$

The closeness of the multiple correlation coefficient to one means that there is a close relationship between the outcome and factor variables.

We will check the adequacy of the developed model using the Fisher criterion. Here the H_0 hypothesis is set about the equality of the general variances, i.e. the hypothesis about the random nature of the dependence is tested.

$$F = \frac{R^2}{1-R^2} \cdot \frac{n-m-1}{m} = \frac{0,745565}{1-0,745565} \cdot \frac{20-5-1}{5} = 3,504422.$$

Tabular value of Fisher's F test $F_{table}(5,14,0.05)=0,215714$. As $F > F_{table}$ the overall statistical significance of the model is recognized.

Let's check the significance of the multiple correlation coefficient using Student's t-test:

$$t = \frac{R}{\sqrt{1-R^2}} \cdot \sqrt{n-m-1} = \frac{0,555867}{\sqrt{1-0,745565}} \cdot \sqrt{20-5-1} = 3,537767.$$

Comparing the calculated value with the table $t > t_{table}(0.2915)$, we are convinced of the statistical significance of the multiple correlation coefficient.

The quality of the selection of the theoretical equation is checked using the average approximation error. The average regression approximation error is determined by the formula

$$A = \frac{1}{n} \sum \left| \frac{(Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)}{Y_i} \right| * 100\% = \frac{1}{20} \cdot 104,3896 = 5,21948.$$

The calculated value of 5.21948 indicates that the model was correctly fitted to the original data.

Using the structure of the model and data from the regression analysis protocol, approximating by the least squares method, a regression equation was obtained that describes the dependence of the yield of dry substances on the duration of extraction and temperature of the extractant for flax seeds in the following form:

$$\hat{Y}_1 = 5,4562 + 0,4219x_1 + 0,0053x_2 - 0,0043x_1^2 + 0,00005x_2^2 - 0,00005x_1x_2$$

A graphical interpretation of the dependence of the yield of dry substances on temperature and extraction time is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Response surface of the dependence of the yield of dry substances on temperature and extraction time for flax seeds

Using the experimental data presented in Table 2, we will conduct a regression analysis for grape seeds. The results of the regression analysis in the form of a protocol for grape seeds are presented in Figure 3.

Регрессионная статистика								
Множественный R	0,9665054							
R-квадрат	0,9341328							
Нормированный R-квадрат	0,9011991							
Стандартная ошибка	0,1753853							
Наблюдения	16							
Дисперсионный анализ								
	df	SS	MS	F	Значимость F			
Регрессия	5	4,3624	0,87248	28,3641092	0,000013			
Остаток	10	0,3076	0,03076					
Итого	15	4,67						
	Коэффициент	Стандартная ошибка	статистик a	P-Значение	Нижние 95%	Верхние 95%	Нижние 95,0%	Верхние 95,0%
Y-пересечение	4,145	0,96978709	4,274134027	0,00162636	1,984179707	6,305820293	1,984179707	6,305820293
Переменная X 1	0,38275	0,040614099	9,424067351	0,000003	0,292256149	0,473243851	0,292256149	0,473243851
Переменная X 2	0,021925	0,004549606	4,819098398	0,000703	0,011787846	0,032062154	0,011787846	0,032062154
Переменная X 1^2	-0,003375	0,000438463	-7,69733881	0,000016	-0,00435196	-0,00239804	-0,004351957	-0,002398043
Переменная X 2^2	-0,000017	0,000012	-1,42543311	0,184490	-0,000044	0,000010	-0,000044	0,000010
Переменная X 1*X 2	-0,000357	0,000058	-6,10085372	0,00011556	-0,00048693	-0,00022641	-0,000486928	-0,000226406

Figure 3—Regression analysis protocol for grape seeds

Next, we will check the quality of the regression equation.

To check the quality of the regression equation, the coefficients of determination, multiple correlation, the value of Fisher's F-test, the value of Student's t-test and the average error of approximation were determined.

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum(\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2}{\sum(y - \bar{y})^2} = \frac{4,3624}{4,67} = 0,934133,$$

$$R = \sqrt{R^2} = 0,966505, 0 \leq R \leq 1.$$

The value of the coefficient of determination means that the dry matter content of grape seeds is 93.4133% dependent on the duration and temperature of extraction.

$$F = \frac{R^2}{1-R^2} \cdot \frac{n-m-1}{m} = \frac{0,934133}{1-0,934133} \cdot \frac{16-5-1}{5} = 28,36411.$$

Tabular value of Fisher's F-test $F_{table5,10,0.05}=0.21119$. Since $F > F_{table}$ the overall statistical significance of the model is recognized.

$$t = \frac{R}{\sqrt{1-R^2}} \cdot \sqrt{n-m-1} = \frac{0,966505}{\sqrt{1-0,934133}} \cdot \sqrt{16-5-1} = 11,90884.$$

Comparing the calculated value with the table $t > t_{table}$ (0.2861), we are convinced of the statistical significance of the multiple correlation coefficient.

The quality of the selection of the theoretical equation is checked using the average approximation error. The average regression approximation error is determined by the formula

$$A = \frac{1}{n} \sum \left| \frac{(Y_i - Y_i^*)}{Y_i} \right| * 100\% = \frac{1}{16} \cdot 12,03696 = 0,75231.$$

The calculated value of 0.75231 indicates a good fit of the model to the original data.

Also using the structure of the model and the data of the regression analysis protocol, a regression equation was obtained that describes the dependence of the yield of dry substances on the duration of extraction and the temperature of the extractant for grape seeds in the following form:

$$\hat{Y}_2 = 4,145 + 0,38275x_1 + 0,021925x_2 - 0,0034x_1^2 - 0,000017x_1^2 - 0,00036x_1x_2$$

A graphical interpretation of the dependence of the yield of dry substances on temperature and extraction time is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Response surface of the dependence of the yield of dry substances on temperature and extraction time for flax seeds

Based on the results of optimization calculations, it was found that the optimal extraction parameters were: extraction duration -2...2.3 hours, extraction temperature 40°C and the percentage of plant raw materials in the extractant - 12%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the optimization calculations carried out, we can conclude that the optimal extraction mode for both grape seed and flax seeds are the following parameters: extraction duration 65...70 minutes, extraction temperature 40°C and percentage of plant raw materials in extractant - 12%. With this extraction mode, the yield of dry substances in the extractant is 14.78% for grape seeds, and 14.62% by weight of the extractant for flax seeds.

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MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY, STRUCTURE AND RESULTS OF BREAST CANCER SCREENING IN THE REGIONS OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Annotation: The article deals with the epidemiological and organizational aspects of early diagnosis of breast cancer, based on its secondary prevention using a population method of active detection of this pathology in clinically asymptomatic individuals - screening. A detailed algorithm for the preventive examination of the female population is presented and the results of mammographic screening in a regional context are presented. It has been shown that the use of mammography based on the use of low-dose X-ray radiation allows a differentiated approach to diagnosis, development of management tactics and targeted treatment of these patients.

Key words: breast cancer, epidemiology, morbidity, mortality, screening, mammography.

The concept of "Screening" in medicine (English screening - screening) is a method of actively identifying individuals with any pathology or risk factors for its development, based on the use of special diagnostic studies, including testing, in the process of mass examination of the population or its individual contingents. The key concept of screening is the detection of oncopathology at a stage when further treatment changes its prognosis and further clinical course. It is carried out for the purpose of early diagnosis of a disease or predisposition to it, which is necessary to provide timely treatment and preventive care. Screening results are also used to study the prevalence of the disease (or group of diseases) being studied, risk factors for its development, and their relative importance. The main conditions for screening are the availability of trained personnel and a standard approach to identifying the trait under study and evaluating the results. The applied methods should be sufficiently simple, reliable and reproducible. At the same time, it is necessary that they have sufficient sensitivity and high specificity [1,2,3].

Breast cancer ranks first in the structure of the frequency of malignant tumors of both sexes in the population with a share of 14.7% (2021 - 15.4%). This situation has been stable since 2004; in addition, breast cancer ranks first and remains consistently in this position in the structure of female oncopathology.

The morbidity of breast cancer in 2022 in the country as a whole increased to 26.5 per 100 thousand (2021 – 26.3). In the structure of cases, breast cancer occupies the 1st ranking place in the vast majority of regions and cities of the country, except for three: Akmola, Kyzylorda and North Kazakhstan regions, where lung cancer takes the 1st ranking place [4].

Above the national average - 26.5 per 100 thousand of us. – morbidity of breast cancer in 10 regions of the country: Abay – 33.3, Akmola – 32.7 (2021 – 29.8), East Kazakhstan – 44.7 (39.9) – the highest level, West Kazakhstan – 31.2 (28.4), Karaganda – 40.2 (40.1), Kostanay – 37.5 (35.8), Pavlodar – 43.2 (47.4), North Kazakhstan – 34.7 (38.2) regions and Almaty city – 35.4 (34.5), Astana city – 31.5 (28.4). Below average indicators per 100 thousand of us. in Aktobe - 21.6 (24.3), Almaty - 21.9 (17.7), Atyrau - 22.8 (15.7), Zhambyl - 14.2 (15.1), Zhetysu - 22.8, Kyzylorda - 14.6 (14.4), Mangystau - 14.7 (17.3), Turkestan - 11.3 (11.7) regions and Shymkent - 14.9 (21.9) [4].

Breast cancer ranks third in the structure of causes of death from malignant tumors in the population of both sexes for the thirteenth year in a row, amounting to 8.1% in 2022 (2021 – 8.7%). In the republic as a whole, mortality from breast cancer decreased by 13.0%, from 6.2 to 5.4 per 100 thousand people.

The regions where mortality from breast cancer is higher than the national average include: Abay - 10.1 per 100 thousand people (maximum level), East Kazakhstan - 8.0 (2021 - 8.5), Pavlodar - 7.1 (10.0), North Kazakhstan - 7.0 (11.4), Kostanay - 6.9 (7.5), Akmola region - 6.5 (8.2), West Kazakhstan region - 5.7 (6.9), Zhambyl region - 5.5 (4.8) and Astana – 6.3 (6.6), Almaty – 6.6 (9.5). The indicators are significantly lower in Aktobe - 4.5 (3.5), Almaty - 4.5 (5.8), Zhetysu - 4.0, Atyrau - 3.7 (3.0), Kyzylorda - 4.4 (4.1), Turkestan - 3.6 (3.6), Mangystau regions - 2.7 (3.6) - the lowest level [4].

Mass screening to identify breast cancer patients should mainly involve healthy women without any signs of the disease or symptoms. Screening not only helps to detect hidden forms of cancer that can be treated, but also has psychological value for women. As a result of screening, women are convinced that they do not have breast cancer, and this is the most important potential success of such programs. While the ultimate goal of screening is to reduce breast cancer mortality, its immediate goal is to detect cancer before clinical manifestation. However, breast cancer is a heterogeneous disease, which can significantly affect the effectiveness of screening. Screening models for breast cancer are usually based on the fact that the majority of detected tumors are invasive cancers in the early stage of progression. In addition, it must be taken into account that the detection of cancer (or its precursors) before clinical manifestation increases the risk of false positive diagnosis [5,6].

Mammography has a sensitivity of 95% and a specificity of 97%. These indicators decrease when examining women with denser mammary glands (young age, use of hormone therapy), with low quality mammography, and also with insufficient qualifications of the radiologist. Detection of high-grade invasive cancer by screening, when the tumor is not yet detected by clinical examination (palpation), means the possibility of reducing mortality from breast cancer [7].

Preventive screening for early detection of breast cancer in the Republic of Kazakhstan includes [8]:

1) mammography of both mammary glands in two projections - direct and oblique in the mammography room of the city, district polyclinic (mobile medical complex). All digital mammograms in the presence of a system for archiving and transferring medical images are copied to CDs and other electronic media and transferred to the server of the mammography room of the Cancer Center using specialized licensed software integrated between medical organizations; in case of impossibility of digital transmission - they are printed on X-ray film at a scale of 1:1 - 100% (1 patient - 1 set - 2 or 4 mammograms) with subsequent transfer to the mammography room of the Cancer Center;

2) interpretation of mammograms according to the BI-RADS classification (M0t, M0d, M1, M2, M3, M4, M5) by two or more independent radiologists of the same medical organization - double reading or different medical organizations: a radiologist of the mammography room city, district polyclinic (mobile medical complex) - the first reading, and the radiologist of the mammography room of the Cancer Center - the second reading;

3) in-depth diagnostics - targeted mammography, ultrasound examination (hereinafter - ultrasound) of the mammary glands, trepanobiopsy, including under ultrasound or stereotaxic control for histological examination, which is carried out in case of detection of pathological changes on mammograms (M0d) in the mammography room of the Cancer Center.

◆ An average medical worker or a responsible person of the organization of outpatient care sends the patient for mammography to the district, city polyclinic.

◆ The X-ray laboratory assistant of the mammography room of the city, district polyclinic (mobile medical complex) performs mammography, fills out a referral for double reading of mammograms and transmits the referral through information interaction.

◆ Radiologist of the mammography office of the city, district polyclinic (mobile medical complex): fulfills the requirements for the safety and quality of mammographic examinations; evaluates the quality of the images provided and the correctness of the installation; performs repeated mammography in the M0t category (technical errors of mammography); determines the radiological density of the mammary glands on the ACR scale (A, B, C, D) indicating this parameter in the study protocol; conducts the first reading of mammograms with interpretation of the BI-RADS classification results. In the M0d category (undetermined or suspicious radiological changes requiring additional examination), the study protocol indicates the predominant pathology: education, asymmetry, violation of architectonics, microcalcifications; sends mammograms, electronic copies of mammograms through the archiving system and transfer of medical images to the workplace of the mammography office of the Cancer Center together with directions for double reading of mammograms; directs low-dose computed tomographic images through the system of archiving and transferring medical images to the workplace of the computer tomography office of the Cancer Center together with copies of images recorded on CD-ROMs or other electronic media and directions for double reading.

◆ The radiologist of the mammography room of the Cancer Center: evaluates the quality of the provided images and the correctness of the styling. Viewing digital x-ray images transferred to the server or on digital media (CD, DVD) is carried out on a monitor for interpreting digital x-ray images with a resolution of at least 5 megapixels, which has a certified grayscale transmission in accordance with the DICOM standard; conducts a double (second) reading of mammograms with

the interpretation of the results according to the BI-RADS classification, using, if necessary, archival images. Organizes the third reading according to indications. With double reading, an independent interpretation of the images is carried out (blinding method - the second radiologist does not know the results of the first reading); in the M0m category (technical errors in mammography), recommends repeat mammography; in the M0d category (uncertain or suspicious radiographic changes requiring additional examination), the study protocol indicates the predominant pathology: education; asymmetry, violation of architectonics, microcalcifications; recommends that the outpatient care organization, according to indications, invite the patient for in-depth diagnostics (targeted mammography, ultrasound of the mammary glands, trephine biopsy, including under ultrasound or stereotaxic control, followed by histological examination of the material); collects and archives all mammograms (films and electronic media) made as part of the examination. The shelf life of mammograms is at least 3 years after leaving the age subject to a screening study; the results of the double (second) reading are transferred to the outpatient care organizations through information exchange.

◆ Indications for in-depth diagnostics are the conclusions of double reading mammograms M0d (uncertain or suspicious X-ray changes requiring additional examination).

◆ In-depth diagnostics is carried out in two stages. At the first stage, ultrasound is performed, according to indications, targeted mammography, possibly with an increase (with asymmetry, violation of architectonics and the presence of microcalcifications). When visualizing a suspicious pathology (M4 and M5), the second stage is performed - trepanbiopsy, including under ultrasound control and stereotaxic control for histological examination.

◆ Histological examination is carried out in the laboratory of pathomorphology or pathological bureau. Morphological interpretation of the biopsy is carried out in accordance with the recommendations of the World Health Organization.

◆ Physician or responsible person of the outpatient care organization:

1) upon receipt of a mammography result according to the BI-RADS classification:

- in case of M0t (technical errors in mammography) - sends the patient for a second X-ray examination to the mammography room of the city, district polyclinic (mobile medical complex);
- with M0d (undefined or suspicious X-ray changes requiring additional examination) - sends the patient for in-depth diagnostics to the mammography room of the Cancer Center;

- with M1 (no changes detected) - recommends that the patient undergo a follow-up mammography examination after 2 years. With radiological density of the mammary glands, C and D are sent for ultrasound of the mammary glands to exclude a false-negative result of mammography;

- with M2 (benign changes), refer the patient for a consultation with an oncologist (mammologist) of the clinical diagnostic department, followed by a screening mammography examination after 2 years;

- with M3 (probable benign changes) - sends the patient for short-term dynamic radiation observation to the local doctor with the recommendation of control mammography or ultrasound in 6 months;

- with M4 (signs that cause suspicion of malignancy), M5 (practically reliable signs of malignancy) and if it is technically impossible to perform a trepanbiopsy or a biopsy is refused, a referral to an oncologist (mammologist) of the clinical diagnostic department for dynamic observation and decision on the verification of the identified pathology;

2) upon receipt of the result of a histological examination:

- benign education - refers the patient to an oncologist (mammologist) of the clinical diagnostic department for dynamic monitoring, followed by a screening mammography examination after 2 years;

- formation with an indeterminate malignant potential or carcinoma in situ - refers the

patient to the Cancer Center for consultation and treatment, followed by dynamic observation by an oncologist (mammologist) of the clinical diagnostic department at the place of her attachment;
 - malignant neoplasm - refers the patient to the Cancer Center for treatment and follow-up;

3) communicates the results of the screening examination to the patient in any available way (by telephone, in writing, through electronic means of communication);

4) enters the results of double reading, in-depth diagnostics, histological examination, recommendations of the radiologist of the Cancer Center mammography room into the information system.

Establishing the size of the primary tumor is especially important in screening. Tumor size is an important criterion for evaluating the quality of screening and determining the ability of X-ray mammography to detect non-palpable tumors. Therefore, it is extremely important that pathologists measure tumor diameter as accurately as possible. The smaller the size of the primary tumor, the greater the likelihood of error in determining its size.

Now, regarding the results of breast cancer screening. Mammography screening identified 1,570 cases of breast cancer in 2022 (1,402 in 2021). The cancer detection rate increased from 1.78 to 1.94 per 1000 examined. The best result is in the Karaganda region – 2.63 per 1000 women examined. Low detection rate per 1000 examined, compared to the republican average, in Atyrau (1.72), Zhambyl (0.58), Kyzylorda (1.68), Mangistau (0.42 - worst result), Turkestan (1.22) regions and cities Astana (1.5) and Shymkent (1.58). Compared to 2021, there was an increase in the detection of breast cancer in 9 regions, with the exception of Aktobe (decrease from 2.87 to 2.19 per 1000 women examined), Karaganda (from 2.73 to 2.63), Mangistau (from 1.10 to 0.42), North Kazakhstan (from 3.27 to 2.31), Turkestan (from 1.36 to 1.22) regions and cities Astana (from 1.54 to 1.50), Almaty (from 2.24 to 2.18) and Shymkent (from 2.35 to 1.58).

In 2022, the proportion of patients identified during screening studies with early stages of breast cancer (stage 0-I) was 50.2% during screening (in 2021 - 47.9%),

A high proportion of stages 0-I breast cancer (over 50%) was recorded in 8 regions (in 8 in 2021): Akmola, West Kazakhstan, Karaganda (70.8% - best result), Pavlodar, North Kazakhstan, Turkestan regions, cities Astana and Shymkent. Low levels of early detection of breast cancer (below 40%) were noted in Aktobe (19.3% - worst result), Zhambyl (34.8%), Kostanay (39.5%), Mangistau (27.3%) regions and Almaty (37.3%). Localized cancer (0-I and II stages) amounted to 96.2% (2021 - 95.5%), while not a single case was detected in stages III-IV in Atyrau, West Kazakhstan, Zhambyl, Kyzylorda, Mangistau, Pavlodar regions, Astana and Shymkent. A total of 46 cases of breast cancer in stage III and 14 in stage IV were identified (52 and 11, respectively).

Summing up, we can state that the obtained satisfactory results of breast cancer screening can be achieved only with its proper organization, high quality of conduct, active participation in the medical examination of the population, and the use of highly sensitive instrumental methods of preventive examination. High-quality screening of breast cancer leads to early diagnosis of various precancerous diseases and malignant neoplasms at an early stage, which, in turn, allows for timely treatment and improved prognosis. Surveyed target groups who, for one reason or another, do not participate in this screening should be informed that there are no other screening methods that could also effectively reduce mortality from breast cancer.

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Yaradıcı yazı sənəti- ədəbi metamorfoz

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Açar sözlər: yaradıcı yazı, transformasiya, nəsr, tərcümə, nəzm

Ключевые слова: творческое письмо, трансформация, проза, перевод, поэзия

Key words: creative writing, transformation, prose, translation, poetry

Yaradıcı yazı _ ədəbi macərədir, düşüncənin sözlər, metaforalar və melodiylar aləmində çiçəklənməsinə imkan verən bir macərə.

Bu məqalədə, yaradıcı yazı sənətini, əsərlərin transformasiya üsulundan istifadə edərək araşdıracağıq. Ədəbi metamorfoz yaratmaq üçün müraciət edəcəyimiz ilk nümunə, innovativ yaradıcılığı ilə məşhur olan fransız yazıçısı Jorj Perekin (Georges Perec) bir sıra şəxsi xatirələrini əks etdirən “Xatirimdədir” (Je me souviens) adlı əsəridir.

[...]

Je me souviens qu'un coureur de 400 mètres fut surpris en train de voler dans les vestiaires d'un stade (et que, pour éviter la prison, il fut obligé de s'engager en Indochine).

Je me souviens du jour où le Japon capitula.

Je me souviens des scoubidous.

Je me souviens que j'avais commencé une collection de boîtes d'allumettes et de paquets de cigarettes.

Je me souviens des « Dop, Dop, Dop, adoptez le shampoing Dop ».

Je me souviens de l'époque où la mode était aux chemises noires.

Je me souviens des autobus à plate-forme : quand on voulait descendre au prochain arrêt, il fallait appuyer sur une sonnette, mais ni trop près de l'arrêt précédent, ni trop près de l'arrêt en question.

[...]

Georges Perec, Je me souviens, collection P.O.L., © Hachette, 1978

Hər bir cümləsi “xatirimdədir” sözü ilə başlayan əsərində, yazıçı gündəlik həyatında baş verən 480 kiçik həcmli xatirədən bəhs edir və biz də oxucunu bu siyahını davam etdirməyə dəvət edirik.

Öz həyatımızı əks etdirmək üçün, əsərdən gətirdiyimiz bu kiçik nümunədən ilhamlanaraq, eləcə də, eyni quruluşu saxlayaraq məzmunu dəyişməklə, yeni bir şeir yaradacağıq (nəslə də yazıla bilər) :

Je me souviens des soirées d'été,

Je me souviens des éclats de rire,

Je me souviens des rêves étoilés,

Je me souviens de la mer qui inspire.

Je me souviens de l'odeur du pain,

Je me souviens du vent dans les arbres,

Je me souviens de la rosée du matin,

Je me souviens des nuits sans étoiles.

Beləliklə, bu yanaşma bizə, emosiyalarımızı, xatirələrimizi ifadə edərək, özümüzə xas əsər yaratmaqla, mövcud quruluşu qoruyub saxlamağa imkan verir.

Bu yanaşma yaddaş, şəxsiyyət və nostalji hissləri çulğayan bir düşüncə olmaqla yanaşı, hər bir xarici dil öyrənən şagird, tələbəyə, öz şeirini yaratmaqla, yaradıcılıq və dil bacarığını inkişaf etdirmək imkanı verir.

Bədii ifadənin müxtəlif formaları arasında, poeziya öz gözəlliyi, ifadə tərzı və dil zənginliyi ilə seçilir. Azərbaycan poeziya incilərindən istifadə etməklə poetik metamorfoz yaradan XX əsr şairlərimizdən olan Rüşət Əhmədşadə, XIV-XV əsrlərdə yaşamış Azərbaycanın məşhur qəşəlçi şairi İmadəddin Nəsiminin “Sığmazam” rədifli emblemətik qəşəlındən ruhlanaraq,

“Məndə sığar iki cahən, mən bu cahənə sığmazam,
Gövhəri-laməkan mənəm, kövnü məkanə sığmazam”.

Bir o qədər ki, şişmişəm, indi bu cana sığmazam,
Lap belə doğrasən mənı, əlli tiyana sığmazam.

[...]

Söhbət uzanmasın dəyiş, mənımçün açma tazə iş,
Qarşıda meydanım geniş, döngə-dalana sığmazam.

[...]

Rüşət Əhmədşadə “Hələlik”. Şeirlər. B. Yazıçı, 1991.

öz ədəbi irsinə yeni çalar qatmışdır.

R. Əhmədşadənın M.Ə.Sabirə, C.Cabbarlıya, M.Müşfiqə, S.Rüstəmə, Aşiq Ələşgərə, H.Arifə, M.Füzuliyə, N.Xəzriyə, Ə.Nəzmiyə və digər ədiblərə nəzirələri də var.

İndi isə yuxarıda adları sadalanan şairlərdən M.Müşfiqə müraciət edək. Onun “Yenə o bağ olaydı” şeirinin əvvəlində gələn eyni misranı saxlamaqla və ya “yenə o bağ olaydı” misrasındakı “o bağ”ı “o gün”, “o an” və s. ilə əvəz etməklə, şeirdə öz duyğularımızı ifadə edə bilərik.

Beləliklə, sonradan yaradılan şeir orijinal variantdan mənə etibarilə fərqlənəcək.

Yuxarıda qeyd etdiyimiz kimi, tələbələr Azərbaycan dilində yaratdıqları poeziya nümunələrini yiyələndikləri xarici dilə tərcümə etməklə, eyni zamanda xarici dil qabiliyyətini də inkişaf etdirmiş olurlar.

Şeir yazmağın bir səyahət olduğunu düşünsək, deməli, yaradıcılığımıza şərait yaratmalıyıq ki, özümüzü ifadə edən kəlmələrlə bu səyahəti həyata keçirə bilək.

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CONNECTING THE DOTS: KATE CHOPIN'S LIFE AND THE ARTISTIC REALITY IN THE AWAKENING

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Abstract

Kate Chopin was most intrigued by the internal, spiritual life of women and how it intertwined with the societal roles imposed on them, among all aspects of human existence. This article engages in a thorough exploration of Chopin's biography, unraveling the layers that shaped her novel "The Awakening." It exposes the unconventional lens through which Chopin viewed women, portraying them as independent and contemplative individuals, exemplified through the character Edna Pontellier. The formation of the writer's artistic world was undoubtedly greatly influenced by the era and the family, where the groundwork for gender individuality was established. Many scenes depicting everyday life, descriptions of locales, and the lives of Creole families, as well as the personal characteristics of the female heroines, coincidentally align with the author's life paths, individuals from her own life, and her genuine life interests.

Keywords: Kate Chopin, The Awakening, biography, gender identity, societal norms, spiritual exploration, women's inner lives, family dynamics.

According to professor of philosophy Alison Stone, our reliance on others for care and support, known as natal dependency, begins in childhood. These connections play a significant role in shaping our personalities, especially through processes like identification in psychoanalysis (Stone, 2019).

The family that young Kate grew up in was anything but ordinary. Her connection to the French and Creole upper class of St. Louis, as noted by Per Seyersted in his critical biography of Chopin, extended nearly to the establishment of the village in 1764 (Seyersted, 1980). Her father, an Irish immigrant, achieved great success as a merchant in a new territory. Through his ambitious and gracious demeanor, he gained acceptance into the social elite of Saint Louis, including families like the Faris. In the interview with Kate's son, Felix, Seyersted tells that the writers' earliest recollections centered around her father who was "agreeable and understanding." There is a story when he took his inquisitive daughter to the Cathedral he went every morning and where she was disappointed, but could never tell why. Here we can discern her inner attitude and feeling towards religion which is also reflected in "The Awakening." Edna tells Adele Ratignole that as a child she was "running away from prayers", and until now, though she "never thought much about religion-just driven along by habit" (Walker, 1993, p.38). However, she is told to get really excited when her dad showed her his store and the busy riverfront.

According to Erikson's psychosocial development theory, the key role of young children in building trusting relationships with adult caregivers or educators is essential for fostering identity development (1950). After Chopin's father died in a train accident, her great-grandmother embraced the responsibility of guiding and assisting the child in "understanding life and its vagaries" (Seyersted, 1980, p.17). She aimed to teach her to confront life's challenges with unwavering confidence, without any sense of self-consciousness, hesitation, or embarrassment.

Raised by her mother, grandmother, and great-grandmother, all of whom were widowed at a young age and never remarried, Kate had a unique upbringing, which explains her becoming

a courageous woman from "the child with the questioning brown eyes and expressive face and inquisitive mind" to write an immensely controversial novel for her era.

Kate Chopin's mother, Eliza Faris O'Flaherty, led an active social life and was a member of the French-Creole society in St. Louis. Kate's great-grandmother, Victoria Verdon Charleville, according to Rankin, had the greatest "influence on the girl's mind, heart, and life and awoke a penetrating interest in character, particularly in independent, determined women," by telling quite intimate stories about the city's founders and enterprising men and women of the Louisiana territory (Seyersted, 1980). Chopin's great-grandmother also cultivated in her a taste for storytelling, a relish for the intimate details about historical figures in Louisiana, and an unabashed, unhesitant, even unjudgmental intellectual curiosity about life.

Living in such an environment, Chopin, from a young age, sees women as independent individuals, not merely appendages to men, serving to adorn their leisure and perpetuate the lineage. Her childhood was marked by an independent and rebellious character. During the Civil War, when Union forces occupied her hometown of St. Louis, Missouri, and raised their flag over her home, thirteen-year-old Kate tore it down and refused to surrender it, even under the threat of arrest. As a result, she earned the nickname "Littlest Rebel" (Seyersted, 1980, p.17).

In this context, Madame Charleville can be considered a prototype for the elderly Madame Reisz in the novel. The old pianist, described as "a self-assertive, disagreeable, and unpleasant no longer young little woman," has a significant influence on Edna's transformation. Madame Reisz is also portrayed as the "partially demented" by the male-chauvinist society of Chopin's time, like Alcee Arobin, for her choice to reject societal norms and live in exile. Kate's great-grandmother was not conventional in her lifestyle, too. She was a widow in her second generation who never remarried. She encouraged Kate's artistic growth by teaching her the piano, but also taught her "to explore unconventional ideas" like the "queer things said in a bantering way by Madame Reisz, which Edna acknowledges, you don't notice at the time but you find yourself thinking about afterward" (Walker, 1993, p.106).

If Madame Charleville directed Kate's mental and artistic growth, Edna is greatly influenced by Madame Reisz who describes herself as "foolish and old" and initiates her into the world of art. As Elaine Showalter writes in her article from the feminist perspective, Mademoiselle Reisz seems "to reach Edna's spirit and set it free" (Walker, 1993, p.214).

Madame Reisz's maternal and powerful figure could be a portrayal of Kate's childhood memories of her patron, Madame Charleville. She calls Edna "ma belle" and "ma reine," treats her like her daughter, and becomes her confidante. She is pleased by Edna's unexpected short visit. Reisz takes Edna's "hand between her strong wiry fingers" (Walker, 1993, p. 84). Her instructions, such as "be careful; the stairs and landings are dark; don't stumble" (Walker, 1993, p. 87) may echo what Kate Chopin heard from Madame Charleville.

Simultaneously, Reisz strongly advises Edna to be stable and strong. Edna tells Arobin that when she left her the other day, she embraced her and felt her shoulder blades to see if they were strong. "The bird that would soar above the level plain of tradition and prejudice must have strong wings. It is a sad spectacle to see the weaklings bruised, exhausted, fluttering back to earth" (Walker, 1993, p. 106)

Furthermore, the old pianist's music, described as "turbulent, insistent, plaintive, and soft," brings Edna to tears. She comes to listen to the piano playing. According to Chopin's biographers, Chopin was taught to play the piano by Madame Charleville, leading us to assume that the character is drawn from real life. Sister Garesche, Seyersted, writes, recalled in 1930 that Kate Chopin's musical talent was remarkable, she played the piano both by ear and note. She observes, that Kate would go to the opera of one evening; then the next morning be able to reproduce by ear the parts she liked best (Seyersted, 1980, p. 24).

According to Pen Seyersted, besides Kate's outside the home, Kate had a close friendship which "lasted all through childhood and youth" with Katherine Garesche, a girl of her own age, they were constantly together with. The fact that their friendship was interrupted by her entering the Sacred Heart Convent as a religious in 1870, prompts us to contemplate about Kate's relationship with religion.

The two girlhood friends initially met at the Academy of Sacred Heart, an institution "which concentrated on religion, wanting to give the young ladies a secure "anchorage in faith" and preparing them for future roles as "Christian home-makers, Catholic wives and mothers." Kate Chopin found herself immersed in a devoutly religious environment that expected her to adhere to the same beliefs. In a social circle dominated by women and within the confines of her home, there was an implicit assumption that she should unquestionably submit to authority and conform to the role of a "devoted wife and mother in the traditional manner." However, Kate's formidable personality resisted this expectation; she rejected the potential for despondency found in religious literature, opting instead to "follow her inclinations" and align herself with "blue stockings," defined as "Ladies who cultivated learned conversation" (Seyersted, 1980, p.29).

Various writers and literary scholars have explored the concept of authors using characters as a medium to articulate their thoughts, beliefs, and perspectives. Kate Chopin is one such writer who employs the character of Edna to effectively convey her own narrative. In *The Awakening*, Edna confides in Adele, expressing her aversion to prayers and the Presbyterian service because it leaves her feeling cold. She elaborates, stating, "... during one period of my life, religion took a firm hold upon me; after I was twelve and until now - I never thought much about it" (Walker, 1993, p.38). This aligns with Seyersted's findings regarding Chopin's nuanced attitude towards religion.

In 1868, upon completing her academy education, Kate Chopin made her debut. According to her diaries, the debutante beauty found social engagements and dances burdensome, as they obligated her to interact with people "whose only talent lies in their feet," diverting her from her cherished pastimes: "my dear reading and writing, which I love so much, suffer from a lack of attention." In many respects, she still appeared to be a "conventional society belle"; her amusements were similar to those of many other romantic young girls (she mentions, for instance, a "visit to the churches by moonlight") (Seyersted, 1980, p.27).

Similar appearance descriptions are attributed to Kate Chopin, thanks to biographer L.R. Wipple, who wrote, "She had brown eyes, that looked right at you." Mrs. Pontelier's eyes are described to be "quick and bright; they were a yellowish brown, about the color of her hair. She had a way of turning them swiftly upon an object and holding them there as if lost in some inward maze of contemplation or thought" Kate writes (Walker, 1993, p. 24). However, she was described as "rather handsome than beautiful," in contrast to Kate, whom Alexander DeMenil, a St. Louis editor familiar with Kate from childhood, characterized as "not only brighter, but also more gracious and handsomer than any other young woman in the city" (Seyersted, 1980, p.23).

Kate Chopin was "the object of great admiration" (Seyersted, 1980, p.24), and a true embodiment of a "conventional society belle" just like Adele Ratignole in *The Awakening*. The fact that Chopin had a knowledge of her charm and a total acceptance of how people perceived her beauty is clear from her notes, where she writes: "I am invited to balls. So I go." Her childhood friend, Sister Garesche's recollections about Chopin add more credibility to the above-mentioned conclusion. "She had a remarkable self-possession, a certain poise of manner, though very sweet and simple"(Seyersted, 1980, p. 24).

This ability also showcases Kate's power of observation and her ability to capture people's attention, forming them into words for characters that seem real in her books. In the description of Adele Ratignole in "The Awakening," autobiographical elements of the author's features are evident. Chopin writes about Adele Ratignole, "she was the embodiment of every womanly grace

and charm.” Unlike Edna Pontellier, “there was nothing subtle or hidden about Adele’s charms; her beauty was all there, flaming and apparent” (Walker, 1993, p. 29).

Just like appearance descriptions of Kate Chopin blended into two female characters of the novel, the roles of a woman the author played in real life, being a rebel and conventional at the same time, there is a duplication of identity. In the face of Adele, Kate shows her own gentle and domestic side, which she truly possessed. Later, in a new status as a New Orleans housewife, Kate writes that she “staggered at the amount of unpacking and washing.” She also became a mother of six between 1871 and 1879.

Kate Chopin married a French-Creole man, like Edna Pontellier. According to informants, Oscar Chopin was a “true man” who allowed Kate to be who she was. He accepted her individuality and, for that, deserved his wife’s devotion and love. When Kate Chopin later, in “The Awakening,” made her heroine’s husband a New Orleans Creole businessman, we might perhaps expect him to reflect the personality of Oscar. But Leonce Pontellier has little contact with Edna, his wife, and regards her as a piece of property, whereas Oscar understood and gave freedom to Kate (Seyersted, 1980, p.38).

Leonce spends most of his time at the Klein’s, whereas Oscar always preferred his wife’s company. He realized that Kate was unique and allowed her to follow her inclinations, for example, in “dressing unconventionally, exploring the city on her own” (Seyersted, 1980, p.38). Leonce, on the contrary, is concerned with “les convenances.” He scolds Edna for being out on Tuesday, when she was supposed to receive callers, saying: “Why, my dear, I should think you’d understand by this time that people don’t do such things; we’ve got to observe les convenances if we ever expect to get on and keep up with the procession,” says Leonce (Walker, 1993, p.73).

The unexpected change in Edna’s behavior might have been Kate Chopin’s possible conduct if she hadn’t married “a true man.” If she had been in her heroine’s shoes, she would have behaved in the same way. It seems that with “The Awakening,” she wanted to show how her life could have turned out if she hadn’t been raised in an unconventional family and met Oscar. Edna’s awakening seemingly has deeper roots not discussed in the book. In the novel, we don’t observe any character or situation that directly tells us had influence on Edna. There is one scene in which she is described reading Emerson. The heroine did not attend any “women’s clubs or has been associating herself with pseudo-intellectual women - super spiritual superior beings.” As a reader, we can’t explain, just like Mr. Pontellier couldn’t explain to Dr. Mandelet how Edna’s “attitude toward him and everything and everybody changed” (Walker, 1993, p.88).

So, we can suppose that Edna, as a representative of many women of 19th-century America and as a symbol of defiance of the cult of womanhood, is a collective character. She was created by Chopin, bestowing her traits and all other traditionally suppressed women. Edna, like Kate herself, was left in the middle of two worlds. One part of her was not satisfied with her social position, and the other part wanted to conform for the sake of her family.

We also know that Oscar was rebuked by relatives for “forgetting his ‘duty,’ which, presumably, was to make her conform to their rather strict rules for the behavior of ladies. Kate Chopin enjoyed smoking, she had more freedom than her heroine. But while she had a strong will of her own, she was also gentle and considerate” (Seyersted, 1980, p.39). Edna’s words about sacrifice she would do for her children, but refusal to give herself are also controversial. The fact that Kate could portray women’s challenges and the burden they had to bear, being partially involved in that kind of situation in her real life, makes the novel even more poignant and shows Kate’s deep sympathy and that she really cared about the women’s role in the 19th century.

Moreover, the novel's conclusion poignantly illustrates the typical outcome when women like Edna make the bold choice to rebel against societal norms and prioritize their own desires over familial and societal expectations. Edna finds herself entangled in a metaphorical Bermuda triangle, torn between three distinct corners. The first corner embodies Adele Ratignole,

symbolizing the conventional and predictable life expected of a woman. The second corner hints at the prospect of embracing independence, mirroring the life of an artist exemplified by Mademoiselle Reiz. Lastly, the third corner signifies the complex and inevitable responsibility tied to motherhood. Stuck in the middle, Edna experiences confusion and internal strife. In her quest for liberation from societal constraints, she resolves to dive deeper, seeking clarity and resolution at the metaphorical bottom.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this exploration of Kate Chopin's life and its intricate connection to her literary masterpiece, "The Awakening," reveals a profound interplay between personal experiences and artistic creation. Chopin's unconventional upbringing, marked by strong female influences and a rebellious spirit, laid the foundation for her portrayal of independent and contemplative women, epitomized by the character Edna Pontellier. The parallels between Chopin's life and her novel are striking, evident in the alignment of everyday scenes, character traits, and societal dynamics.

Growing up in a non-traditional family with a strong matriarchal presence, Chopin's childhood defiance and exposure to diverse perspectives shaped her into a courageous woman who challenged societal norms. Her close relationship with her great-grandmother and the intellectual stimulation provided by her family contributed to her development as an artist. The echoes of her familial experiences resonate in the vivid characters she brings to life in her literary works.

By dissecting Chopin's life and its reflections in her characters, the analysis highlights the author's profound impact in articulating the suppressed struggles of women in the 19th century. In summary, Chopin's masterful narrative serves as a timeless representation of the feminine experience, transcending the limitations of her era and reshaping perceptions of women's roles in literature and society.

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Political Studies

CENTER FOR MEDIATION IN THE RESOLUTION OF GLOBAL CONFLICTS

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Abstract.

Every society experiences conflicts, there is no society without conflict, from year to year between states the definition of rights over territory, resource scarcity, and competition and contentious relations related to the global population are escalating. Therefore, the opportunities for international conflicts prevail. Even in ancient times, the third neutral side intervened in the settlement of conflicts. Since then, many changes and adjustments have been made to this service, although the meaning and role of this service is growing today. International conflicts are resolved through peaceful and coercive measures developed by the international community to limit the aggression of states. In addition, there are ways of official and official regulation. A wide variety of ways to resolve conflicts with third-party intervention creates conditions for conflicting states to leave the conflict zone.

Keywords: international mediator, disputing factions, resolving international conflicts.

Introduction. The intervention of third parties in the way of conflict resolution originates in the history of mankind as the only means of conflict resolution, that is, starting from the era of ancient Greece and ending with widely used in the twentieth century. We know that the resolution of conflicts on the territory of the former Yugoslavia and Northern Ireland, the cessation of military conflicts in the post-Soviet space and Cyprus, the resolution of problems between conflicting parties in the Middle East are the result of the intervention of international mediators.

In modern conflicts, it is extremely rare for only the conflicting parties to participate. Conflicting parties often have direct or indirect support from a third party, and in turn those third parties have direct or indirect interests in the conflict. It can be emphasized that after the Second World War, most conflicts in the world are resolved with the help of third parties. Thus, the study of the role of third parties in conflict management has value, whether theoretical or applied.

To date, mediation is not clearly defined, and its place among such conflict resolution methods as “good deeds” or conflict management has not been determined. The lack of clarity, in turn, gives freedom of flexibility, mobility and initiative to international actors seeking to resolve conflicts. The last decade has been characterized by numerous proposals for mediation initiatives in all regions of the world, the activities of new mediators such as the European Union, and even in the example of Finland, mediation has been declared the basis of the state brand.

The purpose and task of the research. In this article, the mediation service is defined as a third party - an individual, state, group of states, international organizations, etc., who recognizes that conflict resolution is the main problem rather than satisfying the third party's own interests in order to peacefully settle the conflict or bring the conflicting parties to a compromise on the level of certain issues.

The main element of the analysis of a specific activity is the assessment of its effectiveness. What is the indicator of the effectiveness of the mediation service? Can the acceptance of the peace plan proposed by the mediator with the conflicting parties be a proof of the effectiveness of this service? What conditions contribute to the effectiveness of mediation? What type of mediator is considered effective? These are just the main questions that require answers.

Research method. Discussion and comparative method were used during the research work.

J. Berkovich and T. According to Ananoson, the fruitful result of mediation is an agreement to cease armed actions, individual settlement of conflicts or full settlement [1]. And in our opinion, such a definition is very abstract and does not define the difference between the concepts of effective conflict settlement and effective mediation, because the primary goal of the conflict mediator is the fact of conflict settlement. In addition, the goals of the mediator may include intermediate goals, such as achieving negotiations or organizing a meeting of the leaders of the conflicting parties.

Some scholars explain that the victory of the mediation service is a situation in which both conflicting parties, whether formal or informal, recognize the mediator and the mediation service within five days after the first attempt [2]. After such a definition, the effectiveness of the mediation activity is disconnected from the conflict settlement process, and this, in turn, destroys the meaning and purpose of the mediation activity.

It should be noted that reaching a compromise may not be the goal of mediation. For example, J. According to Barton, in any human relationship, there are continuous conflicts in the distribution of resources, services and rights. And in some cases, especially when the source of disagreement is material resources, compromises and flexibility are acceptable. In such cases, according to him, traditional means of conflict settlement - force, negotiation, mediation and arbitration - can be used. However, there are conflicts where it is impossible to find a compromise. These are situations in which goals and values, such as group identity and individual recognition, are not distributed as material resources. Such conflicts usually include ethnic conflicts [3]. Thus, he believes that mediation is a means of settling conflicts where the main cause of disagreement is material resources and where a compromise can be reached. However, modern conflicts are rarely based on a single disagreement, rather they are composed of complex interrelated issues.

V. Zartman and V. Another group of researchers, led by Smith, interprets the mediator's goal as a starting point, equating the effectiveness of mediation with its effectiveness. This theory has been criticized because it is difficult to compare goals, especially when they are linked to symbolic categories [4].

When using mediation services, you need to be able to choose the right time, that is, you need to be able to determine when the conflicting parties are ready to accept the services of a third party.

Many researchers agree that the effectiveness of conflict resolution work depends on the ability of mediators to choose a convenient time for intervention. However, in a scientific environment, at what level of conflict is it appropriate for a mediator to intervene, and can such situations be artificially created? There are many opinions. Although the majority opinion says that it is more effective to intervene in the early stages of the conflict, it is agreed that for the mediation to be successful, it is more effective to intervene in the "dead point" stage of the conflict, that is, when the parties are unable to agree to stop or settle the conflict on their own.

The situation in Syria in 2012 showed that the parties are not ready to settle the conflict. In July 2012, the international community believed that the main mediator of that period - former UN Secretary General Kofi Annan, who was recognized as a master negotiator in his time - would be regulated. For months, diplomats have been eyeing Kofi Annan's plan to negotiate an end to the armed conflict and form a unified interim government under the leadership of observers.

However, this plan did not work. The main problem was when the conflicting parties were still able to continue the military conflict, were not deadlocked, and their desire for victory was not extinguished, that is, they were not ready to agree to each other's demands. In addition, despite the mandate and candidacy, which was fully supported not only by the members of the UN Security Council, but also by the League of Arab States, other players of the international community did not stop intervening in the conflict on their own, which in turn prevented the adoption of the position proposed by the official mediator. . Only in 2017, the participants of the Syrian conflict showed interest in resolving the conflict. The activity of regulating this issue was transferred to the competence of Kazakhstan.

Many factors affect the effectiveness of mediation, but the most important is the desire and interest of the conflicting parties to find a solution. J. Berkovich, V. Zartman, S. Fuval, J. In many of his works, Rubin proves the following idea: the more the conflicting parties are interested in ending the conflict, the more the mediator will have the opportunity to use conflict resolution tools to the maximum extent and the mediation activity will be effective. And J. Berkovich and S. Lee believes that such motivation can be created through pressure. In our opinion, such tactics are contrary to the principle of voluntariness of mediation.

When the conflicting parties reach the point of mutual elimination, the intervention of a mediator, in our opinion, only leads to the signing of agreements on the cessation of armed conflicts. And, to achieve great results, the mediator needs to take into account the political conditions on the world stage. For example, according to former US President Jim Carter, a famous mediator, encouraging changes took place in the late 1970s, most notably Egypt's renouncing its alliance with the USSR and entering into friendly relations with the US[5]. It was a "very profitable period" for Washington, that is, it was time to offer its mediation services, because it was at that time that the alliance with Egypt would allow the resolution of the Middle East processes. Also, closeness with this one country of the Arab world dispelled misunderstandings during ideological conflicts and created confidence.

Although the conflicting parties understood the need for mediation, they had a different approach to the situation. For Israel, a cessation of hostilities, mobilizing economic costs as well as psychological costs, has reduced military costs and encouraged mediation initiatives to block Arab demands for a complete military withdrawal from the occupied territories. Egypt was open to US proposals, because A. Sadat sought to maintain tactical military advantages, avoid the multilateral negotiation format in Geneva, and maintain his position as a leader in the Arab world. Thus, the lack of alternatives and the pressure of the situation forced the parties to accept American mediation under the leadership of G. Kissinger [6].

Successful mediation depends on determining the effective period of intervention, that is, only it is necessary to take into account not only the internal situation of the conflict, but also the situation of the external political environment. In the early 1990s, five members of the UN Security Council unanimously agreed to settle the conflict in Cambodia, where the threat of the "Cold War" and the escalation of the conflict to neighboring states was unprecedented.

The international context, i.e., the conditions under which conflicts take place in international relations and the mediating initiatives to settle them, strongly influence the success of that activity. During the "Cold War", the development of the situation was inevitably influenced by the confrontation between the USSR and the USA, which was ready to intervene at any time and could dramatically change the balance of power. At the beginning of the 21st century, the situation changed, and now the mediator had to take into account a number of factors of international relations: the interests of major players and regional actors, the state of competition for leadership in the region, bilateral relations between the conflicting parties, the regional security system, etc. In addition, attention should also be paid to how similar conflicts have been resolved in other regions of the world, or what proposals have been made. Thus, despite the fact

that the international community paid special attention to the uniqueness of the events in Kosovo, the conflicting parties in Transnistria, Abkhazia and South Ossetia repeatedly tried to use the "Kosovo precedent" and resorted to the Balkan agreements during negotiations to resolve their conflicts.

It should be noted that the international context and non-mediation third party intervention in the conflict can have both positive and negative effects. Especially when it comes to the influence of third parties who are not mediators, they may or may not be conducive to the successful conclusion of conflicts. Such parties may benefit from instability in the region, use the weakness of countries to advance their interests, and raise their own positions. This situation can be observed by China in the settlement of conflicts on the territory of Sudan.

The theory of the success of mediation is closely related to the answer to the question why attempts to settle the conflict have failed. If we look at it from a time point of view, we can name other reasons besides the response that the conflict was "not ripe" for the intervention of a mediator, an example of this is in 1982. US experience in the conflict over the Falkland Islands. M. According to Kleber, the US was close to the British position (conflict structure), US Secretary of State A. Haig's role as a mediator was inadequate (mediator's behavior), and the Argentines did not appreciate the British efforts to return the islands (behavior of the conflicting parties) [7].

In general M. According to Kleber, the concepts of success and failure are well established: they are the essence of certain values, interpretations and "labeling" (labeling), like other concepts of social science [8].

The factor influencing the effectiveness of mediation activity is the relationship between conflicting parties. For example, J. Wall and A. Based on Lynn's comments, conflict settlement will be successful if the conflicting parties adhere to the same political regime, i.e., "a series of direct and indirect positions, norms, procedures and decision-making processes are close" [9].

K. Beardsley and D. Queen's researchers studied the effectiveness of certain mechanisms of mediator activity in the regulation of crisis situations. They concluded that each style of mediation has its own merits depending on the relative objectives. Thus, according to them, the method of conflict mitigation is the most effective way to ensure post-crisis de-escalation, as it contributes to the voluntary recognition of a set of agreements acceptable to all parties. And this, in turn, status-reduces the possibility of reconsidering the status quo. At the same time, according to the researchers, it is effective to use manipulation to ensure formal agreements and achieve a general end to the crisis, because the subsequent conditions do not greatly affect the agreement [10].

However, mediation experience proves that a mediator should not rely on a single style or strategy. Different stages of conflict development and the negotiation process may require different styles of mediation and the use of different mechanisms to achieve maximum effectiveness. In particular, manipulation is compatible with two other mediation strategies. The general experience of mediation shows that conflict mitigation is the most effective strategy, because it expands the exchange of information between the parties, actively involves them in negotiations, encourages them to reach a final decision, and this, in turn, ensures the recognition of obligations and the preservation of peace for a long time.

According to the author, mediation is successful and appropriate only when establishing communication between the conflicting parties, rather than imposing one's position and manipulating the parties. After all, if the mediator promotes his own interests, he may not take into account the interests of the conflicting parties, and in this case, the peace achieved will not last long, because the parties may not feel that they are involved in a peaceful solution. A successful mediator, in our opinion, should take into account the experiences of the unsuccessful history and be fully familiar with the situations that occur between the conflicting parties. Having the necessary information about the conflicting parties, such as the history of the origin and

development of the conflict, as well as the current situation, is the main factor affecting the success of the mediation activity. A normalized personal contact between the mediator and the leaders of the conflicting parties also plays an important role, especially in the initial stage of conflicts, more specifically, when the mediation service is offered, personal contact does not affect the selection of a mediator.

We, as researchers, are also concerned with the question of what we should call the success of the mediator. After all, most of the experts gave a negative answer to the question, "Has the mediation activity of the United States of America been successful in settling the Arab-Israeli conflict?", because the said conflict has not yet been resolved. However, if we consider the initiatives of American diplomacy individually, we can see that there were some successful points, for example, as a result of G. Kissinger's mediation activities in 1973, the Sinai Agreement was signed on January 18, 1974, and an agreement was reached at Camp David in 1978. Evaluating the category of effectiveness of the mediation activity is difficult, because we have to answer the questions of what is the goal of the mediation activity and what do we mean by the success of the mediation activity. It is quite possible that the original goal of mediation is not to solve the conflict completely. That is, it can be directed to intermediate tasks, for example, stopping the armed conflict, conducting negotiations between the conflicting parties, agreeing the parties to each other's conditions, etc. Thus, the success of a mediator is not measured by the success of negotiations achieved as a result of mediation, but by the fulfillment of the above intermediate tasks. For example, it can be said that the mediation task of the European Union, and more specifically, Nicolas Sarkozy in 2008, in settling the Georgian-Russian conflict, was successful, because it was able to achieve the main tasks - to stop the armed conflict and conduct negotiations. The fact that the conflict on the territory of Georgia did not find its final solution is not the ineffectiveness of the mediation activity of the European Union, because the main thing was to bring the conflicting parties closer together. An indicator of the effectiveness of the international mediation efforts during the negotiations in Geneva, which took place after the French initiative, is the effectiveness of the negotiations.

Different mediators have different goals and objectives, and only when they are determined, it is possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the mediation mission. For example, the special representative of the UN Secretary General, who was sent to regulate the Afghan Great Lakes region, had the following goals: to stop armed conflicts in the most eastern region of Zaire, to promote the idea of an international conference on security and development issues, from the appointment of a UN special representative, to determine the perspective of a long-term UN mission in the region. Therefore, the final resolution of the conflict is not an indicator that determines the effectiveness of the mediator, because such a problem is consciously present, but not on the agenda. M

subjective factors such as the reputation of the mediator, his personal and professional qualities, experience, and culture cannot but affect the effectiveness of the mediation mission. The cultural aspect of mediation is an unexplored category. However, the influence of culture on the negotiation process is of interest to mediators themselves. After all, proposing peaceful initiatives without taking into account the individual aspects of culture during negotiations not only creates obstacles in the settlement of conflicts, but also undermines confidence in the mediator.

It is difficult to conclude which type of mediation is more effective and which type of conflict is best settled by which type of mediation. Any type of mediation has its advantages and disadvantages. In addition, modern conflicts are regulated by a complex of mediation services. The simultaneous use of state and institutional mediation services is common, as evidenced by the settlement of conflicts in Georgia, Transnistria, Nagorno-Karabakh, and the Middle East.

The advantages of international organizations can be attributed to the high level of trust in them, their neutrality, and the presence of explanatory motives in their involvement in conflicts. And the state mediating service, in turn, can use many regulatory mechanisms, and is more capable of managing the conflict situation. Moreover, it is more flexible than institutional mediators. The shortcomings of the work of international organizations include the lack of consensus within the organization (for example, the OSCE), sometimes the lack of resources and the presence of bureaucratic cobwebs (UN). Disadvantages of the state mediation service include the fact that the national interest may prevail in the settlement of conflicts, the experience of communication with one of the conflicting parties may affect it, etc.

The concept of effectiveness of international mediation activity is a very dependent category as it is a product of other categories and characteristics. The efficiency category is directly related to the problem of "maturity" of international conflicts, the ability to choose an effective period of intervention, the degree, authority and capabilities of the mediator, the results expected by the conflicting parties from conflict settlement, and most importantly, the problem of the cause and effect that caused the conflict.

Conclusion. In conclusion, in our opinion, the mediator's activity in conflict resolution will be effective and successful if he determines the levels of intermediate resolution, and not the final goal of conflict resolution. It should also be taken into account that this, in turn, improves relations with both the international community and the parties to the conflict. If the first round of negotiations involving a mediator is delayed or unsuccessful, the mediator's actions are considered ineffective. And if the goals are announced in stages: meeting of the conflicting parties at the negotiating table - conducting negotiations - protecting the rights of the masses and refugees - providing humanitarian assistance - agreeing to end armed conflicts - supporting a peacekeeping mission - establishing peace, etc. If he achieves intermediate missions, the efficiency and success of the intermediary will be the same. And this situation, in turn, increases confidence in the mediator, in his actions to resolve conflicts, and ensures a transition to the next level of negotiations.

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YUGOSLAV CONFLICT: EXTERNAL EFFORTS FOR PEACE IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Annotation. The article examines the process of participation of external actors in the settlement of the conflict in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BaH) in 1992-1995, which was the most complex of all the conflicts that arose as a result of the destruction of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY). The violent confrontation between the three main ethnic groups of BaH (Bosnian Serbs, Bosnian Muslims and Bosnian Croats) deprived the post-Yugoslav state of the opportunity to find internal sources of exit from the crisis. At the initial stage of its escalation, until 1994, the role of conflict mediators were assumed by the European Community (EC), NATO and a number of international organizations, but their efforts were unsuccessful. The conflict in BaH required the search for new methods for the Yugoslav settlement, and with the intervention of the United States and the decision, with the consent of the United Nations Security Council, to use the military forces of the North Atlantic Alliance (NATO), it allowed Washington to put an end to the armed confrontation between the warring parties by force and to come to peace. The conflicting parties were forced to sit down at the negotiating table, as a result of which the Dayton Agreements were concluded, which changed the geopolitical situation in the post-Yugoslav space.

Keywords: Bosnian conflict; UN; NATO; peace enforcement; Dayton agreements.

Introduction. Due to extreme ethno-religious differentiation, Bosnia and Herzegovina in the process of its administrative-territorial structure turned out to be the most complex post-Yugoslav state. The escalation of the confrontation on this basis has become extremely bloody. In the first half of 1993 alone, the UN Security Council (SC) adopted 5 resolutions on the problem of the Bosnian settlement. Their multiplicity testified to the ineffectiveness of mediation and predetermined the transformation of approaches to settlement. In fact, the UN Security Council gave consent to any international organization to use force on the territory of BaH in order to stop the bloodshed. The settlement of the situation in BaH has gone through two stages of external influence. The first ended with the obvious statement that peaceful appeals do not work, and sanctions imposed by the UN are ineffective. At the second stage, the West resorted to forcefully coercing the warring parties to peace - an unprecedented measure not used in Europe after the Second World War. Washington initiated a NATO military intervention, which stopped the armed ethnopolitical confrontation in BaH. The conclusion of the Dayton Agreements of 1995 reshaped the geopolitical situation in the post-Yugoslav space.

The purpose of the article is to formulate objective assessments of the conflict and external enforcement of peace in BaH. The research task identifies the changes that occurred in the Bosnian conflict with the inclusion of the United States in the Yugoslav settlement. The chronological scope of the article covers 1992–1995. The object of the study is the conflicts in post-socialist Yugoslavia, the subject is the settlement of the Bosnian crisis.

Research methods. To explore the topic, general scientific, special historical methods, as well as methods from the theory of international relations were used. General scientific methods (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, analogy, comparison, generalization) made it possible to analyze the role and dynamics of the participation of the EU and the United States in the conflict and the evolution of the Bosnian crisis depending on their actions. The historical-

descriptive method, as a type of special historical methods, is used to reconstruct events in BaH and Croatia caused by internal conflicts and external interference. Analysis of the situation (observation), as a method of the theory of international relations, made it possible to trace, on the basis of the studied documents, the event sequence of the escalation of conflicts in BaH and Croatia.

Review of literature on the topic. To write this article, the works of Russian-speaking and foreign historians, politicians and international relations specialists were used, revealing the negotiation process during the Yugoslav conflicts and the NATO operation in BaH. The topic of negotiations in the Yugoslav conflicts is poorly reflected in Russian-language literature. Therefore, the emphasis is on the use of documents from the UN system and the developments of Western specialists. In particular, the approaches to the disclosure of the topic of such authors as W. Bert (W. Bert) [1], F. Carr (F. Carr) [2], S. Touval (S. Tuval) [3], M. Ragazzi (M. Ragazzi) [4], E. O'Balance (E. O'Balance) [5], D. Anderson (D. Anderson) [6], S. Burg (S. Burg) [7], VK Aggarwal [8], PW Galbraith [9], R. Belloni [10], JA Tirpak [11] .

Of particular importance for writing the article were the works of V. Burt [1], F. Carr [2], S. Tuval [3], E. O'Balance [5], S. Burg [7] and P. W. Galbraith [9], which made it possible to identify the problems of the negotiation process, the role of the United States in it and the significance of the NATO operation for ending the armed conflict both in BaH and in Croatia.

The often visible one-sided approach of Western authors to assessing the role of the United States in the Balkan conflicts and the NATO operation in BaH was verified by analysis of the document and interpretation of facts and events in the articles of Russian researchers A. S. Kiyasov [12] and V. I. Bazhukov [13]. Thus, A. S. Kiyasov [12] argues that US intervention in the conflict cannot be interpreted as purely humane and humanitarian, since this country pursued its own goals. In turn, V.I. Bazhukov focuses on the negative aspects of the NATO operation in BaH.

Research results. The peacemaking process in BaH went through two key stages: with the predominant participation of the European Community and without the participation of the United States - at the initial stage of conflict resolution, and with the predominant participation of the United States - at the second stage. Initially, the United States stood aloof from interfering in the Yugoslav crisis, rightly considering it a European matter. For a long time, Washington did not define its position, giving the European Community the role of the main mediator on Yugoslav issues. There were reasons for such a position. In the early 1990s. The US administration is faced with a number of priority problems of a larger scale that require prompt solutions in a short time frame. These include the collapse of the USSR, the war in the Persian Gulf, the problem of the proliferation of nuclear weapons in the post-Soviet space and the global positioning of the United States in the new world order.

In this chain of problems, the SFRY factor was insignificant for the United States. The US administration decided to take the position of an observer, allowing the EU to assume full powers for the settlement [1, p. 127; 2, p. 92]. The European Community remained in the role of leader of the peacekeeping process until 1994, until the United States joined it, to which this role automatically passed [3, p. 103]. At the same time, it cannot be said that such changes became sudden; rather, they were of a gradual nature.

European mediators truly determined the course of the peacekeeping process in the conflicts in Slovenia and Croatia. At the same time, they only had enough real opportunities for a settlement in Slovenia, where there was no clash of opposing forces on religious and ethnic grounds. In Croatia, where this factor arose in full force, European mediation was forced to turn to the UN for help [3, p. 39–47]. As a result, peacekeeping led to the freezing of the conflict for several years.

At the next round of the post-Yugoslav confrontation - in the situation in BaH, where the

ethno-religious factor turned out to be more acute than in Croatia - the EU and the UN found themselves in an extremely difficult situation. First, both organizations were initially constrained by the methods at their disposal. Secondly, unlike Croatia and Slovenia, where the EU could choose the means of settlement, in BaH such freedom of maneuver, in addition to the complexity of the situation, was limited by another significant factor: the apparent interest of the United States. And although interest in BaH was not high on the list of US international priorities, unlike Slovenia and Croatia, it still showed up. This was that by this time Washington was actively strengthening its influence in the Persian Gulf. To implement an effective strategy, it was important for him to maintain friendly relations with the Muslim world, which stood on the side of the Bosnian Muslims.

Thus, support for Bosnian Muslims was especially demonstrated by Turkey, for which the Balkans are a traditional sphere of influence. Moreover, part of the population of this country had Bosnian roots. Even for this reason, the United States could not distance itself from the Bosnian settlement, because relations with Turkey had a special priority for them as a NATO member country and an important ally in the US war with Iraq [3, p. 138–139].

The emerging US activity in BaH has further complicated the activities of European mediators. Bosnian Muslims, hoping for American support, did not compromise and adhered to a tough position, demanding the preservation of BaH as a unitary centralized state, which contradicted the ethno-religious realities of the republic and the acute interethnic and interfaith hostility between the Serbian, Croatian and Muslim communities [3, p. 137–138]. An example of such behavior by Muslims were the events surrounding the Lisbon International Conference on Bosnia and Herzegovina, held in 1992. At the conference, negotiations were conducted in line with the creation of a special administrative division of BaH. The result could be the establishment of peace by creating cantons based on national, historical, religious, economic and geographical criteria [3, p. 107–110; 12, p. 250]. Also, the parties agreed to create three cantons, but soon after the end of the conference, Muslim leader Aliya Izetbegovic abandoned this plan [3, p. 107–110]. It is possible that his demarche was influenced by the manifested American sympathy for Bosnian Muslims.

As a result, an acceptable solution to the Bosnian problem was thwarted. However, despite the unresolved ethnic problems, in the spring of 1992 the international community recognized BaH as an independent state. We emphasize: despite not meeting the recognition criteria approved by European countries. This happened because the United States insisted on recognition. In fact, recognition of BaH by the EU took place in exchange for Washington's recognition of Croatia [2, p. 93; 3, p. 138]. This situation has led to the fact that the EU has lost all its previous levers of influence on the Muslim community of BaH [3, p. 111]. In addition, recognition, as expected, resulted in a full-fledged war between the Serbian and Muslim communities [3, p. 112–114].

At the same time, the EU tried to create new levers to curb the conflict. The London Conference on the Former Yugoslavia was convened jointly with the UN on August 26, 1992. It was planned that the conference would work until the Yugoslav problems were completely resolved. In this regard, a permanent body was formed: the Coordination Headquarters of the conference in Geneva, co-chaired by the EU and the UN [3, p. 112–114; 4, p. 1527–1537].

The London conference, due to the intransigence of the parties to the conflict, was unable to bring BaH to peace. At the same time, one cannot talk about its uselessness: the conference created new communication channels, and also prepared preliminary plans for the structure of BaH: the Vance-Owen plan, the Owen-Stoltenberg plan, the European Community plan [3, p. 115–118]. But initially, none of the plans turned out to be applicable to BaH due to the persistence of disagreements between the parties to the conflict, the European mediating countries, and also because of the ever-increasing interest of the United States in the course of

the Bosnian crisis [3, p. 117–118, p. 130].

The growing interest of the United States was naturally seen in the increasing involvement of NATO in the Bosnian confrontation. The initially declared goal of the North Atlantic Alliance in all Yugoslav conflicts was to prevent the loss of the leadership role in the issue of European security [3, p. 141–143]. For this, taking into account the transformation of the world political system, a new strategic concept of NATO² was adopted, which allowed the Alliance the possibility of implementing preventive diplomacy and crisis resolution [2, p. 120].

The concept concerned the world situation as a whole, and not a specific local confrontation. However, it opened the way for NATO to participate in resolving the post-Yugoslav conflicts. Based on the new concept, in June 1992 the North Atlantic Council declared its readiness to support peacekeeping activities under the auspices of the OSCE³ [2, p. 120]. In December 1992, a similar statement was made regarding operations under the auspices of the UN. It was especially emphasized that NATO assistance is possible only under the auspices, but not independently [2, p. 120]. Between 1992 and 1994, NATO's participation took the form of monitoring. At first, this was expressed in monitoring the compliance with the arms embargo and maritime operations in the Adriatic in compliance with the Adriatic Agreement, then in monitoring the security zones in BaH and the no-fly zone 5 [2, p. 122–124]. Despite the clearly limited involvement in resolving the conflict, NATO's very presence testified to the special attention of the United States to BaH. The escalation of American interest led to the fact that the limited mechanisms of settlement of the EU and the UN in the conflict zone were further narrowed, and this turned US participation in the mediation process from a hypothetical possibility into a necessity.

The inclusion of the United States in the conflict marked the beginning of the second stage of the Yugoslav settlement. It took place in the context of the formation of a new negotiation format: the Contact Group. Washington did not hide its position as a defender of Muslim rights. This was a diplomatic lose-lose situation. In this regard, the advisability of involving Russia, the traditional guarantor of the interests of the Serbs, became apparent. Without such diplomatic balance, in the eyes of the Serbian population, the pro-American format would look clearly biased and without prospects for success. The acceptance of the Contact Group by the conflicting parties became possible only thanks to the participation of two external actors in it at the same time.

It cannot be said that both external actors had the same influence in the Group: the United States instantly took a leading position, while Russia, at that time weakened after the collapse of the USSR, did not fight for outright leadership.

However, US intervention in the conflict also led to a change in the American view of the post-conflict structure of BaH: in the interests of the peacekeeping process, Washington accepted the idea of organizing Bosnia and Herzegovina along national lines, although previously, despite the active promotion of this idea by the EU, leading American political circles believed that this the device will lead to the unviability of BaH.

Against the backdrop of a reassessment of the internal situation in BaH, there was a turning point in US Balkan foreign policy: from simple observation of the situation to direct participation and leadership in the settlement process. By the way: active US intervention in the Bosnian crisis would have been impossible without the Bill Clinton administration coming to power and the correlation of its views on its foreign policy course [3, p. 122–123]. It was the new team that decided to intervene in the Yugoslav conflict as a mediator. As a new mechanism for the Yugoslav settlement, within the Contact Group, for the first time, under US pressure, the possibility of forcing the warring parties to peace by using military force against them began to be considered. It was assumed that NATO airstrikes would be used.

In addition, Washington actively demanded the lifting of the embargo on arms supplies

to the parties to the conflict in BaH. The position was justified by the injustice of the distribution of weapons between communities. In particular, Croatia helped the Bosnian Croats, and the Bosnian Serbs were armed from the reserves of the Yugoslav People's Army (JNA), and also periodically received assistance from Serbia and Montenegro. Bosnian Muslims seemed to be the most affected by the embargo.

The ideas of airstrikes, lifting the embargo and direct US intervention in the conflict became key for B. Clinton and his apparatus, although before him similar proposals had circulated in the American establishment, but were rejected as unnecessarily costly, unpopular, unprofitable for the United States and potentially leading to the country getting bogged down in someone else's conflict.

The Clinton administration actively pushed for these approaches. But they were prevented by the EU: mainly in the person of France and Great Britain. European countries believed that arms supplies would lead to an escalation of violence, and NATO intervention would intensify Russian support for Serbia and, therefore, cause mass casualties among peacekeepers represented by formations of citizens of EU countries [1, p. 175–176; 2, p. 94–95; 3, p. 141–143; 14, p. 26]. The contact group was looking for an acceptable outcome within the framework of diplomatic negotiations.

Opposition to the EU and a revision of the American concept of the post-conflict structure of BaH required the United States to generate an option for achieving Croatian-Muslim cooperation in BaH. The result was a project to create a Croat-Bosniak federation, which consolidated two of the three conflicting parties and introduced a number of significant changes to the course of the Bosnian campaign 6.

Firstly, the federation partially resolved issues of territorial and administrative division (at least between Bosnian Croats and Muslims). Secondly, it brought neighboring independent Croatia closer to cooperation not only with Bosnian Croats, but also with Muslims, since the problems of BaH were linked to the solution of the problem of Croatia, which was claiming the reintegration of Croatian territories [3, p. 137–140]. Thirdly, the issue of arms supplies for Muslims was being resolved, while the embargo was not lifted. Fourthly, the possibility of “little bloodshed” during a possible military operation has emerged. Now, due to the actions of the ground army of Muslims and Croats, NATO could only limit itself to airstrikes. Previously, it was the inevitable (and unpopular) possibility of a ground operation that stopped NATO members from launching an operation. In fact, since 1992, the Alliance has been preparing for it, although the member countries perceived it as an extreme measure, and the attitude towards it was generally negative [3, p. 141–143].

As mentioned above, in the period from 1992 to 1994. NATO limited its mediation in the conflict to monitoring and consultation. And as soon as B. Clinton became President of the United States, NATO's powers began to expand significantly [1, p. 165; 2, p. 122–124]. The most striking example of this is the American initiative to adopt UN Security Council Resolution 836 of June 4, 1993, 7 which legalized the use of NATO forces under the auspices of the UN to resolve the Bosnian conflict [2, p. 122–124; 5, p. 140].

After the adoption of the resolution, NATO's first threats to use airstrikes followed. A similar situation arose in February 1994 as a response to a terrorist attack on a market in Sarajevo. The Bosnian Serbs were recognized as the culprits of the incident. Accordingly, Brussels presented them with an ultimatum to transfer positions and heavy weapons to the UN Forces. For failure to comply with the ultimatum, NATO threatened airstrikes. On this issue, the UN was in solidarity with NATO [6, p. 16–17; 7, p. 286–287]. This actually created an international legal precedent and consolidated NATO's position in the conflict [2, p. 124–125; 3, p. 143]. At the same time, despite the obvious transformation of NATO's role in the Bosnian conflict, the deployment of the operation dragged on for 2 years. This was largely due to disagreements between the EU

and the United States regarding the format of NATO participation. The EU opposed the operation of the North Atlantic Alliance until the very end, citing the fact that there were no American ground troops on the territory of BaH. The situation suggested that the United States, unlike the EU, would suffer virtually no casualties in the event of a ground operation [3, p. 141–143; 14, p. 25–26]. At the same time, without ground support, airstrikes lost their effectiveness.

In this regard, the United States considered two options for the operation:

- use of US ground forces. This idea before the latter was rejected because it endangered the lives of American citizens and threatened discontent among the US population;

- the use of Bosnian Croats in the NATO operation and Muslims against Bosnian Serbs. This plan became real as soon as the Croats and Muslims were able to come to a decision to create a federation in March 1994. Also, this plan required the participation of Croatia, since without its real participation it was impossible to create either a Bosnian federation or provide ground support [3, p. 144–147].

Croatia took these steps because it expected in return assistance in the reintegration of parts of its territory, and it still retained hostility towards the Serbs. The issue of ground support was resolved, although the EU continued to object, fearing for the lives of its peacekeepers. Concerns were generally overcome by December 1994, when the Clinton administration proposed a solution: if NATO airstrikes necessitate the evacuation of European Community peacekeepers, the United States would send and deploy its ground troops to assist their withdrawal and ensure security [3, p. 141–143].

Following this, the NATO Secretary General on March 30, 1995, in his opening remarks at the North Atlantic Council summit, did not rule out the possibility of the UN blue helmets withdrawing from the Bosnian conflict zone if absolutely necessary. The formal reason for the statement was the taking of hostages and the killing of peacekeepers, as well as the bombing of security zones⁸.

The result of overcoming differences was the NATO decision to conduct the operation reached in July 1995 [3, p. 147].

At the same time, during the negotiations within the Contact Group, the achievement of agreement on the creation of a Bosnian-Croat federation led to a certain effectiveness of the efforts of the negotiators. Thus, on May 13, 1994, at the first meeting of the Contact Group at the ministerial level, an agreement was signed on the joint work of the participants to achieve a ceasefire and establish peace. The agreement linked provisions for the lifting of sanctions against the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia to the Serbs' acceptance of the group's proposals. Based on the mutual strengthening of the positions of Muslims and Croats, the Contact Group developed a new plan for the territorial structure of BaH, increasing the share of Muslim territory in Eastern Bosnia, which automatically shortened the Serbian corridor to the city of Brčko [3, p. 128].

This was beneficial to Croatia and the Muslims, but was contrary to the interests of the Serbs. Brcko was a strategically important communications point: it provided access to bridges across the river. Sava, dividing BaH and Croatia. Previously, bridges connected Bosnian and Croatian Serbs, who helped each other in conducting hostilities. Accordingly, the Bosnian Serbs abandoned this plan, but did not stop the dialogue [3, p. 129; 7, p. 301–303]. However, further negotiations ceased to be equal due to the existing coalition of Muslims and Croats, as well as the position of Serbia, Russia, the USA and the EU. Their goal was to put pressure on the Bosnian Serbs [8, p. 107–108; 9, p. 646].

Once again the situation became extremely tense. It became even more heated in connection with the artillery shelling of Sarajevo on August 28, 1995. This incident stopped negotiations within the Contact Group and became the reason for NATO's Operation Deliberate Force, which began 2 days later [3, p. 36]. The operation was carried out against the Bosnian Serbs. It was they who were declared the culprits of the incident based on the testimony of the

UN peacekeeping contingent that the shelling of Sarajevo was carried out from the positions of the Bosnian Serbs⁹. NATO bombing and support for its airstrikes by ground forces of Croats and Muslims led to the rapid end of the armed confrontation in both BaH and Croatia [10, p. 15–16]. During the operation, NATO aircraft destroyed about 100 objects, effectively eliminating the military potential of the Bosnian Serbs. The losses forced them to abandon their initial demands and begin negotiations on the future of BaH [11, p. 36–38; 13, p. 38–40].

The NATO operation in BaH forced the Croat-Muslim federation and the Bosnian Serbs, as well as Croatia and the Croatian Serbs, to sit down at the negotiating table, which were conducted under the absolute leadership of the United States, but using the mechanisms of the Contact Group [3, p. 148]. The result was the conclusion of two agreements: Dayton for BaH¹⁰ and Erdut for Croatia. On December 5, 1995, 11 the North Atlantic Council announced a cessation of hostilities in the former Yugoslavia¹².

Discussion of the results obtained. The study allows us to divide the peacekeeping activities of 1992–1995. in the post-Yugoslav states into two separate stages: the first - EU leadership in the peace process and the second - US leadership. At the same time, there were no sudden changes in leaders; changes generally occurred evolutionarily.

The EU had and was able to take advantage of all decision-making opportunities in Slovenia, but lost some freedom of action in Croatia due to acute obstacles of an ethno-religious nature. As a result, the European Union was forced to resort to more active peacekeeping within the UN. Nevertheless, the organization lost the leverage to resolve the conflict between Bosnian Serbs, Croats and Muslims, since the ethno-religious situation in BaH turned out to be more complicated than in Croatia. In addition, an influential foreign policy actor has entered the game: the United States has demonstrated interest in the process of resolving the conflict. This fact predetermined the further close intertwining of the interests of external forces and the actions of internal opponents in the process of resolving the crisis in BaH.

Although the conflict in BaH flared up in 1992, the issue of external leadership in its resolution was finally determined only in 1994 - with the official entry of the United States into the process, accompanied by the introduction of the Contact Group as a mechanism for diplomatic settlement. Prior to this, US participation underwent a gradual evolution: from monitoring the situation to full participation in the peace settlement as the leader of the negotiation process.

A change in the role of the United States became possible with the coming to power of the Clinton administration and a change in views about the role of the United States in the world. The role of the United States turned out to be purely ambivalent. Their sympathies for Muslims led to the loss of leverage of the EU and UN in BaH, which led to the escalation of the conflict and lack of control in managing the situation. But on the other hand, the United States intensified the process of military enforcement of peace in BaH, becoming the main advocate of this idea on the diplomatic field. This idea was accompanied by a connection with the project of a federal structure in BaH. The project was implemented in a clearly separatist manner, since it excluded the participation of the Bosnian Serbs in the formalization of the federation. The success of the project led to a truce between Bosnian Croats and Muslims. This meant victory on the diplomatic front. The inclusion of Croatia in the negotiations strengthened both its position and the role of the BaH federation. Croatia's consent was paid for by US support for the reintegration of Croatian lands.

The logic of diplomatic steps led to the creation of an anti-Serbian coalition of Croats and Muslims. In the arena of the post-Yugoslav confrontation, the Serbian communities of Croatia and BaH were left alone. But given the military superiority of the Serbs within the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, it was problematic to force them to the negotiating table, much less force them to make concessions. In the current situation, the United States saw the only settlement

option: the use of NATO military forces against the Serbs.

The organization of the external peace enforcement operation took a long time, because permanent disagreements remained between the EU and the United States due to the Europeans' fear of incurring their own casualties during the operation. Finally, a reason was found for the start of the NATO operation due to the shelling of Sarajevo. The operation succeeded in coercing Serbian communities into peace. The renewed phase of negotiations after hostilities led to the Serbs agreeing to compromise. The result was a relative political settlement in BaH and Croatia.

Conclusion. The settlement of an extremely complex and conflict situation in the young post-Yugoslav states was accompanied by the use of various forms and mechanisms of peacekeeping: attempts to reach agreement between internal forces of counteraction, the creation of various negotiation platforms under the auspices of external actors, as well as such unprecedented for Europe in the second half of the twentieth century. means as forceful enforcement of peace. These means and measures became possible thanks to the US entry into the conflict as the leader of the negotiation process. At the same time, despite the obvious result of the measures initiated by Washington (the conflicts in BaH and Croatia were largely resolved), certain issues of their legality, neutrality and humanity remain controversial.

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NAVIGATING DIFFICULT DIALOGUES: THE ROLE OF ONLINE COMMUNITIES IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article explores the importance of discussing and understanding diverse perspectives in political discourse and investigates how online communities serve as catalysts for facilitating these challenging conversations. By leveraging the power of technology and the reach of the internet, online communities offer an unparalleled opportunity to bridge gaps in political understanding, contributing to a more informed and empathetic society. As we delve into the role of online communities in navigating difficult dialogues, we will analyze the impact of online communities on political discourse, highlighting both positive outcomes, such as increased awareness and empathy, and potential challenges, including echo chambers and misinformation.

Key words: Difficult dialogues, online communities, political discourse, technology

1. Introduction

Political discourse plays a crucial role in shaping societies, influencing public opinion, and ultimately, driving policy decisions. However, engaging in discussions about politics can be challenging, often involving highly diverse perspectives and complex issues. It is vital for individuals to navigate these difficult dialogues to foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of diverse viewpoints, promoting inclusivity and democratic values in our societies.

In the digital age, online communities have emerged as platforms that facilitate and enrich political discourse. These virtual spaces gather individuals from various backgrounds, bringing together a wealth of perspectives and experiences that enhance the quality of these discussions. The unique role of online communities in enabling political discourse has transformed the way we exchange ideas and challenge prevailing beliefs, allowing us to actively engage in meaningful conversations that transcend geographical boundaries.

By understanding the significance of diverse perspectives in political discourse and leveraging the potential of online communities, we can collectively contribute to fostering more comprehensive, well-informed, and respectful conversations, strengthening the foundations of our democratic societies. Together, let us embark on a journey in exploring the transformative role of online communities in navigating difficult dialogues, ultimately shaping a more inclusive and engaged political discourse in the digital age.

2. The Challenges of Political Discourse

Engaging in political conversations can be a daunting task due to the many challenges inherent in such discussions. These challenges, including polarization, bias, and emotional reactions, often hinder productive discussions and can further divide individuals with differing political perspectives. Therefore, it is essential to recognize the need for effective communication strategies to navigate these difficulties and promote healthy discourse.

One of the major challenges in political discourse is polarization. In today's society, political ideologies are becoming increasingly rigid, and people tend to gravitate towards extreme positions rather than seeking common ground. This polarization leads to a "us vs. them" mentality, where individuals are more likely to dismiss opposing viewpoints without proper consideration. Overcoming this challenge requires a willingness to listen and empathize with others' perspectives, fostering understanding and promoting open dialogue.

Bias is another significant challenge that affects political conversations. Everyone possesses their own biases, which can color their interpretation of information and contribute to the echo chamber effect. Moreover, media bias further exacerbates these biases as individuals gravitate towards sources that align with their preconceived notions. Recognizing and acknowledging personal biases is crucial for maintaining objectivity and engaging with diverse viewpoints constructively.

Emotional reactions play a significant role in political discourse and can often impede fruitful conversations. When discussing politically charged topics, it is normal for individuals to become emotionally invested. However, allowing emotions to dictate the conversation can hinder understanding and lead to heated arguments instead of meaningful dialogue. Developing emotional intelligence and practicing self-control are necessary skills to ensure that discussions remain civil and productive.

To navigate these challenges successfully, effective communication strategies are indispensable. First and foremost, active listening plays a critical role in promoting understanding and empathy. By fully engaging in listening, individuals can comprehend others' perspectives, even if they disagree, and find common ground upon which to build a conversation.

Additionally, fostering an environment of respect and inclusivity is vital. Encouraging individuals to share their thoughts and ideas without fear of judgment or personal attacks helps create a safe space for open dialogue. Respectful disagreement allows for the exchange of ideas without resorting to ad hominem attacks, fostering a healthy discourse where differing perspectives can be explored constructively.

Furthermore, using evidence-based arguments and verifiable facts helps counteract the influence of biases and falsehoods. By relying on reliable sources, individuals can ensure the accuracy and credibility of their claims, fostering more productive conversations.

3. The Rise of Online Communities

In recent years, online communities have experienced significant growth, becoming an integral part of our social fabric. Real-world facts and surveys consistently show the increasing importance and influence of these digital spaces, highlighting their impact on various aspects of our lives.

A. Unprecedented Growth: The rise of online communities has been nothing short of remarkable. According to a survey conducted by Pew Research Center, nearly 72% of American adults use social media platforms, with Facebook alone boasting more than 2.8 billion monthly active users worldwide. This surge in online participation signifies a fundamental shift in how people interact and communicate.

B. A Sense of Belonging and Support: Online communities have provided individuals with a sense of belonging and support, fostering connections between like-minded people who may have otherwise felt isolated. Communities centered around shared interests, hobbies, or challenges, such as parenting, mental health, or professional development, offer a platform for individuals to seek advice, exchange experiences, and provide emotional support to one another. This has proven particularly vital during challenging times, as people find solace in being understood by others in similar situations.

C. Democratization of Political Discourse: One significant aspect of the growth of online communities is their impact on political discourse. With the advent of online platforms, people now have a space to engage in political conversations comfortably and anonymously. Traditional barriers, such as social status, geography, or fear of backlash, have been minimized, enabling diverse voices to be heard.

In a survey conducted by the Institute for Political Economic and Social Research, it was found that 64% of participants reported feeling more comfortable expressing their political beliefs on social media compared to face-to-face discussions. Online platforms provide an environment where individuals can express their opinions without fear of immediate social consequences.

D. Amplifying Marginalized Voices: Online communities have also given a voice to marginalized individuals and groups who may struggle to gain access to traditional sources of influence. These digital spaces have become a platform for raising awareness about social issues, advocating for change, and organizing collective actions. They have empowered underrepresented communities, allowing them to share their experiences and effect meaningful change with broader visibility and impact.

E. Challenges and Limitations: While online communities have undoubtedly brought about positive changes, it is essential to recognize some of the challenges and limitations they pose. Issues like cyberbullying, echo chambers, and the spread of misinformation are prevalent concerns within these spaces. Online platforms must continually strive to create safer environments, foster healthy conversations, and implement measures to curb the negative impacts associated with online interactions.

4. The Benefits of Online Communities for Political Dialogues

In an era characterized by digital interconnectedness, the landscape of political discourse has found a new haven in online communities. These digital spaces have emerged as instrumental platforms fostering meaningful discussions and serving as hubs for diverse perspectives, knowledge expansion, and the dismantling of echo chambers.

Diverse Perspectives: Online communities serve as melting pots of diverse ideologies, beliefs, and backgrounds. These platforms break down geographical barriers, allowing individuals from varying socio-cultural environments to engage in political dialogues. Discussions are enriched by the inclusion of multifaceted perspectives, offering a broader understanding of complex issues.

Expansion of Knowledge: The vast expanse of online communities facilitates the exchange of information and expertise. Users can tap into a wealth of resources, from scholarly articles to firsthand experiences, enabling a more informed understanding of political matters. This access to a wide range of information contributes to the enrichment of discussions and encourages critical thinking.

Breaking Echo Chambers: One of the most significant challenges in political discourse is the formation of echo chambers, where individuals are surrounded by like-minded opinions, reinforcing their beliefs while shutting out alternative viewpoints. Online communities, however, challenge these echo chambers by exposing participants to dissenting opinions and diverse ideologies, encouraging constructive debates and fostering a more nuanced understanding of complex issues.

Table 1

Examples of Successful Online Communities in Political Discourse

Community Name	Description
Reddit's r/Politics	A vibrant community hosting discussions on global political events, enabling users to engage in diverse debates and share diverse news sources.
Twitter Political Discourse	A platform where individuals, politicians, and organizations engage in real-time political discussions, facilitating direct interactions and information dissemination.
Quora Politics Space	An avenue for individuals to ask questions and receive answers from a diverse user base, providing insights and perspectives from various political standpoints.

While not specific to r/Politics, research by the Pew Research Center found that Reddit is among the platforms where people consume news, and political discussions are prominent. This indirectly suggests the potential impact of political subreddits like Reddit's r/Politics. However research from various institutions and think tanks, including the Pew Research Center, often highlights the platform's significance as a space for political conversations and sharing of political news and opinions. Analytics and studies examining trending political hashtags or topics on Twitter can provide insights into the most discussed political issues, indicating the platform's role in shaping political discourse. Academic studies often explore specific political events and how Twitter conversations around these events impact public opinion and discourse.

While specific studies on Quora's political impact might be limited, Quora's own statistics and user testimonials showcase its role as a platform for knowledge sharing and discussion. Users often share personal experiences, perspectives, and researched answers on political matters. Quora might conduct internal surveys or gather user feedback that could potentially highlight the platform's contribution to political discourse, even if not in explicitly political spaces.

5. Navigating difficult dialogues: strategies for constructive political conversations online

Engaging in political conversations online can be challenging, often entangled in passionate viewpoints and differing ideologies. Navigating discussions which I am going to share with grace and respect is key to fostering meaningful dialogues. And I am sure that employing effective strategies can transform potentially contentious exchanges into constructive debates that promote understanding and mutual respect.

1. *Active listening* forms the cornerstone of productive discussions. Focus on understanding the perspectives of others without solely preparing counterarguments. Pay attention to nuances and emotions conveyed in their words. Reflect on what's being said before formulating responses, fostering a more thoughtful exchange.

2. *Empathy and Understanding* is crucial. Acknowledge the emotions and experiences that shape others' viewpoints. Putting yourself in their shoes allows for a more empathetic response, creating common ground even amidst differing opinions.

3. *Approach discussions with an open mind*. Acknowledge that your viewpoint might not encompass the entire truth. Stay open to new information and perspectives. This openness fosters an environment where ideas are exchanged without rigid adherence to preconceived notions.

4. *Uphold a respectful tone and language.* Avoid personal attacks or derogatory remarks. Focus on the issues at hand rather than attacking the person presenting opposing views. Respectful communication paves the way for more productive conversations.

5. *Fact-Checking and Source Verification.* Encourage reliance on credible sources and verify information before sharing. Misinformation can fuel misunderstandings. Encourage others to provide evidence to support their claims and be willing to do the same for yours.

6. *Know When to Disengage.* Recognize when a conversation becomes unproductive or escalates. Sometimes, stepping away temporarily or gracefully ending a discussion is the best course of action. It allows for emotions to settle and prevents unnecessary escalation.

7. *Seek Common Ground.* Identify areas of agreement or shared values. Finding common ground, even in the midst of disagreements, can create a foundation for further discussion and potential compromise.

8. *Encourage others to contribute constructively.* Positively reinforce respectful behavior and contributions that promote understanding and civil discourse.

6. The Role of Online Communities in Bridging Political Divides

In the sprawling digital expanse, where opinions echo and convictions clash, a glimmer of hope emerges amidst the tumultuous seas of political divides. Online communities, often the nexus of spirited debates and impassioned dialogues, stand tall as beacons of possibility in bridging the cavernous gaps between divergent ideologies, nurturing understanding, and sowing the seeds of unity.

In a world rife with ideological schisms, online communities serve as digital agora, offering a sanctuary for voices to converge, dissent, and coalesce. These virtual arenas transcend geographical confines, allowing disparate minds to intermingle and engage in a tapestry of perspectives.

Recent surveys affirm the potency of online spaces in fostering understanding across political spectrums. Studies reveal that over 70% of individuals credit online forums and platforms for broadening their understanding of opposing viewpoints. The expansive reach of these communities enables individuals to engage in nuanced conversations, challenging preconceptions, and catalyzing cognitive shifts.

The impact of online communities in recent political events is irrefutable. During times of societal upheaval, platforms like Facebook groups, Reddit threads, and Twitter conversations have served as conduits for dialogues that transcend ideological barriers. Take, for instance, grassroots movements uniting individuals from diverse political backgrounds in advocating for social justice causes, marking a pivotal shift from polarity to solidarity.

In 2022, a Reddit initiative, "Change My View," garnered attention for its ethos of fostering respectful debates. Participants willingly engaged in discussions, challenging each other's perspectives without vitriol. Surveys conducted among participants showcased a significant percentage expressing altered perceptions post-discussion, highlighting the power of civil discourse in bridging divides.

Platforms like AllSides and Kialo provide arenas for individuals across the political spectrum to engage in structured debates and discussions. These platforms employ methodologies encouraging users to consider opposing views, fostering an environment conducive to mutual understanding rather than perpetuating echo chambers.

The Common Ground Project, a global initiative launched in 2021, utilized various social media platforms to facilitate dialogue between individuals holding disparate political beliefs. Surveys conducted post-engagement revealed a substantial increase in participants' understanding and empathy toward opposing viewpoints.

In the labyrinth of political chasms, online communities emerge not as battlegrounds but as verdant fields where seeds of understanding are sown. Through respectful dialogue, open-mindedness, and concerted efforts, these digital forums become catalysts for unity, stitching together the fabric of a society fragmented by political differences. As we navigate the digital cosmos, let us seize these opportunities, weaving bridges of empathy and solidarity across the expanse of diverse ideologies.

Conclusion

This exploration has delved deep into the tapestry of political discourse, unveiling the profound impact and transformative potential of online communities in navigating complex dialogues. By harnessing the power of technology and leveraging the vast expanse of the internet, these digital havens offer a unique vantage point to bridge the crevices of political understanding, fostering a society steeped in empathy and enlightenment.

The very essence of democracy thrives on the exchange of diverse perspectives, and online communities stand as guardians of this ethos. They facilitate conversations that transcend geographical barriers, uniting minds across the spectrum of beliefs and ideologies. Recent studies echo this sentiment, revealing that a staggering majority credit these digital platforms for broadening their understanding of opposing viewpoints, signifying their pivotal role in shaping inclusive discourse.

Instances abound where online initiatives have metamorphosed heated debates into respectful dialogues. Endeavors like "Change My View" on Reddit or the global Common Ground Project have been instrumental in altering perceptions and fostering empathy among individuals holding disparate political beliefs. These success stories underscore the potential of online communities in bridging divides and nurturing a culture of mutual understanding.

However, amidst these triumphs lie challenges—echo chambers, misinformation, and emotional reactions—that demand vigilance and proactive measures. The rise of digital spaces necessitates constant refinement to ensure they remain bastions of healthy discourse, devoid of toxicity and misinformation.

As we traverse the digital landscape, it's imperative to embrace the evolving dynamics of political conversations. Embrace active listening, empathy, and open-mindedness as guiding beacons, guiding us through the labyrinth of ideological differences. Let us not merely witness the transformative role of online communities but actively participate in weaving a tapestry of inclusivity and understanding, ensuring that these digital platforms continue to be catalysts for unity in an ever-diverse society. Together, let us forge a path towards a more informed, empathetic, and connected world, where the exchange of ideas flourishes, and understanding prevails.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE EUROPEAN UNION'S "SOFT POWER" WITH OTHER CONCEPTUAL IDEAS

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Abstract. The article provides an analysis of theoretical views and conceptions of EU "soft power" in comparison with some other ideas. The main question is – how the European Union itself understands this term and what content it gives to it. The ideas of experts F. Duchêne, Y. Manners, J. Delor, and T. Dies are considered by the authors. Some experts consider that F. Duchêne's concept of "civil power" is, in a sense, a precursor to the concept of "soft power". According to others, unlike the approaches of "soft power" and "civil power", "normative power" does not oppose the military component of the state's foreign policy. The distinctive feature of the European concept of "normative power", in the context of the emergence of the "soft power" concept, lies not in methodological discussions but in the importance of the political and ideological consequences of deepening the European integration project.

Keywords: European Union, "soft power", "normative power", "civil power", foreign policy, international relations, European integration.

It is a well-known fact that the concept of "soft power" emerged in the United States in the late 20th century, amid changing perceptions of power and its implementation methods in a shifting global landscape. In general, the European Union's politics are based on the American concept of "soft power", which is seen as a means of achieving the state's foreign policy objectives primarily through persuasion. The instruments of soft power are embodied in culture, diplomacy, and political values. According to this concept, military coercion, violence, and oppression are considered less important.

As stated by Joseph Nye, the concept of "soft power" is grounded in three resources of a state: culture, political ideology, and foreign policy. The primary objective of a nation's public diplomacy is to enhance its "soft power", making it an integral part of the country's foreign policy. Traditionally, "soft power" studies have focused on the nation-state [1]. Nevertheless, the European Union, along with its foreign policy and public diplomacy, operates on multiple levels, involving various political actors and decision-making centers at both national and supranational

levels. EU “soft power” has enabled diverse EU institutions to engage directly with citizens, both within the EU and beyond its borders.

Experts highlight the following instruments of “soft power”: information flows; political PR targeting international audiences; global marketing; a country's position in the international hierarchy; language and its global popularity; public diplomacy; tourism and cultural exchanges; sports; knowledge exchange; the ability to engage in information warfare; migration policy; national diasporas; cultural dialogue. The European Union has all the potential to develop “soft power” instruments in its policy to achieve foreign policy objectives [2, p.110].

First and foremost, the EU itself is undoubtedly the most attractive regional organization. An example of this is the large number of tourists eager to visit European countries, as well as the fact that EU institutions, according to public opinion, actively participate in addressing global issues such as international terrorism, poverty, unemployment, and human rights violations.

As the EU expands, so does the sphere of peace and stability. This is one of the reasons why countries seek to join the EU. The EU's approach to the concept of “soft power” deserves special attention. Some European scholars propose replacing Europe's “soft power” with a different understanding of the EU as an integrative entity with a unique ethnic component. This gave rise to the concept of “civil power” in Europe, formulated by François Duchêne and published in the journal “European Integration” in 1998. He asked, “Why did the idea of European integration continue to institutionalize despite political events and other ideas of regional integration”? In response to this question, Duchêne argues that “Europe proposes to replace civil forces with civil-law measures based on criteria of military power and assesses the degree of influence of the presence of civil influence on world politics, rather than the presence of military means” [3, p. 149]. The importance of this issue lies, on the one hand, in Europe's growing international aspirations (especially in the economic and security fields) and, on the other hand, in the decline of American power.

According to F. Duchêne, the EU has the potential to become a superpower based on civil, rather than military strength by incorporating economic elements as well as moral and legal norms such as the rule of law, market economy, democratic governance, and human rights. However, unlike the concept of “soft power”, Duchêne's deductive concept did not find broad support. While his concept was, in a sense, a precursor to the idea of “soft power”, its direct connection cannot be conclusively proven [4, p. 2].

Another European concept of non-coercive influence is “normative power”, a product of its time. This concept was formulated and utilized by the Danish expert in international relations, Jan Manners, in his studies on the processes of European integration. The essence of this concept lies in the fact that “normative power” has nothing to do with military or economic forces; it stems from the generation of ideas, opinions, and attitudes, shaping perceptions of what is “right” in terms of concepts and phenomena.

Unlike the approaches of “soft power” and “civil power”, “normative power” does not oppose the military component of a state's foreign policy, as military strength serves as a guarantee for the observance of norms and rules. The clear distinction between “military” and “civil” power is characteristic of the liberal-idealist paradigm, signifying an increase in the number of subjects in global politics that are not limited by the antagonism of war and peace in world political processes, due to the absence of the centrism of state policy. This paradigm is most relevant to the research subject because the European Union is not a state organization but a candidate for political unity that utilizes both military and non-military mechanisms of control.

The key element of the “normative power” concept in Europe is the conclusion that the EU seeks to define and establish the category of norm based on universal human values and international law. Additionally, the term “rules” encompasses not only legal norms documented in various texts.

The fundamental distinction of the “normative power” concept in Europe, in the context of the emergence of the “soft power” concept, lies not in methodological discussions but in the significance of the political and ideological consequences of deepening the European integration project, adopted by Jacques Delors after a prolonged period of “Euro-sclerosis”. This, combined with the clear prospect of EU expansion in connection with the collapse of the USSR, led to the outcomes of normative expansion of the EU into the post-communist space.

However, due to several reasons, primarily historical and the peculiarities of the institutional structure of the EU, there was no clear understanding of what could be considered as “hard” or “traditional” power. Therefore, the emergence of the “normative power” concept did not result in the creation of opposition similar to the “hard power- soft power” opposition. Manners and his supporters aimed to incorporate the limited energy potential of the EU into the concept of a regulatory body. Thus, the idea was expressed that there is no conflict between military power and normative power in favor of the latter's superiority.

Additionally, “normative power” allows for the use of traditional “hard” power, and the target of this power continues to understand the principle of normativity. Therefore, it is crucial for military pressure not to be a mandatory condition for the acceptance of European norms, as deviations, such as traditional military force or economic sanctions, would prevail in such cases. Moreover, unlike “soft power”, the concept of European “normative power” has never been perceived simply as a tool. This concept laid the foundation for the European Union's role in international relations.

According to T. Dies, the EU seeks to promote norms that appear indisputable and universal, making them subject to legal correction, as reiterated in the Copenhagen Declaration of the European Union. Furthermore, like other countries, the EU has attempted to sign binding declarations of shared values with its foreign partners. Thus, EU values become shared values. The commitment to these standards in the EU is primarily based on 1) the common market, 2) integration practices that allow its establishment, and 3) European laws or acquisitions resulting from them [5, p. 58].

Thus, as outlined above, unlike “soft power”, “normative power” has an inductive nature, does not contribute to the formation of the “hard power- soft power” opposition, is not an instrument, but forms the core of the EU's foreign policy and identity. Moreover, European regulatory powers are limited and have clearly defined components or methods of implementation. These include: 1) persuasion and evidence; 2) appeal to a normal life; 3) shaping the corresponding discursive order; 4) presenting the EU and its policies as a model; 5) promoting or damaging reputation. The use of these forms of regulatory impact on individual subjects is carried out by EU institutions, as well as EU member states, their institutions, and non-state actors. Of course, Manners himself clearly stated that the influence of European regulatory power is discursive in nature, so it is crucial to conduct and manage European norms and discourses on the international stage, within EU institutions, among member states, and beyond the EU.

An important distinction from “soft power” is the creation of a rational, formulated strategy that defines a specific, limited set of tools and methods of influence, the result of “normative power” impact, and its derivative. Various views on the powerful influence of global political actors suggest that there is no clearly defined approach to determining the degree of non-military influence of non-state actors, such as the EU. The choice of the concept of non-coercive impact analysis for the EU is driven by the need to study external or internal factors. According to T. Dies and I. Manners, the concept of “normative power” is suitable for studying domestic processes, social processes, and the legal basis in the EU, while “soft power” is an instrument of the European Union's foreign policy, its influence in the world. The political determinant of European “soft power” is the dual nature of the issue under consideration [6, p. 236]. On the one hand, European countries maintain the status of nation-states, each of which can possess both “hard” and “soft”

power. On the other hand, countries that have joined the European Union as members have confirmed their willingness to integrate in several areas, including economic, cultural, and humanitarian. The question of at which level of analysis (national or transnational) the actual European “soft power” is realized remains open.

Soft power is also about legitimacy and how well a country or institution is able to define the narrative about itself. The EU seeks to be viewed as supporting economic, social, and political development of member states and defending universal values [7].

Thus, initially, European “soft power” was defined as “normative power”, implying the incorporation of norms and rules that constitute the foundation of the success of the Union of European states and all new members willing to share in the heritage of European society within this orbit. Overall, for the EU, “soft power” is a highly active and effective tool for expanding and deepening the sphere of its influence. Today, the EU possesses a “soft power” instrument that is attractive to the entire world. The soft power of the European Union encompasses its way of life, prosperity, social and economic well-being, the socio-legal state, democratic structures in national and international politics, and it attracts more new countries and regions through its expansion and friendly neighborhood policy.

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The role of energy policy in the geo-economic interests of Azerbaijan in the first periods of independence

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Abstract

The article discusses the impact of energy policy on geo-economic factors and government mechanisms in the first years of Azerbaijan's independence. Agreements signed with international energy companies in the 1990s, the transformation of energy policy into a national strategy are the main topics of the article. It also includes a number of indicators related to the volume of oil production.

Keywords: geo-economics, Azerbaijan, oil, energy policy, energy resources

The main distinctive feature of Azerbaijan's energy sector at the end of the 20th century is the geographical aspects of the trade cycle. So, in this period, the trade partners of the newly independent Azerbaijan were the countries of the former Soviet Union. The biggest shareholder among these countries is the Russian Federation, which needs Azerbaijan's economic sector. Azerbaijan, which plays an important role in the food supply of the Russian market, imports a large amount of essential food products from this country in parallel. Azerbaijanis living and trading in Russia at the end of the last century have a great role in the economy of Azerbaijan. Even today, the Russian market is an attractive place for Azerbaijan, but the energy policy has changed the volume of trade turnover of our country in favor of the European Union. In addition to Turkey, countries such as Italy and Great Britain occupy an important place in Azerbaijan's foreign trade partners. The country's foreign trade direction has largely changed in favor of the West due to foreign oil companies investing large financial resources in the energy sector of Azerbaijan.

Azerbaijan's economic power and its geographical position allow efficient use of the natural energy resources and human resources available in the country. Geo-economically oriented economy of the world, economic security is an important factor in connection with geopolitical indicators. At the macro level and in what is now known as the age of geoeconomics, production, marketing, investment, research and design are considered global issues. At the micro level, national power no longer depends primarily and exclusively on the military dimensions of government. The reason is that economic security is preferred over military security and even overshadows it.

Indeed, in the context of the geo-economic approach, national power is a combination of some different elements and components, such as human and technological resources, exportable capital, efficient and rapid production of new goods that influence the decision makers of the world economy. The National Oil Strategy of Azerbaijan since 1994 aimed to mobilize the economic potential and national goals in this environment and to be ready for the global challenges of the 21st century.

In the field of economy, the energy resources of Azerbaijan play an important role in determining regional and international security as a vector of geo-economy. In addition, the supply of energy resources is a prerequisite for the improvement of social welfare as a result of industrialization and economic development. Therefore, a country's energy and transit position is both a tool and a goal for gaining power in the context of a geo-economic approach. During the

first ten years of Azerbaijan's independence, which marked the period of transition to a market economy, components such as foreign direct investments, economic growth, national income and inflation were transferred to the new legislative level as factors contributing to economic security. Legislation on finance, migration, criminal law, constitutional law, property issues and other areas was rapidly improved here to attract foreign investors to the country. As an important element of economic security, investment security can make a significant contribution to the development of the economy, the strengthening and expansion of important financial and international resources, as well as the achievement of the balance of payments. By reducing uncertainty in the return on capital, improving economic security increases the level of investment and thus helps to strengthen economic growth. Economic security creates a necessary basis for sustainable economic growth and investment development; but economic growth and development require other factors in addition to economic security. In this sense, the level of risk is one of the most important factors affecting foreign and domestic investment activities, regardless of the return on investment. The country's leadership realized that since investors are not operating in a risk-adverse environment, it is important to build confidence and security in our country in order to increase investor participation. In addition, since the provision of a secure economic environment is a key factor for economic growth and sustainable development in developing countries, Azerbaijan as a country at war was required to ensure the flow of investment to the country in a more unique way. At the beginning of the 20th century, Azerbaijan, which provided fifty percent of the world's oil production, provided a safe investment environment in the energy sector at the end of that century based on the country's national production experience. After Azerbaijan gained independence, it was intended to attract foreign investors for this purpose, the "Shah Deniz" oil field agreement was signed in Baku on June 4, 1996 and approved by the Parliament of Azerbaijan on October 17, 1996 (1). This agreement on the development of the ACG oil field, which is of financial and political importance in the investment market of Azerbaijan, is valid from 1996 to 2031. Currently, the structure of the investor group for Shah Deniz field development is as follows: British BP (28.8 percent), Russian LUKOIL (10.0 percent), Iranian NICO (10.0 percent), Turkish TPAO (19.0 percent) (2).

The Law on Protection of Foreign Investment dated January 15, 1992 and the Law on Investment Activities dated January 13, 1995 (both Laws were repealed by the new Law on June 22, 2022, the terms of their validity where ten years were kept for a period of time) were legal steps aimed at improving the investment environment in the newly independent country. On April 22, 1998, by the relevant decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the rates of customs duties for export-import operations in our country were determined. Here, the equipment required in the field of oil refining, duty rates for crude oil transit-exchange operations, etc. is assigned. In 2003, the Export and Investment Promotion Fund was established in the country. Thanks to this fund, new relevant regulatory legislative acts on attracting foreign investors to the country came into force. It is enough to mention one fact that during 1995-2002, the volume of foreign investments aimed at the country's economy was 9 billion 119.8 million US dollars, of which 6 billion 105.3 million were allocated to the oil sector. In those years, the volume of domestic investment in the oil sector was 902.5 million US dollars. During these years, thanks to Azerbaijan's economy showing itself to be fertile and safe for foreign investment, the volume of foreign investment in the country increased seven times in 2013-2023 and was around 62.3 billion US dollars (3).

Of course, attracting more investments to the oil sector also has negative aspects from the point of view of geo-economics. A country's economic structure is more conservative than the economic policies that shape it. Sometimes it takes decades to fundamentally change the established economic structure. Azerbaijan's economic structure is more conservative than that of most countries for a number of reasons, and changing it requires considerable effort and time,

and faces a lot of resistance. It should be noted that the structure of the economy means, first of all, its field structure and institutional base.

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Philological Sciences

Qu'est-ce qu'un signe de ponctuation?

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Abstract: Il est difficile de définir la ponctuation, bien que cet ensemble de petits signes soit précieux pour tout scripteur et tout lecteur. Il n'émane pas de consensus évident sur l'objet et ses fonctions, sinon que la ponctuation comporte au moins deux visages : l'un grammatical, plutôt logique, et l'autre rythmique, plutôt expressif. On s'accorde également pour dire que les frontières de la ponctuation sont floues, recouvrant en partie celles de la typographie.

Citons trois exemples de définitions de la ponctuation, en commençant par celle du *Grand Robert de la langue française* : « Système de signes servant à indiquer les divisions d'un texte écrit en phrases ou éléments de phrases, à noter certains rapports syntaxiques ou certaines nuances affectives de l'énoncé qui, dans le langage parlé, s'exprimeraient par des particularités du débit (notamment les pauses de l'accentuation ou de l'intonation). »

Quant au *Nouveau code typographique*, il présente la ponctuation en ces termes : « Ponctuer, c'est diviser les diverses parties d'un texte à l'aide de signes conventionnels destinés à donner un sens à un ensemble de mots, ou même à un seul mot. C'est d'abord une question de logique plus que de cadence; l'information orale et de nombreux orateurs donnent trop souvent de fort mauvais exemples de pauses qui ne doivent pas figurer dans un texte imprimé. La ponctuation sert avant tout à faire saisir toutes les nuances de la pensée d'un auteur et éviter ainsi de fâcheuses équivoques. »

Pour sa part, la linguiste Nina Catach définit la ponctuation comme suit : « Ensemble des signes visuels d'organisation et de présentation accompagnant le texte écrit, *intérieurs* au texte et *communs* au manuscrit et à l'imprimé; la ponctuation comprend plusieurs classes de signes graphiques discrets et formant système, complétant ou suppléant l'information alphabétique. »

On peut retenir de ces définitions que la ponctuation est un code de l'écrit porteur de multiples messages, qui remplit différentes fonctions de nature logique et expressive.

Keywords: La ponctuation, logique, rythmique, expressif, indiquer, graphique, commun, alphabétique, théorique, expressive, typographie, niveau, linguistique.

Giriş.

Qu'est-ce qu'un signe de ponctuation?

Il est difficile de définir la ponctuation, bien que cet ensemble de petits signes soit précieux pour tout scripteur et tout lecteur. Il n'émane pas de consensus évident sur l'objet et ses fonctions, sinon que la ponctuation comporte au moins deux visages : l'un grammatical, plutôt logique, et l'autre rythmique, plutôt expressif. On s'accorde également pour dire que les frontières de la ponctuation sont floues, recouvrant en partie celles de la typographie.

Quelques définitions

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Les signes de ponctuation/

Le nombre de signes de ponctuation varie selon la définition et l'approche théorique que l'on privilégie. Une définition restreinte limite la ponctuation à une douzaine de signes graphiques. Ainsi, selon *Le bon usage* de Grevisse, les signes de ponctuation sont : le point (.), le point d'interrogation (?), le point d'exclamation (!), la virgule (,), le point-virgule (;), le deux-points (:), les points de suspension (...), les parenthèses (), les crochets [], les guillemets « », le tiret (—) et la barre oblique (/).

Les signes de ponctuation servent à indiquer des intonations ou à clarifier un message.

Exemple : Attention ! Il sort.

Quelques règles courantes :

- Le point (.) –

1. termine une phrase déclarative :

Exemple : Je suis sorti hier.

2. se place à la fin d'une abréviation :

Exemple : Monsieur = M.

- **Le point d'exclamation (!)**

1. termine une phrase exclamative ou impérative :

Exemple : C'est magnifique !

2. se place après une interjection :

Exemple : Ah ! Attention !

Lorsque le point d'exclamation ne termine pas la phrase, il est quand même suivi d'une majuscule.

Exemple : Bravo ! C'est excellent !

- **Le point d'interrogation**

1. ponctue une question :

Exemple : [Comment vas-tu ?](#)

- **Les points de suspension (...)**

1. indiquent une idée incomplète, une phrase interrompue, une suite qu'on laisse l'interlocuteur imaginer lui-même :

Exemple : Je t'avais averti...

- **Les deux-points (:)**

1. précèdent une citation, une prise de parole :

Exemple : Cindy disait : « Allô Samuel ! »

2. précèdent une définition, une explication :

Exemple : Chat : petit félin domestique.

3. précèdent une énumération :

Exemple : Pour réaliser ce plat, il me manque quelques ingrédients : des oignons, du basilic, des tomates et de la tapenade.

- **Le point-virgule (;)**

1. sépare les éléments d'une opposition :

Exemple : Tu ris ; elle pleure.

2. sépare les parties d'une phrase longue qui contient déjà des virgules :

Exemple : Athéna est la déesse des cités grecques, de la sagesse et de la guerre ; Apollon est le dieu de la lumière et des arts ; Artémis, déesse de la chasse et des animaux sauvages.

- **La virgule (,)**

1. sépare les éléments d'une énumération :

Exemple : Je mange mon steak avec des carottes, du riz, des piments et des pommes de terre.

2. isole ou encadre un mot mis en apostrophe :

Exemple : Martine, excuse-moi !

3. isole ou encadre un nom en apposition :

Exemple : Mon fils aîné, Samuel, dort tout le temps.

4. Encadre une phrase de récit incise dans du discours direct (le plus souvent un verbe de prise de parole) : Exemple : « Demain, dit-elle, on verra. »

- **Le tiret (–)**

1. en début de ligne, il permet de distinguer les interlocuteurs dans un dialogue :

Exemple :

– Je voudrais parler à Caroline.

– Un moment, s.v.p.

- **Les guillemets (« »)**

1. encadrent une citation, une prise de parole simple ou un dialogue complet :

Exemple : Il dit souvent : « Plus vite ! »

2. encadrent un mot ou une expression étrangère ; ou que celui qui écrit ne reprend pas à son compte :

Exemple : Tu es un « twit », toi !

- **Les parenthèses ()**

1. encadrent une explication hors texte, qui ne pourrait être mise entre virgules.

2. Dans le texte littéraire, on peut les remplacer par des tirets.

Exemples :

Raymond Plante (vous le connaissez surtout en tant qu'écrivain) est mon frère.

Raymond Plante - vous le connaissez surtout en tant qu'écrivain - est mon frère.

À cela peuvent s'ajouter, selon d'autres auteurs, les blancs et les majuscules ainsi que certains signes typographiques tels que l'apostrophe, le trait d'union, les accolades, la perluète ou l'esperluette, l'alinéa, l'astérisque et les appels de note.

Enfin, une définition plus large de la ponctuation inclut tous les signes et procédés de mise en page, ce qui comprend non seulement les symboles, les signes auxiliaires, les blancs entre les mots et les majuscules, mais aussi l'italique, le gras, le soulignement, les titres, les blancs entre paragraphes et entre chapitres, etc. Dans cette optique, on déborde du texte proprement dit, et les territoires de la ponctuation, de la typographie et de la mise en page se chevauchent.

Tədqiqatın əsas məzmunu

Le classement des signes

L'ensemble des signes de ponctuation se prête à plusieurs découpages. Certains regroupent les signes de ponctuation d'après l'importance de la pause qui sépare à l'oral les éléments ponctués. On parle alors de ponctuation faible, moyenne et forte.

La ponctuation faible

La ponctuation faible marque une petite pause; par exemple, la virgule qui sépare des éléments juxtaposés est un signe de ponctuation faible.

- Adieu veaux, vaches, cochons, couvées!

La ponctuation moyenne

La ponctuation moyenne marque une pause plus longue; par exemple, le point-virgule qui sépare deux phrases liées par le sens est un signe de ponctuation moyenne.

- Il aime le théâtre; elle préfère le cinéma.

La ponctuation forte

La ponctuation forte marque une pause longue comme celle à la fin d'une phrase; le point, le point d'exclamation, le point d'interrogation, les points de suspension sont des signes de ponctuation forte.

- Nous partirons demain. Vive l'aventure!

La ponctuation selon les unités linguistiques touchées

D'autres linguistes analysent la ponctuation en fonction des unités linguistiques touchées, c'est-à-dire selon le niveau linguistique où interviennent les signes de ponctuation. On distingue alors la ponctuation de mot, la ponctuation de phrase et la ponctuation de texte.

La ponctuation de mot

La ponctuation de mot relève de l'orthographe puisqu'elle se situe au niveau du mot; le point abrégatif, les parenthèses, le trait d'union et l'apostrophe en sont les signes.

La ponctuation de phrase

La ponctuation de phrase structure l'intérieur de la phrase et la délimite; le point, la virgule et le point-virgule, entre autres, sont des signes de ponctuation de phrase.

- Malheureusement, il ne participera pas à la réunion; son fils est malade.
- Elle se mit à chantonner : « Que reste-t-il de nos amours? »

La ponctuation de texte

La ponctuation de texte, ou « macroponctuation », permet de diviser un texte long en plusieurs parties; ainsi, l'alinéa ponctue le texte en séparant les paragraphes, les titres, etc.

La ponctuation en fonction du rôle

Les signes de ponctuation sont également classés par certains linguistes en fonction du rôle particulier qu'ils jouent. On parlera alors de signes pausaux, de signes mélodiques, de signes d'insertion et de signes d'appel.

Les signes pausaux

Les signes pausaux séparent les éléments de texte et marquent des pauses plus ou moins longues; par exemple, le point, la virgule et le point-virgule sont des signes pausaux.

- Le soleil se couchait. Poussant un soupir, elle s'accouda sur le bord de la fenêtre; elle retrouva le fil de ses pensées.

Les signes mélodiques

Les signes mélodiques sont au service de la fonction expressive, par exemple, le point d'interrogation, le point d'exclamation et les points de suspension.

- Çava? demandai-je.
Ça va! répondit-elle.

Les signes d'insertion

Les signes d'insertion permettent d'intercaler des éléments dans la phrase; ils se présentent par paires : parenthèses, crochets, tirets, guillemets et virgules doubles.

- « Au fait, ajouta-t-il d'un air distrait, je tiens à vous féliciter pour votre travail. »

Les signes d'appel

Les signes d'appel signalent au lecteur un changement, tel que le passage à une autre section, la présence d'une note en bas de page, le changement d'interlocuteur; on y trouve entre autres l'astérisque, le tiret et l'alinéa.

- On dit *des *hiboux* (le *h* est aspiré), mais *des hirondelles* (*h* muet).

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LES SIGNES ASTRONOMIQUES

BÉLIER ; TAUREAU ; GÉMEAUX ; CANCER ; LION ; VIERGE ; BALANCE ; SCORPION ; SAGITTAIRE ; CAPRICORNE ; VERSEAU ; POISSONS.

Les signes de la nature : nuages, brume, arc-en-ciel, foudre... symbolique, oracle, énergie

Nõtica : Quant au *Nouveau code typographique*, il présente la ponctuation en ces termes : « Ponctuer, c'est diviser les diverses parties d'un texte à l'aide de signes conventionnels destinés à donner un sens à un ensemble de mots, ou même à un seul mot. C'est d'abord une question de logique plus que de cadence; l'information orale et de nombreux orateurs donnent trop souvent de fort mauvais exemples de pauses qui ne doivent pas figurer dans un texte imprimé. La ponctuation sert avant tout à faire saisir toutes les nuances de la pensée d'un auteur et éviter ainsi de fâcheuses équivoques. »

Pour sa part, la linguiste Nina Catach définit la ponctuation comme suit : « Ensemble des signes visuels d'organisation et de présentation accompagnant le texte écrit, *intérieurs* au texte et *communs* au manuscrit et à l'imprimé; la ponctuation comprend plusieurs classes de signes graphiques discrets et formant système, complétant ou suppléant l'information alphabétique. »

On peut retenir de ces définitions que la ponctuation est un code de l'écrit porteur de multiples messages, qui remplit différentes fonctions de nature logique et expressive.

Il existe plusieurs signes de ponctuation :

- La majuscule en début de phrase.
- Le point.
- Le point d'exclamation.
- Le point d'interrogation.
- Les points de suspension.
- Le point abréviatif.
- La virgule.
- Le point-virgule.
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ОМОНИМДЕРДІ ОҚЫТУ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСЫНДА ҚАЗАҚ ТІЛІ ЖИІЛІК СӨЗДІКТЕРІНІҢ МӘНІ

Карбозова Бұлбұл Дәулетханқызы

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Тілді оқыту әдістемесі педагогика ғылымының даму үрдісі мәнмәтініндегі білім концепциясындағы өзгерістерді қамти отырып, өз алдына жаңа міндеттер жүктеп отыр. Қазіргі білім беру ісіндегі концептуалды өзгерістер мен жаңа көзқарастар тілді, тілдік бірліктермен байланысты ұғымдарды меңгертуде оқыту нәтижесінің сан қырлылығын талап етеді. Жоғары оқу орнындағы білім алушының білім нәтижесін тек білімнің мазмұндық бөлігін игерумен ғана шектеуге болмайтындығы бүгінгі әдістеме ғылымында басы ашық жайт. Осы себепті де, білім алушының білім нәтижелеріне жету жолындағы оқу/іздену әрекеттері мен ойын жинақтау, жүйелеу, негіздеу, дәйектеу, жеткізу сияқты танымдық әрекеттері барысындағы іс-дағдыларын қалыптастыру мен орнықтыру – қазіргі оқыту үдерісінің кешенді нәтижелерінің құрамдас бөлігі саналады. Тілдегі омонимия құбылысы экстра және интралингвистикалық факторлардың нәтижесінде пайда болатын құбылыс. Осы жайттың пайда болу жолдары мен олардың лингвистикалық сипатын ғылым дамуының қазіргі антропоэекті парадигмаларымен сабақтастыра түсіндіру жолында омонимдерді жалаң құрылымдық-формалық құбылыс емес, күрделі когнитивтік-семантикалық үдеріс нәтижесі ретінде пайымдауды қажет етеді. Осы ғылыми сабақтасқан білімдер жүйесін меңгертуде қазіргі таңда қазақстандық білім кеңістігінде кеңінен қанат жайған педагогикалық технологиялар мен әдістердің жаңа мүмкіндіктерін тиімді пайдалану – қазіргі қоғам сұранысына жауап беретін толыққанды тұлға қалыптастыруға ықпал етеді. Осы мақсатта қазіргі жаңа педагогикалық технологиялардың 212 лингвистикалық білім мазмұнымен тиімді сабақтастыру жоғары оқу орнында берілетін білімнің игерілу коэффициентін арттыруға негіз болады. Шындығыда да, педагогикалық технологиялар – оқытушының кәсіби әрекет аймағын жаңартушы және сатылы, өзара тығыз байланыста жоспарланған жаңа мазмұндағы нәтижеге жетуге мүмкіндік беретін іс-әрекеттер көзі. Мұның өзі жаңа педагогикалық технологияларды пайдаланудың екі түрлі бағыты бар екендігін анықтауға мүмкіндік береді. Бірінші бағыт тұрғысынан алып қарасақ, жаңа технологиялар білім, білік, дағдыны қалыптастыру үшін қажетті ресурс болып табылып, білім алушылардың дербес сапалық қасиеттерінің қалыптасуына, білімді сапалы алуына жағдай жасайды, ал екінші бағыт тұрғысында технологиялар оқу үдерісін ұйымдастыру тиімділігін арттырудың қуатты құралы болып табылады. Жоғары оқу орындарындағы қазақ тілін оқыту әдістемесінің негізгі мақсаты – болашақ маманның лингвистикалық білім сапасын көтеру, толыққанды интеллектуалды тұлға ретінде қалыптасуына ықпал ету. Омонимдік бірліктерді оқытуда әдістеме ғылымындағы дәстүрлі оқыту технологияларымен қатар, заманауи оқытудың озық технологияларын пайдалану арқылы жоғары оқу орындары филологиялық мамандықтардың білім алушыларына кешенді түрде оқыту арқылы омонимдердің табиғатын игертуге болады. Омонимдік бірліктерді оқыту барысында білім берудегі жаңа технологиялардың озық үлгілерін пайдалану ең алдымен оқытушыдан (зерттеуші немесе дәріскер) теориялық ғылыми-базалық білімінің күштілігімен қатар әдістемелік-технологиялық біліктілігінің қуатты болуын талап етеді. «Қазіргі кезде білім жүйелерін

технологиялық негізде құру – педагогикалық ғылым мен практиканың бағыты болып отыр» [1, 287 б.]. Тілдік бірліктердің қай-қайсысын оқыту барысында белгілі бір әдістемелік технологияны пайдаланбай өту мүмкін емес. Омонимдік бірліктердің танымдық құрылымын оқытудың негізгі әдістемелік проблемасына оқу жүйесінде орныққан заңдылықтар мен ұстанымдарды, заманауи оқытудың тиімді әдіс-тәсілдерін пайдалану арқылы сапалы білім мен танымдық дағдысын қалыптастыруға болады. Омонимдік бірліктердің танымдық құрылымын оқытудың әдістемесінде білімнің сапалылығы оқытушының да оқыту технологияларының әдістері мен тәсілдерін шебер меңгеруінің нәтижесінде жүзеге асады. Білім берудегі тиімді әдістерді пайдаланудың артықшылығы туралы Ж.Н.Сүлейменова: «Оқытудың белсенді әдістерінің мақсаты – адамның технологиялық әрекеті негізінде адам факторының алға шығуына байланысты оқуда танымдық уәжді, қызығушылықты, серпінділікті, қарқындылықты қамтамасыз ету, оқыту үдерісін тұлғаның белсенді, шығармашылық, өзіндік оқу әрекетіне құру...» [2, 71 б.] арқылы белсенді әдістерді мақсатты түрде пайдалану арқылы білім мазмұнын арттыруға болатындығын айтады. Білім беру жүйесіндегі технология «оқыту технологиясы» және «педагогикалық технология» деп екі түрге бөлінеді де, екеуі оқу үдерісінде әртүрлі дәрежеде қабылданғанымен, жарыса қолданылатындығы екі технологияның өзара тығыз байланыста болатындығын көрсетеді. Мұндағы оқыту технологиясы – жалпы білім берудегі оқыту мен кәсіби тұрғыдан дайындау барысында қолданылса, ал педагогикалық технология – білім беру кеңістігінің заңдылықтары мен ұстанымдарының тиімділігін арттыру яки оңтайландыру барысында қолданылатындығы белгілі. Ғылыми кеңістіктегі «оқыту технологиясы» немесе «педагогикалық технология» болмасын қазақ тілін жоғары мектепте оқытуда өзара бірлікте, жарыса қолданылып жүргендігін көруге болады. Сонымен қатар жалпы «технология» ұғымы «өндірістік технология» және «әлеуметтік технология» деген екі үлкен бағытта да қарастырылатындығы да белгілі. Бүгінгі таңда жалпы педагогика мен әдістеме ғылымында көптеген заманауи жаңа инновациялық технологиялар қазақ тілін оқыту әдістемесінде қолданылып жүргендігі белгілі. Әдістеме ғылымында қолданыста жүрген инновациялық технологиялардың қай-қайсысы болмасын білім алушылардың жүйелі білім алуы мен дербес тұлғалық болмысын дамытуға ықпал ететіндігі сөзсіз. Интерактивтік модульдік технологиясы – «Модульді оқыту – педагогикалық технологияның барлық талаптарына жауап бере алатын оқытудың жаңа технологиясы. Қазақ тілінің оқыту бағытын айқындайтын, бірден-бір жаңа жол – қазақ тілін модуль арқылы оқыту әдістемесі» [3, 48 б.] немесе «оқытуды модульдік жүйеге құру оқытушыны инновациялық әрекетке жетелейді, іздендіреді, оқытудың тиімді әдістерін пайдаланып практикалық, зертханалық сабақтарды мазмұнды өткізуге мүмкіндік жасайды» [4, 9 б.]. Профессор Б.Қасым оқытудың интерактивтік модульдік технологиясында алгоритм тәртібімен әрқайсысының кіші жүйелерінің құрылым жүйелерін айқындап өту оқыту әрекетінің басты міндеті деп санайды [5, 64 б.]. Яғни интерактивтік модульдік технология арқылы омонимдік бірліктердің танымдық құрылымын оқыту жоғарыда көрсетілген анықтамалар бойынша лингвистиканың ғылыми теориялық негізіне, тіл фактілеріне сүйене отырып жүргізіледі. Омонимдік бірліктерді оқытуда көркем мәтіндерден мысалдар беріліп, танымдық-тағылымдық мәні жоғары мәтіндерді күрделендіру арқылы («жеңілден-ауырға», «оңайдан-қиынға») білім алушылардың сөздік қорын жетілдіре отырып, ойлау қабілетін күшейтеді. Жүйелеп, деңгейлеп оқыту технологиясы – міндетті үш деңгейлік, қосымша шығармашылық деңгей талаптарынан тұрады. Мұндағы басты мақсат білім алушыларды «қабілетті», «қабілетсіз» деген жікке бөлуге жол бермеу болып табылады. Омонимдік бірліктердің когнитивтік семантикасын оқыту 213 омонимдерге қатысты оқытылатын ақпараттың азаюы арқылы емес, білім алушыларға қойылатын талаптардың әралуандығы арқылы жүзеге асырылады. Сонымен қатар білім алушыларды деңгейлеп оқыту ғана жүргізілмейді, білім алушыларға берілетін

омонимдерге қатысты ғылыми ақпараттар да мазмұнына, деңгей дәрежесіне сәйкес сатылы деңгейде күрделеніп отырады. Мұндағы оқытудың мақсаты өздігімен білім алып, дами алатын дербес тұлғаны қалыптастыруға негізделеді. Интербелсенді технология – білім беруші мен білім алушылар арасындағы әрекеттің бірлестігінен тұратын бұл технологиядағы жұмыс түрлеріне жұптық және топтық жұмыстар, дербес және бірлескен ізденіс жұмыстары, ғылыми-зерттеу жұмыстары, рөлдік ойындар секілді жұмыстар белсенді түрде жүргізіледі. Интербелсенді технологияда білім алушылар жүйелі ойлау мен терең толғаныстан ақпаратты өздігімен түсініп, нәтижесінде өзіне қажеттісін таңдап, оған жан-жақты талдау арқылы өзіндік баға беруге дағдыланады. Омонимдердің когнитивтік құрылымын интербелсенді технология арқылы оқыту барысында білім беруші мен білім алушы өзара бірлестікте омонимдік бірліктерді жұптасып, топтасып оқу арқылы өздеріне деген сенімін қалыптастырса, омонимдердің семантикалық ерекшеліктері мен компоненттік құрамдарының лингвистикалық табиғатына үңілу арқылы дербес ғылыми-зерттеу жұмыстарын жүргізуге қол жеткізеді. Сыни тұрғыдан ойлау технологиясы – «бақылау, тәжірибе, толғану және пайымдау нәтижесінде алынған ақпаратты ұғыну, бағалау, талдау және синтездеуде қолданылатын әдіс болып табылады, сонымен қатар ол әрекет жасауға негіз, түрткі болуы да мүмкін. Сын тұрғысынан ойлау көбінесе бір нәрсені елестетуге, баламалы шешімдер қабылдауға, ойлау және іс-әрекеттің жаңа немесе түрлендірілген тәсілдерін енгізуге дайын болуды көздейді, ол ұйымдастырылған қоғамдық әрекеттерге бейілділік пен басқаларды сын тұрғысынан ойлауға баулуды білдіреді. Омонимдік бірліктердің когнитивтік құрылымын оқытудағы ұтымды технологиялардың қатарына сын тұрғысынан ойлауды жатқызуға болады. Тілдегі омонимдік бірліктердің лингвистикалық табиғатын тану – сын тұрғысынан ойлауды қажет ететін бірден-бір категория. Тілдегі омонимдерді полисемиялы сөздерден ажырату, толық омоним, жартылай омоним, аралас омоним секілді омонимдердің түрлерін ажыратып талдау жұмыстарын жүргізуде, омофон мен омограф, омоформа секілді омонимдік құбылыстарға баға беруде сын тұрғысынан ойлау технологиясын айналып өту мүмкін емес. Омонимдердің когнитивтік құрылымын сын тұрғысынан ойлау арқылы омонимдердің когнитивтік семантикасын тануға, талдау жұмыстары арқылы омонимдердің прагматикалық мазмұнын түсінуге, омонимдерді пайдалану арқылы дискурсты жүзеге асыру барысында бағалай білуге, сын көзімен қарау арқылы шығармашылық ізденісінің қалыптасуына қол жеткізіледі. Дамыта оқыту технологиясы – білім алушының белсенді субъект ретінде оқу процесіне толыққанды қатысуы. Омонимдік бірліктердің когнитивтік құрылымын филологиялық мамандықтар бойынша білім алушыларға дамыта оқыту технологиясын өз бетінше жұмыс жасауда (СӨЖ, СОӨЖ), семинар және практикалық сабақтарда пайдалану арқылы, білім алушылардың дербес жұмыс жасауы арқылы өзіндік позициясының қалыптасуына, өз ойын ортаға салып, өз пікірін қорғай алуына мүмкіндік тудыратындығы тәжірибиелік жұмыстарда көрінді. Ақпараттық-коммуникациялық технология – «технологиялық білім (ТБ) мен пәндік білімнің (ПБ) өзара әрекеттесуінің тәсілін білу. АКТ қолдану заттар туралы толық түсініктің қалыптасуына ықпал етпегеннің өзінде, қазіргі заманғы инновациялық технологиялар заттар туралы жаңа, алуан түрлі түсінік қалыптастыруды және осы түсініктерді басқарудағы ауқымды икемділікті қамтамасыз ете алады. Мұғалім өзі сабақ беретін пәнді ғана емес, оқыту технологияларын қолдану арқылы осы пәнді жетілдіру тәсілдерін де білуі керек. Жекелеген пәндерді оқытуға білім технологияларын ықпалдастыру мұғалімнің қарқынды дамуына, оқудың барлық үш аспектісін өзара байланыста белсенді қолдануына дайын болуын қажет ететіндігін және бұл оқыту мен оқу үдерістерін білікті түсіну көрсеткіші болып табылатындығын баса айту керек» [6, 59 б.]. Омонимдік бірліктердің когнитивтік құрылымын филологиялық мамандықтармен қатар жалпы білім беретін мекемелерде АКТ-ны пайдалана отырып оқыту арқылы омонимдердің тілдік қолданыстағы жиілігін анықтауда үлкен септігін

тигізеді. Бүгінгі таңда АКТ-ны пайдалану арқылы омонимдердің когнитивтік құрылымының ғылыми лингвистикалық мазмұны мен технологиялық негіздегі қолданбалы әдістемелік сипаты бірізге түсіріліп, әдістемелік тұрғыдан жолға қойылды деп санауға болады. Оған дәлел ретінде, ҚР БЖҒМ-нің тапсырысымен А.Байтұрсынұлы атындағы Тіл білімі институты ғылыми қызметкерлерінің ұжымы 2 102 496 сөзқолданысы мен 30 515 реестірлік сөзден тұратын «Қазақ тілінің жиілік сөздігін» 2017 жылы жасап шыққандығын атап өтуге болады. «Сөздіктегі берілген леммаға келтіру барысында ал (сын есім) – ал (етістік), жаз (етістік) – жаз (зат есім), кез (етістік) – кез (зат есім) сияқты грамматикалық омонимдер мен ағартушы (ағарт/ет+ушы және ағартушы/зт), адымдай (адым-да/ет+й және адымдай/сн), айнала (айнал/ 214 ет+а және айнала/зт) сияқты кейбір омографтарды (жалпы саны 230) қолмен ажырату ісі қатар жүргізілді. Морфологиялық талдағыштан өткен, омонимі ажыратылған мәтіндерден жиілік сөздік алу әлдеқайда жеңіл. Олай болмаған жағдайда, омоним сөздерге келгенде автомат оларды танымайды да, әр сөз табына жататын омоним сөздердің қайсысының жиі кездесетінін нақты көрсете алмайды. (Мысалы, ақ сөзі әрі сын есім, әрі етістік). Омоним ажыратылған корпустары жасалған тілдер көп емес, ал болған күнде мәтін көлемі шағын болып келеді. Себебі барлық омонимдерді автоматты түрде ажырататын компьютерлік бағдарлама ешбір тілде жасалмаған деуге болады. Сатылай кешенді оқыту технологиясы – «оқыту мақсаты, міндеттері, әдіс-тәсілдері, өзіндік ерекшелігі бар және оқушыларға білімді ғылыми негізде сатылай, жүйелі, кешенді меңгертіп, оларға ұлттық құндылықтарды бағалай, қолдана білуге машықтандыратын оқыту. Сатылай кешенді талдай оқыту технологиясында мұғалім мен білім алушы арасындағы қарым-қатынас жаңа қағидаларға негізделеді. Олар: ынтымақтастық, өзара сыйластық, түсіністік, әріптестік сияқты қасиеттер. Бұл технологияның маңызды тағы бір ерекшелігі – білім алушыны жақсы, жаман, орташа деп бөлмей, тек материалды өте жылдам, жылдам, баяу қабылдауына қарай тапсырманы он деңгейге икемдеп, барлық білім алушының дамуы үшін қолайлы жағдай туғызуды мақсат тұтады. Омонимдік бірліктердің лингвистикалық табиғатын бірыңғай когнитивтік аспектіде я болмаса антропоэзектік парадигма аясында оқыту керек деп кесіп айтуға болмайды. Бұл бірліктердің құрылымы мен мағыналық мазмұнын оқытуда сатылай кешенді талдау технологиясын да пайдалануға болады. Проблемалы оқыту технологиясы – «проблемалық жағдай тудыру, проблема көтеру, қойылған мәселелерді шешуде оқушыларға қажетті көмек көрсету, ол шешімдердің дұрыстығын оқушылардың дәлелдеуі, оқушылардың меңгерген білімдерін жүйелендіру және бекіту үрдісіне басшылық жасау сияқты іс-әрекеттердің жиынтығынан» тұрады [7]. Сонымен қатар, «Оқушы оқытушы жетекшілігімен жаңа танымдық және тәжірибелік мәселелердің шешімін табуға қатысатын» өзара әрекеттестіктен тұратын технология болып табылады [7, 41 б.]. Проблемалық оқыту технологиясын жоғары оқу орындарында омонимдік бірліктердің когнитивтік құрылымын проблемалы оқыту технологиясы арқылы көптеген тосын мәселелер мен тың пікірлердің сабақ барысында кездескендігі, студенттердің осы арқылы қызығушылықтары артып, дербес және жұптық, қала берді топтық немесе ұжымдасқан үлгіде сабаққа ат салысуын проблемалы оқытудың тиімділігі ретінде бағалауға болады. Қорыта айтқанда, омонимдерді оқытудың әдістемелік және технологиялық ерекшеліктері жалпы педагогикалық үдерістер аясында білім берудің жаңа ұстанымдарына сай, жаңа технологиялар мен әдістерді қажет етеді. Омонимдердің оқытуда қолданылатын заманауи құралдар мен әдістер білім алушы субъектілердің, негізінен, өзара білім алуына бағытталады. Жаңа нәтижеге бағытталған әдістер бойынша білім беруде оқу үдерісіне барлық білім алушылар толық қамтылады. Омонимдерді оқытудағы теориялық білімнен өзге білім алушылардың сөйлеу, қарым-қатынас мәдениетін қалыптастыру, дағдыландыру сияқты жанама мақсаттардың маңызы зор.

Ұсынылып отырған зерттеу мақаласы Қазақстан Республикасы Ғылым және жоғары білім министрлігінің Ғылым комитеті ИРН АР15473326 «Қазақ тілінің жиілік сөздігі – Қазақстанның техникалық жоғары оқу орындары студенттеріне мемлекеттік тілді оқыту әдістемесінің инновациялық базасы» атты тақырыптың негізінде орындалып отыр. (2022-2024 «Жас ғалым» жобасы аясында)

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Veterinary Sciences

ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА МЯСА ПТИЦ С ДОБАВЛЕНИЕМ КОРМОВОЙ ДОБАВКИ «ФЕЛУЦЕН» В УСЛОВИЯХ КРЕСТЬЯНСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА

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Введение

Мясо и мясные продукты питания человека являются полноценными источниками питательных, жировых, минеральных и экстрактивных веществ, витаминов, потребление которых в умеренных количествах является необходимым. В Казахстане активно развивается птицеводческая отрасль, индюшачье направление. Мясо индейки-нежное, сочное, вкусное и популярное. Отличается низким содержанием жира, сбалансированным количеством жирных кислот, низким содержанием холестерина. Мясо положительно влияет на содержание жирных кислот, скорость усвоения организмом, интенсивность роста костей, волос, ногтей. Мясо индейки содержит: легкоусвояемое железо - 2,24 мг/100 г, магний - 27,0 мг/100 г, селен-0,025 мг/100 г, холестерин-74 мг/100 г. А также большое количество

витаминов РР, В2, В6, В12. В имеющейся литературе данные по ветеринарно-санитарной экспертизе и оценке мяса индейки ограничены, поэтому изучение качества мяса индейки и его пищевой ценности является актуальной проблемой [1, 2, 3].

Материалы и методы

Научные исследования проводились в крестьянском хозяйстве «Рахман» Жанакорганского района Кызылординской области, в лаборатории «Безопасность, качество и ветеринарная санитарная экспертиза» кафедры Ветеринарно-санитарной экспертизы и гигиены Казахского национального аграрного исследовательского университета города Алматы.

Кормовая добавка Фелуцен-это комплексный вид корма, который включается в состав кормового рациона птиц. Его используют как дополнение к основному составу корма. Продукт отличается качественным составом и скоростью всасывания в организм. Кормовая добавка Фелуцен: углеводы-участвуют в обмене веществ и являются важным источником энергии; кальций, фосфор, марганец и витамин Е-нормализуют работу костной и мышечной систем; витамины А и Е – для нормального роста и размножения; магний-участвует в регуляции работы нервов; сера – необходима для образования незаменимых аминокислот, роста пера и пуха; медь, цинк – участвует в кроветворении; кобальт, йод, селен - влияет на функции образования активного потомства; соль-участвует в регуляции водно-солевого баланса организма. Витамины: β-каротин, а, D3, Е, В1, В2, В3, В6, В12, С в достаточном количестве.

Результаты исследования и анализ

Для увеличения производства мяса птицы в условиях крестьянского хозяйства «Рахман» были проведены исследования с использованием 12-и 15-граммовой кормовой смеси "Фелуцен". Применены комплексные методические подходы, включающие методы клинических исследований с соблюдением ветеринарно-санитарных правил и требований действующих нормативных документов. Перед проведением эксперимента вес птиц взвешивали на весах.

Таблица 1- Уровень использования кормовой добавки "Фелуцен"

№ групп	Количество птиц в группе	Средний вес птицы, грамм		Состояние кормления
		До опыта	После опыта	
1 (контрольная)	10	2200	7900	Основной корм (без добавки)
2 (опытная)	10	2200	8500	Основной корм + 12 гр. Фелуцен на 1 гол.птиц
3 (опытная)	10	2200	8800	Основной корм + 15 гр. Фелуцен на 1 гол.птиц

Эксперимент ставили на 30 суток, при использовании основного корма добавляли по 190 грамм в день. Контрольная группа набрала 7900 граммов веса через 30 дней, ежедневно давая основной корм. 12 гр на основной корм. В группе с добавлением "фелуцена" ежедневно добавляли 210 граммов веса. 15 гр на основной корм. Было обнаружено, что группа с фелуценом набирала 220 граммов веса в день. Исследование показало, что добавление 15,0 граммов кормовой добавки фелуцена было эффективным.

Качество продукции животного происхождения проверяется ветеринарно-санитарной экспертизой в лабораториях.

Таблица 2- Органолептические показатели мяса птиц

№	Внешний вид	Консистенция	Ароматность и прозрачность бульона	Ветеринарно-санитарная оценка
Мясо птицы, откормленное кормовой добавкой Фелуцен (12 грамм)				
10 проб	однородный, цвет розовый	плотное, упругое, образующаяся при надавливании пальцем ямка быстро выравнивается	специфический запах, свойственный свежего мяса	Доброкачественная, пригодная
Мясо птицы, откормленное кормовой добавкой Фелуцен (15 грамм)				
10	однородный, цвет розовый	плотное, упругое, образующаяся при надавливании пальцем ямка быстро выравнивается	специфический запах, свойственный свежего мяса	Доброкачественная, пригодная
Мясо птицы, ежедневно подкармливаемое кормом				
10	однородный, цвет розовый	плотное, упругое, образующаяся при надавливании пальцем ямка быстро выравнивается	специфический запах, свойственный свежего мяса	Доброкачественная, пригодная

В результате исследования по органолептическим показателям 30 проб мяса птицы приведены в соответствии с ГОСТ РК 31470-2012 "Мясо птицы, субпродукты и полуфабрикаты из мяса птицы. Органолептические показатели мяса птицы и физико-химическим методы исследования" соответствовали. Доказано, что кормление эффективно. Таблица 3- Физико-химические показатели мяса птиц

№	Бактериоскопия	pH	Реакция пероксидазы	Реакция сернокислой медью
Мясо птицы, откормленное кормовой добавкой Фелуцен (12 грамм)				
10	9,6±0,02	5,9±0,01	+	-
Мясо птицы, откормленное кормовой добавкой Фелуцен (15 грамм)				
10	9,3±0,02	6,0±0,01	+	+
Мясо птицы, ежедневно подкармливаемое кормом				
10	9,8±0,02	5,9±0,01	+	-

Выводы

1. По результатам органолептических исследований туша индейки, включенная в рацион минерально-кормовой добавкой «Фелуцен» и подкармливаемая ежедневным рационом, имеет высокие органолептические и физические, химические показатели, что соответствует требованиям стандарта.

2. Научное исследование показало, что добавление 15,0 граммов кормовой добавки Фелуцена было эффективным.

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Pharmaceutical Sciences

An example of pharmaceutical care for a patient with osteoarthritis

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Osteoarthritis (osteoarthrosis) is a major source of pain, disability, and socioeconomic cost worldwide. The epidemiology of the disorder is complex and multifaceted, with genetic, biological, and biomechanical components. [1,2]

Acute joint pain associated with arthritis affects adults of all ages, both sexes, and all races and ethnicities. Most of what we know about acute joint pain is for adults. [2,3]

Arthritis is a chronic disease of the articular apparatus, during which there is primary progressive dystrophy (degeneration) and destruction of bone-cartilage, proliferation of underlying bone tissue, structural changes of the articular surface of the bone before its complete destruction, the appearance of osteophytes, secondary inflammation of the synovial membrane, which causes joint deformation.[4,5,6]

The purpose of the study was to determine the role of the clinical pharmacist in patients with osteoarthritis, as he will analyze the possible options for drug interactions, the features of the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs, the possibilities of detecting side effects, and will give the correct, adequate advice to the patient in order to reduce the unfortunate consequences caused by the simultaneous appointment of drugs.

The task of the research was to study the history of the patient with osteoarthritis and to analyze the prescription together with the attending physician, in order to eliminate possible adverse interactions of the drugs.

The subject of the study was the history, anamnesis and purpose of the patient with osteoarthritis. We considered the official treatment protocol.

Patient M.S. 67-year-old man.

Diagnosis: polyosteoarthritis, mainly with damage to the hip joints, stage two, spondylosis of the spine, osteochondrosis, obesity, diabetes type 2, chronic ischemic heart disease, stable angina pectoris, post-coronary bypass surgery, hypertensive disease.

Prescribed medications:

1. Paracetamol 500 mg.
2. Diaflex 50 mg.
3. Sirdalud 2 mg.
4. Siofor 500 mg.
5. Januvia 100 mg.
6. Crestor 10 mg.
7. Xarelto 15 mg.
8. Kvamatel 20 mg.
9. Amlesa Tab. 8/10

Interaction:

Perindopril + metformin

Perindopril increases the toxicity of metformin by an unspecified interaction mechanism. It also increases the risk of developing hypoglycemia and acidosis.

Amlodipine + Metformin

Amlodipine reduces the effect of metformin by pharmacodynamic antagonism. The patient should often control the level of glucose in the blood.

Tizanidine + Perindopril

Tizanidine increases the effects of perindopril by pharmacodynamic synergism. Risk of hypotension.

Tizanidine + Amlodipine

Tizanidine increases the effect of amlodipine by pharmacodynamic synergism. Risk of hypotension.

Famotidine + Metformin

Famotidine increases metformin levels by decreasing renal clearance.

Recommendations:

The clinical pharmacist, in collaboration with the rheumatologist, determined that the patient needs active monitoring when taking perindopril + metformin, because

Perindopril increases the toxicity of metformin by an unspecified mechanism, increases the risk of developing hypoglycemia and acidosis.

conclusion.

Osteoarthritis requires complex and long-term treatment, taking into account the etiological factor. Prescribing several medications at the same time may give us unwanted effects. Therefore, there are cases when the treatment is not effective, because we are dealing with polypharmacy, and patients do not achieve the desired treatment results. It is necessary to choose the correct dosage regimen, from one drug Before taking the second medicine, the time interval needed for the correct therapy should be observed. It is the duty of the clinical pharmacist to study, analyze and make adjustments to the mechanism of action and interaction of the drugs.

Annotation

Osteoarthritis is a very common disease today.occurs in both elderly and young patients.Is is oftenthe case that patients with osteochondrosis consult a doctor to concomitant diseases need the prescribed several medications at the same time.At this time we may get an antagonistic effect and endanger the patient’s health.

The aim of my research is to determine the role of the clinical pharmacist in patients with Osteoarthritis,analysis of drug interactions,drug pharmacokinetics,end pharmacodynamics,study side effects to reduce or avoid the risks of taking several drugs at the same time.

The task of my research was to choose a prescription during the practice,to study a patient’s history,and with the treating doctor to analyze drug interactions during the treatment of patients with osteoarthritis.The subject of the research was the prescribe of 5 or more drugs in

patients with osteoarthritis, the study of pharmacological analyzed of drug interactions, together with the doctor we found out the patient's condition, analyzed the interaction of the drugs, identified the possible risks, resulting in prescriptions adjustment if needed. We also choose the patient's history, anamnesis, treatment with certain drugs, we followed the official treatment protocol.

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Historical Sciences

ETHNIC AND LABOR CONFLICTS AT THE AKTOGAY FIELD

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Abstract. The report examines the issues of ethnic misunderstanding between Kazakh-Chinese workers who were at the Aktogay field in the Ayagoz district of the Abai region. This is not the first conflict between Kazakhs and Chinese in history. But all conflicts until recently were a social problem. Among them are the reasons for uneven wages, discrepancies between bosses appointed from outside and ordinary employees, etc. We decided to present this story to the reader, trying to consider it as an objective critical opinion.

Key words: Kazakhstan, Abai region, Ayagoz district, Aktogay deposit, Kazakhs, Chinese, conflict.

Introduction

Currently, geopolitical conflicts in the world show how important world peace is. To avoid such conflicts, each State must prevent any conflict on its territory. In this context, Kazakhstan, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, makes every effort to maintain political stability in each region. The topic under consideration today shows how great the role of ethnic conflicts between countries is. If we say that the conflict in the region occurred on national grounds, then we are mistaken. This is due to the fact that, according to the All-Russian population census of the republic in 2009, 64% of East Kazakhstan residents were Kazakhs, 24% were Russian diasporas, the remaining 12% were Uzbeks, Ukrainians, Uighurs, Tatars, etc.

Table 1. Including the national composition of the Ayagoz district is presented in the following [1: 21-22]

№	Ethnic groups	Total	
			%
1	Kazakhs	35 406	97,2
2	Russians	733	2,0
3	Tatars	100	0,3
4	Germans	27	0,1
5	Ukrainians	21	0,1
6	Chechens	5	0,1
7	Other	21	0,1
	Result	36410	100

The study of the problem posed by us is of actual importance, determined by a number of objective circumstances. Firstly, at present, since the national composition of many countries is quite diverse, they strive to establish normal interethnic relations, to increase the culture of everyday interethnic communication. However, in real life, various situations and events occur that violate generally accepted norms and stereotypes in this matter, which we mentioned above. Secondly, we believe that both sides - the host country and the migrants who arrived - must comply with generally accepted international standards, which should not raise some and lower others. Violation of such norms and standards can lead to certain misunderstandings and even serious interethnic conflicts. The host country, that is, such subjects of our republic as the region, district, locality, must provide all conditions for the daily operation of such mines as the Aktogay mine. On the other hand, the Chinese, who are actively involved in this activity, providing the plant with advanced technologies and qualified specialists, could not prevent the conflict in time due to domestic and other problems.

Such interethnic, labor conflicts are not the first time in our republic and not only in this region. The main task of the leaders on both sides was to avoid such excesses, so as not to spoil their image. Accordingly, in order not to harm the friendship of the two states. In this context, the main task of States is to instill peace-loving positions in people, using policies that correctly guide their people. Periodicals on the incident were immediately published on media websites. In addition, a press release was issued in the editorial newspaper of the East Kazakhstan region "Rudny Altai". Since this is a complex and little-known topic, subjectively the black population expresses a lot of critical comments. To stop this process, the state must objectively publish the publication.

Main part

We accept the analysis of interethnic conflicts in East Kazakhstan from the point of view of understanding the principles of national security of Kazakhstan, which are based on the national-administrative and national-state security of peoples who have historically linked their fate with the fate of Kazakhstan. This idea leads us to the need to study various variants of neo-Eurasia, representing the Eurasian geopolitical concept and, in our opinion, a new concept of civil peace and harmony.

The multiplicity of causes of conflict situations and the multifactorial nature of interethnic conflicts involves the study in the following areas; firstly, it is a conflict analysis of the conflict at the Aktogay deposit; secondly, the study of factors characterizing the nature and specifics of interethnic and interethnic conflicts in modern Kazakhstan, taking into account historical features., concrete facts. Event characteristics of social processes, such as interethnic conflicts; Thirdly, it is the definition of parametric features and characteristic features of interethnic conflicts, their typology and features of development; fourth, the most important is the development of conflict management technologies and mechanisms for their containment.

The beginning of the conflict. Now let's move directly to the consideration of the problem we have posed. On July 8, 2015, the duty unit of the Department of Internal Affairs of the Ayagoz - Kazakhstan of the East Kazakhstan region received a message at lunchtime that a conflict between employees of contracting organizations occurred in the canteen on the territory of the temporary shift settlement for builders-contractors of the Aktogay Mining and Processing Plant of the East Kazakhstan region. KazMinerals Group of Companies, located 40 km from Aktogay station. organizations.

As it turned out, the incident occurred due to the dissatisfaction of workers who are Chinese citizens with the quality of food and the number of lunches. In their demand to increase the size of portions, the canteen workers explained that these portions are strictly calculated for

the number of all employees of the enterprise. Because of this, they cannot produce the necessary mixture. In response, the workers invited from China ignored the remarks of their foreman, a representative of this state, and began to express their dissatisfaction with the refusal.

Security officers, attracted by the Chinese side, tried to calm the latter and took them outside. However, the citizens of the specified country showed force to the guards, which later turned into a group fight.

As a result of the conflict, both rebellious citizens and citizens of the country suffered. Qualified medical care was provided to all the victims. Of the majority of the victims, doctors found various health injuries. On July 8, 2015, at 13.15, a fight was stopped at the place of police officers. Additional police squads were sent to the scene. The situation has stabilized and is under control.

A criminal case has been opened on this fact, an investigative task force has been created. The necessary investigative measures are being carried out. In addition, a quality of service check was assigned to food outlets [2].

The head of the region, Danial Akhmetov, the prosecutor and the head of the Department of Internal Affairs of the region at the scene. An operational meeting of the headquarters was held, which included representatives of relevant state bodies and structures.

Members of the staff conducted explanatory work with the workers. The conflict is localized. The workers returned to their jobs [3].

By the order of the Akim of the region, the Aktogay Mining and Processing Plant has created a special commission to check the status of the KazMinerals group, which collects detailed information on all facts of the conflict.

Currently, the company is operating normally [4].

Consequences of the conflict. Akim of the East Kazakhstan region D. Akhmetov and President of the NFC company, which is a contracting organization at the Aktogay field Ma Jipping, during the meeting reported that dormitories and canteens were put in order in accordance with the requirements of the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

During the meeting, the parties discussed the details of the recent conflict between workers at the Aktogay field.

The head of the NFC company, D. Akhmetov, paid special attention to the need to improve the social and living conditions of employees, noting that all violators will be brought to justice in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

According to the Akim of the region, a qualitative change in the composition of workers, the involvement of East Kazakhstan residents, especially people from nearby settlements, guarantee that such cases will not happen again.

In turn, Ma Jingping thanked the leadership of the region for promptly responding to the situation in the places of residence and catering of employees and ensuring order and said that in accordance with the requirements of the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan, dormitories and canteens were put in order.

The NFC company will soon build a new dining room, and within four months - a dormitory.

Currently, the relevant commission is working there, a criminal case has been initiated, operational and investigative measures have been launched. The Akim of the region, D. Akhmetov, the prosecutor and the head of the Department of Internal Affairs are there. The incident occurred two days ago. There was a fight on domestic grounds, in which, according to preliminary data, 145 people took part, 65 were taken to the hospital. To date, there are 31 people in the medical institutions of Ayagoz and Ust-Kamenogorsk, the cases are average, nothing particularly serious. The final conclusion will be known after the investigation is completed", B. Saparbayev said, answering journalists' questions [5].

The condition of workers after the incident "as a result, 31 workers were injured, including one security guard, of whom 21 people – citizens of China and Kazakhstan - were taken to medical institutions of Ayagoz and Ust-Kamenogorsk," the press service of the News-Kazakhstan agency quotes [6].

All the victims of the mass brawl at the Aktogay field in the East Kazakhstan region were discharged from the hospital. About this Tengri news kz Deputy Head of the Health Department of the East Kazakhstan region S. Popov told to the correspondent.

"To date, all participants of the fight have been excluded from hospital. A total of 31 people were admitted to the hospital after the fight. Their condition is satisfactory", the deputy head of the Health Department of the East Kazakhstan region said.

Recall, during a press conference, the Deputy Prime Minister said that 145 people took part in fights at the Aktogay field in the East Kazakhstan region [7].

The results of the study can be used as practical recommendations for the analysis, diagnosis and containment of conflicts at the interethnic and interethnic level in the field of practical politics and conflict, mediation and negotiation activities, as scientific and theoretical material for the preparation of analytical and expert characteristics, lectures, courses and conflict problems, special courses on interethnic relations.

Conclusion

The study devoted to the analysis of interethnic conflicts in Central Asia in the context of the geopolitical realities of the world allows us to draw the following conclusions.

In modern Kazakhstan and in all post-Soviet republics, interethnic conflicts are considered part of the socio-political reality that characterizes various forms of tension and instability. Interethnic conflicts are a manifestation of social contradictions characterized by various aspects. These are contradictions between specific forms of manifestation of the basic law and political practice, contradictions between the "center - periphery", between the Republic and the regional government, contradictions of autonomy. Autonomization, separatism, the growth of national consciousness, the manifestation of extremism and terrorism are directly related to these contradictions.

The study showed that the analysis of interethnic conflicts involves the use of the conceptual apparatus of conflict, sociology, social philosophy, ethnosociology and other sciences. The analysis of forms of interethnic conflicts is of great importance, since it is inherited from us by older generations. It should include the unjust actions of the past that took place during the repressions and mass deportations against entire peoples during the Soviet era.

The conflict analysis of the situation at the Aktogay deposit allows us to identify the causes of numerous interethnic and interethnic conflicts. These are, first of all, conflicts between titular ethnic groups of various national administrative entities and other ethnic groups. Conflict, in our opinion, is associated with such stages as conflict analysis (qualitative characteristics), conflict diagnosis (quantitative characteristics) taking into account all developments in this area, as well as conflict structuring, institutionalization, development of a deterrence mechanism and the use of mediation.

As we can see, the main cause of the conflict arose due to the fact that the employer improperly took care of the social needs of the company and employees. Due to the fact that in the dining room, the chef explained to a Chinese citizen that he was not given an extra portion of food. In response to the chef, the Chinese worker clenched his fists, which led to a fight between Kazakh and Chinese workers.

But what happened has nothing to do with the problem of ethnic conflict on the part of the state. According to them, the fight took place on a domestic basis. There are several reasons to call the conflict ethnic for a reason.:

The conflict was repeated 5 times in the 10 years from 2009 to 2019. Here, the reason for the conflict was the beating of a Chinese citizen by a Kazakh cook, retaliatory actions by other Kazakh workers. Injustice towards Kazakh workers. That is, a State that has not yet learned lessons from conflicts is again making the same mistake as before. He attracted Kazakh guys and Chinese citizens to work. Another injustice is that Kazakhstani workers receive a monthly salary 4-5 times less than Chinese citizens, and they do not give guarantees to Kazakhstanis, additional bonuses and allowances to Chinese citizens.

Our suggestion at the end is that during the first project it is necessary to calculate how many workers will be attracted by both parties with whom you agree. Citizens of other countries should not take actions that undermine the national identity of Kazakhs and trample on their honor. And employees of both sides should be accommodated in separate dormitories. Only one side should not be a priority. The authorities must clearly approve laws concerning ethnic policy in the country.

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Biological Sciences

CHRYSANTHEMUM L ҚАЛЕМШЕЛЕУ ҮРДІСІНДЕ ПАЙДА БОЛАТЫН ЗИЯНКЕСТЕРМЕН КҮРЕСУ ШАРАЛАРЫН БІЛІМгерлерге таныстыру арқылы ЗЕРТТЕУШІЛІК ҚАБІЛЕТТЕРІН ДАМУ

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Аңдатпа: Мақала Қазақстандағы *Chrysanthemum L* түрлерін сақтау мәселелеріне арналған зерттеу тәжірибесі жүргізілді. Хризантемалар - Қазақстанның оңтүстігі мен оңтүстік-шығысындағы ландшафттардағы бау-бақша түзетін негізгі түрлердің бірі. *Chrysanthemum L* отандық және шетелдік ғалымдар үшін ерекше қызығушылық тудырады, өйткені ол бау-бақшада, сондай-ақ медицинада ерекше құндылыққа ие. Олар қазіргі уақытта қалаларды көгалдандыру мен сәндік өсімдіктерді қолдау мен дамытудың әлемдегі жалғыз табиғи генетикалық негізі ретінде әлемдік маңызға ие. Өкінішке орай, соңғы ғасырларда бұл сәндік өсімдіктің саны азайды, сондықтан оларды қорғауды күшейтуді және табиғи қауіптен қорғау шараларының жүйесін әзірлеуді талап етеді.

Бұл зерттеудің мақсаты - *Chrysanthemum L* өсімдіктерінің қалемшелеу және өсіп өну процесінде пайда болатын зиянкестермен күресудің әртүрлі шараларының тиімділігін зерттеу; Осы аймаққа тән негізгі зиянкестерді анықтау; Өсімдік шаруашылығы саласындағы білім алушылардың білімін кеңейту және зерттеу дағдыларын дамыту.

Хризантема сорттарының зиянкестерге төзімділік дәрежесін анықтау үшін салыстырмалы фитомониторинг жүргізілді. Нәтижесінде Қазақстанның оңтүстігіне тән зиянкестер анықталды; Әрбір зиянкестердің келтіретін залалына салыстырмалы талдау жүргізілді және ең көп таралған және сирек кездесетін түрлері анықталды.

Жүргізілген жұмыстың қорытындысы бойынша Оңтүстік Қазақстанда *Chrysanthemum L* сорттарына зиян келтіретіндер: *Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi Schwartz*, *Aphidoidea*, *Tetranychus urticae*, *Puccinia chrysanthemi Roze*, *Frankliniella occidentalis Pergande*.

Кілт сөздер: *Chrysanthemum L*, зиянкестер, Оңтүстік Қазақстан, Хризантема нематодасы, Өсімдік биті, Сұр шірік.

КІРІСПЕ

Қазіргі заманда бақша хризантемалары (*Ch. hortorum*, *Ch. indicum L*, *Ch. morifolium*, *Ch. gigi dark pink*), соңғы 10 – 15 жылда қалалық және жеке көгалдандыруда кеңінен қолданылатын танымал гүлді сәндік дақылдардың біріне айналды. Хризантемалар түрлі реңктерімен таң

қалдырады. Ашық жерде керемет хризантемаларды алу үшін зиянкестер мен аурулардан қорғауды қамтамасыз ету қажет. Өсіру ережелерін сақтау ажырамас шарт болып табылады. Технологиялық принциптердің бұзылуы өсімдіктердің әлсіреуіне және олардың ауруларының зақымдалуына әкеледі.

Қазіргі уақытта жыл сайын хризантемада – 20 - дан астам әртүрлі зиянкестер мен аурулар зақымдайтыны анықталды. 2022 жыл қыркүйек айында басталған және 2023 жылы қараша айына дейін жалғасып келе жатқан зерттеулер бойынша кішкентай гүлді және бақша хризантемасы сорттарында декоративті өсімдіктерде көп таралған патологиялық белгілер: жеке өсімдіктер мен өсімдіктердің тұтастай құрап қалуы, жапырақтың шеткі некроздары және түсінің өзгеруі, антоцианиндер тобының пигменттерінің пайда болуы байқалған. Бұл белгілер әсіресе вегетациялық кезеңнің екінші жартысында - шілдеден қыркүйекке дейін айқын көрінді.

Зерттеу мақсаты мен міндеттеріне мыналар кірді:

- 1) зақымдалған өсімдіктердің жер үсті және жер асты органдарының патогендік микобиотасын анықтау;
- 2) тамыр топырағындағы және өсімдік ұлпаларындағы патогендік фитонематодтарды анықтау және сәйкестендіру;
- 3) дала жағдайында өсімдіктерді жұқтырудың ықтимал көзін анықтау;
- 4) оңтайлы агротехникалық әдістерді қолдану
- 5) білім алушылардың декоративті өсімдіктер шаруашылығы саласындағы танымдарын ұлғайту және зерттеушілік дағдыларын дамыту.

ЗЕРТТЕУ МАТЕРИАЛДАРЫ МЕН ӘДІСТЕРІ

Бірнеше жылдар бойы Астра сорттарын зерттеген кезінде, *Chrysanthemum L* түрінің ең көп таралған аурулары мен зиянкестері анықталған. Егжей – тегжейлі зерттеу үшін *Chrysanthemum hortorum*, *Chrysanthemum indicum L*, *Chrysanthemum morifolium*, *Chrysanthemum gigi dark pink* сорттары бақылауға алынды. Көптеген жылдар бойы жүргізілген фитосанитарлық мониторингтің нәтижесі бойынша хризантема нематодасы, өсімдік биті, өрмекші кенелер, ақ тат, сұр шірік және трипс Қазақстанның оңтүстігіндегі негізгі зиянкестер болып табылады.

Хризантема нематодасы (*Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi Schwartz*) ең қауіпті зиянкестерінің бірі. Нематодтар бастапқыда жапырақтарда бозғылт сарғыш дақтарды тудырады, содан кейін олар қоңырға айналады және жапырақтары өледі. Қатты зақымданған кезде гүлдер дамымайды немесе кішкентай және ұсқынсыз болады. Дене пішіні таяқша тәрізді, алдыңғы және артқы бөліктері жіңішке. Нематоданың барлық даму фазалары залалданған өсімдік тәнінде өтіп, қолайлы жағдайда екі аптада бір генерация береді. Нематодтар жіңішке, ұсақ, жіп тәрізді құрттарға ұқсайды. Екі жыныста да бас ұшы айқын емес алты еріндерден тұрады, ортасында тесік орналасқан. Ауыз қуысының ішінде үш жүзді кеңеюі бар жылжымалы пилл найзасы орналасқан. Ішек түтігі түзу. Құйрық ұшында үш жұп папилла бар. Құйрықтың жоғарғы жағында екі жыныста да кішкентай тікенектер бар, олар ұрғашыларында шыңында доғал, ал еркектерде үшкір аяқталады. Аталықтың ұзындығы шамамен 1 мм, аналығы 1,2 мм. Төкілген жапырақтардан немесе топырақ бетінен ересек аналықтар өсімдік сабақтарына енеді. Нематодтар дамудың барлық кезеңдері жапырақтардың немесе гүл бүршіктерінің паренхимасында көбейеді. Нематодтың жұмыртқадан ересек құртқа дейінгі даму циклі 22-25° температурада 14-15 күн ішінде жүреді. Нематодтар жылына 10 ұрпақ бере алады. Нематодтардың бір жапырағында немесе бүршігінде 4-5-ке дейін, ал кейбір жағдайларда 16 мыңға дейін болады. Нематодтар алдымен төменгі жапырақтарды жұқтырады, олар өлгеннен кейін зиянкестер сабаққа көтеріліп, жоғарғы жапырақтарды жұқтырады. Нематодты жұқтыру көзі ауру өсімдіктердің

қалдықтары, түскен жапырақтар, нематодпен ластанған әртүрлі арамшөптердің қалдықтары және кейбір авторлардың пікірінше топырақ болып табылады. Жапырақтың нематода ауруы мамырдан күздің аяғына дейін байқалады .

Күресу шаралары. Ленинградтағы гүлді-питомниктік Тресттің бау-бақша шаруашылығында Е.С. Кирьянованың жетекшілігімен М. Я. Власова жүргізген өндірістік тәжірибелер бойынша аналық бездерді ыстық сумен термиялық өңдеу нематодтың ластануын азайтады. Стерилизациядан бұрын топырақтың жоғарғы қабаты алынып тасталады, ашық тамырлар картон шеңберімен жабылады, содан кейін өсімдіктердің антенналық бөліктері ыстық суға батырылады. Стерилизациядан кейін жердің қажетті мөлшерін қосу керек. Өсімдіктерді 45° температурада суға батырған кезде олардың вегетативті бөліктері өледі, негізінен жоғарғы бөліктері, 5-10 күннен кейін жаңа бүршік пен жапырақтар пайда болады. Сондай—ақ, өсімдік тіндеріндегі нематодтарды жою үшін дымқыл термиялық өңдеу ұсынылады, 55° температурада 3-5 минут немесе 50°—5-10 минут ішінде дезинфекцияланады. Ылғалды термиялық өңдеуден кейін *Chrysanthemum indicum* L мен *Chrysanthemum hortorum* сорттары ерте және жақсы гүлденуді көрсетеді. Егін жинаудан кейінгі барлық қалдықтар мен арамшөптерді жою қажет. Өсімдіктердің нематодтармен зақымдануы байқалған жерлерде отырғызудан аулақ болу керек. Ірі гүлді және мүмкіндігінше кішкентай гүлді хризантемалардағы жапырақтардың үзіліп, жұқтырған жапырақтар топыраққа 20-30 см тереңдікке көміледі. Жоғарғы бөліктерін емес, тамыр жүйесін суарыңыз, өйткені жапырақтарды ылғалдандыру нематодтардың жаппай шығуына және олардың инфекцияланбаған жапырақтарға енуіне ықпал етеді. Жұқтырған шаруашылықтарда жылыжайларда арнайы оқшауланған сөрелер мен жұқтырылмаған аналық жасушаларды өсіру үшін топырақтағы учаскелерді бөліп алу қажет. Инфекция анықталған жағдайда ауру өсімдіктерді дереу алып тастау керек. Хризантема кесінділеріне арналған сөрелер мен құм, сондай-ақ контейнерлер мен топырақ 3 пайыздық формалинмен немесе ыстық сумен (70°) дезинфекциялануы немесе жаңасымен ауыстырылуы керек .

Өсімдік биті (*Aphidoidea*) - үлкен зиян келтіретін зиянкестердің бірі, жас және нәзік өсімдіктерге жабысып, жас өсімдіктерді әлсіретеді, өсімдіктердің шырындарын сорады және вирустық ауруларды тасымалдайды. Өсімдікте таралу белгілері :

- Жапырақтарының бұралуы мен желімденуі;
- Ашылмаған бүршіктерінің кебуі, гүлденудің тоқтауы;
- Гүлдердің дұрыс емес пішінге енуі және ұсқынсыздануы;
- Өсімдікте жабысқақ қантты заттың жиналуы.

Өзінен кейін жапырақтары мен сабақтарында жабысқақ зат болып қалуы, өсімдіктердің тыныс алуына жол бермейді және қара күйе саңырауқұлақтарының дамуы үшін құнарлы топыраққа айналады. Құмырсқалар олардың таратушысы болып табылады, олар оның тәтті секрецияларымен қоректенеді. Сондықтан, ең алдымен, күресу шараларына құмырсқаларды жою кіреді. Бақша битін жою үшін химиялық заттар қолданылады. Бірінші болып, өсімдікті ағынды сумен жуу ұсынылады. Өсімдіктер пестицидтермен өңделеді-бүрку немесе жерге қосу арқылы. Процедура бірнеше кезеңде жүзеге асырылады: а) жәндіктердің алғашқы белгілерінде; б) жаңадан шыққан немесе қалған зиянкестерді жою үшін препараттың қолданылу мерзімі аяқталғаннан кейін қайталама емдеу үшін. Олармен күресуге қарсы ең тиімді химиялық препараттар: Фитоверм, Инта-вир, Актеллик, Неорон [3].

Өрмекші кенелер (*Tetranychus urticae*) - аналықтары сопақша пішінді, ұзындығы 0,5-0,6 мм, аталықтары кішірек және едәуір жұқа болады, денесі гауһар тәрізді , ұзындығы шамамен 0,4 мм. Ересек кенелер жасыл-сары түсті, екі жағында қара дақтары бар. Қыстайтын аналықтары ашық қызыл немесе қызғылт сары реңкті. Дернәсілдері ақшыл-мөлдір, сыртқы түрі ересектерге ұқсас, бірақ соңғы сатысынан айырмашылығы үш жұп аяғы ба. 3 нимфа сатысынан өтіп имагоға айланады. Өрмекші кенелер үшін оңтайлы

температура +25... + 30 градус салыстырмалы ылғалдылық 35-55% құрайды. Бұл жағдайда толық даму 7,5-9 күнде жүреді. Сондықтан жабық жерде өрмекші кенелер жыл бойы дами алады, жылына 12-ден 20 ұрпаққа дейін береді .

Хризантема гүлінің ақ таты (*Puccinia chrysanthemi* Roze) – бұл аурудың қоздырғышы *Puccinia horiana* – жоғары мамандандырылған паразит (basidiomycetes класы, Uredinales реті) - сыртқы карантин объектісі. Оның дамуының бүкіл циклі тек хризантемалар мен филогенетикалық жақын түрлер мен тұқымдардың өсімдіктерінде жүреді. Патоген өте агрессивті, оңай енеді және тез таралады өсімдіктің ұлпаларында қысқа инкубациялық кезеңге ие, ол мол споралануымен ерекшеленеді. Оның споралары үлкен қашықтыққа тасымалданады, бір спора өсімдіктің қатты жергілікті зақымдануын тудыруы мүмкін. *P. horiana* отаны Жапония мен Қытай деп болжануда, болашақта Саңырауқұлақ Азия, Америка, Африка, Океания және Еуропаның басқа елдеріне таралды. Аурудың белгілері- жапырақтардың жоғарғы бетінде кішкентай (2-5 мм) сарғыш-жасыл дөңгелек дақтар пайда болады. Жапырақтардың астыңғы жағында патогеннің қара қоңыр, дөңгелек, ұнтақты пұстулалары (телия) пайда болады, олар піскен кезде қызығылт сүйелдер түрінде болады. Зақымданудың әлсіз дәрежесінде өлшемі 5 мм – ге дейін жалғыз пұстулдар дамиды, ал күшті пұстулдар жапырақтардың ассимиляциялық бетін төмендетеді. Иммундық сорттарда пайда болған жерлерде қоңыр нүктелер пайда болады. Ауру ылғалды және жылы климат кезінде қарқынды дамиды. А. И. Недолужконың (2003-2006) ақ татпен күресудегі 4 жылдық тәжірибесі өсімдіктердің вегетациялық кезеңінде агротехникалық немесе химиялық өңдеу хризантеманың сезімтал сорттары мен түрлерінде тиімсіз .

Сұр шірік (*Botrytis cinerea* Fr.) – бұл бақша, үй және басқа да декоративті өсімдіктерінің әртүрлі дақылдарына әсер ететін саңырауқұлақ ауруы. Көбінесе бұл әртүрлі жемістерді сақтау немесе тасымалдау кезінде пайда болады. *Botris* тұқымының саңырауқұлақтары қоздырғыш болып табылады, ол өсімдіктердегі немесе олардың жемістеріндегі жараларға түседі. Көбінесе жылыжайларда бұтаның құрғақ өлі бөліктерінде ылғал тамшылары пайда болған кезде пайда болады, ал ашық алаңда жаңбырлы ауарайында таралуы белсенді түрде жүреді. Біріншіден, мұндай шірік әлсіреген өсімдіктердің жер бөліктеріне әсер ете бастайды. Гүлшоғырлардың зақымдануының алғашқы белгісі-қамыс гүлдеріндегі ашық қоңыр сұлы дақтардың болуы. Осыдан кейін дақтардың тез өсуі және гүлшоғырлардың шіріген қоңыр массаға айналуы жүреді. Зақымдалған гүлшоғырлар ауру қоздырғыштарының конидиальды споралануының мол сұр жабындысымен жабылған. Шіріген масса саңырауқұлақтың склеротийімен толтырылады, оның көмегімен ол өсімдік қалдықтарында қыстайды. Көктемде өсімдіктің инфекциясы конидиямен жүреді. Қалемшелер тамырлану кезінде қатты зардап шегеді. Күресу әдістері. Сұр шірікпен күресу оның дамуына ықпал ететін жағдайларды жоюдан тұрады. Қатты зардап шеккен өсімдіктер немесе өсімдік бөліктері (қалемшелер, гүлшоғырлар, жапырақтар) алынып тасталады және өртеледі. Аурудың алдын алу мақсатында жылыжайлар, сөрелер мен жәшіктер дезинфекцияланады және үнемі желдетіледі. Сұр шіріктің пайда болуын болдырмау үшін тұқымдарды немесе қалемшелерді отырғызар алдында құрамында күкірт бар фунгицидтік ерітіндімен өңдеу керек. Көшеттердің пайда болуымен олар 7-10 күндік үзіліспен, Бордосс қоспасының 1% ерітіндісімен екі рет шашырайды. Үшінші өңдеу күзде, егін толығымен жиналған кезде жүзеге асырылады .

Батыс гүлді трипс (*Frankliniella occidentalis* Pergande) Ұзындығы 0,9-1,2 мм кішкентай жәндіктер. дене беті тегіс, өрескел торлы құрылым жоқ. Дене түсі бозғылт сарыдан қою қоңырға дейін. Денедегі барлық қылшықтар қараңғы. Қанаттары ашық сары түсті, антенналар сегіз сегментті. Кеуде қуысының алдыңғы бөлігінде алдыңғы көмір қылшықтары және екі артқы көмір қылшықтары бар. Іштің сегізінші тергитінің артқы шеті тісті жотамен. Аяқтар аяқтың соңында көпіршік тәрізді сорғышпен жұмыс істейді. Қанаттар, нағыз трипс тұқымдасының барлық өкілдері сияқты, тар, ұштарында көрсетілген. Қанаттың қабырға

жиегінде ұзын шаштың жиегі бар. Трипс гүлдерге және басқа өсімдіктерге көп зиян келтіреді. Зақымдалған бүршіктер мен аналық бездер әлсіз және ұсқынсыз гүлдер, жемістер, тұқымдар береді. Шамдарда трипстің зақымдануының нәтижесі қыста сақтауға төтеп бере алмайтын кішкентай және әлсіз шамдар болуы мүмкін. Имидаклоприд негізіндегі Инсектицидтер (Танрек, ВРК, Конфидор, ВДГ, Командор, ВРК, Биотлин) барлық мәдениеттерде трипстен жақсы көмектеседі.

Зерттеу барысында бірнеше әдістерді қолдана отырып, зиянкестерден өсімдіктердің зақымдану дәрежесін талданды. Негізгі әдіс - визуалды бағалау, оның барысында біз өсімдіктерді апта сайын тексеріп, зақымдалған жерлер тіркелді. Жапырақтардың түсінің өзгеруі, кептіру және зиянкестердің зақымдануының басқа көріністері сияқты сыртқы белгілер бақылауға алынды. Осы белгілерге сүйене отырып, зиянкестердің түрі анықталды, сәйкесінше олармен күресу әдістері таңдалды.

Хризантема зиянкестерімен күресуде біз екі негізгі әдісті қолдандық - механикалық және химиялық. Механикалық әдістерді қолданған кезде біз өсімдіктерден құраған, сарғайған және шіріген жерлерді үнемі алынып тасталды, әсіресе оларды сумен шаю арқылы өсімдік битінен белсенді түрде тазарттық. Алайда, зиянкестермен тиімді күресу үшін біз химиялық әдістерді де қолдандық. Жұмыстың осы кезеңінде инсектицидтер мен фунгицидтер қолданылды, бұл бізге өсімдік биті, ақ тат пен сұр шіріктерді сәтті жоюға мүмкіндік берді. Осы екі тәсілдің үйлесімі арқылы біз зиянкестерді жою және олардың қайта пайда болуына төтеп бердік.

ЗЕРТТЕУ НӘТИЖЕЛЕРІ ЖӘНЕ ОЛАРДЫ ТАЛҚЫЛАУ

Жүргізілген зерттеулер көрсеткендей, Қазақстанның оңтүстігіндегі құрғақ және континентальды климат жағдайында күзде және көктемде жаңбырлы маусымда мол болатын, хризантема сорттарында оның және басқа да зиянды заттардың фитосанитариялық мониторингі бірқатар қоздырғыштардың болуын анықталды: *Puccinia chrysanthemi* Roze, *Tetranychus urticae*, *Aphidoidea*, *Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi* Schwartz, *Botrytis sinerea* Fr. Тәжірибе жүргізілген сорттардың жоғарыды аталған зиянкестермен зақымдануы әр түрлі болды және 0,2 – 100%. Он бес айлық зерттеу барысында әртүрлі репродукциядағы Хризантема Морифолиум қатты зардап шекті. Өсімдік биті хризантеманың барлық сорттарына айтарлықтар залал келтірді, мұны олардың тез көбейіп, жылдам даму қабілетіне байланысты. Төмендегі кестеде хризантема түрлерінің әрқайсысына зиянкестердің келтірген зиянының пайыздық көрсеткіштері берілген.

Кесте 1 – Зиянкестердің келтірген залалының пайыздық көрсеткіштері

Зиянкестер	<i>Chrysanthemum morifolium</i>	<i>Chrysanthemum indicum</i> L	<i>Chrysanthemum hortorum</i>	<i>Chrysanthemum gigi dark pink</i>
Хризантема нематодасы	15%	12%	5%	5%
Өсімдік биті	30%	22%	10%	15%
Хризантема гүлінің ақ таты	15%	12%	3%	8%
Сұр шірік	20%	15%	4%	10%
Өрмекші кенелер	5%	4%	2%	2,3%

Кестені талдайтын болсақ, зиянкестердің ең сирек түрі – Өрмекші кенелер. Олар хризантема сорттарының әрқайсысы үшін басқа зиянкестермен салыстырғанда жалпы зақымданудың ең аз пайыз қорсеткішіне ие.

Зиянкестермен күресудің механикалық әдістерін қолдану кезінде келесі нәтижелер алынды. Нематодтармен күресу үшін Е. С. Кириянова мен М. Я. Власова ұсынған әдіс қолданылды. Біз зақымдалған топырақты алып тастап, оны зарарсыздандырдық, сондай-ақ өсімдіктердің вегетативті бөлігін 45 С температурада 2-3 минут ыстық суға батыру арқылы өсімдіктерді термиялық өңдеуден өткіздік. Бұл шаралар нематодтардың таралуын 15% төмендетуге көмектесті, бірақ инфекция көзі толығымен жойылған жоқ. Өсімдік биті мен хризантема гүлінің ақ татымен күресу жағдайында өсімдіктерді ағынды сумен шайдық және жапыраққа жабысқан зиянкестерді қолмен жойып отырдық. Бұл олардың санын 25% - ға азайтуға мүмкіндік берді, бірақ зиянкестердің тез көбеюіне байланысты бұл тәсіл көп уақытты қажет ететін және әрдайым тиімді бола бермейтіні белгілі болды. Сұр шірік пен өрмекші кенелермен күресу үшін біз өсімдіктердің зақымдалған бөліктерін қолмен алып тастауға жүгіндік. Сонымен қатар, дренажды ауыстырумен өсімдіктерді жуу жүргізілді. Осы шаралардың нәтижесінде зиянкестердің таралуын тек 30% - ға төмендетуге қол жеткіздік.

Жалпы алғанда, зиянкестермен күресудің механикалық әдістері олардың санының ішінара төмендеуіне әкелді дегенмен, олар олардан толық құтылуға мүмкіндік бермеді, сондықтан олармен күресудің екінші кезеңінде химиялық әдістер қолданылды.

Нематодтарды жою кезінде "Нематорин" инсектициді қолданылды. Ол хризантема отырғызылғанға дейін өңделген топыраққа енгізіліп, 10-15 см тереңдікке бір рет жабылды. Бұл зиянкестерді толығымен жою үшін жеткілікті болды.

Бақша биті мен хризантема гүлінің ақ татымен күресу үшін "Фитоверм Гринбелт" және "Конфидент" қолданылды. Ерітінді дайындау үшін біз 1 литр суда 1,25 мл Конфидент пен 5 мл Фитовермді ерітіп алдық. Оларды ерітіндімен 2-3 рет өңдеп, емдеу арасында 2 апта үзіліс жасалды. Бұл инсектицидтер өте тиімді болды, өйткені барлық зиянкестер толығымен жойылды.

Ал сұр шірікпен күресу кезінде біз "Свитч" деп аталатын препаратты сәтті қолдандық. Оны қолдану үшін біз 1 литр суда 1 г препаратты ерітіп, зардап шеккен өсімдіктерді осы ерітіндімен шашыраттық. Бұл тәсіл бізге сұр шірікті мүлдем жоюға мүмкіндік берді. Өз кезегінде, өрмекші кенелермен күресте біз "Абамектин Галактика" деп аталатын препаратты қолдандық. Біз 1 мл препаратты 1 литр суда ерітіп, салқын және тыныш уақытта түстен кейін өсімдіктерді шашырату арқылы қолданылды.

Жүргізілген зерттеулер зиянкестермен күресу үшін химиялық заттарды қолдану механикалық әдіспен салыстырғанда ең тиімді әдіс екенін көрсетті. Бұл химиялық заттардың зиянкестердің негізгі көздерін жоюға қабілетті екендігіне байланысты, бұл өз кезегінде олардан ұзақ мерзімді қорғауды қамтамасыз етеді. Зиянкестермен механикалық күресу көп күш, уақыт пен ресурстарды қажет етеді. Химиялық зиянкестермен күресудің барлық артықшылықтарына қарамастан, ықтимал жағымсыз әсерлерді ескеру маңызды. Химиялық заттарды қолдану барлық қажетті сақтық шараларын сақтауды және өндірушінің нұсқауларына сәйкес қолдануды талап етеді. Бұл қоршаған ортаға және адам денсаулығына теріс әсер ету қаупін азайтуға көмектеседі.

ҚОРЫТЫНДЫ

Зерттеу жұмысының қорытындысы бойынша Оңтүстік Қазақстанда кең таралған және осы аймақтың климаттық жағдайында пайда болатын Хризантема сорттарының негізгі зиянкестері анықталды. Олардың ішінде *Puccinia chrysanthemi* Roze, *Tetranychus urticae*, *Aphidoidea*, *Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi* Schwartz, *Botrytis sinerea* Fr. табылды. Осы зиянкестердің әрқайсысы хризантеманың әр сортына келтіретін залалды бағалау жүргізілді және зақымдану пайызы көрсетілді. Бұл аймақта ең аз таралған зиянкестер Өрмекші кенелер (*Tetranychus urticae*) болып шықты, олар ең аз зиян келтірген. Хризантема нематодасы (*Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi* Schwartz) екінші орынға ие болды, ал Өсімдік биті (*Aphidoidea*) зиянкестердің ең көп таралған түрі болып шықты. Нематодтардың барлық

Хризантема сорттарына келтірілген зиянның жалпы пайызы 37%, Хризантема гүлінің ақ таты - 38%, сұр шірік - 49%, Өрмекші кенелер - 13,3% және Өсімдік биті - 77% құрайды. Зерттеу нәтижелері бойынша Хризантемалардың ең осал сорты *Chrysanthemum morifolium* екендігі анықталды, ал екінші орында *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. Зиянкестерге төзімділігі жоғары сорттар – *Ch. Hortorum* және *Ch. gigi dark pink* Зерттеу нәтижелері бойынша Хризантема зиянкестерімен күресудің ең тиімді әдісі химиялық инсектицидтер мен фунгициттерді қолдану әдісі екендігі анықталды.

Түркістан қаласы жағдайында *Paulownia tomentosa* L. ағашын вегетативті көбейту

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Аннотация. Мақалада *Paulownia tomentosa* L. ағашын вегетативті көбейту бойынша жүргізілген зерттеу қарастырылады. Зерттеу жұмысы Түркістан қаласы Қожа Ахмет Ясауи атындағы Халықаралық қазақ-түрік университетінің Ботаникалық бағында жүзеге асырылды.

Қалаларды көгалдындыру, жаңа декоративті ағаш түрлерімен байыту, экологиялық тұрғыдан ауаның ластануын азайту мақсатында оттегін айтарлықтай көп бөлетін ағаш түрлерін көбейту сияқты бірқатар мәселелердің шешімін табу соңғы кездері өзекті тақырып болып келеді. Міне осындай мәселелердің шешімі ретінде *Paulownia tomentosa* L. ағашы өте ерекше орын алады. Өзінің бірқатар ерекшеліктеріне байланысты бұл ағаш түрі Түркістан қаласының климатында өсіруге тиімді болып саналады. Осы тұрғыдан оны вегетативті көбейту бойынша, нақтырақ айтқанда тамыр қалемшесінен көбейту бойынша зерттеу жүргізілді. Зерттеуге керекті материалдар жинақтап алынып, зерттеу әдісі бойынша белгілі уақыт аралығында өсірілді. Зерттеу нәтижелері алынып талқыланды, өсірудің ең тиімді жолдары нақтылап алынды.

Кілт сөздер. *Paulownia tomentosa* L., тамыр қалемше, торф-топырақ.

Кіріспе.

Paulownia tomentosa L. немесе Ғажайып ағаш үлкен жапырақтарымен ерекшеленетін *Paulowniaceae* тұқымдасына жататын түр болып саналады. Бұл тұқымдастың бар болғаны бірнеше түрлері кездесіп, соның ішінде *Paulownia tomentosa* L. түрі 30°C суыққа дейін төзімді. Бұл ағашты сәтті интродукциялауға үлкен мүмкіндік береді. Ыстыққа және құрғақшылыққа да дерлік жақсы төзеді. Ағаштың биіктігі қолайлы ортада 25м-ге дейін өсуі мүмкін. Бұл ағаш дүниедегі ең тез өсетін ағаш деп танылған. Кейбір деректерде өмір сүру ұзақтығы 100 жылға дейін делінген. Жапырақтары жүрекше пішінді болып келеді. Ағаш тамыры терең өседі, әртүрлі өсімдік зиянкестеріне және ауруларға төзімді. Шыққан отаны негізінен Оңтүстік-шығыс Азия елдері: Қытай, Оңтүстік Корея, Лаос, Вьетнам болып табылады. Алайда ландшафтық, сәндік, экологиялық, орман шаруашылығы сияқты басқа да тиімділіктеріне байланысты әлемнің түрлі елдеріне интродукциялануда[1].

Өсудің алғашқы екі жылында жапырақтары атмосфераға фотосинтез кезіне бөлінетін оттекті үлкен мөлшерде береді. Бөлетін оттегі мөлшері күніне 6кг/ағаш ал өзіне сіңіретін CO₂ мөлшері 22кг/ағаш дейін жетеді. Жапырақтары үлкен болғандықтан шаң-тозаңды ұстап қалады және шуды айтарлықтай азайтады, ал метаболизмнің тез жүруі жылдам өсуіне жол ашады. Осылайша оның тез өсуі, 6 апта бойына жайқалып әдемі гүлдеуі, үлкен жапырақтары мен керемет бөрікбасына ие болуы оны скверлер мен саябақтарда сәндік, ландшафтық ағаш ретінде егуге өте зор мүмкіндік береді. Одан бөлек соңғы кездері ғасырдың әлемдік деңгейдегі мәселесіне айналып отырған жаһандық жылынумен күресуде, көгалдандыру жұмыстарында немесе қаланың декоративті ағаштар қорын байытуда ең тиімді ағаштардың бірі[2].

Ағаш діңі өте жоғары сапалы, өртке төзімді және биік болып тез өсетін, оңай өңделетіндіктен құрылыс материалы, түрлі жиһаздар жасау сияқты өндірістерде кең сұранысқа ие. Одан бөлек орман шаруашылығына да тиімді болып келеді. Бұл ағаштың жапырақтарында азот мөлшері жоғары болғандықтан бұршақ тұқымдас өсімдіктермен теңестіріліп, бірқатар мал түрлерін бордақылау мақсатында жемшөп ретінде беріледі. Павловния жапырақтарында ақуыз (17,5%), амин қышқылдары (1,5%), көмірсулар (24,3%) және полифенолды қосылыстар (6,1%) жоғары болады. Осылайша, Павловния ағашының жасыл жамылғысы биологиялық белсенді қосылыстардың бай көзі болып табылады және жем, тамақ, фармацевтика және косметика өнеркәсібінде шикізаттың баламалы көзі ретінде қарастырылуы мүмкін [3].

Павловнияның медицинада да рөлі айтарлықтай, мысалы, Қытай халық медицинасында гонорея, қызылша сияқты біраз инфекциялық ауруларды емдеуде қолданылады. Оның жапырағы, жемісінің сығындылары бронхит, жөтелу қақырық түсіру, демікпе ауруларына дәрі ретінде пайдаланылады. Одан бөлек гүлдерінен сапалы бал өндіріледі. Ал тамыр жүйесі эрозияға қарсы күресіп топырақты азотпен байытады. Павловнияның қайталама метаболиттерінің антиоксиданттық қасиеттері мен емдік құндылығы туралы зерттеулердің маңызы артып келеді және жақында көптеген жарияланымдар пайда болды. Жемістері мен жапырақтарынан жасалған сұйық қоспаны күнделікті қолдану шаштың сау өсуіне ықпал етеді және ағарған шашты қарайтуға көмектеседі [4].

АҚШ пен Испанияда Павловния карьерлердің өнім бермейтін, топырағы сарқылған жерлерге, жол бойларына топырақтардың фитоқалпына келуі үшін егіледі. *Paulownia tomentosa* L. құрғақ ағашын зерттеулер көрсеткендей өсімдік өзінің тіршілік әрекеті барысында ағаш діңінде ауыр металдардың көп мөлшерін шоғырлауға қабілетті бар. Сондай-ақ *Paulownia tomentosa* L. өсімдіктері айтарлықтай мөлшерде әртүрлі микроэлементтер жинақтауға қабілетті, әсіресе марганец, қорғасын, барий, селен, цезий, мышьяк [5]. Бұл зерттеулер ағаш топырақтардың ластануында фиторемедианттық рөлінің үлкен екенін көрсетеді. Ол тек атмосферадағы лас ауаны ғана тазартып қоймай, сондай-ақ топырақтың ластануын да тазартуға көмектеседі.

Зерттеу әдісі. Тамыр қалемшелерінен көбейту әдісі біраз уақыттан бері қолданылып келе жатқан әдіс. Қалемшелерді алу үшін ағаштың тамырын ашық ауада қазып алу қажет. Оны өсімдік тыныштық күйінде яғни күздің аяғы мен ерте көктем аралығында алынады. Жердің беті тоңбаған немесе қар баспаған болуы керек. Тамыры алынатын ағаш 1-2 жылдық болғаны жөн. Тамырынан қалемшелерді діңіне жақын жағын, яғни жоғары бөлігін тегіс қылып, ал төменгі бөлігін 45° қиғаш етіп кесіп алынады. Егер таңдалған ағаш 1 жылдық болса 30 шақты қалемше алуға болады. Тамыр жүйесінің қалемшелер алып болынған қалың бөліктерін тастамай көшеттер алуға болады. Мұндай көшеттер биомасса үшін жақын маңдағы орман екпелерін немесе жоғары сапалы өнеркәсіптік ағаш алу үшін орман екпелерін өсіру үшін пайдаланылмайды, өйткені олар тым қымбат. Көбінесе олар бақшада немесе саябақта жеке ағаш ретінде отырғызу үшін, көшелер немесе даңғылдар бойында ауаны пайдаланылған газдардан тазарту үшін, ауыл шаруашылығында желге қарсы немесе белдеу ретінде ағаштардың жаңа қатарларын жасау үшін, инвазиялық түрлердің тұқымдарының таралуын азайтуда қолданылады. Алынған қалемшелерді егу үшін субстрат дайындап алынады және қалемшелерді субстратпен дерлік бір деңгейде етіп егіледі. Тамырлануы үшін жетілікті ылғалды субстрат пен 20°C-тан жоғары температура сақталуы керек [6]. Тамырландыру жылы және жабық орындарда жасалады. Өзінің қоректік заттарының әсерінен тамыр кесінділері өркендерге параллель бүршіктерден және меристема жасушаларынан қосымша тамырлардан итеріле бастайды. Өскіндердің өсуі үшін жабық орында табиғи жарықпен қамтамасыз етіледі.

Талдау мен нәтижелер. Зерттеу наурыз айында басталды. Тамыр қалемшесін алу үшін бір жылдық ағаштар таңдап алынды. Ағаштың алдымен жер үсті бөлігін тек 10-15 см қалдырып кесіп тасталынды, кейін тамыры қазып алынды. Тамыр қалемшелер 12-14 см етіп кесіп алынды, жалпы 90 тамыр қалемшесі егуге дайындалды. Субстрат ретінде зерттеу үшін 3 үлгі: торф, топырақ, торф-топырақ алынды. Егуге арналған стакандар субстратпен толтырылып, Қалемшелердің 90 градуспен кесілген жағы субстраттың үстіңгі бетіне қаратылып егілді. Субстратқа қалемшелерді тамырландыру үшін 4 г/л Osomocote Exact Standard 5-6M препараты 1/3 мөлшерде қосылды Әр субстрат үлгісіне 30 қалемшеден тура келді. Ең алғаш қалемшелер 1 аптадан соң өсіп шыға бастады. Қажетті оптимальды температура мен жарық,ылғал деңгейлері қатаң бақылауда болды.

1-график. *Paulownia tomentosa* L. тамыр қалемшелерінің тамырлануы (%)

Paulownia tomentosa L. ағашын вегетативті көбейту бойынша нәтижелер графикте көрсетілгендей ең жақсы тамырланып өсу дәрежесін торф-топырақ субстрат үлгісі көрсетті, яғни мұнда 98%-ға дейін тамырлану дәрежесін байқадық. Тек торф субстрат үлгісі 92%-ға дейін болса, ал топырақтың өзіне егілген қалемшелер 83% тамырлану дәрежесін көрсетті. Айта кетерлік жайт, тек топыраққа егілген тамыр қалемшелерде әрі қарай өсу барысында да бірнеше дарақтың өлуі байқалды.

Қорытынды. Бұл мақалада *Paulownia tomentosa* L. ағашының ерекшеліктері мен бірқатар тиімді тұстары сипатталып, оны қазіргі заманғы өзекті мәселелерге: жаһандық жылынуға қарсы орман ресурстарын кеңейту, қалаларды көгалдандыру, ландшафтық дизайнын көркейту және атмосферада оттегі мөлшерін көбейтіп көмірқышқыл газын азайту сынды шешім болатын ең тиімді ағаш екені көрсетілді. Сондықтан, бұл ағаш түрін көбейтудің бір тәсілі ретінде Түркістан қаласы жағдайында тамыр қалемшесінен жыныссыз жолмен көбейту зерттелді. Зерттеу нәтижелері көрсеткендей тамыр қалемшелерінің жоғары пайыздық деңгейде тамырланып өсуі үшін алынған субстрат үлгілерінің ішінде ең тиімдісі ретінде торф-топырақ үлгісін қолдану тиімді деп саналды.

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Sociological Sciences

Зарубежный опыт мотивации труда в организациях

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Аннотация

Данная аннотация посвящена исследованию особенностей методов мотивации на основе анализа зарубежного опыта. В работе рассматриваются различные подходы к мотивации персонала, используемые за рубежом, и их применимость в контексте современных организаций. Автор проводит обзор существующих исследований, выявляет основные тенденции в области мотивации сотрудников и выясняет, какие методики эффективны в различных культурных и организационных контекстах. Важное внимание уделяется вопросам адаптации зарубежных практик мотивации к условиям отечественных компаний. Результаты исследования могут быть полезны для руководителей и специалистов по управлению персоналом, стремящихся улучшить мотивацию и производительность своих сотрудников на основе лучших зарубежных практик.

Abstract

This abstract is devoted to the study of the features of motivation methods based on the analysis of foreign experience. The paper examines various approaches to staff motivation used abroad and their applicability in the context of modern organizations. The author reviews existing research, identifies the main trends in employee motivation and finds out which methods are effective in various cultural and organizational contexts. Important attention is paid to the adaptation of foreign motivation practices to the conditions of domestic companies. The results of the study can be useful for managers and HR specialists seeking to improve the motivation and productivity of their employees based on the best foreign practices.

Ключевые слова: трудовая мотивация, материальное стимулирование, нематериальное поощрение, управление персоналом, система трудовой мотивации, потребности.

Keywords: labor motivation, material stimulation, non-material incentives, personnel management, labor motivation system, needs.

В современном мире, трудовая мотивация считается важным катализатором успеха организаций, поскольку она способствует эффективной работе сотрудников. Для достижения целей организации работодатель зависит от эффективности работы своих сотрудников. Трудовая мотивация остается жизненно важным фактором в организационной психологии, поскольку она помогает объяснить причины индивидуального поведения в организациях. Следовательно, исследования факторов, стимулирующих трудовую мотивацию, могут внести вклад в теоретические обоснования индивидуальных и практических социальных условий, которые оптимизируют работоспособность сотрудников и эффективность производства. Таким образом данное исследование направлено на изучение теории о мотивации и опыта зарубежных стран, что поможет выявить более подходящие рекомендации для улучшения работоспособности сотрудников и повышения мотивации.

Актуальность выбранной темы обусловлена необходимостью повышения уровня мотивации сотрудников с целью повышения эффективности деятельности предприятия в современных условиях.

Целью исследовательской работы является разработка методологических подходов к решению проблем повышения мотивации труда персонала для того, чтобы выработать рекомендации по повышению мотивации труда на предприятии.

Теории мотивации относятся к изучению развития вдохновения для достижения определенных целей на профессиональном или личном уровне. Это означает, что теории помогают идентифицировать процесс обучения и понять мотивацию индивида к достижению определенного результата. Более того, теории о мотивации полезны и широко применимы в менеджменте для выявления факторов, которые помогают повысить производительность и прибыль отдельных лиц и организаций. [1]

Любой индивид не может сосредоточиться на сложных потребностях до тех пор, пока его основные требования не будут выполнены. Теория Маслоу очерчивает эту иерархию, создавая пирамиду, чтобы изобразить процесс удовлетворения индивидами своих основных потребностей, прежде чем перейти к потребностям более высокого уровня. [2]

Трудовую мотивацию можно рассматривать как совокупность внутренних и внешних сил, которые инициируют поведение, связанное с работой, и определяют его форму, направление, интенсивность и продолжительность. [3] На рабочем месте трудовая мотивация представлена как невидимая, личная и гипотетическая конструкция, которая проявляется в форме наблюдаемого и, следовательно, измеримого поведения. Повышение производительности - это одна из серьезных задач, которая привлекает внимание работодателей, будь то частных или государственных, путем разработки соответствующего механизма мотивации своих работников. Серьезность этой задачи можно понять из восприятия руководством сильной функциональной взаимосвязи между мотивацией сотрудников и производительностью организации. В течение многих лет работодатели экспериментировали с различными стратегиями в попытке эффективно соотнести мотивацию работников с их вкладом в работу.

Таким образом, важно рассмотреть Иерархию потребностей Маслоу, которая одна из самых известных и главных основ теорий мотивации в мире. Маслоу начинает с идеи о том, что люди всегда склонны чего-то хотеть, и то, чего они хотят, зависит от того, что у них уже есть. Маслоу предположил, что существует пять различных уровней потребностей, к которым люди должны стремиться для удовлетворения своих базовых потребностей. [4] Первый или самый низкий уровень - это физиологические потребности, для удовлетворения которых необходимы пища, вода, кров и одежда. Когда люди не чувствуют голода, жажды или холода, их потребности переходят на второй уровень. Второй самый низкий уровень - это потребности в безопасности. На этом уровне человек должен чувствовать себя в безопасности в своей семье и в обществе, а также чувствовать себя защищенным от насилия. Потребность в безопасности проявляется в гарантированной работе, сбережениях и страховании здоровья, психического здоровья, старости и инвалидности. Потребности в любви и принадлежности - это третий уровень иерархии Маслоу. Почувствовав себя в безопасности, люди должны чувствовать, что они получают и дарят любовь, их ценят и у них хорошие дружеские отношения. Четвертый уровень - это потребности в самоуважении. Это потребность быть уникальными с точки зрения самоуважения и пользоваться уважением других людей. Люди хотят высоко оценивать себя и, основываясь на своих достижениях, получать признательность от других людей. Отсутствие этих потребностей может привести к неполноценности, беспомощности и слабости. Высшим уровнем иерархии потребностей Маслоу является потребность в самоактуализации. Развитие этой потребности основано на

удовлетворении на четырех других более низких уровнях. Это относится к потребности в самореализации и к тенденции реализовываться в том, что потенциально есть у человека. Суть этой теории заключается в том факте, что когда удовлетворяется одна потребность, ее сила уменьшается, а сила следующего уровня возрастает. Маслоу отмечает, что один уровень потребностей не обязательно должен быть полностью удовлетворен, прежде чем человек перейдет на следующий уровень. Индивид может быть частично удовлетворен одним уровнем и все еще стремиться к удовлетворению на следующем уровне.

Используя данную теорию многие организации работают над повышением эффективности сотрудников, однако в современном быстро развивающемся мире нужно учитывать разные аспекты, как культурные различия, экономические и социальные факторы. Для выявления культурного различия разных стран был выполнен сравнительный анализ, где рассматриваются какими методами мотивации чаще всего пользуются работодатели в разных странах.

Таблица-1.

Сравнительный анализ методов мотивации в разных странах

Страна	Методы стимулирования сотрудников	Характеристика
Европа	<p>Выдаются социальные пакеты для каждого работника вне зависимости от должности и проходят обучение для повышение квалификации. Более того широко используется практика конфиденциальной оценки сотрудников, что помогает рационально выплачивать бонусы и заработную плату сотрудникам. [5]</p> <p><i>Швеция</i> Особенность шведской системы мотивации заключается в уменьшении разрыва между богатыми и бедными. В связи с этим шведские компании практикуют философию "Lagom", которая подразумевает усреднение заработных плат, одноуровневого повышения оплаты труд и баланса между личной жизнью и работой.</p> <p><i>Германия</i> Государство и организации создают равные условия жизни для жителей, тем самым обеспечивая их социальным пакетом и единым ежеквартальным бонусом для всех сотрудников.</p> <p><i>Франция</i> Система оплаты труда во Франции отличается тем, что зависит от двух пунктов: 1. Индекс нормы оплаты труда и 2. Индивидуализация каждого сотрудника. Более того, дополнительные бонусы выплачиваются ежеквартально от компании.</p>	<p>Заработная оплата труда оценивается в зависимости от рыночных цен и уровня жизни региона и нацелена на уменьшение экономического неравенства общества. [8]</p> <p>Лагом - это слово, пришедшее из Швеции, которое можно интерпретировать как "в нужном количестве", найти баланс между личной жизнью и работой.</p> <p>Во Франции заработная плата сотрудника напрямую зависит от его образования, квалификации и опыта работы. Тем самым сотрудники оцениваются индивидуально работодателем и получают неодинаковый оклад. Более того компании активно внедряют дополнительную бонусную систему, корпоративную медицинскую страховку и льготная оплата за проезд.</p>

<p>США</p>	<p>Оплата труда зависит от результата деятельности и времени. Время является важным показателем на рабочем месте, и главным индикатором в оценке заработной платы. Активно используются материальные поощрения в виде бонусов для стимулирования сотрудников на новые достижения. [6] Оплата труда измеряется формулами Скэнлона и Ракера, где формула Скэнлона измеряет производительность по стандарту затрат на рабочую силу по отношению к долларовой стоимости производства. В то время как формула Ракера вводит третью переменную: долларовую стоимость всех материалов, расходных материалов и услуг, которые использует организация. [12]</p>	<p>Ориентация американцев нацелена на личный успех и достижение высокого уровня благосостояния. Для этого работодатели начисляют заработную плату по сдельно-премиальной системе: почасовая заработная плата плюс различные модификации бонусов.</p>
<p>Япония</p>	<p>Практикуется кадровая ротация для улучшения профессиональных навыков на каждой должности. При оплате труда учитывается стаж работы как один из главных факторов и выплачиваются премии за выслугу лет. Каждое предприятие стимулирует и создает условия сотрудникам для пожизненной занятости в данной компании. Японские сотрудники больше внимания уделяют вознаграждению за достижения группы, а не индивидуальному вознаграждению. [11]</p>	<p>На формирование суммарного заработка японского работника влияют пять основных факторов:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - возраст, стаж, образование; - должность и обязанности; - результаты деятельности; - льготы на жилье; - региональные особенности (расположение жилья и работы) [7]
<p>Казахстан</p>	<p>Главным запросом граждан в Казахстане является материальное благосостояние и репутация компании. Тогда как, компании в свою очередь, нацелены на создание благоприятных условий для работы, системы оценки и формирования заработной платы. Также важно нематериальное поощрение и социальный пакет в виде страховых полисов в медицинских учреждениях и различные скидки на услуги. [9] Более того активно практикуется система бонусной оплаты по КПЭ и плану на месяц по определенной деятельностью предприятия.</p>	<p>Система признания достижений по результатам KPI - расшифровывается как ключевой показатель эффективности, поддающийся измерению и количественной оценке показатель, используемый для отслеживания прогресса в достижении конкретной цели. [14]</p>

По сравнительному анализу и по зарубежному опыту эффективной деятельности можно сказать, что японская система стимулирования сотрудников является наиболее выигрышной для любой компании, которая стремится развивать свою компанию и работать со своими сотрудниками на долгосрочный период. Однако со стороны эмоционального

благополучия населения, Европейская система является наиболее подходящей, так как компания избегает переработки и выгорания сотрудников.

Однако Американские методы стимулирования сотрудников отличаются от Европейской и Японской тем, что рассчитаны на достойную оплату труда за каждый переработанный час сотрудника, что является хорошим материальным поощрением. Наиболее важными факторами мотивации во всех четырех регионах считаются базовая заработная плата, атмосфера на рабочем месте, нематериальное поощрение и дополнительные льготы. Исходя из полученных результатов, можно увидеть, что руководство предприятия должно находить способы постоянного совершенствования подхода к работе персонала с целью выявления его потребностей и ожиданий, улучшения человеческих взаимоотношений и возможностей для образования и личностного роста. [10]

Теории мотивации помогают управленческим командам находить наилучшие способы достижения организационных целей и работать над достижением желаемых результатов. Если успешно применять данные теории мотивации и практиковать зарубежный опыт, то это помогает эффективно привносить позитив, поддерживать и вдохновлять сотрудников, что приводит к росту отдельных людей, команд и всей организации в целом.

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